

**AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP IN A
DEVELOPING ECONOMY: A STUDY OF
NIGERIAN OIL COMPANIES**

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Philosophy

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for another academic award with comparable criteria. It does not contain any previously published material to which no reference is made in the text.

Signed:

Personal details withheld.

Date: 4th of March 2024

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to Yeshua, the powerful and awesome one who has protected me ever since I was conceived and continues to do so. Kingsley Obinna Omeihe, my dearly loved husband, you have been my guiding light through the years. Because of your companionship, I now have the confidence to take bold steps and write without inhibitions.

This award belongs to my cherished children, Jose Obinna and Grace Chizara Omeihe, just as much as it does to me. We have completed the requirements for the doctoral degree together, and I cannot express how proud I am of both of you. We have achieved victory!

My wonderful parents, Austin and Jumoke, whose support has helped me achieve many of my goals and brought me to this point in my life.

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This thesis is a tribute to the numerous leaders who aim to embody authenticity in their leadership roles, whether first time leaders or persons seeking to repair and improve their leadership within various organisations. My personal experiences, specifically observing the challenges faced by a leader who strived to have a positive impact, served as the impetus for me to conduct this investigation.

Although, my name is printed on the front cover as the author, this thesis could not have been completed without the contributions of several other people. I owe a particular debt of gratitude to the members of my supervisory team, Professor Christian Harrison and Dr Tom Keegan, whose direction and comments were influential in developing this research. Christian stoked my intellectual curiosity and impressed upon me the significance of gaining exposure to various viewpoints and making conceptual linkages within the leadership domain.

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ABSTRACT

This thesis is a study of authentic leadership, an emergent and valuable leadership approach in the oil sector of a developing economy context. It is mainly focused on the experiences of both leaders and followers, providing valuable insights into the dynamics of the leadership approach within a specific setting. Consequently, the study aimed to examine authentic leadership within a developing economy context, identify its components, the challenges authentic leaders encounter, and illuminate the process of becoming authentic. The dearth of research that explores the qualitative understanding of authentic leadership necessitates the undertaking of this study.

At a theoretical level, the study draws on two main perspectives: an ideal leadership approach and a four dimensional construct as they form the core of the issue. The thesis also draws on a complementary perspective of it being a root construct as it presupposes an understanding of authentic leadership located within social and institutional contexts.

At the empirical level, a qualitative approach guided the investigation of 46 oil industry participants. Through semi-structured interviews, the findings reveal rich qualitative data which exposed the contextual factors influencing authentic leadership and its implications for leadership effectiveness. The results of the study uncovered six distinct components of authentic leadership: clarity of purpose, follower development, relational transparency, self awareness, internalised moral perspective, and concern for people. This finding was critical as it extends the current conceptualisation of the four prevalent components of authentic leadership within extant literature. Secondly, family structure, beliefs and convictions, leadership, and legacy emerged as key factors that inspire authentic leadership development. Thirdly, the study identified four challenges namely, financial constraints, inadequate governance and regulation, economic difficulties, and leadership complexities that authentic leaders encounter. These challenges cast light on the contextual challenges and internal contradictions faced by authentic leaders on their path to leadership. Finally, giving followers a voice, facilitating follower growth, and demonstrating consistency and transparency were highlighted as key actions that shape perceptions of authentic leadership. In the context of a developing economy, these actions play a crucial role in influencing how followers perceive and respond to authentic leadership.

This thesis concludes with a model that empirically incorporates the components, factors, challenges, and actions associated with authentic leadership within a developing economy. The findings contribute to the existing corpus of knowledge on authentic leadership and provide practical insights for leaders, organisations, and policymakers. This is in response to the growing concern that authentic leadership should be understood from the context in which it occurs.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

- AL: Authentic Leadership
- APC: All Progressives Congress Party
- BRIC: Brazil, Russia, India and China
- CIA: Central Intelligence Agency
- COVID: Coronavirus Disease
- DPR: Department of Petroleum Resources
- FCT: Federal Capital Territory
- FDI: Foreign Direct Investment
- GDP: Gross Domestic Product
- IOC: International Oil Company
- MINT: Mexico, Indonesia, Nigeria, and Turkey
- NBS: National Bureau of Statistics
- NDR: National Data Repository
- NNOC: Nigerian National Oil Corporation
- NNPC: Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation
- PDP: Peoples Democratic Party
- SAFRAP: Société Africaine des Pétroles
- SDG: Sustainable Development Goals
- SLR: Systematic Literature Review
- TENNECO: Tennessee Nigeria Limited

- UN: United Nations
- UNDP: United Nations Development Programme
- WW: World War

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this first chapter is to establish the basis for exploring authentic leadership within the context of a developing economy with an overarching goal of unpacking the complexities and contextual components inherent in this leadership approach.

This study is motivated by the growing recognition that organisations operate within challenging environments; this complexity has been further amplified by factors such as financial scandals, leadership malfeasance, and rapidly changing technologies (Sendjaya *et al.*, 2016; Johnsen, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2023). These challenges have sparked a topical crisis, triggering a renewed interest in the actions of business leaders and necessitating the proposition of a leadership approach capable of actively inhibiting crises (George, 2003; Luthans and Avolio, 2003; Liu, Liao and Wei, 2015; Gardner *et al.*, 2021; Gardner and McCauley, 2022). Inadvertently, challenging prevalent views on leadership expectations from executives (Spitzmuller and Ilies, 2010; Painter-Morland and Deslandes, 2017). This is because attaining success within the organisational environment require leaders that promote ethical behaviours and actions.

Amidst these complexities, the rise of authentic leadership has gained traction with its capacity to address leadership malfeasance within contemporary organisations. Likewise, the rise of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has been linked to the demand for authentic leaders who can engage with society responsibly, making it a significant and timely (Lawler and Ashman, 2012) leadership theory (Kim *et al.*, 2018; Fox, Davis and Baucus, 2020). Hence, a deeper understanding of the construct becomes imperative.

While, in recent years, there has been a significant increase in the number of research focusing on authentic leadership and its impact on organisational outcomes (Azanza *et*

al., 2018; Chang, Busser and Liu, 2020; Knox, Crawford and Kelder, 2023), the existing literature primarily reflects Western perceptions of authentic leadership. Bill George, Faith Wambura Ngunjiri, Kathy Hernandez, self acclaimed authentic leaders (George, 2003; Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017), along with other Western figures such as Eleanor Roosevelt, Martin Luther King Jr., Warren Buffet, Herb Kelleher, and John Gardner, dominate the narratives in this field (George, 2003; Avolio *et al.*, 2004; du Plessis and Boshoff, 2018b). However, it is crucial to acknowledge that authentic leadership is still in its early stages of development, both conceptually and empirically, and that there is a dearth of knowledge regarding its perception and functioning. One drawback of the current approach to probing the construct is the strong bias towards Western lens evident in leadership theories (Dickson, Den Hartog and Mitchelson, 2003; Eagly, 2005; Lyu *et al.*, 2019; Omeihe, Harrison and Omeihe, 2021).

This bias overlooks the significant variations in leadership processes across different geographical regions. Accordingly, an evident paucity of research on the construct beyond the predominant Western narrative, highlighting the need for investigations that capture contextual elements and expand upon existing conceptualisations (Sidani and Rowe, 2018; Omeihe and Harrison, 2022). This is because scholars have stated that leadership processes exhibit substantial variations across contexts (Dorfman *et al.*, 1997; Mittal and Dorfman, 2012; Dinh *et al.*, 2014; Banks *et al.*, 2016). This inherent complexity of authenticity, enacted within specific contexts and in relation to other actors, further emphasises the relevance and urgency of this study (Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017; Vendette *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, there is no consensus regarding the link between authenticity and authentic leadership (Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018; Iszatt-White, 2023). This evident dearth of research highlights the need for a more in depth investigation into how authentic leadership is perceived and practised in different settings.

In addition to this, the pandemic caused by Coronavirus has resulted in an increasing demand for authentic leaders (Ladkin, 2020; Tomkins, 2020; Grint, 2020). The crisis

exposed leaders from various domains, including nations, health agencies, and organisations, as these leaders were accused of providing inadequate and, in extreme cases, false information to the public (Ladkin, 2020). These leaders tried to demonstrate authenticity to reassure followers of their good intentions reaffirming the complexity and ambiguity intrinsic to the leadership approach, as evidenced by televised vaccinations of world leaders (Ljungholm, 2020).

The illumination of the components of the construct is a crucial part of the discourse on authentic leadership. In describing these key components, several scholars draw on Kernis (2003) description of authenticity, which was captured in the article on optimal self esteem. In this piece, “authenticity” is put forward as the foundation for achieving one's highest potential levels of self esteem. The author went on to identify four aspects of authenticity, which are “awareness”, “unbiased processing”, “action”, and “relational orientation” respectively. These components of authenticity have been developed further and integrated into the domain of leadership. Furthermore, these dimensions have been incorporated into the descriptions of the construct by several scholars (Gardner *et al.*, 2005; Fusco, O’Riordan and Palmer, 2015a). Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) conducted a critical research which presented the first measurement tool “the authentic leaderships questionnaire” to the domain. The study also refined the components of authentic leadership. These components are “self awareness”, “an internalised moral perspective”, “balanced processing”, and “relational transparency”. Although, there have been over 40 meta analyses focused on the construct (Hoch *et al.*, 2018; Wernsing, 2018), very few researchers have studied the components of this construct beyond the initial conceptualisation of the four components refined by Walumbwa *et al.* (2008).

In addition, the recent works that have been published on authentic leadership acknowledge the significance of followers within the theory. According to Carsten *et al.* (2010), leadership and followership are linked; as a result, it is impossible to understand each independently of the other. As a result, it is imperative to emphasise the

importance of this relationship in the authentic leadership process and this should be brought to the forefront of the discussion (Sidani and Rowe, 2018). For instance, Leroy, Palanski and Simons (2012) study revealed that followers actively contribute to the interactions between a leader and a follower among Belgian service businesses. This supports the argument that authentic leadership emerges through the reciprocal exchanges between leaders and the people they lead (Avolio and Reichard, 2008). Nevertheless, there is still limited studies on the perspectives of employees and their opinions on the leadership of their superiors (Jensen and Luthans, 2006a; Sajfert *et al.*, 2017). This research acknowledges the importance of this relationship, and this recognition is reflected in both the research problem and the methodology employed. Therefore, the research explores authentic leadership from the lens of individuals in leadership positions and those who follow them.

The significance of this study lies not just in its potential to address organisational complexities but its capacity to re-evaluate the foundations upon which this construct is built; as a result, it can offer a broader conceptualisation of the construct. Given this, the study seeks to explore authentic leadership within oil companies in the context of a developing economy, with a particular focus on Nigeria. To do so, this research collects data from 46 respondents, evidence from 16 authentic leaders who are identified by two or more followers within a particular organisation. It puts to the forefront what is known and unknown about the construct within the context of a developing economy.

Therefore, the organisation of the remaining parts of this chapter will be structured as follows: Initially, a rationale for the study was offered, followed by a summary of the background and the emerging themes that are relevant to the study. The following sections address these discussions by outlining the research aim and presenting the research questions, which provide the justification for the study. In addition, a summary of the methodology that was used is presented here. The proposed structure is expected to offer a broad overview of the importance and contributions of the study discussed at the end of the chapter.

1.1 Entry into Subject

The underlying causes behind leadership failures have been a subject of profound ambiguity, particularly in relation to CEOs who partake in illicit activities without considering the consequences for their followers, organisations, and society. As my career at an oil company was ending, I engaged in an emotionally charged discussion with a colleague concerning the leadership style and changes of our manager. This conversation took place after the yearly Christmas party in 2012.

Over the years, upon reflecting on this conversation, I have often questioned the leader's motivation and desperation for trying to change my colleague's perception, occasionally resorting to subtle threats or rewards to influence her. This implicit negotiation process was enacted by both parties. At the time, comprehending the leader's expectations and my colleague's hesitations was challenging, despite the shared frustration experienced by both parties.

Likewise, I observed a female leader who idolised another female CEO and made deliberate and conspicuous efforts to emulate her style, behaviour and even surprise her followers with gifts. Nevertheless, her followers failed to perceive or acknowledge her as an authentic leader. Despite her apparent desire, her attempts seemed to have a negative impact on her followers. The reasons underlying her aspiration were perplexing, as were the reactions of her subordinates. I couldn't stop myself from reflecting on the reasons why her followers were hesitant to affirm her authenticity as a leader, and I also wondered whether some people did, in fact view her as authentic. It remained unclear whether her authenticity or inauthenticity required the validation of an individual follower or a collective response to her leadership approach. Although, I was unable to explore these social interactions at the time they occurred, the experience continued to perplex me for years without plausible explanations.

The chance encounter with Professor Christian Harrison in 2018 at the University of the West of Scotland, and my subsequent exposure to leadership theories planted the seeds of this research endeavour. This association proved pivotal as I became deeply

engrossed in authentic leadership, applying it to the recollection of the 2012 conversation and my current understanding of leadership. It allowed me to contextualise the issues that were evident at the time but lacked adequate explanations. Without such explanations, the discontentment experienced by my colleague and the apparent frustration of the leader appeared to lack viable solutions.

A notable observation was that authentic leadership theory emphasised the significance and benefits of transparent interactions (George, 2003; Seco and Lopes, 2013; Al Samkari and David, 2019). This was one of the more noteworthy findings. However, scholars have not adequately examined how authentic leaders and followers participate in the complex and iterative developmental process. This illustrates the intricate and challenging nature of authentic leadership and its development, some of which this thesis will attempt to address.

The exploration of authentic leadership and the challenges encountered during the emotionally charged conversation in 2012 revealed a wide range of difficulties in describing the mechanisms that contribute to being perceived as an authentic leader and how followers respond to such expressions. Despite significant theoretical advancements, scholars argue that there is still a need to fully uncover the components of authentic leadership (Ladkin and Spiller, 2013; Steffens *et al.*, 2016; Avolio, Wernsing and Gardner, 2018) and how it can be developed. It is also crucial to assess what factors contribute to authentic leadership and whether it involves a change from the leader to the follower or vice versa. Even though, there are suggestions that the evolving nature of the context may render the goal of definitive answers unattainable, comprehending leadership within its context cannot be overstated as it forms the basis for proposing leadership development interventions. A likely part of the missing puzzle to the dilemma described in the beginning of this section.

My pursuit of a postgraduate degree began with the intention of gaining knowledge of why so many organisations are unsuccessful. This drive was fuelled by an instinctive desire to uncover the most effective leadership approach for today's businesses and

organisations. I focused on assessing Martin Luther King Jr.'s portrayal in the film "Selma" and how he expressed his vision, aspirations, worries, doubts, and, most importantly, his hopes with his followers. This further heightened my latent curiosity regarding authentic leadership. As a result, upon completing my master's degree thesis titled "The role of the entrepreneurial leader: A case study of Nigerian Fashion SMEs" one major finding significantly shaped the current study. The social dynamics between leaders and followers are best understood by considering local actors and the context from which they emerge. This motivated me to pursue a doctoral study focusing on leadership within Nigeria. It is my hope that this research with its strengths will play a significant role in distilling knowledge on the authentic leadership construct.

1.2 Background to the research problem

The infamous scandals that occurred in the 20th century had significant implications that extended well beyond the world of organisations. These scandals followed one another in quick succession, leading to loss of jobs and financial resources within the organisations, in addition to a loss of confidence and trust from external stakeholders (Mendes and Wilke, 2013; Omeihe, Harrison and Omeihe, 2021). It became clear that leadership played a significant role in the unethical behaviour of these organisations, highlighting the need for business leaders that do not engage in opportunistic behaviour to ensure their success.

Notably, the collapse of Enron in 2001 resulted in a loss of around \$74 billion for the company's shareholders and the elimination of 85,000 jobs, in addition to the indictment of the company's accounting firm (Sims and Brinkmann, 2003; Stein, 2007; Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer, 2015a; Iszatt-White, 2023). In a similar vein, WorldCom's asset inflation in 2002 led to a loss of approximately \$180 billion and 30,000 jobs, and in 2003, Dennis Kozlowski, who was the CEO of Tyco at the time, was accused of stealing more than \$170 million from the company (George, 2003; Harvey, Martinko and Gardner, 2006). The most prominent case of bankruptcy in US history

occurred in 2008, when Lehman Brothers concealed over \$50 billion in toxic loans (Seco and Lopes, 2013; Imam *et al.*, 2020).

These scandals resulted in significant financial losses for corporate America and exposed the behaviour of leaders to public scrutiny (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Gardner *et al.*, 2011). In addition, the scandals prompted a more thorough examination of the qualities possessed by contemporary business leaders (Detert, Treviño and Sweitzer, 2008; Sendjaya *et al.*, 2016) as there was a considerable decrease in confidence and trust in these leaders (Mendes and Wilke, 2013; Shahzad, Raja and Hashmi, 2020). These events spurred action and prompted the exploration of solutions for a better future (Seco and Lopes, 2013; Iqbal *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, authentic leadership emerged as a response to the mounting concerns regarding societal issues (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008; Corriveau, 2020). This emergence is attributed to three main factors aptly described as “publicised company scandals, organisation malfeasance, and wider social challenges”(p. 90) as asserted by Walumbwa *et al.* (2008).

In response, interest in authentic leadership was sparked simultaneously by both practitioners and scholars (George, 2003; Gardner *et al.*, 2005; Eagly, 2005; Sparrowe, 2005). As it emerged as an approach to addressing organisational complexities, with its benefits extending beyond organisational achievements to encompass broader societal issues (George, 2003; Avolio *et al.*, 2004; Gardner and McCauley, 2022). This leadership approach is characterised as value based, emphasising the authenticity and true nature of leaders (Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang, 2005; George *et al.*, 2007; Cashman, 2008). It advocates for genuine leadership based on decisions that promote the greater good of individuals and society (Ladkin and Taylor, 2010; Menkes, 2011).

Similarly, the construct is perceived as an embodiment of virtues with no faults or inadequacies (Alvesson and Sveningsson, 2013; Einola and Alvesson, 2021; Alvesson and Einola, 2022). This suggests that authentic leadership may indeed present a set of propositions defining what leadership should be, in contrast to what it has been

evident from the scandals of the 20th and 21st centuries. This aligns with recent arguments that authentic leadership may be an idealised leadership theory, romanticised (Gardner *et al.*, 2021), holding appeal (Jones and Grint, 2013) and offering the promise of an ethically guided future (Johnsen, 2018). The attention and enthusiasm it garners among both practitioners and scholars are characterised as unreflective feelings (Alvesson and Einola, 2019; Alvesson and Einola, 2022). However, it is crucial to acknowledge that this depiction presents a potentially misleading account of the leadership approach (Wilson, 2013).

Authenticity lies at the heart of authentic leadership theory (Harter, 2002; Liu, Cutcher and Grant, 2015; Iszatt-White and Kempster, 2019), with suggestions that understanding authenticity will provide the tools that will be valuable in identifying outstanding leaders. The increase in self-esteem, personal growth and wellbeing accentuates the undeniable psychological outcomes of authenticity, aligning with prevalent arguments, that authenticity is ultimately desirable because it is linked to positive outcomes. Caza and Jackson (2011) contend that outcomes of authenticity may not always be advantageous, as earlier suggested by Harter (2002) and may also lead to adverse outcomes. For instance, psychological dysfunction is linked to inauthenticity as the study of 619 adults suggest disturbances in psychological wellbeing arise from the misalignment between an individual's true self and their life encounters (Boyras and Kuhl, 2015) .

A notable argument within the body of knowledge is that authenticity is open to interpretation and can convey several meanings depending on the aspect of the concept being examined (Dutton, 2003). This is extremely important regarding the direction of future research agenda on the construct. Whether authenticity has been adequately incorporated into the domain of leadership is debatable. The statement holds true when considering the relationship between authenticity and authentic leadership (Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018; Iszatt-White *et al.*, 2021). This has led to several calls for scholars to devote efforts to uncovering the ontological dimensions of

authenticity, which is primarily ingrained in humans prior to its application to leadership (Algera and Lips-Wiersma, 2012; Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018). There are also suggestions that the existing application of authenticity to leadership is restricted, and the outlook above will expand and strengthen the construct of authentic leadership (Berkovich, 2014; Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018; Ladkin, 2021).

Scholars argue that authentic leadership should not be conceptualised in the same way as other leadership approaches, where traditional skills can be enhanced as authentic leadership is contextual (Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018; Chully and Jose, 2022) and learning interventions should be appropriate and suitable for aspiring or inauthentic leaders. Although, there has been a significant amount of research on leadership and leadership development, this holistic viewpoint has not been applied to the construct.

The dearth of studies on authentic leadership beyond the Western narrative is one of the reasons why this research is important and timely. This is because the contributions of the study will advance the domain as the nature of leadership varies within and across nations. Accordingly, Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber (2009) assert that conducting cross-contextual investigations is necessary for authentic leadership research as these efforts will determine whether the construct is widely perceived as a positive root construct, regardless of its specific form as advanced by extant literature (Peus *et al.*, 2012; Tibbs *et al.*, 2016). A further benefit of investigating authentic leadership across diverse contexts is that it allows researchers to examine leaders' behaviours, emotions, and characteristics in their natural environment (Kelemen, Matthews and Breevaart, 2020). As authentic leaders navigate through paradoxes and cross-cultural variances, thus context cannot be neglected due to the role it plays in leader follower interactions (Lord, Brown and Freiberg, 1999; du Plessis and Boshoff, 2018c).

Although, context has been overlooked (Gardiner, 2016) there is a tacit understanding that the differences between authentic leaders in terms of challenges and motivations

are primarily based on their experiences and life stories (Gardner *et al.*, 2005; Shamir and Eilam, 2005; Sergeeva and Kortantamer, 2021). Surprisingly, little reference is made to the lived experience of the local actors (Ladkin and Spiller, 2013; Sinclair, 2013). Therefore, a need to further explore the role of context across diverse locations including developing economies (Gardiner, 2016).

To put the discussion above into perspective, business enterprises are viewed as vehicles for achieving sustainable development goals (SDG) due to their significant impact on the issues addressed by these goals (Storey, Killian and O'Regan, 2017; Weybrecht, 2017; Corriveau, 2020). Therefore, it is proposed that the achievement of these SDGs require authentic leaders, who must become agents that seek to address societal challenges (Parkes, Buono and Howaidy, 2017; Haertle *et al.*, 2017). These leaders are suited for these objectives, because they perform well in ambiguous situations, particularly when facilitating innovation and transformation, providing motivation for their followers (Ahmed *et al.*, 2018).

This echoes the more heroic interpretations of authentic leadership (Ladkin and Spiller, 2013; Alvesson and Einola, 2019) as there is limited understanding on the developmental process and the role of followers in this process. Thus, extant literature is replete with examples of renowned leaders, who have been judged authentic based on their accomplishments and broader influence on their followers. For example, Mother Theresa is a compelling example of an authentic leader who assembled 4,000 missionaries worldwide (George, 2003). The literature, except for a few scholars (Nyberg and Sveningsson, 2014; Sendjaya *et al.*, 2016; Sidani and Rowe, 2018) have ignored the weaknesses of these authentic leaders. These scholars suggest that authentic leaders may also exhibit questionable behaviours, such as the same Mother Theresa receiving questionable donations from a known embezzler Charles Keating in the 1910s. In contrast, Skilling of Enron is a known example of a leader who lacked authenticity. However, business professionals praised Skilling's leadership prior to his downfall (Stein, 2007; Johnsen, 2018). Less prominent but no less significant are

examples of authentic leaders who have emerged in smaller organisations. As existing conceptualisations of authentic leadership draw attention to the individual life stories and triggering events of famous authentic leaders, even though these fewer known leaders have acquired legitimacy as authentic. Perhaps as opposed to echoing the heroic actions of famous authentic leaders, it may be more beneficial to analyse the unique experiences of authentic leaders within organisations. In attempting to identify factors that inspire authentic leadership development and the uncovering challenges they encounter.

This is crucial, because formal positions within organisations give leadership some meaning, but fail to explain why some superiors are not viewed as leaders (Bedeian and Hunt, 2006; DeRue and Ashford, 2010). Similarly, why some individuals are perceived as leaders despite not holding formal leadership positions (Charan and Tichy, 2000; Spreitzer and Quinn, 2001). This becomes fascinating as managers are assigned roles within the organisation to increase value (Mintzberg, 1993; Monzani *et al.*, 2019); however, their acceptance is contingent on their subordinates (Hollander and Julian, 1978).

Drawing from the above and the efforts of scholars in examining the positive consequences of the construct (Caza and Jackson, 2011; Peus *et al.*, 2012; Liu *et al.*, 2018; Nübold, Van Quaquebeke and Hülshager, 2020), except for a few scholars who argue that authentic leadership may also be linked to adverse outcomes. Extant literature is replete with studies that affirm the positive consequences of a follower's perception that a leader is authentic. However, more research should be conducted on the factors that contribute to these perceptions (Fields, 2007; Gardner *et al.*, 2011).

Few questions about followers' perceptions of authentic leadership have been posed until recently (Steffens *et al.*, 2016; Nübold, Van Quaquebeke and Hülshager, 2020). Therefore, it is unsurprising that existing research has not thoroughly explored the followers' perceptions of authentic leadership (Peus *et al.*, 2012; Leroy *et al.*, 2015). Indeed, it is difficult to avoid the perceptions of followers as some manifestation of

authentic leadership as scholars contend that managers must observe their own behaviour and the responses of their followers in order to uphold their leadership position (Van Vugt, Hogan and Kaiser, 2008; DeRue and Ashford, 2010; Monzani *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, it is important to examine the factors that shape followers' perception of authentic leadership, as what is considered authentic in one setting may be interpreted differently in another environment.

The primary focus of this research is the investigative context, being the country with the largest economy in Africa, Nigeria provides a robust context for extending the understanding of authentic leadership. This country is recognised as a trading nation, and its social practises likely reflect those of other West African nations (Ezeh, Ezeh and Otuagbo, 2019; Otekunrin and Sawicka, 2019). Context offers a fresh perspective to the broad role of authentic leadership, which currently needs to be narrower as most of the research on authentic leadership have emerged from well established organisations and societies. Within the Nigerian context, Oil companies were chosen because they serve as a growth catalyst for developing economies (Steel and Webster, 1991; Quartey *et al.*, 2017).

The problem of identifying authentic leaders within organisations will be examined from the followers' perspective. While scholars have outlined various characteristics of authentic leaders, such as honesty, integrity, and transparency (Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017), communication skills (Gill *et al.*, 2018), self awareness (Weiss *et al.*, 2018), these characteristics alone do not ascertain authentic leadership, as it necessitates the recognition and acceptance of such leadership by followers. Similarly, extant literature also offers some implicit guiding principles that include self-acclamation, occupying prominent roles in the organisation or society and undertaking responsibilities associated with the collective good (George, 2003; Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017; du Plessis and Boshoff, 2018a) to be labelled an authentic leader. These are valuable suggestions; however, this research only includes authentic leaders identified by two or more followers within an organisation. To

identity authentic leaders within organisations, a follower attribution perspective has been adopted (Bradley-Cole, 2018). This represents the methodological starting point in the research.

Against this background, this thesis makes a case for exploring the construct within Nigeria. It contends for a viewpoint that captures authentic leadership outside Western narratives and identifies the factors that shape followers' perceptions. The study seeks to contribute to the academic debates on the conceptualisation of authentic leadership, exploring authentic leadership through the lived experiences of leaders and followers within the developing economy context. Furthermore, expanding on the complexities and contextual components that have thus far received limited attention. Therefore, by adopting a qualitative lens, the study draws on empirical data from semi-structured interviews to offer a broader understanding of the construct. The inquiry will, in the end, not only contribute to the advancement of the domain, but it will also offer practical consequences for organisations that are looking for effective leadership.

1.3 Research Aim

The background of the study provided in section 1.2 revealed that the primary subjects of the study are authentic leaders and followers within Nigerian oil companies. Thus, the main aim of this study is to examine authentic leadership within the context of a developing economy. The study seeks to identify the key components of authentic leadership, identify factors that inspire its development, explore the challenges that authentic leaders encounter, and illuminate the process of becoming an authentic leader.

1.4 Research Objectives

To attain the above research aim, five research objectives were developed as follows:

RO1. To identify the key components of authentic leadership.

- RO2. To examine the factors that inspire authentic leadership development.
- RO3. To explore the challenges encountered by authentic leaders within a developing economy.
- RO4. To examine actions that shape the follower's perception of authentic leadership.
- RO5. To propose an empirical based model that contributes to the understanding of authentic leadership.

1.5 Research Questions

This study will investigate the underlisted research questions on authentic leadership. These questions were framed from the literature review and are as follows:

- RQ1. What are the components of authentic leadership?
- RQ2. What are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders?
- RQ3. What are the challenges authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy?
- RQ4. What specific actions shape the followers' perceptions of authentic leaders?

1.6 Methodological Approach

The view that the methodological approach provides the best way of conducting research is grounded and well defined. As such research methodology is described as the science and philosophy that shapes a study. It captures perspectives on the nature of knowledge discovery, specifically how it is created (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Gray, 2022; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). The methodology acts as a compass that allows the readership to navigate the research wholistically by allowing access to the underpinning assumptions that shape the study.

Three main philosophies; positivism, realism and interpretivism, have emerged within extant literature with several others described as being a variation or an extension of these three philosophies (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2018; Babbie, 2020). Interestingly, Lincoln, Lynham and Guba (2011) state that a thorough understanding of philosophies and their associated assumptions allow scholars recognise the limitations of the different viewpoints.

Based on the exploratory nature of the study, it adopts the interpretivist philosophy as this viewpoint emphasises the uniqueness of human inquiry (Schwandt, 1994). A key outcome of adopting this philosophy was that it provided a rich understanding of true interpretations and perceptions of the local actors (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023) enabling access to insider knowledge from the respondents' experiences.

Consistent with the preceding paragraph, a critical understanding of research philosophies, influence selecting and applying an appropriate research method, and ultimately research design. The research method describes the technique of executing research and in broad terms, there are two primary approaches to conducting research: quantitative and qualitative methods, respectively (Babbie, 2020; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). The quantitative method draws from the methodological philosophies of positivism and neo-positivism (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014) that follow a stringent research plan preceding the real investigation. In contrast, qualitative research employs diverse methodological approaches shaped by varied theoretical principles. This approach seeks to describe social interactions and the lived experiences of research respondents. This method also provides appropriate frames to capture people's lived experiences (Yin, 2015; Galloway and Haniff, 2015; Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017).

The qualitative approach was adopted for this study based on the paucity of research and empirical evidence on authentic leadership. Also, the concerted attempt to uncover insightful information on followers' perceptions that will stimulate further debates on authentic leadership. Also, the qualitative method was adopted, because

the researcher sought to capture meaning and not merely sequences (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). This was appropriate as qualitative studies chart the path towards uncovering complex phenomena (Cypress, 2017).

Drawing on the recommendations of Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2023), authentic leaders and followers were selected through purposive and the snowballing sampling technique. The selection of purposive sampling follows Marshall and Rossman (2014) recommendation that the sampling frame should be selected based on the research objective. In light of the above, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 46 participants. These participants were separated into two groups: 16 authentic leaders, and 30 followers. This allowed the capturing of thick and rich descriptions from the lived experiences of local actors (Morse, 2015) and following the advice of Boyatzis (1998) and King, Horrocks and Brooks (2019) thematic analysis was chosen because it provided a structured procedure for highlighting key themes within specific data sets. Chapter five provides an extended discussion of the methodological choices that shaped the study.

1.7 Originality of study

Originality in research is a core criterion in assessing success of a study (Nightingale, 1984; Murray, 2017) with debates on what constitutes originality in a PhD been explored as far back as the 19th century (Wilkins, Neri and Lean, 2019). Within research, scholars have discussed various ways in which it can be demonstrated such as the presentation of discoveries and new knowledge. Several higher education institutions, scholars and examining bodies have also offered discussions on how to show originality within a piece of work (Clarke and Lunt, 2014; Phillips and Johnson, 2022).

Despite these varying arguments on the appropriate way of demonstrating this, there is implicit consensus that originality is at the heart of PhD regulations as it is awarded

as emphasised by Phillips (2015, p. 101) “for an original contribution to knowledge”. A discussion on the study’s contributions will be provided in section 1.8.

Scholars have proposed conditions that, if satisfied, will demonstrate originality, and validate the contribution of researchers to knowledge (Phillips and Pugh, 1994; Guetzkow, Lamont and Mallard, 2004; Murray, 2017). However, this study draws on the recommendation of Phillips and Pugh (1994) cited in Eggleston (2001) and Guetzkow, Lamont and Mallard (2004). See the adapted schedule below highlighting how originality may be demonstrated in Table 1.

Table 1 Criteria for Originality

Originality by Guetzkow, Lamont and Mallard (2004)	Tick		Tick	Originality by Phillips and Pugh (1994)
Exploration of a new topic			*	Research Category <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A new piece of study • Extending an original study • Original study planned by a senior colleague • New research areas • Exploring an uncharted path • New Knowledge
The use of a new approach, theory, method, or data			*	Technique Category <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A new technique, observation, or result • Coordination of multiple research activities • New synthesis • Cross disciplinary and methodologies
Conducting research in an understudied area	*		*	Evidence Category <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New empirical study • New interpretation of existing material • Cross country investigation • New evidence on extant issues
Offering new findings	*			

Adapted from Phillips and Pugh (1994); Guetzkow, Lamont and Mallard (2004)

Based on Table 1, Phillips and Pugh (1994) suggest that originality by a scholar can be demonstrated in 14 plausible ways; these approaches are aptly captured under 3

distinct but related categories as presented in Table 1 above. In accordance with Phillips and Pugh (1994), this study demonstrates originality in the three categories of research, technique, and evidence and in two of the four broad practices proposed by Guetzkow, Lamont and Mallard (2004) as highlighted above. These are further discussed in the succeeding subsections below.

1.7.1 Research category

This study demonstrates originality in this category by extending original studies. This research extends the seminal works within the domain by offering an authentic leadership model underpinned by empirical evidence and expanding the understanding of the phenomenon beyond the prevalent Western conceptualisation. It also brings to the fore the criticality of the followers' role within authentic leadership, challenging the established debates on the passive role of followers.

1.7.2 Technique category

Typically, academics use pilot studies to refine data collection instruments prior to the main study. The study intended to triangulate evidence obtained from the pilot studies' data sets with the results of the main study. This was not accomplished because the self-proclaimed authentic leaders, such as Bill George and Faith Wambura Ngunjiri, who were purposively selected for the pilot study from the extant literature did not respond and partake in the research as intended. However, the five most cited researchers in the field were contacted to validate the domain's research gaps. Fred Walumbwa, Bruce Avolio, William Gardner, Fred Luthans and Alice Eagly who have a combined citation of over 500,000 were among the authors who responded and offered their views. This study also includes a systematic literature review that evaluates the boundaries of the domain, followers' perception of authentic leadership and provides insights into the current state of the field.

1.7.3 Evidence category

Under this category, this thesis demonstrates originality by providing empirical data on authentic leadership, which is sparse and limited. This study provides fresh

perspectives on the role of perceptions in the process of developing authentic leadership. In addition, new evidence from a developing economy context is provided, which extant studies have neglected. The thesis explored empirically uncharted territory by gathering data from such contexts and bringing new perspectives to the academic conversation. Beyond the theoretical and empirical contributions, the study is embedded within the larger academic environment. Extant literature is appraised to shed light on the gaps that the thesis sought to address ensuring the originality of the study is both clear and supported.

1.8 Contributions of Study

Scholars suggest that a doctoral thesis should offer new insights, perspectives and knowledge to existing domain of knowledge (Dwivedi, Ravishankar and Simintiras, 2015). This is described as crucial as research seeks to broaden existing understanding of a phenomenon or subject of enquiry. Consequently, the thorough review of extant literature and exploration of contemporary debates were essential components of the research as this provided the knowledge base, furthermore, gaps in existing literature were identified, and an appropriate research design developed to address the gaps. The contribution of the study is both meaningful and incremental as methodological, theoretical and empirical contributions were made (Dwivedi, Ravishankar and Simintiras, 2015).

1.8.1 Methodological contributions

In general, methodological contributions facilitate the revaluation of prevailing inquiries in a more rigorous way and addresses new questions (Bergh *et al.*, 2022). By using a systematic literature review (SLR) approach an evidence based methodology, the study provides unbiased data that capture knowledge gaps in the literature and opens new lines of research enquiry. This is because the SLR enables an objective appraisal and analysis of data (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003; Denyer and Tranfield, 2009; Harrison, Paul and Burnard, 2016; Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017).

1.8.2 Empirical contributions

The context makes the study's empirical contribution clear. This study adds empirically to the understanding of authentic leadership as it focuses on businesses within the Nigerian oil sector (Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018). The study provides insights into the peculiar challenges of authentic leadership within the context of study. This was novel and meaningful as the connection between challenges and factors that inspire the development of authentic leadership became evident.

Furthermore, the study provides support on the value of authentic leadership within organisations and by extension the broader society. This was done by offering evidence from the rich data gathered on the actions that shape perceptions of followers. This data would be valuable in the design and development of leadership interventions by organisations and policy makers.

1.8.3 Theoretical contributions

By examining the perceptions, and meanings that authentic leaders and their followers ascribe to their experience's, this study provided new theoretical insights on authentic leadership. Also, by uncovering new components of the construct, the study expands the existing body of literature in the field. With evidence that establish that four key factors, which can occur at any level of the organisation, can inspire authentic leadership, this study offers a path for authentic leadership development.

The model depicted in figure 26, extends conceptual links to the subcomponents while presenting the six components of authentic leadership. The model reveals a relationship between authentic leadership's challenges and the factors that facilitates its development, which is not made clear in the body of existing literature.

Authentic leadership emphasises the uniqueness of leaders and followers' perspectives and how these distinctions influence sense making within organisations. However, extant literature is not clear on the tools for attaining leadership development and repair, if necessary. The study argues that while leaders and followers share a common understanding of the essential components of authentic

leadership, there are specific subcomponents where they diverge, which have implications for the practical repair and development of leadership, supporting the claim that understanding authentic leadership requires consideration of followers' perspectives.

The literature on authentic leadership challenges has not been adequately explored as majority of studies have primarily focused on the challenges that these leaders address within organisations (Mhatre and Conger, 2011; Crawford et al., 2020), with only a few studies highlighting the challenges that authentic leaders face when working with underrepresented groups of people and diverse cultures (Ladkin and Spiller, 2013; Fine, 2017; Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017). This research contributes to the corpus of knowledge by identifying the distinct categories of leadership problems that authentic leaders encounter.

A key contribution of this study is, managerial the implications for human resource practices within organisations, as evidenced by the components identified, particularly relational transparency and concern for people. Relational transparency, characterised by disclosure, vulnerability, and a learning orientation, fosters enhanced work engagement among employees, leading to improved organisational performance, as observed from the respondents' feedback.

Also, the concern for people, a key component of authentic leadership, ensures an alignment of strategic value, resulting in lower turnover rates. Employees perceive themselves not merely as tools but as valuable members of the team, which contributes to better organisational outcomes. The alignment between a organisations HR practice and the leadership approach of its CEO is crucial because when there is synergy between these aspects, it impacts the culture and its outlook.

Finally, as a key theoretical contribution, the thesis proposed a definition of authentic leadership and outlined a research agenda for the future.

1.9 Structure of the thesis

This thesis is structured across three sections. The first section explains the research's purpose, context, and scope. The second section examines the extant literature on authenticity, authentic leadership, and developing economies' context. The final section summarises the study's methodological decisions, findings, discussions, and conclusions. The details of the individual chapters are as follows:

Chapter 1: Overview: The chapter provides an overview of the context and justification for the study. The aim, objectives and research questions are outlined, positioning these within the larger context of the study. An overview of the methodology is presented with a discussion on the originality and contributions of the study.

Chapter 2: Leadership, Leadership Development and Authenticity: Chapter two is the first of the three chapters that review the literature on leadership, leadership development and authenticity within the study. It lays the groundwork upon which the following two chapters on authentic leadership and context are constructed.

Chapter 3: Systematic Literature Review: This chapter presents the findings from an extensive examination of the authentic leadership domain. This section examines the academic literature on the construct. Furthermore, it identifies the factors that inspire authentic leadership development, describes the followers' perception of the leadership construct, and investigates how these interpretations influence authentic leadership.

Chapter 4: Context of Study: The chapter offers an overview of the study's context. It begins with a discussion on the classifications of economies. It also explores the main differences between developed and developing economies. In addition, it describes the country's historical, political, economic, and geographical context. The chapter concludes with an analysis of the Nigerian oil industry, justifying the study's relevance within the context of a developing economy.

Chapter 5: Research Methodology: This chapter describes the methodological decisions that shaped the design of the study. It provides justifications for methodological choices made, which serve as the basis for data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

Chapter 6: Findings- Part A: Chapter six is the first of the two chapters that present the study's findings. Chapter six focuses on answering the first two research questions of the study: What are the components of authentic leadership, and what are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders? The chapter begins with a brief overview of localities within Nigeria, where the respondents are selected to provide the context for the findings. Proceeding to outline the six components of authentic leadership and four factors that inspire authentic leadership development.

Chapter 7: Finding- Part B: Chapter seven is the last of the two chapters that present the study's findings. This chapter presents the results from the last two research questions: What challenges do authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy, and what actions shape employee perceptions of authentic leaders? The chapter highlights the four challenges of authentic leaders, broadly described in two categories: as personal and contextual challenges. This chapter also identifies the four critical actions that shape the follower's perception of authentic leadership.

Chapter 8: Discussion Chapter: This chapter provides a discussion on the relationship between the empirical findings and extant literature, highlighting the significance and associated implications of the study findings. The findings are synthesised, and an empirical model is presented, broadening the current understanding of the construct, and widening the debates that will stir future research efforts.

Chapter 9: Conclusion Chapter: This chapter describes the research's contributions, implications, and limitations. It provides an overview of the study, while highlighting the contributions for consideration. This chapter provides an insightful thesis summary and lays the foundation for future research. Figure 1 depicts the structure of this study.

Figure 1 Layout of the Thesis

CHAPTER 2. LEADERSHIP AND AUTHENTICITY

INTRODUCTION

The second chapter offers an entry point into the three-chapter review of the literature relevant to the study. It serves as the basis for the next two chapters, which discuss authentic leadership and context. This chapter examines the construct of leadership and leadership development before probing the concept of authenticity. As a result, the chapter is split across four major sections. The initial section provides a summary of leadership's definitions, illuminating the diverse perspectives of scholars on this elusive construct. Based on this, a brief historical account is offered, highlighting the emergence of key leadership theories in the field. The second section evaluates leadership theories closely linked to authentic leadership, where distinctions emerge that are interesting and crucial to the study. The third section provides an overview of the debates on leadership development. While leadership scholars are keen on theory development, there are broad arguments on leadership development with a paucity of research across contexts. Finally, the concluding section examines the notion of authenticity, highlighting the complexities inherent to its definition, emergence, and application. See Figure 2 for an overview of the three review chapters of the study.

Figure 2 Literature review map

2.1 Leadership

Leadership is a construct that has been the subject of continuous scholarly discourse (Silverthorne, 2001; Dionne *et al.*, 2014; Northouse, 2021; Kouzes and Posner, 2023). It has also attracted the attention of practitioners and scholars who are interested in defining leadership approaches that facilitate positive organisational outcomes (George, 2003; Harrison, 2018). The term leader dates to 1300s, but “leadership” emerged in the 1800s (Stogdill, 1974). Leadership is argued to be the most influential factor in attaining organisational success (Mumford *et al.*, 2000; Gardner *et al.*, 2020) and a basic Google Scholar search for “leadership” returned 5,260,000 results on the 20th of May 2023. Likewise, searching for *lead on the Wiley online library yielded 5,266,622 results. A cursory examination of the result categories reveals an explosion of literature by researchers and practitioners over the years. For example, the enquiry conducted on March 9, 2021, yielded the following outcomes: from 1791 to 1988, there were 1,007,531 results. From 1989 to 2009, the search yielded 2,105,598 results; from 2010 to 2021, the number increased to 2,362,535. This trend was also evident in other databases, such as Web of Science and Sage journals, where analogous searches were conducted. The attention the phenomenon has received from mainstream literature demonstrates its significance (Northouse, 2018; Northouse, 2021). Yet, the construct lacks a consensual definition, which may be unattainable (Vroom and Jago, 2007; Antonakis, Day and Schyns, 2012; Omeihe *et al.*, 2023). In fact, Stodgill and Bass (1981) assert that the number of definitions are as diverse as the individuals who have attempted to describe it. Table 2 provides an overview of the definitions offered by scholars.

Table 2 Definitions of Leadership

<i>Authors</i>	<i>Definitions</i>
Moore (1927)	"The ability to impress the will of the leader on those led and induce obedience, respect, loyalty, and cooperation (p. 124)."
Bogardus (1934)	"Is a process in which the activities of many are organised to move in a specific direction by one (p. 5)."
Reuter (1941) in Ciulla (2020)	"Leadership is the result of an ability to persuade or direct men, apart from the prestige or power that comes from office or external circumstances (p.133)."
Stogdill (1950)	"Leadership may be considered as the process (act) of influencing the activities of an organised group in its efforts toward goal setting and goal achievement (p. 3)."
Katz and Kahn (1978)	"The influential increment over and above mechanical compliance with the routine directives of the organisation (p. 528)."
Jacobs and Jaques (1990)	"Leadership is a process of giving purpose (meaningful direction) to collective effort and causing willing effort to be expended to achieve purpose (p. 281)."
Rost (1993)	"Leadership is an influence relationship among leaders and their collaborators who intend real changes that reflect their mutual purposes (p. 102)."
Drath and Palus (1994)	"Leadership is the process of making sense of what people are doing together, so that people will understand and be committed (p. 4)."
DeSpain (2000)	"An imperfect art practiced by those who lead in which the leader defines reality for his or her followers, while creating and nurturing a vision of a new, better reality to come (p. 9)."
Barker (2001)	"A process of transformative change where the ethics of individuals are integrated into the mores of a community as a means of evolutionary social development (p. 491)."
Vroom and Jago (2007)	"Leadership as a process of motivating people to work together collaboratively to accomplish great things (p. 18)."
Yukl (2010)	"Leadership is the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish shared objectives (p. 8)."

Lussier and Achua (2015)	“Leadership is the influencing process of leaders and followers to achieve organisational objectives through change (p. 6).”
Cortellazzo, Bruni and Zampieri (2019)	“The leader is understood as a person who guides a group of people, an organisation, or empowers their transformational processes (p.2).”

Source : Adapted from Harrison (2018) and Ciulla (2020)

Interestingly, Ciulla (2020) observed that the definitions of leadership have undergone changes over time from an early emphasis on the “will” of the leaders, where this was impressed on their followers in the 1920s, to the 1940s, where persuasion became prevalent, to the 1960s where influence became salient in the definitions that highlight “relationship within context (p .6).”

These definitions illustrate how scholars have attempted to grasp the construct (Yukl, 2010; Yukl, 2012; Hernandez *et al.*, 2011), reiterating Northouse (2018) claim that the possibilities for defining the construct of leadership are infinite. In a similar vein, Rost (1991) asserts that “attempts to define leadership have been confusing, varied, disorganised, idiosyncratic, muddled, and, according to conventional wisdom, largely unrewarding (p. 99).” With suggestions that neither an accurate nor erroneous definition of leadership exists, but only diverse perspectives offered by scholars (Winston and Patterson, 2006; Summerfield, 2014; Ciulla, 2020). All of these prove that scholars are unrelenting in their study of the construct (Fairholm, 2002).

2.1.1 Historical overview of leadership theories

The domain of leadership is replete with theories rich in content and approaches (Lloyd-Walker and Walker, 2011; Harrison, 2018). Considering this, George *et al.* (2007) state that over the past fifty years, more than a thousand research studies have been conducted to develop an ideal profile of effective leaders. However, leadership scholars are yet to agree on a specific description of great leaders. For the most part, emerging leadership theories have been derived from the Western context, specifically the United States. Therefore, not surprising, that most of these theories have been individually underpinned. The predominant themes within these conceptualisations

have yet to be representative of the dynamic nature of the construct across diverse contexts. In particular, the expectations of followers have not been emphasised. The dominant outlook portrays followers as passive rather than active partners in leadership interactions (Rost, 1993; Gill, 2011; Western, 2019). Therefore, further research from diverse contexts, particularly developing economies, will contribute to the understanding of the leadership, offering a broader perspective of the active role followers play in leadership (Harrison, Paul and Burnard, 2016; Omeihe *et al.*, 2023).

Leadership has been conceptualised and examined from diverse perspectives, resulting in a multiplicity of styles and approaches (Western, 2019; Northouse, 2021), with several theories emerging over time (Dinh *et al.*, 2014). This section provides an overview of the prominent theories within the field by tracing the evolution within the leadership domain (Jago, 1982). The appraisal commences by exploring leadership theories and tracing their development throughout the previous century, shifting from the notion of extraordinary leaders to include traits, behaviour, contingency, and advancing into emergent theories (Stogdill, 1975; Khan, Bhat and Hussanie, 2017). Furthermore, the subsequent section explores leadership theories linked to authentic leadership. The purpose of the distinction is to demonstrate an understanding of the relationship between authentic leadership and other closely related theories.

2.1.1.1 *Great Man theory*

The Great Man theory was advanced by 18th century scholars like Carlyle, Nietzsche, and Galton (Vroom and Jago, 2007; Spector, 2016). This theory characterises leaders, typically historical figures with lofty objectives, such as Winston Churchill and Nelson Mandela. The perspective asserts that great men altered the course of history, and that these leaders are heroic examples (Grint, 2011; Harrison, 2018). The theory posits that leaders are born, not made. These great men steered society to the right path and are further described as visionaries. In contrast, other scholars have described great leaders as “mere puppets of social forces” (Vroom and Jago, 2007, p. 19), claiming that these forces select leaders and shape their behaviour to drive shared interests.

Between the 1930s and 1940s, the theory declined (Klingborg, Moore and Varea-Hammond, 2006) paving the way for development of other theories within the field.

2.1.1.2 Trait theory

There have been active efforts to distinguish leaders from non leaders (Bass, 1990; Bryman, 1992; Fouquet and Brummer, 2023) because leadership success and achievement are contingent upon certain traits. The perspective is embedded in Carlyle's (1841-1907) writings on heroic leaders (Fairholm, 2002) and it emphasises influential leaders' desirable or innate traits (Wright, 1996). Proponents of this theory assessed the qualities of great leaders to identify the traits that differentiate effective leaders from their ineffective counterparts (Fairholm, 2002; Bass, 1990). The theory is rooted in the biographies of heroic individuals (Jennings, 1960), thereby supporting the argument that uncovering leadership traits require a cursory examination of leaders. George Washington (Clark, 1995), Napoleon Bonaparte, and Martin Luther King, Jr. (Carson, 1987) are among the examples of these admirable leaders. The search for these traits from great leaders led to the development of an inexhaustive list of leadership traits (Harrison, 2018).

The research on the trait's theory began by focusing on general personality traits. Then it identified traits across various circumstances, such as appearance, self-confidence, and social background (Stogdill, 1974). In the seminal study by Stogdill (1948), 124 studies across 43 years on traits were appraised. Stogdill categorised all the traits identified into six groups. The traits linked to leadership were "capacity, achievement, responsibility, participation, status, and situation" implying that these contributed to organisational success. However, Klingborg, Moore and Varea-Hammond (2006) argue that traits alone do not adequately describe leadership, hence its description as optimistic yet idealistic (Rost, 1993; Zaccaro, 2007). The trait approach has been criticised due to several limitations, including the need for a definitive inventory of traits that effective leaders must possess (Stogdill, 1948). This resulted in minimal attention from scholars over the years, as it was challenging to identify common

qualities shared by all leaders (Harrison, 2018; Northouse, 2021). In a similar vein, Vroom and Jago (2007) claim that another core limitation of this theory is that it is not measurable or quantifiable because if it were, it would have been easier to place leaders with leadership traits in the appropriate positions. In addition, it is characterised as being rudimentary and variable, making it an unreliable foundation for leadership development (Rost, 1993). However, contemporary leadership theories demonstrate the enduring nature of this leadership perspective.

This enduring nature is evident in current leadership theories as the perspective re-emerged in the 1980s (Rost, 1993), and justifications were made for this resurgence (Northouse, 2018). For instance, Goleman (2006) research on emotional intelligence draws from the traits perspective. Similarly, Kirkpatrick and Locke (1991) research suggests that leadership has evolved from trait to behaviour and situational perspectives. The resurgence of the trait perspective is being redefined, with the personal qualities of leaders reemerging within the literature. Debates suggest that while these qualities are essential, they alone are not sufficient to attain organisational success (Northouse, 2021).

2.1.1.3 Behavioural theory

In the 1950s and 1960s, disillusionment with the trait theory led to the emergence of the behavioural theory (Rost, 1993). As behaviours are more susceptible to observation, this perspective has been described as a more empirical approach to the study of leadership (Stogdill and Coons, 1957). The behavioural theory emphasises leadership behaviours that enhance organisational effectiveness (Rost, 1993). It evaluates the leadership behaviours towards subordinates and evaluates the behaviour of leaders in relation to their leadership actions (Northouse, 2021). The perspective was described as a more scientific approach to leadership study as behaviours are more susceptible to measurement and observation (Stogdill and Coons, 1957).

Lewin, Lippitt and White (1939) conducted the initial study at Iowa State University. The study compared autocratic and democratic leadership approaches. However, the behavioural theory is argued to have originated from research conducted at Ohio State University and the University of Michigan, respectively. Ohio State University researchers used questionnaires to investigate the behavioural dimensions of consideration and initiating structure (Vroom and Jago, 2007; Hemphill and Coons, 1950; Stogdill, 1974; Yukl, 2010; Harrison, 2018).

The initiating structure stresses task completion, while the consideration dimension emphasises relationship behaviours. While scholars from the University of Michigan validated the Ohio State University's findings. This group described working dimensions that included interactions, techniques, and achievements (Fairholm, 2002; Vroom and Jago, 2007). The University of Michigan's study identified two important orientations: employee orientation and production orientation (Lussier and Achua, 2001; Harrison, 2018).

This perspective initiated the recognition of context. It shifted from the trait perspective's emphasis on the influence of key leaders to the recognition that situations influence the behaviour of leaders (Vroom and Jago, 2007). The most prominent model was therefore proposed (Northouse, 2021). This behaviour-based matrix explaining the behaviours of leaders was developed by Mouton and Blake (1964).

Concern for people and tasks were juxtaposed in the behavioural model to define five leadership styles. Though, the authors suggest that the team manager is the most effective. The behaviourally based grid has been criticised extensively because of its focus on the outcomes of leader behaviours, (Gill, 2011; Northouse, 2018). For this reason, the perspective advanced the study of leadership but did not offer a framework or model to guide practice as the interaction between leader behaviours and success was wide-ranging across studies.

The primary distinction between the traits and behaviour perspectives is that the traits perspective focuses on how leaders appear, while the behaviour perspective focuses on their actions. Other behaviour based theories have emerged, examining leadership perceptions, interaction, and exchange (Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995; Hollander, 1997). The surge in leadership research overlapped the efforts of scholars who sought to investigate the rigours of management. With suggestions that the confusion between leadership and management emerged from this perspective. Furthermore, the inadequate consideration of the influence of context on leadership led to the emergence of the contingency perspective.

2.1.1.4 Contingency theory

This theory emerged due to the limitations of the behavioural perspective, which did not adequately address the inherent complexities of the business world (Fairholm, 2002; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004). This was critical as the combination of traits and behaviour offered new opportunities for leadership effectiveness. The contingency leadership theory explores the efficacy of leaders in various circumstances (Gill, 2011; Fiedler, 2005; Deshwal and Ali, 2020) as it posits that leaders adapt their behaviours to situational exigencies to ensure followers achieve their objectives (Western, 2019). Furthermore, the perspective explores the diverse variables that influence the selection of leadership styles, behaviours (Fairholm, 2015) as the perspective argues that leadership action must suit the emergent complexities leaders encounter. Therefore, there is no ideal leadership approach.

Fiedler (1967) a proponent of this theory emphasised relationship and task but argued that, situational demands influence leadership effectiveness. Fiedler (1978) proposed a model investigating leadership traits and situational variables (Gill, 2011). Based on a leader's assessment using the least preferred co-worker scale (LPC), the model classified leaders into relationship and task motivated clusters. Since a leader's motivation is stable and long-lasting (Vroom and Jago, 2007), the findings of Fiedler (1967) suggest that it is more closely related to the trait than the behavioural

perspective of leadership. Fiedler analysed two types of leaders across eight situational groups based on (a) leader–member relations, (b) follower–task structure, and (c) leader–position power. The research contends that leaders should be placed in situations that suit their approaches.

However, Fielders model is riddled with criticisms and inconsistencies (Yukl, 2010; Northouse, 2018) and has generated significant controversy (Vecchio, 1977; Kerr, Von Glinow and Schriesheim, 1977; Vecchio, 1987). These criticisms are based on the proposed scale's lack of validation. Another limitation of this perspective is that it defines leadership in terms of circumstances while ignoring the sentiments leaders elicit (Fairholm, 2015). Despite the limitations of the perspective, it advanced the traits and situational perspectives at the time. Table 3 provides a summary of the earliest established leadership theories.

Table 3: Evolution of Leadership Research and Theory

Historical Thread	Descriptions	Key Authors
Great Man	The perspective argues that great men changed history and these leaders are heroic models.	Carlyle's (1841/1907) essays
Trait Theory	It is rooted in the biographies of heroic individuals. It emphasises the desirable or inborn traits of effective leaders. Personal qualities, character, and personality.	Stogdill (1948); Stogdill (1974) Mann (1959) Jennings (1960) Bass (1990) Kirkpatrick and Locke (1991)
Behavioural Theory	The perspective was described as a more scientific approach to leadership study as behaviours are more susceptible to measurement and observation. The perspective assesses how leaders behave with specificity to their actions in leadership enactment.	Lewin et al. (1939) Hemphill and Coons (1950) Stogdill and Coons (1957) Mouton and Blake (1964)

Contingency Theory	The perspective asserts that leadership is not decontextualised as it emerges from specific environments.	Fielder (1967; 1978) Vroom and Yetton (1973) Hersey and Blanchard (1979) Vecchio (1987) Yukl (2010)
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There is an ongoing debate regarding the nature of leadership. Multiple perspectives have emerged since the introduction of the Great Man theory as evidenced by the table 3 above. While the domain has been plagued with varying arguments, these arguments have contributed to the understanding of the construct. The following section examines other leadership theories, particularly those closely linked with authentic leadership, such as transformational, servant, ethical, and charismatic leadership (Ofori, 2008; Kiersch and Peters, 2017; Anderson *et al.*, 2017).

Authentic leadership is also briefly introduced to provide a context for the arguments within the sub sections.

2.2 Emergent leadership theories

Existing literature supports the argument that effective leadership is emerging in response to organisational and global complexities. Given this claim, the section examines prominent leadership theories from the late 20th century and the emerging theories of the 21st century. These theories have been closely linked to the authentic leadership theory and are collectively described as positive leadership approaches within extant literature (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Ahmad, Gao and Hali, 2017).

2.2.1 Transformational leadership

For over 35 years, transformational leadership has been the subject of extensive research (Harrison, 2018; Cui, Wang and Zhou, 2023) and it emerged in the 1980s in response to the turbulent business environments. Burns (1978) defines transformational leadership as a type of leadership that motivates and instils a sense

of morality in both leaders and followers, while also enabling and promoting change. The scholar first proposed the theory of transformational leadership, which was later refined by Bass and Avolio (1990); Bass and Avolio (1993). This theory was refined by advancing a model with four essential characteristics “idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration (Dionne *et al.*, 2004).” The model has been refined further to incorporate vision. This integration into transformational leadership has given rise to visionary leadership, which is beyond the scope of this study (Bennis and Nanus, 1985). In transformational leadership, the goals of followers and leaders are aligned to achieve a common objective (Fairholm, 2002; Alegbeleye and Kaufman, 2020). The leadership perspective revolves around power, and values to understand the motives of leaders, followers and how they enhance performance. The leadership theory suggests that leadership transcends the situation and is consistent across exigencies.

Critics of transformational leadership contend that these leaders convey compelling future visions (termed idealised influence) to their followers, which they then adopt (Bass and Avolio, 1993). Based on this ability, scholars argue that transformational leaders can manipulate their followers into adopting the leader's unscrupulous mission as their own (Conger and Kanungo, 1998; Bellé, 2014; Liborius, 2017). This criticism brought the ethical underpinning of transformational leadership under scrutiny (Alvesson and Sveningsson, 2013). In response, Bass and Steidlmeier (1999) made a distinction between authentic transformational and pseudo-transformational leaders. The former term was used to describe transformational leaders shaped by moral and ethical standards, while the latter term, pseudo-transformational leaders, was used to describe leaders who do not consider moral principles. The term authentic was used to characterise the moral outlook of transformational leaders. Thus, it is argued that authentic leadership emerged from Bass and Steidlmeier's criticism of transformative leaders who engage in the manipulation of their followers (Bandura and Kavussanu, 2018). Transformational Leadership is closely linked with authentic

leadership (Michie and Gooty, 2005; Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber, 2009) sharing similarities and differences discussed below (Banks *et al.*, 2016).

There is a conceptual overlap between the two positively correlated constructs (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008; Banks *et al.*, 2016; Malloy and Kavussanu, 2021). Yet, these two perspectives are distinct because the underlying dimensions of each construct are unique (Bass, 1985). Authentic leadership is linked to the four behavioural dimensions of transformational leadership; however, transformational leaders do not incorporate authentic leadership components (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008). Also, authentic leaders do not necessarily possess charisma or the ability to inspire others (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; George, 2003) .

Furthermore, a fundamental distinction between the two leadership theories is the object of change. Change is central to the early conceptualisation of transformational leadership, as advanced by Burns (1978). It is argued that change in followers, organisations, groups and, in general, people is the main objective of the transformational leadership approach. In supporting this argument, Bass (1985) argues that charisma is used as a tool and is a crucial quality for transformational leaders. In contrast, authentic leadership involves change, but it is not an essential component in its operational definition, and more importantly, charisma is neither used as a tool of influence nor a core quality of authentic leaders (Luthans and Avolio, 2003).

Likewise, transformational leaders influence and develop their followers to execute leadership functions (Avolio, Bass and Jung, 1999), but authentic leaders develop followers' general self-concept (Avolio and Gardner, 2005). Similarly, authentic leaders focus on self-transformation instead of the transformation of others, emphasised in transformational leadership theory. Interestingly, Wilson (2013), links leadership challenges to deviations from transformational leadership. So, it is not surprising that it is linked to authentic leadership. In other arguments, Clarke, Kelliher and Schedlitzki (2013) suggest that authentic leadership has potentially superseded

transformative leadership as a means of achieving effective leadership. It is worth noting that charismatic leadership was advanced by House (1976) concurrently with transformational leadership. These approaches are described as parallel perspectives (Northouse, 2021) and are also linked to authentic leadership.

2.2.2 Charismatic leadership

Charisma is the root term in charismatic leadership (Northouse, 2018) and it was used to characterise the phenomenal capabilities of humans. Weber (1947) is credited with advancing the most prominent definition of charisma in existing literature. It is defined as the possession of extraordinary powers that elevate individuals to positions of leadership (Conger, 2011). Charismatic leadership theory facilitates transformation by incorporating three essential components: enabling, energising, and envisioning (Nadler and Tushman, 1990) with the foundation of the leadership perspective being the followers' perception of leadership behaviour (Harrison, 2018).

The charismatic leadership perspective has gained traction within the leadership domain (Conger and Benjamin, 1999; Conger, 2015). Even though it is highly debated, that charismatic leadership is deeply rooted in the trait's perspective (Fairholm, 2002), with scholars further refining it (Shamir, House and Arthur, 1993; Conger and Kanungo, 1998; Conger, 2015).

Within this theory, House (1976) emphasised the influence of a leader's charisma on followers. These leaders are argued to possess personal qualities and exhibit peculiar behaviours that influence followers. For instance, qualities such as aspiration to dominate others, self-confidence and clarity on personal moral values (House, 1976; Northouse, 2021).

Similarly, charismatic leaders are described as role models that champion ideologies, beliefs and values, usually rooted in ethical dilemmas (Yukl, 2010). They show confidence in themselves and their followers, which is linked to positive outcomes (Avolio and Gibbons, 1988). These effects are usually prevalent in uncertain contexts where charismatic leaders emerge to liberate their followers (Conger and Kanungo,

1998; Northouse, 2021) and this is usually attained by conveying their vision, which inspires change (Conger and Kanungo, 1998).

Martin Luther King Jr., Mahatma Gandhi are prominent examples of leaders who have demonstrated charismatic behaviours. Interestingly, these leaders are also described as authentic leaders within extant literature. The categorisation has been largely attributed to their heroic life stories (George, 2003), which have also been criticised. Similarly, there have been debates regarding the positioning of charismatic leadership within organisations, with the central question being whether it is an asset or a liability, given that the likelihood of good or evil on a continuum. This is essential because charismatic leaders portray themselves as being superhuman (Rutan and Rice, 1981). For charismatic leadership the primary aim is to be charming, while ethical leaders are predominantly moral leaders which will be discussed in the next section.

2.2.3 Ethical leadership

Brown, Treviño and Harrison (2005) define ethical leadership “as the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision making (p. 120).” These leaders are described as truthful, trustworthy, principled, and ethical role models (Saha *et al.*, 2020). Like transformational, charismatic, servant and authentic leadership, this theory is linked to positive outcomes such as the development of trust for leaders and employee satisfaction (Monahan, 2012; Lawton and Páez, 2015). However, Brown and Treviño (2006) posit that rewards and penalties are used to enforce compliance with ethical guidelines.

These authors made a distinction between an individual's moral character and the managerial dimension of ethical leadership. The moral aspect includes the character of the ethical leader as an individual in the workplace and beyond, encompassing traits like integrity, equity, and empathy. A person of moral standing takes into account the repercussions of their actions and is recognised for being receptive to

others' concerns (Den Hartog, 2015). For this reason, focuses on the follower's perception of the leader, while the manager dimension focuses on the leaders' conscious efforts to shape the ethical behaviours of their followers, cultivating ethics within the organisation. This involves exemplifying ethical behaviour, adopting a system of rewards and penalties to ensure adherence to ethical standards. Several instances of misconduct by prominent figures in the last twenty three years have brought moral conduct under scrutiny(Den Hartog, 2015). This has amplified the expectations placed on corporations and their top executives to uphold ethical standards (Heres and Lasthuizen, 2012; Shakeel, Kruyen and Van Thiel, 2020). Ethical leadership shares similarities with transformational, transactional, spiritual, and authentic leadership but differ in conceptual terms (Hartog, 2015; Lee *et al.*, 2019).

Brown and Treviño (2006) highlight the similarities observed between transformational and ethical leadership. Both leadership theories have a genuine concern for others and serve as models upholding their ideals. However, ethical leadership places emphasis on the use of fairness, moral, and ethical conduct as a mechanism for exerting influence over subordinates. While this approach is not emphasised in the context of transformational leadership. Furthermore, these authors distinguish between ethical leadership and authentic leadership emphasising differences in terms of their underlying beliefs. While ethical leadership is guided by ethical principles, authentic leadership places emphasis on authenticity and self awareness, which are not inherent to ethical leadership.

2.2.4 Servant leadership

Scholars such as Greenleaf (1996); (Greenleaf, 2002) advanced the servant leadership theory which emphasises service as a distinguishing factor for leaders. In stark contrast to the dominant leadership perspectives, servant leadership emerged and positioned leaders as altruistic servants whose primary objective is to empower their followers (Yukl, 2010). The existing literature emphasises the leader's function while

depicting followers as passive contributors to leadership (Russell and Stone, 2002; Lemoine, Hartnell and Leroy, 2019).

This leadership theory echoes the need to serve and suggest ways leader can serve their organisations and society (Fairholm, 2015). The theory promotes the moral dimension across relationships. Servant leadership is described as “the natural feeling that one wants to serve, to serve first. Then, conscious choice brings one to aspire to lead (Greenleaf, 1998, p. 19).” Servant leadership reiterates service to others which can only be attained through effective listening (Daft, 1999). The theory maintains that leadership involves service and aspiration to leadership, a critical component being the leader's selflessness (Lussier and Achua, 2015; Eva *et al.*, 2019).

Servant leaders ask four essential questions, including whether the needs of others have been met, whether the individuals served are growing and whether they are thriving in other areas and evolving. Finally, how the leadership perspective impacts the disadvantaged society in a positive way (Fairholm, 2015). The servant leadership perspective has the potential to positively impact organisational outcomes as its key distinguishing component is “values”, which guide the leader (Russell, 2001). Among the characteristics of servant leaders are empathy, foresight, and stewardship (Crippen and Willows, 2019) and there are suggestions that society will develop as a result of the contribution of people to that change. Like other leadership theories, limitations such as the need for adequate empirical data to support its validity have plagued this leadership theory (Yukl, 2010; Mcquade, Harrison and Tarbert, 2020). Making it a crucial research area but servant leadership differs from authentic leadership in terms of service and leadership (Covelli and Mason, 2017). This perspective also aligns with spiritual leadership, which is beyond the focus of this research and will not be considered.

2.2.5 Authentic leadership (AL)

According to Shamir and Eilam (2005) the relevance of authentic leadership within the leadership domain is contingent on two important considerations. First, the

construct must be distinct in leadership literature. Second, it should not be readily characterised by other leadership approaches, such as transformational leadership, because it could become too broad to measure. Leadership, ethics, and positive organisational behaviours have all contributed to the development of authentic leadership (Luthans and Avolio, 2003). With Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) stating that authentic leadership was conceptualised within the field of positive psychology.

A few researchers have expressed reservations about characterising authentic leadership in terms of positive psychological abilities (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Sparrowe, 2005). Even though, these debates have shaped authentic leadership research, most of the definitions of AL converge on a few primary dimensions (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008). Authenticity is a fundamental aspect of authentic leadership research. This is evident in the article by Gardner *et al.* (2005) which pursued the integration of multiple descriptions of authentic leadership, thereby proposing a “self-based model” for development (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008, p. 92). Extended discussions on authenticity are captured in section 2.4 while chapter 3 explores the construct of authentic leadership in more depth.

This section provides a summary of the key distinctions and similarities between authentic leadership and other closely linked approaches. Authentic, transformational and ethical leadership are described as a “newer genre” of leadership theories (Hannah *et al.*, 2014). In contrast, servant, authentic, and ethical leadership are collectively described as “moral approaches” to leadership associated with positive outcomes (Lemoine, Hartnell and Leroy, 2019). Though, there are arguments that authentic leadership shares a few similarities with the leadership approaches highlighted above, it remains distinct requiring scholarly attention as a valid construct (Alvesson and Einola, 2019; Lemoine, Hartnell and Leroy, 2019). Brown and Treviño (2006) conducted a systematic literature review of ethical leadership. The study's findings acknowledge a positive correlation between the ethical leadership approach,

authentic, spiritual, and transformational leadership based on its shared concern for morals within leadership.

Furthermore, there are conceptual overlaps (Brown, Treviño and Harrison, 2005; Brown and Treviño, 2006) as well as differences between the authentic and ethical leadership. These two theories recognise leaders as moral individuals who are motivated to do what is right. Even though, these leadership approaches have distinct primary objectives, the moral component permeates both of them (Covelli and Mason, 2017).

Regarding authentic and transformational leadership, differences have been highlighted in attributes and relationships with their followers. For instance, authentic and transformational leaders are described as optimistic; followers identify with these leaders but recognise that authentic leaders do not require charisma to be effective (Avolio and Gardner, 2005). Moreover, the relationships established by authentic leaders with their followers are significantly more personal and emotional, while those developed by transformational leaders are more distant. Similarly, Banks *et al.* (2016) did a meta-analysis that juxtaposed authentic and transformational leadership. This review revealed a stronger correlation between authentic and transformational leadership than what is already evident within extant literature. These scholars argue that there should be more distinction between the two theories, articulating the need for additional research on authentic leadership. Table 4 below provides a summary of the distinctions between authentic leadership and the four leadership theories.

Table 4: Authentic and other leadership theories

Parameters	Authentic	Transformational	Charismatic	Servant	Ethical
Concern for others	X	X	X	X	X
Ethical decision-making	X			X	X
Integrity	X	X	X	X	X

Role Modelling	X	X	X	X	X
Visioning		X	X		
Authenticity and self awareness	X				
Transparent relationships with others	X				
Reciprocity between leaders and followers in terms of positive psychological capital	X				

Source: Author

While Authentic Leadership (AL) has been widely acknowledged as a positive leadership approach rooted in positive psychology, some scholars draw attention to its less favourable aspects. Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005) argue that leaders with Machiavellian traits may exploit authenticity to serve their personal interests. These leaders may not genuinely embody authentic leadership but rather manipulate its principles and components to achieve their own goals. This could include feigning authenticity in decision making processes to appear inclusive while prioritising their own agenda, potentially deceiving followers within organisations. Recently, Einola and Alvesson (2021) identified four potential risks associated with authentic leadership. These include undermining scholarly efforts, delegitimising institutions by overlooking long term implications for short term advantage (Alvesson and Einola, 2019; Tourish, 2019), offering unrealistic promises of positive outcomes without considering potential negatives, and finally triggering identity complexities (Gino, Sezer and Huang, 2020) by promoting an ideal set of expectations that may reinforce narcissistic tendencies.

Furthermore, the predominant focus on positive outcomes within the AL theory often overlooks potential negative impacts (Debebe, 2017; Alvesson and Einola, 2022). This narrow focus on success may disguise the complexities and difficulties associated with authentic leadership, neglecting important considerations and implications for

organisational dynamics. The next section explores leadership development and narrows in on discussions on authentic leadership development.

2.3 Leadership Development

The description of leadership as the relationship between leaders and collaborators who interact in a context shaped by multidirectional influence is underpinned by four key arguments. Firstly, the relationship is established through influence. Secondly, both leaders and collaborators are considered as active participants in this relationship. Thirdly, these actors act based on their intentions. Lastly, the intentions of the actors are led by their shared objectives. This delineation is essential as the prevalent notion within leadership literature is that the leader is the sole actor described as the “lone ranger” of leadership (Rost, 1993; Fields, 2013). This perspective has broad implications for leadership development, emphasising leadership development over leader development.

Leadership development is a recently established field in comparison to the broader domain of leadership (Vogel *et al.*, 2020). This crucial area of research has evolved into a distinct subfield, clearly distinguishable from the conventional approach to researching leadership (Day and Dragoni, 2015). Evidence reveals that leadership development is a thriving industry as organisations disburse over \$366 billion yearly on leadership development across all business cadres (Hieker and Pringle, 2021). This spending seems justified due to the apparent impact of enhancing leadership capabilities on organisational performance (Lacerenza *et al.*, 2017).

Leadership development has focused primarily on development within organisations, with research efforts on learning from experience (McCall, 2004; McCall, 2010), developmental mechanisms of management work (Ohlott, Ruderman and McCauley, 1994), which cover the theoretical foundation of leadership development (Vogel *et al.*, 2020). Emerging from this theoretical foundation, new empirical inquiries on experiential learning (DeRue and Wellman, 2009; Dragoni *et al.*, 2009) with different

practice focused themes such as 360-degree feedback (Waldman, Atwater and Antonioni, 1998) leadership skills and capabilities (Hollenbeck, McCall Jr and Silzer, 2006; Mumford *et al.*, 2000) have developed (Maurer and London, 2018). The literature on transactional, transformational (Burns, 1978; Bass, 1985), charismatic, leader member exchange (Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995) embody the roots of leadership development. The apparent goal of above approaches was to develop leaders that enact these specific leadership approaches.

Interestingly, leadership development studies shifted from a practice centred foundation to theory development, exemplified primarily by authentic leadership development (Vogel *et al.*, 2020). The early advocates of authentic leadership pursued a theory of leadership development for the AL construct (Avolio and Gardner, 2005). These scholars focused on uncovering the leadership process, its precursors, and its outcomes. This was mainly prompted by the ethical dilemmas within organisations towards the end of the 20th century (George, 2003; George *et al.*, 2007).

2.3.1 Development approaches

Several scholars have explored leadership development such as Day (2000) article which offered a new perspective on the conceptualisation of the concept by distinguishing between leader and leadership development. Furthermore, it provided a bridge to practice that is rooted in the foundations of leadership development. Lord and Hall (2005) also examined leader identity theory, which outlined the developmental trajectory of leaders. This perspective on leadership development is intricately linked to the cognitive growth of leaders. Further along these lines, DeRue and Wellman (2009) examined leadership development through experiences, uncovering the complex relationship amid developmental problems, skill development and feedback. McCall, Lombardo and Morrison (1988) shed light on the process by which leaders grow and evolve through challenges and job responsibilities, with life narratives been proposed as a significant approach for investigating leadership development (Ligon, Hunter and Mumford, 2008; Sinclair, 2009; Vogel *et*

al., 2020). Other development approaches identified include mentoring, work-related tasks, and coaching (Day, 2000).

Several related studies have examined the antecedents of leadership development, which are positioned within firstly contextual environment, describing external sources of learning such as reflection and training (Janson, 2008), learning on the job (Courtright, Colbert and Choi, 2014), trigger events (Avolio and Chan, 2008) and games (Kark, 2011). Secondly, antecedents are also positioned within personal settings that describe internal sources of learning. For instance, self-efficacy, awareness, and regulation (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Lord and Hall, 2005), in addition, learning attitudes, motivation and individual qualities.

Evidently, the leadership development domain is profoundly influenced by seminal studies on leadership, motivation and learning, which have advanced the development of intrapersonal processes to the detriment of the interpersonal processes. Most of the studies on the outcomes are theoretical, indicating a need for further investigation by scholars. Similarly, more research should be done on the unfavourable side of leadership development. A neglected research area, thus resulting in an inaccurate view of the leadership development process, which Day and Sin (2011) maintain needs to be more consistently constructive and linear. While leadership development is firmly grounded in practice, a critical finding of Vogel *et al.*'s (2020) study is that leadership theories such as identity development and AL development theory have been proposed but have not yet been investigated adequately. Thus, authentic leadership development is a crucial aspect of theory that needs further exploration.

Specifically, in the 2005 special edition of *Leadership Quarterly*, researchers made a deliberate attempt to harmonise practice based leadership development with a theory focused on the advancement of leaders. Gardner *et al.* (2005) argue that the earlier conceptualisation of AL development theorised a multidimensional construct depicting leadership advancement over time. Yet, several scholars have explored

authentic leadership as a style or set of behaviours, thereby disregarding the theory's earlier emphasis on development.

There are suggestions that authentic leadership development processes extend beyond behaviours to include authentic follower development and personal experiences (Avolio and Reichard, 2008). However, these aspects have not yet been extensively researched empirically. For that reason, scholars are advised to question or broaden the prevailing conceptualisations put forward by Gardner *et al.* (2005) and Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) to advance the field scientifically.

Drawing on the recommendations of Ford and Harding (2011) on expanding the theoretical understanding of authenticity and Algera and Lips-Wiersma (2012); Berkovich (2014) suggestion on examining the developmental aspects of authentic leadership, further studies within the domain would prove valuable in attaining increased understanding of the construct. Therefore, this study seeks to identify the factors that inspire authentic leadership development, with a particular focus on determining what motivates the need for change and enquiring whether leaders can be authentic from childhood, as the existing literature consistently describes a defining moment for authentic leadership development. This is evident in the traditional and archetypal leaders referred to as “authentic leaders” as Luthans and Avolio (2003) implied that these leaders share the ability to use events from their personal lives to inspire constructive development in themselves, which prompted them to be authentic.

2.3.2 Becoming authentic.

In becoming authentic, George (2003) claims that leaders develop leadership approaches or styles that are consistent with who they are, their personalities, and their attributes, as authenticity is the foundation of becoming authentic. Based on this perspective, the author identifies five aspects that authentic leaders should aim to develop throughout their professional lives: The five key elements are: 1) understanding purpose, 2) practising values, 3) leading with the heart, 4) fostering

meaningful connections, and 5) exhibiting self-discipline. This is crucial as authenticity requires personal development, experience, and effort. Furthermore, Gill and Caza (2018) posit that others which could be followers or employees attribute authenticity to leaders; inducing a need to manage the expression of the authentic self. This conscious management includes individual perceptions that are critical and do not correlate with organisational values.

An effective authentic leader needs good communication skills and the ability to adapt to the circumstances. As becoming authentic is dependent on the individual decisions of leaders. These decisions shape the identity of leaders and determine their trajectory from a pool of possibilities (Lawler and Ashman, 2012). Similarly, Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer (2015b) argue that an authentic self, developed within a social context will evolve into an authentic leader, as authentic leaders are predicated on the authentic self. Self awareness and self-management are viewed as guiding authentic leadership development.

Followers are also considered essential to becoming authentic leaders, as managers rely on followers to grant them leadership authority, enabling them to effectively carry out their responsibilities (DeRue and Ashford, 2010; Monzani *et al.*, 2019) suggesting that, it is imperative for leaders to recognise the impact and role of followers in this process (DeRue and Ashford, 2010).

2.3.3 Development of authentic leaders

Leadership development refers to the systematic growth of an organisation's members' ability to take on leadership positions. Therefore, scholars such as George (2003) examination of 125 leaders, investigated the process of developing authentic leaders. These scholars attempted to uncover how individuals develop their authentic leadership capabilities through their personal stories (Gardner *et al.*, 2021). The study's findings established that no universal features, qualities, or tactics enabled the respondents within the study attain success. In contrast, their leadership developed

from a myriad of personal experiences, which enabled insight into who they were, affirming the reason and purpose of their leadership.

Several scholars have acknowledged the difficulty associated with authentic leadership development (Baron, 2016; Crossan *et al.*, 2017), linking these complexities to varying personalities, attitudes and conduct. Despite these arguments there is an implicit agreement that authentic leadership can be developed. Furthermore, George *et al.* (2007) concur with the school of thought that leadership capacities can be developed; with the key being self awareness and its application in serving followers. This means that, becoming an authentic leader requires a commitment to continuous self awareness and personal development. These authors suggest that individuals can become authentic leaders by evaluating their personal experiences to increase their self awareness, enabling them to act in accordance with their ideologies. This process requires striking a delicate equilibrium between actions shaped by internal values and external exigencies, which may be associated with rewards or penalties. For example, "Novartis CEO" Daniel Vasella reframed his adversity to reach the pinnacle of the pharmaceutical industry.

Accordingly, George *et al.* (2007) described paths that facilitate authentic leadership development. Five focus on the leader's personal development, while the last technique describes how the authentic leaders concurrently develop their followers. These methods are described as follows; firstly, the leader develops self awareness which progresses by overcoming denials of shortcomings and being willing to accept difficult feedback. Secondly, the leader develops values and philosophies, from personal beliefs. Thirdly, achieving authentic leadership involves harmonising internal and external pressures, as becoming an authentic leader requires reaching a delicate balance between these two competing influences. Fourthly, developing a support team to provide alternate views and opinions ensure authentic leaders stay focused. This safety net aids unhindered self disclosure and acceptance by authentic leaders. Finally, living a balanced life, requires ensuring all the components of the

leader's life align to ensure consistency of self across all areas and situations, reinforced with thoughtful choices. The above designate how leaders can discover and grow as authentic leaders, enabling followers to lead.

Other scholars have offered approaches to authentic leadership development such as experiential learning by Baron (2016) corroborating claims that leadership development is rooted in learning, which propel individuals toward uncovering their innate leadership potential. Accordingly, Shannon *et al.* (2020), state that these learning approaches are open to multiple configurations. However, their research explicitly examines trigger events. leadership crucibles and their potential role in fostering self awareness in authentic leaders. Although, these two concepts appear similar and have been used interchangeably by scholars, they are different and distinct.

Fullick (2010) describes trigger events as occurrences that initiate subsequent actions or occurrences. These trigger events may be planned or unplanned, and research has shown that they lead to authentic leadership development (Luthans and Avolio, 2003; Harvey, Martinko and Gardner, 2006). Similarly, Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005) argue that significant life events can stimulate the personal growth required for authentic leadership development. These events affect, in most cases, reshape the worldview and leadership philosophy. There are assertions that the outlook, principles, and behaviours of a leader are shaped by trigger events (Luthans & Avolio, 2003), because there is no conscious effort to cultivate leadership; rather, it is influenced by a series of unplanned trigger events.

In contrast, Thomas (2008) defines leadership crucibles as difficult or challenging situations that cause individuals to doubt their purpose and what they represent. Like George *et al.*'s (2007) observation that these events have implications which are determined by the interpretations assigned to them. In their study of women of colour in predominantly white institutions, Ngunjiri and Hernandez (2017) found that intrapersonal and interpersonal challenges impede leadership development,

particularly for those whose social identities have placed them in specific contexts. Echoing the significance of context in leadership development and models (House and Aditya, 1997; Day, 2000). According to Luthans and Avolio (2003), self awareness is indeed a crucial aspect of leadership development. So, if a leader lacks self awareness regarding their vulnerabilities, they might make poor decisions because they won't invest the necessary effort to address and improve these weaknesses.

In expanding the discussion on life stories in section 2.3.1, studies have also examined the life histories of leaders to identify early life or professional experiences that may have influenced their development (Avolio and Gibbons, 1988; Burns, 1978). This is because scholars have searched the biographies of leaders for qualities and values to justify their leadership claims. However, Shamir and Eilam (2005) state that the development of authentic leadership is influenced by the experiences that authentic leaders draw upon to shape their life narratives, which in turn reflect their self concept and perception of leadership. Similarly, the study provides evidence to support the use of role models in the construction of life stories, thereby offering a framework for self concept clarity.

Even so, the development of authentic leaders has been a central topic of debate within authentic leadership theory (Caza and Jackson, 2011; Baron and Parent, 2015) with a focus on identifying practical and useful interventions (Gill and Caza, 2018). Although, it has been demonstrated that authentic leadership can be nurtured through developmental programmes (Baron, 2012), scholars are yet to examine the “black box” of AL. This includes the examination of the developmental processes of individuals and the specific training interventions that support this development (Baron and Parent, 2015). With recommendations that organisations develop authentic leaders by exposing them to the factors that inspire authentic leadership development and by examining the role of perceptions in leadership development (Harvey, Martinko and Gardner, 2006). In conclusion, the study responds to the call by Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer (2015b) for a research based approach to the

development of AL , supported by the evidence from the expanding body of research showcasing its benefits within organisations.

2.4 Authenticity

Contemporary discussions on authenticity can be traced back to the age of enlightenment (Gardiner, 2016), where distinctions from morally lax aristocratic contemporaries influenced their emergence. The renowned quote “To thine own self be true” found in William Shakespeare's play Hamlet is often associated with the notion of authenticity (Ford and Harding, 2011; McShane and Cunningham, 2012; Weischer, Weibler and Petersen, 2013; Stiers *et al.*, 2021). This suggests that this concept can be traced back to ancient Greek philosophy (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; McShane and Cunningham, 2012; Stiers *et al.*, 2019). However, contrary to prevalent belief, the phrase was taken from Polonius's dialogue in Shakespeare's Hamlet and not from Greek philosophy (Lawler and Ashman, 2012).

There are also debates regarding the interchangeability of authenticity and sincerity (Erickson, 1995). Though, these concepts have been linked, they are distinct (Gardner *et al.*, 2021). In distinguishing between these two concepts Trilling (2009) defines sincerity as the alignment of external display of emotions and thoughts with their inward experiences. While Harter (2002) defines authenticity as being true to oneself in the entirety of life, including thoughts, emotions, needs, wants, preferences, and beliefs. It entails a profound understanding of oneself and acting in agreement with one's true self. The description emphasises the self referential nature of authenticity (Avolio and Gardner, 2005), and the debates on the “self” (Erickson, 1995) are at the core of the concept.

Sparrowe (2005) presented a compelling argument against associating authenticity solely with a set of values, asserting that such an approach overlooks individual differences. In particular, Sparrowe (2005) argues that authenticity must include character and the lived experience united by the narrative self to have meaning.

Therefore, authenticity is the narrative that connects the character and the consistency of one's own identity (Sparrowe, 2005; Muceldili, Turan and Erdil, 2013). In summary, the values and principles of people may evolve. However, these values still belong to the same individual.

Several scholars have identified approaches to unpacking the concept of authenticity. For instance, Lehman *et al.* (2019) identified three viewpoints on authenticity. The first perspective is rooted in ancient philosophical inquiries beginning with Greek philosophers like Socrates and extending to Existentialist advocates like Heidegger (1962).

Existentialist proponents contend, that the self exists in a social environment. These scholars define authenticity as the congruence of inner beliefs and outward conduct or being true to oneself. The presumption underlying authenticity is that it is unique and subjective. According to the second school of thought, authenticity is the conformity of an individual or phenomenon to the norms of its social group. The underlying assumption is that authenticity is the same. As upheld, the third school views authenticity as the link to a phenomenon as claimed. The underlying assumption is that authenticity varies and is objective. Thus, "consistency, conformity, and connection" (Lehman et al., 2019) are an accurate description of these three prevalent themes of authenticity. But the first perspective on authenticity as consistency has the earliest theoretical foundation and is the most prevalent in extant literature.

Traditionally, authenticity has been described from two angles, firstly, the existential (interpersonal) standpoint, which emphasises personal virtues and the psychological (intrapersonal) standpoint (Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018), which emphasises personal traits. The existential outlook was advanced by Sartre and Heidegger, defining the concept as a dynamic state attained through interactions with other people (Berkovich, 2014; Nyberg and Sveningsson, 2014). These existentialist philosophers Heidegger (1962) and Sartre (1948) investigated authenticity extensively,

associating the notion with the human desire to maintain a balance between individual obligation and collective perspective. The main difference between Sartre and Heidegger's outlook on authenticity is that the latter perceived authenticity as morally desirable while the former did not, as Sartre argues that authenticity is not intrinsically moral through the freedom to make a choice (Lawler and Ashman, 2012; Ciulla, 2013). Existentialist scholars do not recognise the existence of an authentic self because it is detached from the world but instead emphasise context and experiences in authentic leadership (Lawler and Ashman, 2012). These scholars explore authenticity and leadership using existentialism as a lens for investigation, thereby connecting it to its philosophical roots.

In a similar vein, Barrett-Lennard (1998) argues that authenticity is accomplished by regularly incorporating emotions, perspectives, and engagements with the self and others. Specifically, Lehman *et al.* (2019) propose that authenticity is attributable and subjective. More importantly, it is determined mainly by the referent, at a point in time, to what the entity is being compared to. Lending precision to this argument, extant literature is replete with examples of followers' evaluating a leader's authenticity by assigning authenticity marks with a few examples of leaders assessing themselves (Alvesson and Einola, 2019). Evaluating if individuals are true to themselves is a challenging undertaking as impression management may be difficult to uncover or identify. It is argued that authenticity and, by extension, authentic leadership can neither be outwardly measured nor experimentally influenced. This may explain why scholars are yet to explore why some persons are authentic or perceived as more authentic than others (Boyras and Kuhl, 2015). From an existential standpoint, an individual's authenticity is determined by their actions and the choices that shape those actions, which are influenced by interpersonal relationships. Reaffirming, the crucial role of context in defining authenticity (Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018).

In contrast, the psychological perspective of authenticity advanced by Harter (2002) emphasises the pursuit of self knowledge through the proprietorship of individual experiences. This psychological perspective of authenticity was largely inspired by Kierkegaard's idea (DeCarvalho, 1989). This perspective considers the self as a psychological entity apart from the mind and psyche, suggesting that authenticity involves being one's true self and acting in alignment with one's personal values which does not imply any moral foundations. Recently, the positive psychology movement revitalised interest in authenticity, contributing to the development of authentic leadership (Gaddy *et al.*, 2017; Iszatt-White *et al.*, 2019).

Furthermore, in Wood *et al.* (2008) examination of the authenticity, a model was proposed that conceptualises the concept across three critical areas of knowledge: first, the individual's essential experiences; second, the embodied self awareness that emerges from these essential experiences; and third, expressed conducts (Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018).

It appears that authenticity may also be dependent on the chain of command and power relations within organisations (Alvesson and Einola, 2019), as authenticity may be conveyed differently based on a person's position in the environment (Gardiner, 2011). Interestingly, Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005) contend that the impact of national cultures must be taken into account, as authenticity may be perceived differently across national cultures.

The term "authentics" or "authentic" is described in various ways depending on the philosopher's perspective (Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer, 2015a). With an underlying theme of being self made underpinning all these diverse perspectives. For instance, Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer (2015b) argue that Kierkegaard's (1846) account of the true self does not reflect the majority's voice or popular opinion. In modern perspectives, Harter (2002) defines authenticity as assuming responsibility for one's experiences, perspectives, emotions, and beliefs.

With Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer (2015b) claiming that these perspectives served as the foundation for Kernis (2003) definition of authenticity, which stimulated research by scholars. Furthermore, Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer (2015b) contend the development of models for authentic leadership was based on a multicomponent concept of authenticity advanced by Kernis and Goldman (2006). This served as the foundation for the development of models for authentic leadership. Accordingly, Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer (2015b) argue that this framework provided the conceptual basis for the empirically derived and validated models of authentic leadership that came later. With several definitions of authentic leadership tracing their origins to this work.

2.4.1 Authenticity in leadership

The lack of authenticity has eroded the confidence of contemporary business leaders (Sparrowe, 2005; Peus *et al.*, 2012). This premise is reiterated by Luthans and Avolio (2003) who uphold that this concern pertains to all organisational levels and types. These scholars suggest that the leadership required to address challenges will emerge from individuals who are transparent, open, true to themselves and can influence their followers. Trilling (2009) observed there may be a consensus on the definition of authenticity, particularly as a concept used to characterise a phenomenon perceived or alleged to be genuine or authentic. Nonetheless, this apparent use of the lexical concept of authenticity is riddled with debates that reflect the perspectives of scholars in its description and application (Lehman *et al.*, 2019).

Even though, the significance of authenticity varies from person to person, it accounts for a leader's level of motivation to behave authentically. It could explain why these leaders are viewed as authentic (Wood *et al.*, 2008) but as , Sendjaya *et al.* (2016) state may not exist in any entity. This is because authenticity is a "claim made by or for someone, thing, or performance that is either accepted or rejected by the relevant others"(Peterson, 2005, p. 1086), indicating that it is attributed and socially constructed. As contemporary research has documented the benefits of authenticity

for leaders and followers, implying that higher levels of authenticity are linked with performance (Liu and Perrewé, 2006; Kuntz and Abbott, 2017).

Henderson and Hoy (1982) argue that there has been limited exploration of authenticity in leadership. They suggest that related studies on social behaviour have led to definitions of leader authenticity focusing on three key areas: prioritising one's true self over their role, manipulation, and accountability. The prioritisation of the self over one's role suggests that traditional roles do not constrain leaders' behaviours and serves as a marker for authenticity. This aspect of leader authenticity lies at the heart of Seeman's study on inauthenticity (Seeman, 1966).

Inauthenticity is described as an exaggerated reaction to one's position and a tendency to make impractical judgments based on the perceived expectations associated with that role. However, when the role incumbent can overcome role labels and expectations, exploring the challenges of the context and acting accordingly Henderson and Hoy (1982) believe that the leader has manifested authenticity. The absence of manipulation when dealing with subordinates suggests that these subordinates perceive their leader as someone who refrains from employing tactics aimed at exploiting or treating them as mere objects. From this standpoint, authentic conduct entails refraining from manipulating others as though they were mere objects.

Accountability, the third aspect of authenticity within the study, describes the capacity of the leader to acknowledge errors. These authentic leaders take ownership of their actions and the actions of other actors within the organisation. In contrast, inauthentic leaders are perceived by their subordinates as leaders who are quick to transfer responsibility to others. Accordingly, Henderson and Hoy (1982) described it as the degree to which followers regard their leader as actively promoting the acceptance of both organisational and personal responsibility for actions, outcomes, and errors, while prioritising their own interests over their job.

Sendjaya *et al.* (2016) argue that authenticity lies within the observer's gaze, as a leader may perceive themselves as authentic, while others may hold a different opinion, as evidenced by the self report data on authentic leadership in their study. Consequently, problematic when authenticity is revealed through words and actions (Gardiner, 2013).

According to a few scholars, leadership and authenticity are distinct phenomena that operate in opposite directions. Authenticity entails self awareness and being genuine to oneself, while leadership entails guiding and influencing others towards a common goal (Gardner *et al.*, 2021; Einola and Alvesson, 2021). These scholars have questioned the viability of authentic leadership (Alvesson and Sveningsson, 2013; Einola and Alvesson, 2021; Alvesson and Einola, 2022), arguing that authenticity and leadership are two distinct and viable ideas. Gardner *et al.* (2021) argue that the self referential of authenticity makes it challenging to grasp as authenticity extends beyond upholding one's ideals; to putting one's talents and abilities to effective use. The term "authenticity" has become a watchword in the modern world due to its frequent use in a variety of contexts. With suggestions that authenticity is an aspiration rather than a fixed condition (Gardner *et al.*, 2021; Gill and Caza, 2018).

According to Covelli and Mason (2017), Barnard (1938) first alluded to authenticity in management and organisational literature, but in the 1960s the philosophical notions of authenticity in the existing literature on authentic leadership became apparent (Novicevic *et al.*, 2006). The incorporation of authenticity into leadership was evident in Seeman (1966) exploration of inauthenticity. However, Henderson and Hoy (1982) advanced the field by offering "The Leader Authenticity Scale", a 32-item scale.

Across the definitions of authenticity offered by scholars, there is a consensus that authentic leaders align the external with the interior. Thus, actions and behaviours are in accordance with internalised values and principles. This supports Erickson (1995) view that authenticity is conceptualised as a continuum. Therefore, leaders can be described in various ways along a continuum indicating that a leader's authenticity

can increase and become more authentic. Consequently, Harvey, Martinko and Gardner (2006) contend that authenticity is a dynamic process that promotes self awareness, accurate self-perceptions, and facilitates self-regulation, aligning actions with an individual's own values, beliefs, emotions, and ideas (Avolio *et al.*, 2004).

Jones and Grint (2013) argue that the interaction between authenticity and leadership within the authentic leadership construct can be examined from three critical perspectives: veracity, essentialist, and normative. The veracity issue acknowledges that scholars tend to adopt a more individualistic rather than collective perspective regarding how leaders navigate their authenticity. Conversely, the essentialist viewpoint emphasises the shift from being true to oneself to a competency focused approach within authenticity, as initially proposed by Kernis (2003).

Gardner *et al.* (2005) and Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) advanced four components of authentic leadership: "self awareness, balanced processing, an internalised moral perspective, and relational transparency." However, what constitutes ethics and morality is mainly undefined within the AL literature (Jones and Grint, 2013; Alvesson and Einola, 2019). Even though, Avolio *et al.* (2004) aim to enhance understanding by suggesting that true leaders must act in the best interest of the group. The determination of the communal good and its definition remains an open question? This concern is rooted in the trade off between the requirements of the minority and those of the majority (Jones and Grint, 2013).

Therefore, authentic leadership is said to be value laden (Eilam-Shamir and Shamir, 2013). This suggests that the meaning of authenticity has expanded from commonly held discourse (Harter, 2002; Kernis and Goldman, 2006) to include morality and ethics (Eilam-Shamir and Shamir, 2013), and this may be attributed to Aristotle's notion of ethics as the foundation of a praiseworthy life. This concept of morality is prevalent and permeates the literature on authentic leadership (George, 2003; Gardner *et al.*, 2005). This is evident in descriptions of authentic leaders who are moral and, as a result, promote the common interest. However, additional clarification is required

regarding the ethical principles maintained by authentic leaders (Clarke, Kelliher and Schedlitzki, 2013).

Eilam-Shamir and Shamir (2013) analysis of the correlation between a leader's authenticity and values revealed that the interviewed authentic leaders were not motivated by material rewards or the need to meet the expectations of others. Rather, these authentic leaders were driven by aspirations that were profoundly rooted in their passion and were derived from the respondents' personal experiences. In addition, sacrifice and a strong desire to achieve their objectives resonated in the study, but there was no mention of moral obligations, which have become the primary motivation for authentic leaders within extant literature (Eilam-Shamir and Shamir, 2013). These leaders were driven by their desire to fulfil personal aspirations and proactively confronted obstacles that hindered their progress.

Authentic leadership theory is contingent on the follower's perception of the leader's authenticity. As the leader in isolation does not create authenticity; rather, authenticity is perceived by the contributions of followers. Sinclair (2013) argues that followers frequently attribute authenticity to leaders based on implicit criteria derived from their expectations of social group members. Their viewpoint offers a unique approach to understanding authenticity. Such that, norms that confer authenticity on leaders should be identified by focusing on the leader's actions. These standards include gender, institutionalised prejudice, beliefs, and cultural assumptions. Individuals cannot imitate a model or a set of propositions or prescriptions to become authentic. It is a collective construction and production.

Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) study is firmly grounded in social psychology theory and authenticity, as advanced by both Kernis (2003) and Deci and Ryan (2000). It significantly draws from Avolio and Gardner (2005), Gardner *et al.* (2005) and Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang (2005) conceptualisation of authentic leadership. It specifically emphasises the importance of an internalised moral perspective, challenging the idea that authentic leadership can be morally neutral. In addition,

these studies emphasise the state like nature of the construct, highlighting the development potential of authentic leaders and followers (Luthans and Avolio, 2003). The advancement of theoretical frameworks (Gardner *et al.*, 2005; Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang, 2005) and reliable measurement tools that have been validated (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008; Neider and Schriesheim, 2011; Beddoes-Jones and Swailes, 2015) have all contributed to the development of this construct.

However, some scholars argue that this construct has not developed theoretically since its inception (Alvesson and Einola, 2019; Alvesson and Einola, 2022). These scholars suggest that the advancement of the construct has been hampered by misinformed ideology, suggesting that effort should be redirected towards exploring real world paradoxes. In summary, authenticity is perceived as a state of being which can be developed. This development is boosted by self knowledge, which shapes a leader's actions and interactions internally with oneself and externally with others.

2.4.2 Inauthenticity

Authenticity is described as a progression of becoming authentic, thus a continuous path that can never be attained (Lawler and Ashman, 2012). This ambition of striving to become authentic is perceived as being inauthentic. So, inauthenticity is a consequence of complexity derived from how individuals manage the freedom they possess, and the responsibility expected from them by all stakeholders. This is summarised as the freedom responsibility dilemma. The inauthentic person or leader views other people as instruments to attain objectives because these leaders attempt to enforce their truth on others (Lawler and Ashman, 2012; Gardiner, 2017). These leaders are depicted as individuals, who prioritise their own self interest and do not show concern for the wellbeing of others as they engage in exploitative behaviours (Michie and Gooty, 2005; Johnsen, 2018).

When differentiating between authentic from inauthentic leaders, Michie and Gooty (2005) argue that this can pose challenges. Therefore, they recommend relying on values (thoughts) as guiding principles and positive emotions (feelings) that support

morals. These authors suggest that authentic leaders possess self-enhancement and self-transcendence values but prioritise self-transcendence, which are correlated with benevolence (trustworthiness, accountability) and universalism (fairness, impartiality). In addition, Johnsen (2018), provides a concise explanation of the difference between authentic and inauthentic leaders. According to Johnsen, inauthentic leaders are driven by personal rewards, while authentic leaders are motivated by the collective good.

Johnsen (2018) states that extant literature is replete with arguments that positively link values with ethical conduct (George, 2003) neglecting the likelihood that leaders' personal values may have informed questionable actions (Price, 2003). A typical case is an argument that Skilling's participation in the fraud that led to Enron's collapse can be perceived otherwise, as Levine and Boaks (2014) imply that greed was not the main driving behind the actions of Enron's executives. Instead, the motivation to reinvigorate the energy business was oblivious to moral reflections. Johnsen (2018) suggests that one of the parameters for distinguishing between authentic and inauthentic leaders should be a sense of ethical reflection by consistently interrogating one's values and responsibilities. These core values are described as global standards for ethical conduct, not personal beliefs on the perception of good (George, 2003). George established this core values model in 2003 to distinguish between authentic leaders and inauthentic leaders. Authentic leaders demonstrate loyalty to their underlying values, but inauthentic leaders lack commitment to these fundamental values. Interestingly, Avolio *et al.* (2004) contend that behavioural style does not fundamentally distinguish an authentic leader from an inauthentic leader. This amplifies the problematic nature of identifying authentic leaders within organisations and the broader society.

Authenticity is sustained by a deeply rooted change instigated by a leader's intrinsic yearning to become a whole self; in contrast, inauthenticity is a superficial change employed to satisfy the self which represents others (Heidegger, 1962). The prevalent

conceptualisations of authenticity within authentic leadership construct reinforces idealistic expectations of leaders and followers, thereby portraying inauthenticity negatively as opposed to theorising authenticity as an integral part of organisational existence (Lawler and Ashman, 2012).

2.5 Conclusion

This chapter explored studies on leadership, leadership theories, leadership development and authenticity. The first section provided a historical synopsis of leadership, highlighting the debates and viewpoints that have influenced its understanding over time. The subsequent section examined four leadership theories: servant, transformational, charismatic, and ethical leadership. These theories are discussed because they are linked with authentic leadership. The chapter provides an overview of the theory of authentic leadership, which serves as the main subject of inquiry in the thesis.

In the third section, the focus is narrowed to leadership development, with a particular emphasis on developing authentic leaders. This section examines the strategies, and practises that contribute to AL development. The concluding section of the chapter explored authenticity and its implications in several domains. In summary, this chapter lays the groundwork for the next chapter, which will present the findings of the systematic literature review and discuss its practical implications.

CHAPTER 3. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW OF AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP

INTRODUCTION

During its early conceptualisation, authentic leadership garnered considerable attention from both practitioners and scholars (Sidani and Rowe, 2018; Crawford *et al.*, 2020). However, these efforts were not sustained, resulting in the proliferation of studies on AL and organisational outcomes (Gardner *et al.*, 2011; Iszatt-White and Kempster, 2019). Therefore, this chapter presents the findings of a systematic investigation of authentic leadership. It examines the construct in depth by synthesising relevant literature. To this end, 80 articles published between 1970 and 2021 were identified and analysed methodically.

The chapter examines the literature on the construct. In addition, it identifies the factors that inspire authentic leadership development, describes the followers' perception of the construct and explores how these perceptions shape authentic leadership development. Consequently, the review's key findings suggest that authentic leaders develop in phases, which may be the missing link that connects the two differing views on the development of self. Secondly, the followers' perceptions are crucial to the second development phase. However, these perceptions have not been examined adequately, as scholars have focused on the bidirectional nature of these perceptions, that is, how leaders influence the perceptions of followers in the attainment of organisational outcomes (Gaddy *et al.*, 2017; Bakari, Hunjra and Niazi, 2017; Kurian and Nafukho, 2021) and how follower perceptions impact authentic leader effectiveness (McFarlane, 2011; Emuwa and Fields, 2017). This neglects the iterative role the followers' perceptions play in developing authentic leadership. Finally, it uncovers the dominance of specific regions evident in its conceptualisation, which has limited the understanding of the construct across diverse contexts. The relevance of this review is not in doubt as it presents the justification for further

investigation by scholars and provides the necessary evidence to policymakers and practitioners.

3.1 The call for authentic leadership

To advance the authentic leadership domain, it is important to uncover boundaries of extant knowledge in order to map the current state of knowledge and identify knowledge gaps within the domain (Xiao and Watson, 2019). Therefore, a systematic literature review of the field was conducted as "systematic reviews" can enlighten scholars about what is known, how it is known, and how this varies across studies using a rigorous explicit methodology (Gough, Thomas and Oliver, 2012; Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2013). This is essential because one significant limitation of narrative reviews lies in their descriptive nature and potential bias, as authors choose articles based on their personal judgment (Tawfik *et al.*, 2019).

Comparatively, systematic literature reviews (SLR) are objective, transparent, and reproducible reviews conducted to address specific questions (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003; Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2013; Ahn and Kang, 2018). The review applies a systematic approach to the identification of relevant research, review, and analysis of selected studies (Ahn and Kang, 2018; Tawfik *et al.*, 2019). This type of review is described as "...a replicable, scientific, and transparent process; that is, a detailed technique that aims to minimise bias through exhaustive literature searches of published and unpublished studies, and by providing an audit trail of the reviewer's decisions, procedures, and conclusions (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003, p. 209)." In addition, these reviews facilitate the identification of latent knowledge within completed studies (Glass, 1976).

Gardner *et al.* (2011) conducted the first and most influential review of the construct within the domain. This review evaluated the field, clarified the construct and its evolution, providing evidence of the domain's antecedents and outcomes. The review revealed that 93% of the evaluated studies adopted a positivist perspective, while only

7% adopted an interpretivist outlook, necessitating further research (Crawford *et al.*, 2020). Conceptual descriptions and quantitative contributions dominated the field at the time of the review (Iszatt-White and Kempster, 2019). The evaluation of 91 studies on authentic leadership revealed that most of the studies were quantitative in nature. This analysis included 25 empirical publications, with an uneven distribution of 16 quantitative and 9 qualitative studies. This parallels the dichotomy in existing literature. Hence, further qualitative studies will enhance the existing understanding of the construct.

Notably, out of the 91 publications reviewed, only Jensen and Luthans (2006b) and Tate (2008) conducted empirical examinations of perceptions of authentic leadership (Steffens *et al.*, 2016). However, none of the research examined follower perceptions that shape the authentic leadership development. Prior studies (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Shamir and Eilam, 2005; Fields, 2007), have urged scholars to examine the fundamental mechanisms involved. While a few studies (Steffens *et al.*, 2016), have begun investigating these mechanisms, specifically exploring the impact of authentic leadership perceptions on organisational outcomes, further research is required to fully comprehend these fundamental processes. This study offers a point of departure by exploring authentic leadership actions that shape the perceptions of followers within organisations.

Banks *et al.* (2016) conducted a meta-analytic review of authentic and transformational leadership. This article assessed the construct validity of authentic leadership by doing a comparative analysis of the two constructs: authentic and transformational leadership. The study's findings confirmed a strong correlation between authentic and transformational leadership, suggesting that both constructs may be redundant and lack incremental validity.

Furthermore, Suhonen, Malila and Lunkka (2018) conducted a scoping review within the health sector; the review attempted to identify gaps within extant literature and chart future research efforts. Four research themes were found to be prevalent within

the 29 articles included in the review. These themes are “workplace wellbeing, work environment, authentic leadership promotion, and quality of patient care.” It was also evident that quantitative research methods, specifically the authentic leadership questionnaire (ALQ), and cross-sectional research designs were utilised frequently. Alilyyani, Wong and Cummings (2018) also conducted a systematic review to investigate the antecedents, mediators, and outcomes of authentic leadership within the healthcare sector. This article focused on the relational nature of authentic leadership and its effects on organisational outcomes. The review drew on Avolio *et al.* (2004) conceptualisation of authentic leadership, which led to the development of an adapted model based on findings from the health sector. A recent narrative review was conducted by Iszatt-White and Kempster (2019). The article examined the development of authentic leadership and recommends a reconceptualisation of the construct to address the theoretical ambiguity that has plagued the domain, calling for further qualitative research to advance the field.

All the reviews discussed above did not explore the followers' perceptions of authenticity and how they shape authentic leadership development leaders. These significant gaps, when investigated, would offer practical implications for practitioners. In addition, the reviews chart the paths for future research efforts based on the questions explored.

Therefore, the goal of the SLR was to explore the construct by unpacking its meaning to leaders, followers, and configurations within organisations. This review technique was selected for this study for five key reasons: first, it represents a rigorous alternative to narrative reviews (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009). Secondly, it facilitates the identification and evaluation of existing knowledge (Smith *et al.*, 2011). Thirdly, it ensures the separation of research endeavours, ensuring that research efforts are not duplicated. Fourthly, it provides evidence of the knowledge deficits, and lastly, it demonstrates that the new research is influenced by the findings of previous research (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2013). Consistent with the preceding arguments above,

the thesis adopted Tranfield, Denyer and Smart (2003) SLR methodology. The chapter comprises of four sections. The initial section offers a contextual background for the review, as documented in section 3.1. The second section provides a summary of the research's three-stage approach. The section outlines the search terms, the criteria used to choose journals, and the main stages of the evaluation. The results and responses to the review inquiries are reported in the third section. The final part presents the conclusion of the chapter.

3.2 Methodology

This systematic literature review adopted the three-stage process advanced by Tranfield, Denyer and Smart (2003). The main stages are Stage 1: Review Planning, Stage 2: Review Execution, and Stage 3: Review Reporting and Dissemination. This is consistent with the arguments of several scholars that a well conducted review entails planning, conducting, and reporting the review (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007; Brereton and McGlinchey, 2020). In addition, this three-step procedure has been utilised and validated within extant literature (Harrison, Paul and Burnard, 2016; Sawyerr and Harrison, 2019; Mcquade, Harrison and Tarbert, 2020). Figure 3 below captures the stages.

Figure 3 Stages of the review

3.2.1 Stage 1: Review planning

To commence the review process, a review panel was established. The panel members were tasked with three primary responsibilities: ascertaining the review need, specifying the review questions, and developing a review protocol. In facilitating this stage, a scoping study was conducted, which revealed the nature of research within the authentic leadership field. The scoping study was fundamental to developing the keywords (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003) and ultimately shaped the review protocol. The key outcomes of this stage were the development of the review questions and protocol.

Review questions

The first outcome was the development of the review questions. The review questions are practical, thought-provoking, ethical and well defined. These are stated below.

RQ1. What is authentic leadership?

RQ2. What are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders?

RQ3. What are the followers' perceptions of authentic leadership?

RQ4. How do follower perceptions shape authentic leadership development?

The inclusion and exclusion criteria emerged from the research enquiry (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009; Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017). These guiding principles were used to assess the suitability of studies for the review. Furthermore, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were also rational. The criteria for inclusion and exclusion are captured in Figure 4 below:

Figure 4 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The second outcome from stage 1 was the development of a review protocol. This protocol closely mirrors the research design commonly employed in social science studies (Xiao and Watson, 2019). This is because the protocol must ensure a transparent and exhaustive review (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003) because the methodical data selection process specified in the protocol limits the researcher's bias. This enhances the review's quality because it can be reproduced and verified. Table 5 provides an overview of the protocol adopted for this review.

Table 5 Systematic review protocol

<u>Details</u>	<u>Description</u>
Panel	Ibiyemi Omeihe (Principal reviewer) Christian Harrison Raewyn Riach
Affiliation(s)	School of Business and Creative Industries, UWS.
Purpose of study	The purpose of the SLR is to explore the construct of authentic leadership; investigating its meaning to leaders, followers and configurations within organisations in a developing economy.
Review questions	RQ1. What is authentic leadership? RQ2. What are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders? RQ3. What is the followers' perception of authentic leadership? RQ4. How do follower perceptions shape authentic leadership development?
Inclusion Criteria	Peer reviewed articles published between 1970- 2021 Articles originally published in English Language Papers that address one or more of the review questions Papers that focus on authentic leadership
Exclusion Criteria	Articles focused on other styles of leadership Papers unrelated to the research questions Articles without access to full texts Papers that are not peer reviewed The review excludes grey literature (e.g., book chapters, reports, etc.)
Data bases	Business Source Ultimate EBSCO Emerald Ingenta connect Sage Journals Science direct Springer link Taylor and Francis Web of Science Wiley online

3.2.2 Stage 2: Review execution

This section describes the approach taken during the review. It provides an overview of the six critical review steps: identifying studies, screening for inclusion, quality assessment, data extraction, evaluating and synthesising the data (Tranfield, Denyer

and Smart, 2003; Denyer and Tranfield, 2009). The evaluation procedure commenced with the identification of keywords. The keywords were derived from the review questions (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007; Xiao and Watson, 2019), the scoping study, and the review panel's recommendations. The list of keywords and search terms is presented in Table 6.

Table 6 Search Strings

<i>Search String Number</i>	<i>Strings</i>
Search string 01	Authentic*
Search string 1a	Lead*
Search string 1b	Develop*
Search string 1c	"Authentic leadership"
Search string 02	Lead*
Search string 2a	Authentic*
Search string 2b	Develop*
Search string 2c	"Authentic leadership"
Search string 03	Authentic leadership
Search string 3a	Oil and Gas
Search string 04	Authentic*
Search string 4a	Follow*
Search string 4b	Develop*
Search string 4c	Authentic leadership
Search string 05	Follow*
Search string 5a	Authentic*
Search string 5b	Develop*
Search string 5c	Authentic leadership
Search string 06	Follow*
Search string 6a	Perception OR Feelings OR Emotion*
Search string 6c	Authentic leadership
Search string 08	Authentic Leadership (For Google Scholar)
Lead* means leader, leadership etc. Authentic* means authentic, authenticity etc. Follow* means follower, followership	

Identification of studies

The review was protocol driven, and a search strategy was implemented to ensure the process's transparency. The primary objective of the search strategy was to identify all relevant publications (peer-reviewed journals) utilising an array of sources. In February 2021, a strategy comprising a pilot search, database search, and manual search was conducted. The procedure is described in detail below:

1. The pilot search began with a comprehensive Google Scholar search. The first 20 pages of results were examined, and this resulted in identifying essential articles, databases that evidently featured authentic leadership, and confirming the review's abundance of studies. In addition, it helped avoid duplication of research efforts on questions that had already been addressed. For the preliminary research, internet search engines such as Google Scholar were utilised, and flaws were identified. For example, it appears challenging to document the search method, which limits reproducibility (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2013). Despite this flaw, it allowed for the development of a refined search strategy.
2. Checking for "synonyms, abbreviations, and related terms" was also used to conduct the refinement (Rowley and Slack, 2004). For example, "AND" connects primary concepts (Fink, 2019). "OR" was used to incorporate synonyms (Brereton *et al.*, 2007; Brereton and McGlinchey, 2020). A pilot search in three databases was conducted to evaluate the accuracy of the chosen keywords. This resulted in modifying search strings for each database and indexing techniques (Tawfik *et al.*, 2019). Experts and a librarian were consulted to determine whether the search strings adhered to best practices (Xiao and Watson, 2019). As recommended by Kitchenham and Charters (2007), the pilot search results were compared to studies familiar to the researcher to assess the performance of the keywords and corroborate their reliability. This was valuable for the review, as a sign of a successful search is the discovery of previously unknown relevant articles (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2013).

3. A systematic search was then conducted across 10 databases using the refined keywords. These databases are Business Source Ultimate, Emerald, EBSCO, Ingenta Connect, Sage Journals, Science Direct, Springer Link, Taylor and Francis, Web of Science and Wiley Online. These databases were selected for the review because they are recognised as the most appropriate for management research, and they have been used for systematic literature reviews by several scholars (Harrison, Paul and Burnard, 2016; Mcquade, Harrison and Tarbert, 2020). The selected databases are also spread across generalist and specialist subjects, considering that one database may not provide complete results during a search (Stansfield *et al.*, 2012; Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017). To ensure an exhaustive evaluation, the search period spanned more than 50 years of research. The search was completed across the ten databases specified in the protocol between 1970 and February 2021. The results of the inquiry were incorporated into the endnote library and the searches yielded a total of 5,332 results.

Screening of studies

The extensive search for studies meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria returned 5,332 results. One critical criterion eliminated duplicate studies: all papers with the same title, author, and publication year. Thus, 2,867 articles were eliminated from the search results. This resulted in 2,465 total articles in the search pool. All results were exported to an excel spreadsheet, and each study was evaluated based on its title before a full reference was obtained for further evaluation. The filtering of article titles eliminated 1,700 articles from the search pool, leaving 765 articles for further evaluation.

The abstracts of these articles were reviewed to determine their suitability. All identified study abstracts were reviewed, and studies were selected based on abstracts meeting inclusion criteria. The objective was to exclude studies that did not address the research question or satisfy the predetermined criteria. When duplicates were

discovered, they were manually removed, and when full texts were not available, research gate was searched, and full text requests were obtained from the authors. During the screening, the abstracts of 181 articles required additional information and the conclusions of these studies were evaluated for clarity (Brereton *et al.*, 2007). Based on the abstracts, 114 articles were found to be pertinent to the review. The details of excluded papers are recorded for replication, verification, and validation.

The selected studies' reference lists were manually searched; forward and reverse searches (Webster and Watson, 2002; Jones and Evans, 2000; Xiao and Watson, 2019) were conducted to identify additional studies that met the inclusion criteria. In addition, a search for citations was conducted, and seven additional studies were located and included. A second Google Scholar search was conducted to ensure an exhaustive search (Gill and Caza, 2018). This was done because scholars have established Google Scholar's efficacy relative to other search engines (Norris, Oppenheim and Rowland, 2008). The first forty pages of the search results for "authentic leadership" were evaluated, and five additional studies were found. The search was concluded when repeated searches yielded no new results (Levy and Ellis, 2006). Overall, the search uncovered a total of 126 articles.

Quality evaluation

This process is described as assessing individual articles to attain understanding before evaluating and incorporating results (Ludvigsen *et al.*, 2016). The key consideration during the quality assessment of the articles was the relevance of the articles in addressing the review questions (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017) and the presentation of findings based on arguments. This stage was critical as the outcome determined the final articles used for data extraction and synthesis. Scholars suggest that qualitative studies may be ranked based on weight, placing studies in three key categories: high, medium and low (Popay *et al.*, 2006). The weight and strength of these studies directly impact the kind of arguments supported and the final synthesis.

The quality and relevance assessment for the review was underpinned by the search for insight and meaning (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2013).

The final selection was based on the assessment of the full paper. The full texts of 126 articles were assessed to appraise the quality and suitability of the review. Studies that were well cited were also determined to have high quality and included in the review. After the evaluation, a total of 46 articles were excluded. In total, 80 articles were identified as suitable for data extraction and synthesis. Figure. 5 provides a flowchart of the literature search and selection procedure using the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Figure 5 Summary of Literature Search

Data extraction

Data was extracted from the full text using a well thought out extraction Excel sheet. The included articles were read and reviewed thoroughly to capture the context of the original findings (Onwuegbuzie, Leech and Collins, 2012). For this review, study findings were all texts labelled as findings within articles. In addition, some other findings were extracted from the abstracts, which, in some cases, were not explicitly captured as findings within the articles (Thomas and Harden, 2008). The extracted data from the included studies centred on the four questions guiding the review. The data extracted also included the authors' details, the article's title, year of publication, type of study, country of study, method of review, name of the journal, definitions of authentic leadership, citations, data collection techniques, and findings relevant to the review questions. These were appropriate and aligned with the data synthesis method adopted within the review.

Data synthesis

According to Tranfield, Denyer and Smart (2003); Denyer and Tranfield (2009) and Gough, Oliver and Thomas (2013) data synthesis combines all the findings to produce a more definitive response to the review's questions. This method of integrating the findings of multiple qualitative studies was advantageous and meaningful. A thematic approach was employed because it facilitated the transparent synthesis of original findings. Moreover, it resulted in the development of credible answers to the review questions. In addition to compiling the results of the studies, this method provided new interpretations of these results (Sandelowski and Barroso, 2006). Upon completion of the data extraction, the findings were thoroughly examined to identify data patterns. Initial identifiers were assigned to these findings, which were then classified into related areas to develop descriptive themes. Following the examinations of the initial themes, the major themes that characterised the findings were developed. Efforts were made to capture context by providing structured summaries of all the included articles detailing aims, setting and samples (Thomas and Harden, 2008) as captured in Appendix 1. In addition, a descriptive synthesis was

also done to evaluate the characteristics of the included studies to assess if they offered alternate interpretations and explanations.

3.2.3 Stage 3: Review reporting and dissemination

This stage provides an audit trail of the review process. The findings are reported, and recommendations are made for future research (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003; Denyer and Tranfield, 2009; Harrison, Paul and Burnard, 2016). In reporting the findings of the systematic literature review of authentic leadership a detailed description of the process is captured and within the chapter. The rationale for all the inclusion and exclusion criteria was clearly described in section 3.2.1. Furthermore, a flow diagram of the searching, screening and quality assessment is provided. The process was transparent, and the conclusions emerged from the data (Xiao and Watson, 2019).

3.3 Findings of the review

This section provides an overview of the review's findings. The results are presented in two subsections. The first section provides a graphical representation of the descriptive analysis of the included studies. It provides inferences about the data's structure, while the four review questions are addressed in the second section. Refer to appendix 1 for a summary of all articles reviewed for the study.

3.3.1 Descriptive analysis

This subsection describes the characteristics of the included studies using charts, diagrams, and graphs. It provides information on the type of study, adopted methodological approaches, data collection techniques, frequency and distribution of citations, number of publications, sources of literature, and geographical distribution.

Types of Research

The findings included conceptual, review, and empirical articles. 30% of the papers were theoretical, 64% were empirical, and 6% were review articles. The findings are depicted in Figure 6.

Methodological strategies

The empirical studies reviewed utilised quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methodologies. 57% of the findings were quantitative, 41% were qualitative, and 2% utilised mixed methods. The results are depicted alongside publication years in Figure 6 below.

Count of articles

The review includes publications between 1970 and 2021. These publications are depicted in Figure 6 over five years. This graph provides an overview of the articles published over five years, the categories of studies conducted, and the methodology employed.

Figure 6 Five-year interval

The conceptual papers peaked between 2002 and 2006 and dropped over a decade but have recently started gaining traction. This shows that authentic leadership is a relatively new theory, and further research is necessary to ground its conceptualisation. Regarding methodological approaches, the empirical studies within the review adopted quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods. These articles are plotted in figure 6 using a five-year interval and it was done to present the data concisely.

Figure 7 below expands the summary presented in the previous figure by providing a more detailed representation of the findings within the study. The figure below offers enhanced clarity and detail, which helps to illustrate better the focus of the scholars of authentic leadership from 1970- 2021 as captured below in figure 7.

Figure 7 Breakdown of research papers from 1970 -2021

As expected, the prevailing method of data collection employed was surveys, primarily due to the quantitative nature of the studies included in the review. Surveys contributed 58% to the data collection techniques. Regarding qualitative studies, there was a combination of data collection techniques which included interviews contributing 18%, participant observation contributing 2%, dairy studies 12%, and analysis of media articles contributing 2%. Some studies used a combination of focus groups and interviews, contributing 6%, and a combination of interviews and participant information contributing 2%. These are captured in figure 8 below:

Figure 8 Data Collection Techniques

Geographical distribution of studies

Several research articles emerged from western countries, with 66 studies representing 82% of articles within the review. Articles from non western countries contributed 18%, with one study sampled across developing and developing countries. 31 articles were from the United States of America. The UK closely followed with 9 studies, Australia accounting for 6, and 4 were from Canada. Furthermore, 3 studies emerged from South Africa. The other countries contributed between 1 and 2 papers. Figure 9 below presents the geographical distribution of the articles. There were also 8 articles across multiple western countries; however, 2 papers had samples

from developing countries. The results provide evidence that research on authentic leadership is rooted in a western perspective.

Figure 9 Geographical distribution of articles

Only 14 articles examined authentic leadership from a non western perspective as detailed in figure 9. The distribution of the articles are as follows: 2 from Pakistan (Bakari, Hunjra and Niazi, 2017; Mehmood, Schreurs and Hamstra, 2019), 3 from South Africa (Wulffers, Bussin and Hewitt, 2016; Hendricks and Toth-Cohen, 2018; Olckers, du Plessis and Casaleggio, 2020). There were 2 from Nigeria (Emuwa and Fields, 2017; Balogun, Mahembe and Allen-Ile, 2020), 2 from India (Khilji *et al.*, 2015; Shrivastava, 2018), 2 from Korea (Joo and Nimon, 2014; Joo and Jo, 2017), 1 from China (Zhang *et al.*, 2012), 1 from Israel (Shamir and Eilam, 2005) and 1 from Lebanon (Sidani and Rowe, 2018).

Citations

The number of citations varied across the selected studies. The article with the most citation was Avolio and Gardner (2005) paper titled “Authentic leadership development: Getting to the root of positive forms of leadership.” It is considered a seminal work because it provides an overview of the authentic leadership field, describing the factors that have contributed to the emergence of the construct. The paper describes in detail the conceptual foundations, definitions, components, and features of authentic leadership. The article has 5,277 citations. In general, 28 articles within the review have over 100 citations each. Figure 10 outlines the nine most cited articles within the review, which shows the prominence of some authors within the domain.

Figure 10 Overview of citations

A recent review of the citations conducted on January 29th, 2024, regarding the papers highlighted in Figure 10 above revealed a significant increase in their citation count. This development indicates the growing recognition and impact of the research conducted within those papers. For instance Avolio and Gardner (2005) currently has 7,714 citations, Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) has 5,927 citations. This increase in citations

reflects the significance and contribution of the studies to the field. It also affirms that scholars are building upon the insights provided in those papers.

3.3.2 Addressing the review questions.

This subsection outlines the findings that address the review questions of the SLR. The section is divided into four parts per the research protocol.

RQ1. What is authentic leadership?

The construct of authentic leadership has drawn a lot of scholarly and practitioner attention, but it has been criticised for lacking conceptual clarity, embodying philosophical ambiguity, and having a narrow demographic appeal (Iszatt-White and Kempster, 2019; Crawford *et al.*, 2020). This has led to the proliferation of research that has contributed immensely to the development and the confusion on its conceptualisation. To address the review question, a thematic analysis was conducted on all the included articles of the SLR. The review adopted the six-stage methodology advanced by Braun and Clarke (2006) for sense making of the data in order to uncover the prevailing themes. These themes revealed that the authentic leadership construct has been examined from five key perspectives respectively. These five perspectives are as an ideal leadership approach, a four-dimensional phenomenon, a type of transformational leader, a root construct, and a battle of self.

The proponents of the ideal leadership perspective argue that authentic leadership is based solely on positive traits, characteristics, and emotions, with both leaders and followers possessing it. The perspective was advanced to regain the trust (Duignan, 2014) that management misconduct had eroded. Furthermore, it is impersonal and inspirational (McFarlane, 2011) and a leadership multiplier (Beddoes-Jones and Swailes, 2015). These authentic leaders recognise and develop the potential of their followers as the development of these potentials contribute to organisational success. Affirming that authentic leaders positively influence the attitudes and behaviours of their followers, thereby empowering them to succeed (Avolio *et al.*, 2004). Similarly, authentic leadership contributes to positive outcomes within organisations, including influencing the ethical behaviour of followers (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Gardner *et*

al., 2005), fostering creativity, and building resilience (Gaddy *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, Suhonen, Malila and Lunkka (2018) recommend authentic leadership as the preferred leadership style for creating healthy work environments for nurses. With Iszatt-White and Kempster (2019) notably describing the leadership approach as an idealised construct in their paper.

Secondly as a four-dimensional construct, proponents of this perspective describe authentic leadership as a four-dimensional behaviour that is mutually reinforcing. These dimensions or components include self awareness, internalised moral perspective, balanced processing, and relational transparency. Self awareness is rooted in consistent reflections, introspections, and feedback recognising one's strengths and weaknesses (Gardner *et al.*, 2005). Also, grasping the multifaceted nature of the self and how individuals derive meaning from social interactions would advance the domain (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008). This is because self awareness is described as the foundation of leadership development (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Gardner *et al.*, 2005), an essential aspect of authentic leadership.

According to Alilyyani, Wong and Cummings (2018) internalised moral perspective is a self regulation process that is led by internalised principles. The key word is moral, which is open to multiple interpretations but connotes positivity and would be perceived as socially beneficial (Alvesson and Einola, 2019). This explains why authentic leaders are characterised as leaders with high moral standards and integrity (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005). However, there are crucial issues concerning the limits of these morals, and who determines what values are moral.

The third component, balanced processing, was initially conceptualised as unbiased processing. This was revised to reflect the inherent bias nature of human information processing (Avolio and Gardner, 2005). Balanced processing is an approach to information processing that takes all perspectives into account (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008). Finally, the concept of relational transparency in authentic leadership suggests that leaders are expected to engage in positive social interactions, which will have a

beneficial impact on the wellbeing of both followers and leaders themselves as authentic leadership is predominately dependent on relational transparency (Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017). Crawford *et al.* (2020) acknowledge that although interpersonal components are incorporated into relational transparency, the current model of authentic leaders portrays individual's intrapersonal interactions in an inconsistent manner, suggesting that relational transparency is not confined to the individual.

Sims, Gong and Hughes (2017) argue that self regulation is exhibited through relational transparency, an internalised moral perspective, and balanced processing, while the authentic self is presented to followers through all four components. These dimensions have been empirically examined, and the results indicate that different components influence perceptions of authentic leadership to varying degrees. For example, internalised moral perspective is associated with the positive emotions of followers during a time of change (Agote, Aramburu and Lines, 2016). However, existing conceptualisations still need to adequately describe these components (Sidani and Rowe, 2018). It is claimed that further investigation of the components that constitute authentic leadership is vital to the field because of the divergent views with literature. These authors include: Gardner *et al.* (2005), Walumbwa *et al.* (2008), Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber (2009), Peus *et al.* (2012), Agote, Aramburu and Lines (2016), Ngunjiri and Hernandez (2017), Sims, Gong and Hughes (2017), Alilyyani, Wong and Cummings (2018), Sidani and Rowe (2018), Alvesson and Einola (2019) and Crawford *et al.* (2020) .

Thirdly, as a type of transformational leadership, scholars that advanced this perspective contend that authentic leadership and transformational leaders are linked. In general, authentic and transformational leaders are optimistic and authentic leadership is described as a form of transformational leadership (Joo and Nimon, 2014; Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber, 2009). Earlier studies on authentic leadership used the concept of authenticity to describe worthy transformational leaders. These leaders were classified as authentic transformational leaders whose conduct were

underpinned by morals (Sidani and Rowe, 2018). Authors that explored these two leadership theories include: Avolio and Gardner (2005), Gardner *et al.* (2005), Shamir and Eilam (2005), Peus *et al.* (2012), Beddoes-Jones and Swailes (2015), Banks *et al.* (2016) and Tibbs *et al.* (2016).

Fourthly, as a root construct, proponents of this perspective argue that authentic leadership is a root construct for other positive forms of leadership, such as transformational, servant, charismatic, spiritual, and ethical (Avolio and Gardner, 2005). Accordingly, Avolio and Gardner (2005) argue that authentic leadership is a “root construct that underpins all positive forms of leadership and its development (p. 315).” Though, there is an ongoing debate on the incorporation of ethics into authentic leadership which has allowed it to transcend the limitations of transformational leadership and become an independent construct. The argument that authentic leadership is a root construct implies that it incorporates other forms of leadership (Peus *et al.*, 2012); therefore, additional empirical research is required to assess whether it is a root construct or not (Tibbs *et al.*, 2016).

Finally, as a battle of self, proponents of this perspective, argue that authentic leadership emerged from authenticity with two prevailing arguments drawing from the psychological and philosophical concept of authenticity (Algera and Lips-Wiersma, 2012). Consequently, offering wide ranging implications for the construct.

In addition, Sparrowe (2005) outlines four recent conceptualisations of the true self and its connection to authentic leadership: (1) the significance of an autonomous self; (2) the fundamental role of values in shaping the true self; (3) the promotion of consistency through self regulation; and (4) the relationship between authentic leadership and moral leadership. Some scholars contend that these perspectives have limitations, despite the author's attempt to address them using hermeneutic philosophy. Although, Sparrowe (2005) believes that knowing one's true self is fundamental to authenticity, the author disagrees that this knowledge can only be attained by isolating oneself from others. Thus, Sparrowe (2005) rationalises that the

omission is not due to a lack of interest among scholars but rather stems from their oversight of how the authentic self is forged through interpersonal relationships, as highlighted by Joo and Nimon (2014).

Leaders' authentic selves are dynamic, flexible, and stately, alluding to their potential growth. This suggests that context and individuals influence the state of a leader's enduring qualities. The conceptualisation of authentic leadership advanced by Avolio *et al.* (2004) and Gardner *et al.* (2005) extend beyond arguments on the true self to include and emphasise a moral component even though Shamir and Eilam (2005) contested this claim.

In the descriptions and conceptualisation of the construct of authentic leadership several authors have emphasised a singular perspective, while others have adopted a multiplicity of viewpoints. Therefore, scholars have proposed various definitions of the construct. The most prominent definition, which is arguably the most quoted, cited, and referenced definition (Joo and Nimon, 2014; Agote, Aramburu and Lines, 2016; Joo and Jo, 2017; Sims, Gong and Hughes, 2017; Crawford *et al.*, 2020). These authors define authentic leadership as “a pattern of leader behaviour that draws upon and promotes both positive psychological capacities and a positive ethical climate, to foster greater self awareness, an internalised moral perspective, balanced information processing, and relational transparency on the part of leaders working with followers, thereby fostering positive self-development (P.94).”

RQ2. What are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders?

Scholars have devoted a great deal of attention to the factors that foster authentic leadership development. This reiterates the relevance of authentic leadership and reflects an interest in stimulating the authentic leadership development of leaders (Gaddy *et al.*, 2017). Internally and externally motivated factors are the two main categories used to classify the findings on the factors that inspire authentic leadership development.

Internal Factors: The results for this part of the inquiry were quite intriguing and revealed gendered perspectives of authentic leaders, even though this was not the objective of the study. The internal factors are outwardly stimulated; yet the stimulation is not pre planned but a reaction or response to the factors. According to Shamir and Eilam (2005), authentic leadership development is stimulated by four critical factors: adversity, purpose or cause, active learning, and natural stimulation. For instance, male managers perceived themselves as authentic leaders within their organisations. In contrast, role incongruity constrained female administrators (Monzani *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, female leaders in male dominated sectors or positions were motivated to cultivate authentic leadership in order to succeed and be effective (Tibbs *et al.*, 2016).

It is argued that leaders may also find motivation to nurture authentic leadership as a means to pursue their personal aspirations, many of which often originate during their formative years, shaped by experiences of adversity, happiness, or a strong desire to effect meaningful change, as noted by Stiers *et al.* (2019). In one of the earliest works on authentic leadership, Gardner *et al.* (2005) identified the factors that inspire the development of authentic leadership. These identified factors consist of both positive and negative trigger events and experiences spanning personal life, career, education, and trials. For instance, Furthermore, Rudolph Giuliani in the United States drew inspiration from personal experiences and the shocking global events, demonstrating authentic leadership qualities after September 11 terrorist attack (Wright, 2015). Similarly, personal encounters with authentic leaders, also known as the "power of influence," inspired authentic leadership development (McFarlane, 2011; Duignan, 2014). These internal factors are stimulated externally. However, the stimulation is a reaction or response to external exigencies.

External Factors: Simulation can be used to inspire authentic leadership development in relation to external factors (Wulffers, Bussin and Hewitt, 2016). Several scholars have proposed and evaluated various interventions for authentic leadership

development. These interventions range from leadership programmes, research centres (Glowacki-Dudka and Griswold, 2016), training contexts (Baron and Parent, 2015), experiential education (Copeland, 2014), interventions programmes (Shrivastava, 2018) and camping (Hendricks and Toth-Cohen, 2018).

Typically, these interventions occur in controlled environments where coaches, colleagues, and other specialists are positioned to steer the transformation process (Algera and Lips-Wiersma, 2012; Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer, 2015a; Hendricks and Toth-Cohen, 2018). Herein lies the crucial distinction between internally and externally inspired authentic leadership development processes, as authentic leaders personally manage internal factors. While externally inspired authentic leadership development, is managed externally from the outset (Baron and Parent, 2015). Scholars have provided evidence that external factors can be simulated. For instance the wilderness experiences of leaders, led to a greater awareness of self, values, connectedness, and presence, which prompted the desire to cultivate authentic leadership (van Droffelaar and Jacobs, 2017). This demonstrates that the natural environment can also inspire authentic leadership development.

In conclusion, authentic leadership development may be motivated by internal or external factors (Gardner *et al.*, 2005; Puente, Crous and Venter, 2007; Shannon *et al.*, 2020; Wood *et al.*, 2020). Even so, there still several unanswered questions regarding the quantity of trigger events or crucibles necessary to inspire authentic leadership development. In a similar vein, research on the long term effects of these factors is limited necessitating further studies on the underlying processes.

RQ3. What are the followers' perceptions of authentic leadership?

Perceptions characterise a person's comprehension of a phenomenon. A few of the reviewed articles examined followers' perceptions of authentic leadership (Tate, 2008; Hendricks and Toth-Cohen, 2018). However, the majority of these studies have focused on how followers' perceptions are influenced in order to achieve

organisational objectives or improve leadership effectiveness (Kurian and Nafukho, 2021). Hence, Banks *et al.* (2016) contend that employees' perceptions of their supervisors or leaders as authentic have positive implications for authentic leaders. In particular, Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) argue that the extent to which leaders' and followers' perceptions of authentic leadership overlap would result in improved performance.

The perceptions of followers have predominantly been described from two vantage points. The first is embedded in the behaviour of leaders and how these behaviours influence the perceptions of followers. This perspective can be traced back to the earliest conceptualisations of the construct, in which scholars conceptualised the concept in terms of behaviours. These characteristics were referred to as dimensions (Alilyyani, Wong and Cummings, 2018). Other scholars such as Gill and Caza (2018) suggest that followers perceive leaders as authentic when the four-dimensional behaviours are demonstrated. Similarly, followers' perceptions of authentic leadership are influenced by a leader's inconsistent behaviour across various contexts (Mehmood, Schreurs and Hamstra, 2019).

The second perspective contends that followers' perceptions of authentic leadership emerge from their sense making and interpretations within organisations; however, little research has been conducted in this area (Fields, 2007). The analysis revealed that followers' perceptions of authentic leadership vary over time and between followers. In addition, the self perceptions of authentic leaders did not influence followers' perceptions (Tate, 2008), but perceptions of these leaders increased within groups.

In the domain of leadership, the followers' role in the leadership process is acknowledged but frequently overlooked. According to Fields (2007), the process of person perception includes components such as familiarity, overlap, shared meaning, consistency, extraneous information and communication. Examining perceptions is therefore essential for the development of leadership with further studies that will uncover the social perspectives of followers. The advantage of researching the sense making process is that it will facilitate the identification of individuals with a greater

potential to be ascribed an influential status within organisations as this process develops and fluctuates over time (Tate, 2008). It will also reveal what followers consider to be authentic leadership and how they interpret it. This is important because perceptions are processes, and additional research is needed to reveal the nature of these processes, contributing to the advancement of theory.

RQ4. How do follower perceptions shape authentic leadership development?

While addressing this review question, it became evident that there is a significant lack of research on the active role played by followers' perceptions, particularly in relation to how these perceptions influence the development of authentic leadership. In the review, 27 studies examined followers' perceptions. This constitutes 34% of the included articles in the investigation. An additional evaluation of these articles revealed that 22 papers, or 27% of the initial 34% of identified studies, evaluated the influence of authentic leadership on the perceptions of followers. These studies range from topics on resilience to organisational citizenship, authentic leadership development among followers, emotions, change, job satisfaction, engagement, organisational justice, and a healthy work environment. Only 6% of the reviewed studies examined how followers' perceptions influence authentic leadership development (Tate, 2008; Hanold, 2017; Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017; Sidani and Rowe, 2018; Stiers *et al.*, 2019).

Interestingly, the relationship between leadership effectiveness and perceptions is positive (McFarlane, 2011). This relationship has been extensively studied, notably concerning how it leads to positive organisational outcomes (Mehmood, Schreurs and Hamstra, 2019). Accordingly, Avolio *et al.* (2004) found that balanced processing and relational transparency enhance positive perceptions, which contribute to the development of an authentic leader. This argument suggests that followers' perception acts as a tool in evaluating how authentic a leader is perceived. Moreover, employee perceptions of leaders are essential to organisational success, and the extent

to which it relates to a leader's self perception is essential for authentic leadership advancement (Černe *et al.*, 2014).

The perspective has neglected the iterative and active role that followers' perceptions play in influencing authentic leadership development, despite its contribution to the advancement of the field. This may be due to the prevalent notion that followers are passive and expect leaders to stimulate their perceptions.

Regarding, the increase in followers' perceptions, there are suggestions that follower perceptions will increase when authentic leaders demonstrate exemplary leadership qualities. This is typically determined by the criteria followers employ instinctively when evaluating what a leader should be and how leadership practices impact followers on an individual and group level. This is significant because cultural context and social actors influence leadership perceptions (McFarlane, 2011; Zhang *et al.*, 2012; Khilji *et al.*, 2015). Also, empirical evidence demonstrate that authentic leadership emerges from the interaction between leader and follower. So, further research is necessary to comprehend these interactions and how the perceptions of followers contribute to the development process.

3.4 Conclusion

In summary, this chapter has outlined the process and outcomes of an extensive systematic literature review on authentic leadership, from 1970 to 2021. The review of 80 studies provides a comprehensive overview of the field and the current state of authentic leadership research. The inclusion criteria were defined to ensure the selection of studies that focused on authentic leadership, resulting in a robust analysis.

Several scholars have contributed to the development of authentic leadership theory, and it has become the preferred leadership approach among practitioners. However, the focus has shifted from discovering what it means and what makes up the construct to an examination of competencies of authentic leadership and the implications for organisations.

To advance the domain, a clearer conceptualisation of authentic leadership is required (Gill and Caza, 2018), given that the existing definitions are fragmented and convoluted. Similarly, a clear definition of authentic leadership is essential for facilitating a rigorous examination of the construct and illuminating the object of leadership interventions which may focus on the person or process. As the current definitions consists of outcomes alongside cause and effect (Alvesson and Einola, 2019).

Likewise, the identified components of authentic leadership are neither substantial enough to serve as a theoretical foundation for the construct nor do they constitute a logical whole when characterising the construct of authentic leadership (Alvesson and Einola, 2019). To resolve these, it is recommended that scholars strive to explore and uncover additional components of authentic leadership (Crawford *et al.*, 2020). In particular, scholars have implied that the components of authentic leadership be examined with a specific focus on the impacts and outcomes of these components and the relationships that exist amongst them (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Peus *et al.*, 2012) as there still exists debates on the specific components that constitute authentic leadership. Furthermore, scholars have focused primarily on western contexts (Yammarino *et al.*, 2008; Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber, 2009; Liu, Cletcher and Grant, 2017). This predominantly western approach does not account for diversity and disparities across demographics.

The review calls for further research on follower perceptions and how followers' perceptions contribute to the development of authentic leadership (Peus *et al.*, 2012). This is because a deeper understanding of how followers' perceptions influence authentic leadership development have practical implications for leadership development (Copeland, 2014; Steffens *et al.*, 2016).

Finally, the review provides an evaluation of past and current state of authentic leadership research. This is necessary as the plurality of views provide a robust understanding of the construct. The next chapter provides a discussion on the context

of study, Nigeria and presents a schematic overview of the literature that shapes the study.

CHAPTER 4. THE NIGERIAN CONTEXT

INTRODUCTION

This chapter is the concluding literature review chapter of the thesis. It provides an overview of the study's context and is organised into four main segments. The initial segment begins with a discussion on economic taxonomies. It examines the distinguishing characteristics of developed and developing economies, justifying the study's relevance within the context of a developing economy. The subsequent section provides an overview of the socio economic conditions in Nigeria, a country in the process of economic growth. It provides an account of the nation's historical, political, economic, and physical terrain. The third segment commences with an examination of Nigeria's oil industry. It documents the development of the sector starting from the 1930s. This section discusses the significance and function of oil within Nigeria. It also highlights the difficulties endemic to the sector. The chapter concludes with the presentation of the conceptual framework; offering a guiding structure and theoretical lens through which the research is conducted.

4.1 Taxonomy of Economies

The United Nations typically categorises economies as either developing or developed states. Developed nations are countries that have made significant progress in terms of industrialisation and economic independence. Developing countries are characterised by their low per capita GDP and their early stage of industrialisation (Lin, 2012; Haraguchi, Martorano and Sanfilippo, 2019). The disparity between developed and developing nations has significantly widened during the past three decades (Jeníček, 2011; Raynolds, 2004; Jordá and Niño-Zarazúa, 2017). This gap has attracted the attention of scholars (Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 1992; Paprotny, 2021). With the differences being most apparent in the living conditions and economic

strength. Furthermore, this discrepancy has also been attributed to the industrial revolution, which boosted the prosperity of certain nations while neglecting a substantial portion of others (Deaton, 2013; Ricart-Huguet, 2021). Hence, efforts are being undertaken to address these gaps.

For instance, the advancement of the tenth sustainable development goal, which seeks to bridge the gap between countries through several intervention schemes (Keitsch, 2018; Guterres, 2022). There is a debate on how the improvement of the socio economic conditions will drive these developing countries forward, but it is important to focus on the unique regional peculiarities (Jeníček, 2011; Avgerou and Walsham, 2017). Thus, the following section explains the main differences between developed and developing nations.

It is argued that a central motif of “colonialism” permeates the history of developing countries (Jeníček, 2011), contributing to the gap between developed and developing economies. Historically, many nations were economically or politically dependent on their colonial rulers (Ranis, 2004; Alemazung, 2010; Adeyeri and Adejuwon, 2012) and Table 7 outlines the main differences between developed and developing nations.

Table 7 Taxonomy of Economies

Developed Economy	Developing Economy
High GDP	Low GDP
High literacy rate	High illiteracy rate
Low birth and death rate	High birth and death rate
High standard of living	Moderate or low standard of living
Good and adequate infrastructure	Inadequate infrastructure
High Human Development Index	Low Human Development Index

Source: Booth et al. (2001)

Several parameters have been used to categorise economies, with two prominent criteria widely employed by international institutions. The first criterion is based on the

socio economic position of the country and is typically used by United Nations network organisations. The second criterion relies on per capita income and is commonly employed by the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund and it highlights the economic capability of a country (Jeníček, 2011). Developing countries can also be categorised using other factors such as the net trade position, shared characteristics, geographic location, and level of human development. Table 8 presents an overview of both developed and developing nations.

Table 8 Summary of developed and developing countries

Category	Countries
Developed	Andorra, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bermuda, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Greenland, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, San Marino, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, United States of America, Holy See, Faroe Islands, Gibraltar, Saint Pierre and Miquelon.
Developing	Algeria, American Samoa, Anguilla, Antigua and Barbuda, Argentina, Aruba, Bahamas, Bahrain, Barbados, Belize, Plurinational State of Bolivia, Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba, Botswana, Bouvet Island, Brazil, British Indian Ocean Territory, British Virgin Islands, Brunei Darussalam, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Cayman Islands, Chile, China, Hong Kong SAR, Macao SAR, Taiwan Province of China , Colombia, Congo, Cook Islands, Costa Rica, Côte d'Ivoire, Cuba, Curaçao, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Egypt, El Salvador, Equatorial Guinea, Eswatini, Falkland Islands (Malvinas), Fiji, French Polynesia, French Southern Territories, Gabon, Ghana, Grenada, Guam, Guatemala, Guyana, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Islamic Republic of Iran, Iraq, Jamaica, Jordan, Kenya, Democratic People's Republic of Korea , Republic of Korea , Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Malaysia, Maldives, Marshall Islands, Mauritius, Mexico, Federated States of Micronesia, Mongolia, Montserrat, Morocco, Namibia, Nauru, Netherlands Antilles, New Caledonia, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Niue, Northern Mariana Islands, Oman, Pacific Islands, Trust Territory, Pakistan, Palau, Panama, Papua New Guinea, Paraguay, Peru, Philippines, Pitcairn, Qatar, Saint Barthélemy, Saint Helena, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Lucia, Saint Martin (French part), Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Samoa, Saudi Arabia, Seychelles, Singapore, Sint Maarten (Dutch part), South Africa, South Georgia and South Sandwich Islands, Sri Lanka, State of Palestine, Suriname, Syrian Arab Republic, Thailand, Tokelau, Tonga, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Turks and Caicos Islands, United Arab Emirates, United States Minor Outlying Islands, Uruguay, Bolivarian Republic

	of Venezuela, Viet Nam, Wallis and Futuna Islands, Western Sahara, Zimbabwe.
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Source: United Nations (2022)

4.1.1 Developing Economies

The 20th century ushered in an emerging segment of the global economy. This is because developing economies contributed more to natural and human resources, impacting the global economy. Remarkably, over three-quarter of the world's population reside in developing nations; approximately 79.9 percent as of 2005. This contribution is aptly described by (Jeníček, 2011):

“At the beginning of the 21st century, developing countries are spread over the area of little less than one half of the Earth surface (38% without Antarctica). They farm on 62% of the total agricultural and 54% of arable land. In absolute numbers, this represents 77.9 million km² of the Earth surface, 31 million km² of agricultural and 7.6 million km² of arable land (p. 182).”

Initially optimistic, a recent study conducted by Paprotny (2021) reveals that while emerging countries are making overall advancements, these improvements are not evenly distributed. The study spanned a period of a century (1920 to 2020), and its findings were evaluated based on sustainable development goals (SDG). The findings indicate that Sub-Saharan Africa has experienced the most delay in keeping pace with other developing nations. Since reaching its peak in 2001, the GDP per capita has consistently declined. The findings also revealed that most of these nations are plagued with corruption constraining the growth of developing nations.

The impact of “corruption” differs across different developing nations (Strauss, 2001; Uddin and Rahman, 2023). Therefore, it is imperative to examine leadership within this specific context, as the actions of most leaders in Sub-Saharan countries have hindered rather than promoted economic progress (Strauss, 2001). These countries have a younger demography which suggests growth potential based on a prospective larger working population (Cervellati, Meyerheim and Sunde, 2019). Hence, the importance of studying leadership which has now been amplified by the pandemic. Considering

the arguments presented earlier, Nigeria's status as a developing economy provides a suitable context for exploring authentic leadership. The context's suitability will be discussed in the next section.

4.2 Nigeria

Nigeria is the most populated country in Africa and the seventh most populous country in the world (Abubakar, 2011; Akinyemi and Isiugo-Abanihe, 2014; Dambo *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, this section provides an overview of Nigeria's geographical, political, economic, and socioeconomic structure, justifying the significance of investigating AL within this context.

4.2.1 Geography

Nigeria is situated on the coast of the Gulf of Guinea on the West Coast and is located within Sub-Saharan Africa (Agbeja, 2016; Nwalozie, 2020). The country's land area is around 910,768 square kilometres, while its water area is 13,000 square kilometres, resulting in a total area of 923,768 square kilometres (Akinyemi and Isiugo-Abanihe, 2014). It has natural resources, which include natural gas, petroleum, tin, iron ore, coal, limestone, zinc and arable land (CIA, 2022). Nigeria is an oil exporter and possesses the largest natural gas reserves on the African continent (Ayuba, 2023; Morocco-Clarke, 2023). The archaeological evidence indicates that Nigeria has been inhabited by humans for thousands of years (Shelford, 1929; Falola and Heaton, 2008).

Nigeria has 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory, which serves as the country's capital city. These states are governed by 36 Governors, while the FCT is administered by the FCT minister. Lagos, previously the capital of Nigeria, is the third most populous metropolis in Africa and a very cosmopolitan city (Enoh, Njoku and Okeke, 2023; Bandaiko and Nutifafa Arku, 2023). Figure 11 depicts an aerial map of the nation.

Figure 11 A Map of Nigeria

Source: UNGeospatial (2014) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

4.2.2 People and Society

As at July 2018, Nigeria's population was estimated to be approximately 203 million, with an annual growth rate of 2.4% (CIA, 2022). With the population expected to reach 263 million by 2030 (Mubecua and David, 2019; Victory, Oyewole and Olaitan, 2022). This is roughly half of the population of West Africa (WorldBank, 2023). The last population census was conducted in 2006 (Akinyemi and Isiugo-Abanihe, 2014), so these numbers are estimates. However, the current population as at 2021 is 213,401,323 people as stated by World Bank (WorldBank, 2023).

There are more than 250 ethnic groups in the country, with three prominent groups. These three groups make up more than 66% of the population. The Yorubas account

for 21% of the population, the Igbos for 18%, and the Hausas for 27.4% (CIA, 2022). Nigeria is a nation rich in diversity with over 500 languages being spoken in country, according to the CIA (2022). This is also evident from the diversity of religions practised by the populace. Islam is the most prevalent religion, with approximately 51.6% of the population practising it. Traditionalism by 9%, Roman Catholicism by 11.2%, other types of Christianity by 35.7% and unspecified religion accounting for about 5% as at 2013.

4.2.3 Political landscape

Nigeria was under colonial rule until the 1960s when it gained independence on the 1st of October. It operates a Federal system of government (Okwelum, 2023) and the government's legislative comprises of the Senate and the House of Representatives, which have 109 and 360 seats respectively (CIA, 2022). The political scene is currently led by the All Progressives Congress Party (APC), which is the ruling party in the country, with the main opposition party being Peoples Democratic Party (PDP).

In 1963, it became a republic and in 1967, an autonomous group called the Biafrans emerged, resulting in a three year civil war (Obasanjo, 1980; Anthony, 2014). The country has experienced political instability as governments have been toppled in several military coups. These coups began right after independence, and the country was mainly under military leadership from 1966 until 1999 (Abegunrin, 2003). The only exception was when Nigeria transitioned briefly to democracy from 1979 to 1983 (Forrest, 1986; Ekwe-Ekwe, 1985; Agbese, 1990). In 1999, Olusegun Obasanjo was elected president of a democratically elected government in Nigeria (Olukoyun, 2004).

By mid-2007, Umaru Musa Yar'dua became the president but died suddenly in 2010 (Ayeomoni and Akinkuolere, 2012). Vice President Goodluck Ebele Jonathan became president and ruled until 2015. President Goodluck Jonathan invested heavily in infrastructure, evident across the transportation and power sectors. However, this period in Nigeria also witnessed challenges, such as the \$2 billion arms fraud and the rise of an insurgent group, Boko haram (Albert and Okoli, 2016; Ojo *et al.*, 2020). In

2015, power was handed over President, Maj. Gen. (ret.) Muhammadu Buhari and in 2023, following a general election, power was handed to the current Commander in Chief, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu (Ikenga and Oluka, 2023).

Interestingly, the discontinuation of government support for fuel prices has persisted as a significant issue in Nigeria. Therefore, President Tinubu's announcement regarding the removal of fuel subsidies on May 29th, 2023, led to a nationwide increase in petrol and transportation costs. Despite the potential long term benefits, there has been continuous public resistance to this policy (Evans *et al.*, 2023; Ogunode and Ukozor, 2023).

The country has been plagued by insecurity because of the actions of various factions. Since 2011, the Boko Haram terrorist group has gained momentum and consistently terrified Nigeria's northern states. Similarly, the Niger delta region of the country, renowned for its rich oil resources and reserves, have been targeted by armed groups. This is to be expected, given scholars contend that corruption and a lack of expertise are prevalent in developing economies (Bardhan, 1997; Mauro, 1995; Luthans, Stajkovic and Ibrayeva, 2000; Arslan and Alqatan, 2020). The country has experienced political instability in terms of leadership. The nature of the problem is aptly described by Achebe (1984): "The problem with Nigeria is straightforwardly a failure of leadership (p. 1)." Thus, the significance of authentic leadership in this context.

4.2.4 Economy

Nigeria, being a nation characterised by a significant number of traders, perhaps reflects the level of economic activity across the West African region (Yusuff, 2013). The nation is typically described to as the 'Giant of Africa' due to its status as the most populous country on the continent and its ranking in the top 10 countries worldwide. Its economy is the largest and most dominant in Africa (David-West and Nwagwu, 2018; Salawu, 2020).

Nigeria is the continent's largest oil producer (Obioma, 2012; Odeyemi, 2014; Uduji, Okolo-Obasi and Asongu, 2019). Its oil production has stimulated economic growth,

and the economy is significantly dependent on the sector. Figure 12 provides a summary of the Nigerian Gross Domestic Product Report (Q1 2023).

Figure 12 Nigerian Gross Domestic Product Report

Source : National Bureau of Statistics (2023)

Nigeria experienced a 2.31 percent growth in its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) during the first quarter of 2023. The growth experienced is lower than the 3.11% recorded in the first quarter of the previous year and the decrease is attributed to the adverse impacts of the cash scarcity encountered during the quarter (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). The oil sector plays a significant role in the country's gross domestic product (GDP) and ranks fourth in terms of its contribution as captured in Figure 13:

Figure 13 Top Contributing Activities to Real GDP in Q1 2023

Source : National Bureau of Statistics (2023)

The real growth rate of the oil industry in the first quarter of 2023 was -4.21% (year-over-year), representing an increase of 21.83% over the rate recorded in the same quarter of 2022 (-26.04%). There was an increase of 9.18% compared to the fourth quarter of 2022, which experienced a decline of -13.38% (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). The energy sector accounted for 6.21% of the total real GDP. This is a decline compared to the same time in 2022, but an increase compared to the preceding quarter, where it contributed 6.63% and 4.34% respectively (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Other economic indicators are outlined below in Table 9.

Table 9 Economic Indicators

Economic Indicators	1990	2000	2010	2020
GDP (current US\$) (billions)	54.04	69.45	361.46	397.19
GDP growth (annual %)	11.8	5.0	8.0	1.9
Inflation, GDP deflator (annual %)	6.7	22.7	16.3	10.2
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing, value added (% of GDP)	22	21	24	21
Industry (including construction), value added (% of GDP)	35	34	25	26
Exports of goods and services (% of GDP)	21	36	26	15
Imports of goods and services (% of GDP)	10	13	18	18
Gross capital formation (% of GDP)	53	34	18	20
Net barter terms of trade index (2000 = 100)	89	100	184	167
External debt stocks, total (DOD, current US\$) (millions)	33,458	33,514	18,822	50,452
Total debt service (% of exports of goods, services and primary income)	22.6	8.8	1.5	7.9
Net migration (thousands)	-96	-170	-300	-300
Personal remittances, received (current US\$) (millions)	10	1,392	19,745	24,311
Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$) (millions)	588	1,140	6,026	1,997
Net official development assistance received (current US\$) (millions)	255.1	173.8	2,052.4	3,304.9

Source: World Development Indicators database (World Bank, 2020)

Nigeria is described as one of the MINT nations, which includes Mexico, Indonesia, and Turkey, in addition to the BRIC nations (Osinubi *et al.*, 2023). These economies with rapid growth potentials are positioned to attract foreign direct investments. It is argued that for these nations to continue to attract FDI, they must maintain political stability, invest in human capital, and provide investors with a level playing field (Asongu, Akpan and Isihak, 2018). The Nigerian economy attracted FDIs and was classified as a fast growing economy. However, the country is plagued with several challenges, including unemployment and poverty (Ighoshemu and Ogidiagba, 2022; Tukur and Aguiyi, 2022). Regarding unemployment, Nigeria has experienced a consistent rise in unemployment rates throughout the country. This has been attributed to the loss of existing employment and an increase in the labour force, primarily from higher education institutions. These figures differ by state and are affected by the predominant economic activity and seasons within each region (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Figure 14 depicts the Nigerian labour market statistics.

Figure 14 Labour Market Statistics

Labour Market Statistics:							
Year /Quarter	Employed ('000)	Time-related underemployed ('000)	Fully Employed ('000)	Unemployed ('000)	Not in Labour Force ('000)	Labour Force Population ('000)	Working Age Population ('000)
2015-Q1	67,903	12,209	55,694	5,534	29,388	73,436	102,824
2015-Q2	67,947	13,571	54,376	6,063	29,557	74,011	103,568
2015-Q3	68,422	13,206	55,217	7,518	28,374	75,940	104,314
2015-Q4	68,922	14,416	54,506	8,036	28,065	76,958	105,023
2016-Q1	69,001	15,023	53,978	9,485	27,515	78,487	106,001
2016-Q2	67,991	10,644	57,347	11,895	26,804	79,886	106,690
2016-Q3	68,772	11,198	57,574	11,897	27,364	80,669	108,033
2016-Q4	69,472	11,549	57,923	11,680	27,440	81,152	108,592
2017-Q1	70,666	16,837	53,829	11,926	26,847	82,592	109,439
2017-Q2	70,355	17,679	52,676	13,585	26,346	83,940	110,287
2017-Q3	69,090	18,029	51,061	15,998	26,046	85,088	111,134
2017-Q4	68,866	17,701	51,166	17,671	25,581	86,538	112,119
2018-Q1	68,955	17,801	51,154	19,251	24,962	88,207	113,169
2018-Q2	69,166	17,992	51,174	20,344	24,802	89,509	114,311
2018-Q3	69,543	18,216	51,327	20,928	25,022	90,471	115,493
2020-Q2	58,527	22,942	35,585	21,765	32,097	80,292	116,871
2020-Q4	46,488	15,915	30,572	23,187	52,373	69,675	122,049

Source : National Bureau of Statistics (2023)

As at the fourth quarter of 2020, the population of working age (15-64) was 122,049. This was an increase from the 116,871 recorded in the second quarter of 2020. It is estimated that there are 69,675,468 people aged 15 to 64 who are able and willing to work, with an average of 52,373,932 not in the labour force and 23,187,389 unemployed showing a steady increase in the challenging labour market of an increasing population (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023).

Nigeria has experienced a constant rise in unemployment rates. The rate increased to 33.3% from 27.1% Q2 2020 and 23.1% in Q3 2018. Clearly, job creation initiatives have not yet kept pace with the constant growth of the labour force. The quarter by quarter increase in unemployment from 2014 to 2020 is depicted in Figure 15 below.

Figure 15 Unemployment statistics

Source : National Bureau of Statistics (2023)

According to the World Bank (2023), 30.9% of Nigerians were living below the international poverty level of \$2.15 a day before the Covid crisis. With suggestions that the recent pandemic amplified this risk, and the country remains spatially unequal. According to the United Nations report on Human Development (2020),

Nigeria ranks 161 out of 189 countries. This was a drop from its ranking of 152nd in 2014. Despite the abundance of natural resources in the country, the structure and nature of Nigeria suggest that the country is endowed with both natural and human resources; however, effective management and, by extension, effective leadership is required to unlock these immense potentials. The next section elaborates on the structure and role of the oil industry.

4.3 Oil Sector

Oil is a global energy source and a vital commodity for international trade. The oil industry is Nigeria's most prominent industry and its largest export (Obioma, 2012; Odeyemi, 2014; Uduji, Okolo-Obasi and Asongu, 2019). 1956 saw the discovery of commercial quantities of oil and the commodity became the primary revenue generator in the country (Omotuyi, 2023). According to Odeyemi (2014). The commodity accounts for over 90 percent of foreign exchange revenues and over 85 percent of overall government revenue. Before oil discovery, Nigeria's economy was predominantly dependent on agriculture. As a result, the oil industry's overwhelming influence has had adverse effects on other industries, particularly in the agricultural sector, which became apparent as early as the 1970s (Nweze and Edame, 2016; Matemilola, 2017).

The emergence of the oil in Nigeria dates to the early 1900s, when the Nigerian Bitumen Corporation conducted its first exploratory activity. However, this quest was hampered by a lack of financial resources, technological expertise, and the outbreak of World War I in 1914 (Ite *et al.*, 2013). Shell D'Arcy, which later became Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria, was then granted exclusive concessionary rights in 1937 (Dionague and Renouard, 2012; Odeyemi, 2014). In 1956, commercial quantities of oil was discovered in Oloibiri, Niger Delta and in 1958, the amount of oil exported from the Oloibiri field began at 5,100 barrels per day and doubled in 1959 (Udosen, Etok and George, 2009; Ntukekpo, 2012).

The initial exclusive concessionary rights granted to Shell was extended to other industry participants. These multinational corporations were Mobil, Agip, Société Africaine des Pétroles (Safrap) and Tennessee Nigeria Limited (Tenneco) in 1962, and Philips Oil Company in 1964 (Ite *et al.*, 2013; Denny and Jacob, 2022).

In the 1960s, the oil industry began to reshape Nigeria's economy (Ite *et al.*, 2013) and the Nigerian government established regulatory agencies. The Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) was founded in 1970 with the purpose of regulating the sector. In addition, the Nigerian National Oil Corporation (NNOC) was established in 1971 and subsequently rebranded as the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) in 1977. In 1972 the increased exploration efforts of other companies, led to Nigeria being recognised as a significant oil producer and ranked among the top 10 oil producing nations in the world.

Nigeria has three publicly owned refineries in Warri, Port Harcourt, and Kaduna. Warri has a refining capacity of 100,000 barrels of oil, and was built in 1978; Port Harcourt has a refining capacity of 60,000 barrels; the first part was built in 1963 and the second in 1989; and Kaduna has a refining capacity of 100,000 barrels, built in 1980 (Odeyemi, 2014). Other private refineries have been built, with the Dangote group's refinery being the most prominent (Acheampong, Ackah and Karimu, 2023; Afful-Dadzie, Awudu and Owusu, 2023).

The Federal Government, foreign oil companies, and indigenous companies are the three main stakeholders within this sector (Hassan and Farouk, 2014). However, the presence of environmental risks, socioeconomic difficulties, and a lack of effective leadership at both the national and organisational levels have contributed to the plethora of difficulties confronting this industry. Corruption permeates the Nigerian social, political, environmental, and commercial environments, including the oil industry (Hand, 2021; Aluko, 2021). Oil revenues were syphoned off, leading to their depletion. This resulted in demonstrations and uprisings against the government and oil companies. These tumultuous responses and resentment emerged from the

negative outcomes associated with oil exploration. Even though, the thesis examines leadership within organisations, a summary of the problems that have plagued the sector is presented below.

4.3.1 Challenges within the Oil Sector of Nigeria

Challenges within the sector are often characterised as a paradox, where a country experiences scarcity despite its abundant natural resources, as is the case of Nigeria. This is often attributed to poor governance (Ite *et al.*, 2013; Okoi, 2019) and is crucial because a sustainable society promotes economic and social growth. Since the 1970s, the oil industry has become increasingly concerned with the environmental risks associated with oil exploration, production, and transportation (Kadafa, 2012; Odeyemi, 2014). These broad challenges include pollution, which has affected agriculture, aquaculture, the atmosphere as a result of gas flaring, water supply, and the rise in medical conditions (Ite *et al.*, 2013; Gozie Ogbodo and Umadia, 2023). With suggestions that, multinational oil companies did not adopt sustainable practises in their operations over the past 50 years due to costs concerns. Past and present activities such as gas flaring, oil spills, refuse disposal, and contamination continue to impact the environment with Ite *et al.* (2013) suggesting that the loss to the nation is colossal because the nation relies heavily on the commodity for most of its earnings.

The first main oil spill occurred in July 1970. The Bomu-11 oil well operated by Shell experienced a blowout, resulting in the contamination of around 607 hectares of land (Odeyemi, 2014). A similar blowout from Funiwa Oil occurred in 1980, which impacted the water supply. From 1976 to 1980, there were 784 reported incidents (Awobajo, 1981). Many of these environmental hazards have been attributed to multinationals disregarding best practices in managing the environmental degradation in areas of operations (Ite *et al.*, 2013; Okwelum, 2022). With several of these companies refusing to comply with standard regulations, bribing their way through regulatory and monitoring agencies within the country. Environmental hazards and health issues prevalent in oil producing regions are closely connected

with exposure to toxic substances resulting in acute health issues such as respiratory diseases, cancers and tumours, and blood disorders (Freitag and Stokes, 2009; Nriagu, 2011).

In spite of its abundant natural resources, the Niger Delta region, where the majority of oil is extracted, is plagued by violence and destitution (Bribena, 2019). The forced displacement of numerous indigenous communities from farming, fishing, and other livelihoods may also play a role in contributing to the poverty apparent in the region (Nriagu, 2011). This poverty is evident from the absence of essential infrastructure, like power, clean water, educational institutions, and sufficient healthcare facilities. Similarly, crude oil theft and bunkering have also been persistent challenges within the industry (Adishi and Hunga, 2017; Olujobi, Olarinde and Yebisi, 2022).

Ineffective leadership is a major issue in the industry. As the lack of development in the region is a result of poor leadership (Osah, Ogundiwin and Eti, 2017; Nwokolo and Aghedo, 2018). This leadership deficit is evident from the pervasive corruption in the sector and the actions of the sector's officials (Hope, 2017; Nwogbo and Ighodalo, 2021). As an example, one of the former governors, James Ibori, was imprisoned for money laundering and other allegations, demonstrating the necessity of this study on leadership. Specifically, the study focuses on authentic leadership in this industry. As this leadership approach has been found to increase employees' work engagement and organisational citizenship behaviour in the UAE petroleum sector (Ahmad *et al.*, 2016; Cavazotte, Mansur and Moreno, 2021).

4.4 Conceptual Framework

In the context of organisational changes driven by broader global events, a thorough investigation of authentic leadership has become crucial (Wiewiora and Kowalkiewicz, 2019; Daraba *et al.*, 2021). With the evident demand for authentic leaders in organisations and society. Therefore, advancing the field and its contextual application is grounded on thoroughly understanding the peculiarities of this

leadership approach (Laguna *et al.*, 2019; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020). As society continue to evolve, grasping the intricacies of authentic leadership will enable its effective implementation in diverse contexts. Also, by exploring its core, scholars will foster a deeper appreciation of authentic leadership's significance and its potential to address challenges.

The conceptual framework has five interrelated variables: antecedents, components of authentic leadership, challenges of authentic leadership, followers' perspective, and organisational outcomes. This is captured in Figure 16 below:

Figure 16 Conceptual Framework

The prominent definition, put out by Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) highlights four components that have been researched extensively by scholars over the years. These four components are self awareness, internalised moral perspective, relational

transparency, and balanced processing. These scholars draw on Kernis (2003) description of authenticity, captured in the article on optimal self-esteem. The author proceeded to delineate four dimensions of authenticity, namely, awareness, unbiased processing, action, and relational respectively. These components were integrated into authentic leadership and refined further to reflect the main debates within the domain. However, there is a paucity of research on components of authentic leadership beyond the initial four components (Hoch *et al.*, 2018; Wernsing, 2018) proposed by Walumbwa *et al.* (2008). Therefore, it is crucial for future research to investigate these fundamental components of authentic leadership beyond the current conceptualisations.

Authentic leadership components are at the core of the conceptual model, with one variable: antecedents of authentic leadership, influencing it and the component variable directly influencing the other three variables. The three variables: the challenges of authentic leaders, perceptions of followers and organisational outcomes are all linked to the components of authentic leadership where uncovering other components will be critical to the advancement of theory and practice.

Studies on authentic leadership literature have mostly focused on analysing the influence of authentic leadership on organisational outcomes, which have mainly been positive. Most of these studies have focused on quantitative analysis, as seen in Gardner *et al.*'s (2011) evaluation of 91 papers on authentic leadership. This review included a total of 25 empirical articles, consisting of 16 quantitative research and nine qualitative investigations. The consequence of this approach by scholars has led to a vacuum in authentic leadership literature with several questions remaining unanswered. Thus, a need for more qualitative studies that will extend the current understanding of the construct.

The influence of authentic leadership on many organisational outcomes, such as employee involvement, job contentment, and organisational effectiveness, is an essential component of the framework. Therefore, scholars have established a clear

connection between the components of authentic leadership exhibited by authentic leaders and favourable results within the organisation. This correlation is not unexpected, considering the arguments that the construct emerged in response to ethical misconduct in the corporate business environment (Johnsen, 2018). Research has also established the link between authentic leadership and positive results for leaders, followers, and organisations (Caza and Jackson, 2011).

Studies have also shown that authentic leadership is associated with followers', organisational and group level outcomes (Eigel and Kuhnert, 2005; Peus *et al.*, 2012). Many studies have examined the positive effects of authentic leadership on followers' that lead to favourable results, while neglecting the importance of followers' perception in authentic leadership development. These studies have focused on investigating how influencing followers' perceptions can achieve organisational goals or improve leadership (Kurian and Nafukho, 2021). Therefore, Banks *et al.* (2016) argue that when employees perceive their supervisors or leaders as authentic, it also offers benefits to the leaders themselves. Thus, this study would prove valuable for practitioners, scholars, and policymakers, as it aims to uncover the authentic leadership process within a developing economy context.

Across the variables in the conceptual framework, authentic leadership challenges have received the least attention from scholars as the focus has primarily been on the organisational complexity that these leaders encounter within their organisations. This is hardly surprising, considering that the construct emerged to address leadership challenges. Therefore, a key area within the field that is crucial for the advancement of the authentic leadership theory. With the expectation that grasping the complexities associated with authentic leadership will result in the identification of relevant interventions that can be evaluated across contexts.

Finally, scholars have attempted to identify the antecedents of leadership by engaging in critical debates on the key factors that inspire authentic leadership development. Studies have emphasised the significance of trigger events and crucibles in literature,

with some other scholars highlighting the importance of life stories in facilitating the development of authentic leadership. Although the literature offers broad discussions on trigger events and crucibles, additional research is necessary to thoroughly examine the factors that inspire authentic leadership development. Figure 16 illustrates the relationships between authentic leadership components, antecedents, challenges, perceptions of followers and organisational outcomes.

4.5 Conclusion

The fourth chapter of the thesis concludes with an analysis of context, focusing on developing economies and Nigeria in particular. The chapter was divided into four sections, with each section addressing an important aspect of the context of study. The first section began with a discussion on the classification of economies, which served as a foundation for unpacking the characteristics and dynamics of developing economies. By focusing on developing economies, the distinct challenges and opportunities these nations encounter on their path to growth and development were highlighted.

The second section presented an extended discussion on Nigeria, a prominent example of a developing economy. This analysis included several facets, such as Nigeria's geography, political climate, economic structure, and social factors. This section brings to the fore the country specific nuances and offered valuable insights into the larger dynamics of developing economies. The third section focussed on the oil industry, which plays an important role in Nigeria's economy. It highlighted the challenges within the industry. Identifying these difficulties are essential for understanding the operating environment of Nigeria's economy and the potential impact of the study.

The chapter concluded with a discussion of the conceptual framework, which synthesised the findings from the literature review chapters within the study. This

framework serves as a vital link between the literature review and the subsequent chapter, which explores the research methodology of the thesis.

CHAPTER 5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

INTRODUCTION

The preceding chapters introduced the study's context and rationale for the investigation. The first chapter outlines the overall purpose and research concerns. The second chapter evaluates existing leadership literature. Specifically, it examines leadership, leadership development and authenticity, which provide the foundation for unpacking the authentic leadership construct. Collectively, these chapters expose the underlying theories that influence the diverse but complementary conceptualisations of authentic leadership. Chapter three presents the results of a systematic literature review on authentic leadership while the context is evaluated in chapter four. To recap, the research questions as detailed in section 1.5 are outlined as follows:

RQ1. What are the components of authentic leadership?

RQ2. What are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development?

RQ3. What are the challenges that authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy?

RQ4. What are the specific actions that shape employee perceptions of authentic leaders?

This chapter deconstructs the investigative process, providing a detailed explanation of how the unknown is uncovered. It explains the assumptions, philosophy, strategy, method, and techniques used to reveal the unknown aspects of authentic leadership. The chapter explains the process of how meaning is constructed from the rich qualitative data to provide well grounded descriptions of authentic leadership. Therefore, uncovering unanticipated discoveries and connections leading to a broader understanding of AL. As a result, the chapter provides an overview of the assumptions that shape the research.

A research's methodology defines the science and philosophy that inform its design. The methodology captures perspectives on the nature of knowledge, revealing the various ways in which it is created (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022), thereby allowing scholars to recognise the limitations of the various perspectives (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Given that each study requires adapting methods and techniques to attain research objectives, a qualitative research method was adopted within the study, as the researcher sought to capture meaning and not merely sequences (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). Extending beyond snapshots of a specific time to sustained periods of investigations. This study utilised semi-structured interviews as a means of data collection, allowing for the acquisition of rich and vivid accounts of the local actors' lived experiences (Morse, 2015). This was apposite because qualitative research facilitates the exploration of phenomena within specific contexts (Cypress, 2017). Furthermore, qualitative investigations offer a clear description of the research methodologies and approaches employed in the investigative process.

Expanding on this perspective, the chapter commences by providing a summary of the methodological choices that influenced the study. Section 5.1 provides a discussion on the philosophical positioning, its implications for the research, and the rationale for selecting interpretivism for the study. Section 5.2 describes the research approach, while section 5.3 elaborates on the research method. In section 5.4, the research strategy is presented, and in section 5.5, the research design is discussed. The methods for collecting and analysing data are explained in Sections 5.6 and 5.7, where the choice of strategies that aid in data gathering, organising, and interpretation are presented. Building on Miles, Huberman and Saldaña (2018) recommendation for attaining rigour, plausibility, and confirmability, "intersubjective consensus" was attained among peers when drawing conclusions from the study. The chapter concludes with a brief discussion on the ethical boundaries observed during the research, along with an

analysis of the criteria used to assess the research's quality. A schematic view of the chapter is captured in Figure 17 below.

Figure 17 Overview of Methodological Choices

5.1 Research Philosophy

The phrase ‘research philosophy’ describes the nature of knowledge and how it is constructed (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). Gray (2020) refers to this phrase as theoretical viewpoints. However, the term philosophy will be consistently employed

in this section and the broader study. Philosophies, in general, describe the fundamental beliefs that shape a researcher's worldview and guide the decisions made in a study (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2018). This is important because researchers must be mindful of these assumptions, which are reflected in the researchers' philosophical choices as demonstrated within the study. Transcending from demonstrating philosophical awareness within this study, the key focus was to ensure that deep reflections were undertaken about the array of philosophical choices. These reflections informed the philosophical stance of the study (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Gray, 2022). Further along these lines, Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2018) argue that there are four main benefits that accrue to researchers who consider philosophical nuances.

Firstly, the researcher will understand their reflexive function and what can be known about the subject. This is crucial because it explicates the role of reflexivity in knowledge creation and how researchers can actively participate in the process. Secondly, a firm grasp of these philosophical nuances shapes the research design by facilitating the selection of appropriate techniques, from data collection to analysis. Thirdly, it enables researchers implement designs and methods that are appropriate for their research. As a result achieving a fundamental objective of the research design, which is facilitating the collection of data that adequately address the research questions (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Lastly, it assists researchers in the investigation and implementation of unfamiliar research designs, enabling adaptation of research designs as necessary.

Therefore, to justify the rationale behind the selection of the study's philosophical foundations, it is important to discuss the assumptions that influence existing philosophies. This explanation illustrates the researcher's knowledge of research philosophies, and this is crucial because philosophies offer perspectives based on predetermined assumptions.

Ontology and epistemology are the most frequently debated topics among philosophers. An ontology represents the basic assumptions of the researcher (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2018) and for ontological concerns, the researcher needs to address queries such as the form and nature of reality. What type of beings exist, furthermore what is there and what can be known about it (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2011). The focus of ontology is the essence of reality and perception of how the world operates (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023).

Two key ontological positions have emerged: objectivism and subjectivism (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). While scholars often capture terms, concepts and ideas in several ways, evident in the description of ontological positioning. For example, Bryman (2016) described two ontological positions, objectivism and constructionism. This study adopts Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) categorisation and descriptions. The proponents of objectivism believe that reality is concrete, external and is driven by undisputable natural laws and systems. It contends that social phenomena occur outside the influence of social actors. In contrast, the proponents of subjectivism argue that people create and shape reality (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, social phenomena emerge from the perceptions and actions of individuals who are concerned about their own existence. This study is consistent with the latter ontological stance, as it investigates authentic leadership.

Epistemology borders on the theory of knowledge, and there has been an ongoing epistemological debate regarding what constitutes knowledge and how it can be known (Patton, 2014). Thus, an understanding of the epistemological foundations enable researchers discern and choose the most appropriate techniques for investigating a phenomenon (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2018). Epistemology provides a framework for evaluating the various forms of knowledge, directing researchers in defining knowledge as true or false (credible and valid). For epistemological positioning, researchers must consider questions such as what are the most

appropriate methods for investigating the nature of the world (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022).

Throughout the rich tapestry of philosophical history, several epistemological positions have emerged, offering frameworks to facilitate the understanding of how knowledge is acquired. Accordingly, Denzin and Lincoln (2011) draw attention to two dichotomies within human inquiry. Firstly, the debates concerning whether human and social sciences should be seen through individualistic or social lenses (p. 575). Secondly, the dichotomy between objective, signifying an external perspective, and subjective, signifying an internal lens. These scholars, however, argue that these positions are not mutually exclusive but intricately interconnected, especially in practical applications. James and Busher (2009) identify three epistemological positions: Objectivism, Subjectivism, and Constructivism. In objectivism, the argument is that reality exists independently of consciousness, detached from reasoning. Conversely, constructivism argues, that meaning is not inherent but rather crafted by individuals. Subjectivism takes a more radical departure from objectivism. It posits that meaning does not emerge from the interaction between the object and the subject but is entirely imposed on the object by the subject. In this view, reality becomes deeply entwined with the subject's perspective and interpretation.

Similarly, Schwandt (2000) identifies hermeneutics, social constructivism and interpretivism as epistemological positions linked to qualitative inquiry. For hermeneutics, the epistemological stance expounds on the conditions under which understanding occurs. In social constructivism, knowledge is not discovered but rather created against the backdrop of shared understandings. Advocates of interpretivism assert that it seeks to unravel human actions by focusing on extracting meanings that underpin actions, as human actions are understood in that manner, ultimately achieving interpretive understanding (*verstehen*) (p. 191). The study draws on Schwandt (2000) descriptions and adopts the interpretivist epistemological stance.

Similar to the considerations regarding ontology and epistemology, there are axiological (ethical) assumptions that examine the role of values in research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). These values are demonstrated throughout the research process and become apparent when deciding what and how to investigate the subject. It is recommended that researchers examine their values consciously within their research, as this influences their perspective on ethical issues.

In general, the ontological, epistemological, and axiological assumptions serve as the basis upon which methodological decisions are made and debates on methods and techniques are considered (Burrell and Morgan, 2017). Several philosophies have emerged within the research domain. For example, positivism, realism, pragmatism, and interpretivism (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Bryman, 2016; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). However, the two prominent philosophies are Positivism and Interpretivism, which are seen as opposites on a spectrum of epistemological perspectives. Positivism dominated the period from the 1930s to the 1960s and continues to be employed in current research (Gray, 2020).

Positivism coined by French philosopher Auguste Comte (1798-1857), refers to a scientific approach that bases knowledge on what can be observed as opposed to beliefs (Babbie, 2020). It is shaped by principles, although the exact number varies across scholars. Accordingly, Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2014) argue that , positivism is governed by three principles: (1) “the recognition that the social world exists externally and is observed objectively, (2) the belief that research should be free from personal values and biases, and (3) the understanding that the researcher should maintain independence and adopt the position of an objective analyst. For positivists, knowledge is advanced through the observation of phenomena, with results analogous to law like generalisations.

This perspective has consequences for the correlation between theory and observations. Fundamentally affecting the manner in which inquiries are conducted (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). The researcher assumes that visible facts are

objective because they are external and can be reduced to observable or simple elements, thereby focusing on a single plausible explanation for the research phenomenon (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014). As it is argued that observable phenomena produce credible data (Gill and Johnson, 2002). Positivist proponents argue that studies that adopt this philosophical stance employ highly structured methodology to support the replication of findings.

Interpretivism, on the other hand, is an approach to the development of knowledge based on the principle that “objective observation of the social world is impossible (Blumberg et al., 2014, p. 17).” According to Bryman (2016) this epistemological position “captures the arguments of scholars who are critical of the application of the scientific model to the study of the social world and are influenced by various intellectual traditions (p. 26).” In a similar vein, Gray (2020) describes this viewpoint as anti positivist. Proponents of this epistemological stance contend that social sciences focus on people and their institutions, which is in stark contrast to positivists in the natural sciences (Bryman, 2016; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Therefore, distinct logic and methods are required for the study of human beings and behaviour.

For the interpretivist, knowledge is gained from observing a phenomenon; while meaning and interpretation are socially constructed (Ryan, 2018; Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020). In this way, interpretivist proponents contend that meaning is socially derived and is used as a lens to interpret the social roles of actors. These scholars argue that researchers must fully engage in the social environment of their research participants to understand their perspectives. Hence, the interpretivist perspective is well suited for business and management research due to the complexity and uniqueness of these contexts (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022).

Due to the nature of the investigation, an interpretivist stance was adopted in this study. In accordance with the arguments on interpretivism and the position that knowledge emerges from social interactions, i.e., reality is socially constructed, the

study explores how authentic leadership is interpreted in the context of a developing economy and situates these interpretations within a social scientific framework. Therefore, the overall philosophical position of this study is a subjectivist/interpretivist stance.

5.2 Research Approach

The purpose of science is to increase existing knowledge and uncover the truth, which can be accomplished through the development and refinement of theory. With arguments concerning the positioning of theory in the research process. On one hand, there are arguments for theory as the starting point for research, although another school of thought holds that theory should be the result of the research process (Gray, 2020). The term “theory” as defined by Babbie (1998, p. 52), “is a systematic explanation for the observations that relate to a particular aspect of life.” It is also described as “a set of systematically interrelated concepts, definitions and propositions that are advanced to explain and predict phenomena (Adams et al. 2014, p. 8).” Similarly, it is described as a “formalised set of concepts” that systematise explanations and conclusions that explicate a phenomena of study (Graziano and Raulin, 1996).

These definitions and descriptions suggest that theories arise from research studies and serve as a framework to capture knowledge in a structured manner (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). In order to expand this framework, it is necessary to acquire valid evidence from the social world in order to enhance current understanding (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023).

The positioning of theory within research is closely related to the two distinct approaches to reasoning, namely inductive and deductive reasoning. Gray (2020) quotes Dewey (1933) as stating that deduction alludes to proof while induction alludes to discovery. The former conclusion follows from a general description of phenomena

to a specific assertion. It describes the logical process of arriving at a deduction or premise based on knowledge of something accepted as true (Gill and Johnson, 2002; Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). The deductive method proceeds from the general to the specific. The researcher investigates what is known about a topic in order to formulate a hypothesis that may be tested through empirical investigation (Bryman, 2016).

In contrast, theory development may also emerge from inductive reasoning, which describes a logical manner of developing broad propositions grounded in observing specific facts (Gill and Johnson, 2002; Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). It clarifies a particular phenomenon within specific circumstances that existing theory does not adequately describe. In inductive research, theory development is an outcome of the research process as it links data to theory. Based on its logic to theory development, it is appropriate for small sample sizes in contrast to the deductive approach, which requires large sample sizes to validate the study's findings.

Generally, these approaches to reasoning direct the researcher towards probable strategies that would be suitable for a study. Accordingly, Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2018) suggest that a researcher's understanding of reasoning approaches has three positive outcomes. Firstly, it influences the research design, which extends beyond collecting and processing of data to include the overall alignment of the study to address the research objectives. Secondly, it allows the researcher to evaluate the appropriateness and effectiveness of strategies, thereby facilitating the selection of techniques that are appropriate for the research. Finally, it permits the modification of the research design in response to challenges that may emerge in the enquiry process. Although, inductive and deductive reasoning approaches differ in perspective and implementation, both are used for theory advancement (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Table 10 below compares the two ways of reasoning, providing clarity on the specific areas of emphasis for each approach.

Table 10 Differences between deductive and inductive approaches

	Deductive	Inductive
Data type	A predominant use of quantitative data	The use of multiple qualitative methods to obtain diverse views of the research phenomena
Researcher role	The researcher functions as an external entity in relation to the phenomena being researched	The researcher is an integral component of the research process
Theory development	Theory is advanced through rigorous testing of proposition of the hypothesis; it moves from theory to data	The findings from research contribute to theory development; theory emerges from data
Process	The process is general to specific	The process is specific to general
Structure	Highly structured approach that facilitates the application of controls to ensure reliability and facilitate replication	Adoption of a flexible structure that allows multiple explanations and adaption to changes as the research progresses
Focus of enquiry	Seeks to explain causal relationships between variables	Seeks to understand the research context and how the local actors interpret the social world
Sample size	Selecting samples of sufficient size is necessary to generalise statistically	Context is crucial, providing a justification for small samples

Adapted from Gill and Johnson (2002), Easterby-Smith et al. (2018), Saunders et al. (2019)

These two approaches are essential for the development of theories (Hyde, 2000; Bryman, 2016; Babbie, 2020). Scholars, however, assert that both are flawed and have inherent application limitations that must be evaluated in relation to the research objectives (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). For instance, deductive research may be completed faster because data collection is typically conducted in "one take" based on the researcher's prior planning. Emerging from this approach to data collection in deductive research, the lack of response from some research participants entails a lower risk than in inductive research, where this risk is exacerbated by the constant fear that useful findings may not emerge from the collected data. Traditionally, scholars state that these two reasoning approaches are dissimilar and flawed; however, the flaws do not indicate a chaotic approach; rather, the emphasis is on flexibility and application. It has been proposed that both approaches be employed

in conducting research (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

Similarly, Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2014) suggest that both inductive and deductive reasoning may be used sequentially; John Dewey referred to this practise as “double movement of reflective thought” . For induction, the focus is on WHY and WHEN a phenomenon is observed, thus a plausible explanation (Hypothesis) is proposed, whereas deduction focuses on proving or disproving the proposed explanation (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Nonetheless, these two approaches are largely complementary, and researchers frequently transition between them (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014). Interestingly, Yin (2015) asserts that inductive reasoning leads to the development of new concepts, whereas deductive reasoning leads to the refinement of theory. Qualitative research has been linked to the inductive technique, while quantitative research has been associated with the deductive approach (Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2011; Gray, 2020; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022).

A third reasoning approach, labelled "Abductive reasoning" by American philosopher Charles Sanders Peirce (Patton, 2014) and adopted by qualitative researchers (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022) has emerged. This approach to reasoning provides a distinct alternative to traditional inductive and deductive research approaches (Patton, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). Abduction is a theory based approach to conducting research; it begins with a dilemma and then seeks an explanation (Mantere and Ketokivi, 2013). The logic is based on both inductive and deductive reasoning, but data is used to develop theory. According to Saunders et al. (2019), abduction is a type of induction that does not investigate any overarching theory. However, the data provide insights into the probable theoretical framework or theories. It involves developing justifications from data to attain plausible conclusions (Shepherd and Suddaby, 2017).

This is an iterative engagement process from theory and empirical data in which the researcher attempts to discover the best interpretations for the social investigation (Mantere and Ketokivi, 2013; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). The approach to reasoning develops theory based on the experiences and meanings of social actors as revealed in their accounts and descriptions (Blaikie, 2007). This is suitable for the study because it accounts for meanings and interpretations that deductive and inductive reasoning may overlook. Focusing on how social actors perceive and experience authentic leadership from the inside out. The researchers' objective is to gather these deep perspectives without imposing an outsider's viewpoint. The approach also enables researchers gain access to implicit knowledge that is largely unarticulated but crucial as it influences the daily lives and interactions of social actors.

Authentic leadership is a relatively new area of study in the field of leadership; hence little is known about it beyond Western perspectives. This study explored the authentic leadership construct in the context of a developing economy. It pursues the best interpretations and explanations for research questions, on the components of authentic leadership and factors that inspire its development. The study adopts the abductive reasoning, as the research problem should define the approach that will best serve it. Hence, techniques that facilitate respondents' reflections become pertinent to discovering meaning.

5.3 Research Method

Research methods describe the technique of executing research, which is rooted in the broader philosophies of science (Bryman, 2016; Gray, 2020; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Accordingly, Guba and Lincoln (1994) argue that scholars adopt research methods that align with the predetermined methodology. It is also critical for the researchers to select the appropriate method that suit the study's objectives (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Drawing from the

debates within literature, different schools of thought have emerged with different viewpoints on what constitutes good research (Patton, 2014). With ensuing arguments that reveal the value laden prejudices of one research method over the other.

In broad terms, there are two methods: quantitative and qualitative methods. These methods are set apart mainly by the form of information utilised to examine a phenomenon (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014). Galileo's admonition guides the advocates of the quantitative method, "Measure what is measurable, and make measurable what is not so". At the same time, qualitative researchers uphold Edwards Deming argument that "the most important thing cannot be measured". These two quotes above are captured in Patton (2014). It then becomes crucial to demonstrate an awareness of the different methods and provide a justification for the research method adopted within the study.

Quantitative scholars infer, that it employs numerical information such as numbers, figures, and measures, concentrating on the amount or the scale of a particular phenomenon (Gray, 2020; Babbie, 2020). The method is based on the methodological philosophies of positivism and neo positivism and adheres to a rigorous plan established prior to the investigation (Creswell and Creswell, 2017; Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2018). This research method adheres to a rigid, predetermined plan with predetermined methods (Cypress, 2017) with an objective to validate theory through rigorous hypothesis testing (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The quantitative method has been utilised in numerous disciplines, including clinical, epidemiological, and business studies (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014) and typically uses analysis to evaluate the validity of constructs.

In contrast, qualitative methods rely on narratives (non-numeric data) focusing on a phenomenon's meaning, nature, form or character (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). It adopts non quantitative measures neither in data collection nor analysis, even though the distinctiveness of this method extends beyond the absence of numbers (Bryman, 2016). This method seeks to probe

social interactions and define reality from the perspective of research participants (Creswell and Creswell, 2017; Gray, 2022). Accordingly, Gray (2020) describes the method as highly variable with Flick (2022) acknowledging that the method does not adopt a unified methodological strategy. This is essential to note as, over its history; it has comprised several of traditions and stages (Bryman, 2016). The contributions of the Chicago school to sociology in the 1920s and 1930s established the utility of qualitative research in the study of human entities. Parallel to the adoption of the qualitative method, anthropology researchers conducted a ground breaking study (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). This study established the framework for fieldwork, leading to its widespread adoption in the social sciences.

These scholars identify five key defining moments in its history (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Firstly, the traditional period from 1900-1950 considered the works of the Chicago school and social anthropologists. It began in early 1900 until World War 2 (WW2). Qualitative researchers concentrated on unbiased descriptions of their field experiences that aligned with the positivist scientist paradigm. Secondly, the modernist or golden age from 1950-1970 is linked to post positivists arguments. In the period, rigour was at the core of the reflections of qualitative researchers. Thirdly, the blurred genres from 1970-1986 was a period of exploration of several ontological and epistemological positioning for qualitative studies. There was still a leaning towards positivism with early stages of interpretivist awareness. Fourthly, the crisis representation period from 1986- 1990, where researchers sought to locate themselves. Finally, the postmodern period from 1990, where the emergence of diverse techniques of representing research participants became prevalent (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011).

The qualitative method is widely used in the social sciences to effectively capture the lived experiences of individuals, particularly in terms of the meanings attributed to events and experiences (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Hammarberg, Kirkman and de Lacey, 2016). In summary, Denzin and Lincoln (2011) assert that reality is a construct. Their arguments also highlight the value of characterising the

qualitative method by emphasising its distinctions from the quantitative approach. Table 11 below provides a comparison of the two methods highlighting the peculiarities of each method.

Table 11 Differences between quantitative and qualitative methods

Quantitative Method	Qualitative Method
Outlook of the researcher	Outlook of participants
Value free	Value laden
Hard reliable data: Statistics, equations, charts and formulae	Rich deep data: Narratives, stories and case Studies
Empirical generalisations across time and space	In depth wholistic contextually sensitive understanding of the phenomena
Focus on refinement of theory by testing hypothesis	Focus on the generation of theories
Underpinned by deductive logic	Underpinned by inductive or abductive logic
Social reality is external	Social reality is emergent and consistently shifting
Objectivist ontology	Subjectivist ontology
Structured	Unstructured

Adapted from (Bryman, 2016; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Gray, 2020)

Typically, qualitative methods are used to investigate a new phenomenon, followed by quantitative methods to test the validity of hypotheses formulated in previous qualitative studies. Alternatively, the sequence can be reversed as well. Nonetheless, some researchers incorporate quantitative and qualitative approaches in their research, suggesting that a variety of research problems can be examined using both approaches. This choice is predominantly influenced by the researcher's research philosophy, which is primarily an epistemological stance. For instance, positivism suggests that knowledge acquisition is grounded in deductive hypothesis testing, measuring and validating reality (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In comparison, interpretivism suggests that knowledge acquisition is grounded in deep level scrutiny of the phenomenon. Therefore, the quantitative method characteristically pervades the positivists research, while the qualitative method permeates interpretivism studies (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023).

Historically, researchers have utilised either quantitative or qualitative methodologies to advance knowledge in various domains. There are differences between these two methods, as evidenced within extant literature (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2019; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2018; Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2018). Thus, Denzin and Lincoln (2011) contend that it is important to embrace each research method for its unique ability to address specific research problems. Furthermore, Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2014) imply that the significance or suitability of one method over another cannot be answered unequivocally amidst ongoing debates. Their arguments state that neither method is superior to the other nor has a claim to superior knowledge, as both methods share the same values and commitments to a systematic inquiry by ensuring the adoption of appropriate approaches, tools, and techniques throughout the research process.

Hence, research problems can be examined employing either method. However, conclusions may defer in form as the research queries are grounded in the chosen perspective and the specificities of the research problem. Therefore, Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2014) argue that the choice of quantitative or qualitative approach should emerge from the responses to the underlisted queries around: the research problem, the type of study (explorative, descriptive, or predictive), the study objectives, anticipated outcomes, and lastly, the type of information to be acquired. Based on the recommendation above and the nature of the study, a qualitative method was adopted to uncover new dimensions of authentic leadership. This method facilitated the discovery and exposure to the respondents' emic (insider) individual points of view, capturing detailed descriptions during the enquiry process (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Hammarberg, Kirkman and de Lacey, 2016). The method was also chosen because it relies on fewer samples as, the goal was to gather detailed descriptions from research participants (Creswell and Creswell, 2017; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Furthermore, it led to discovery of unanticipated information and relationships (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014) giving the researcher richer insights and access to sensitive data.

Yin (2011) aligns with this view by identifying five characteristics of qualitative research; (1) it can be used to examine how people assign and interpret meaning as they occur in a specific context; (2) it proves valuable in illuminating the perspectives of respondents within a study; (3) It captures the contextual complexities of research participants; (4) it offers insights into evolving conceptions and reasons for social behaviour; and (5) it draws from several sources of evidence. In relation to the authentic leadership research undertaken within the study, the qualitative method was valuable as it uncovered otherwise hidden underlying processes between authentic leaders and their followers. This was crucial as the study sought to investigate meanings within the context of the study.

5.4 Research Strategy

The research strategy defines how a specific research endeavour will be carried out. It outlines the researcher's approach to addressing research questions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). There are several research strategies, each of which may be employed within a study (Babbie, 2020) as no strategy is inherently superior to the others. However, the most important factor to consider when choosing a research strategy is to assess whether it will allow the research questions to be addressed and research objectives to be attained (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Other factors that may influence the decision on a research strategy include the breadth of existing literature, philosophical perspective, time and resources (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Bryman, 2016; Babbie, 2020; Gray, 2020; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022).

The research strategy is the methodological link between an investigation's underlying philosophy and data collection techniques. Therefore, employing a suitable strategy is crucial for the successful completion of a research project. This is important because the research strategy is determined by the research queries. Consequently, the outcomes or findings of a study that employs an appropriate strategy will address the research questions and invariably advance knowledge.

When researchers transition from their philosophy to the empirical world, they employ a collection of assumptions, and practises known as strategies (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Therefore, the researcher must gain clarity about the investigation and consider the best approach for addressing the research problem. Research strategies in qualitative research are also known as strategies of enquiry or qualitative approaches to enquiry (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Several scholars have identified qualitative approaches but this study will discuss five approaches, as highlighted by Creswell and Poth (2018): narrative, phenomenological, grounded theory, ethnographic and case study research.

The narrative research strategy can take on numerous forms (Casey, Proudfoot and Corbally, 2016; Miller, 2017; Creswell and Poth, 2018). If it is utilised as strategy of enquiry, the focus is on individual lived experiences and accounts from prior events, but the context in which these experiences occurred is also considered. This strategy typically focuses on one or more individuals through the use of personal accounts of their experiences (Hamilton, Cruz and Jack, 2017; Gray, 2020). From these narratives, data is collected, and meaning is generated. A few challenges of this enquiry strategy include gathering broad data about the individuals and context, power relations and their impact on the inquiry process (Clandinin and Connelly, 2004).

The phenomenological strategy aims to deduce the shared meaning of a phenomenon from the lived experiences of multiple individuals. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), the focus is on condensing lived experiences of a phenomenon in order to provide "composite descriptions of the essence of the experience." The proponents of this strategy argue that human consciousness actively shapes the world and its perception (Gray, 2020).

The grounded theory strategy aims to generate theory. This new theory provides explanations for the topic of enquiry from the perspectives of multiple participants (Bryman, 2016; Creswell and Poth, 2018). The original proponents of this strategy later diverged on the strategy's meaning and implementation with Charmaz (2006)

introducing a new perspective referred to as "constructivist grounded theory" 39 years after its initial conception. Overall, the distinct feature of grounded theory includes theory development as a key outcome of a study.

The ethnographic research strategy initially associated with anthropology (Gray, 2020) requires an immersion in the context of the study to identify cultural patterns shared by a culture sharing group (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Typically, the strategy is supported by long term observation of a large group of people by researchers (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). There are various forms of ethnography, and it becomes a suitable strategy when investigating a closely connected cultural community. Its primary aim is to illuminate facets of this community that may not have been understood (Bryman, 2016; Creswell and Poth, 2018).

Finally, the case study strategy facilitates the development of multiple perspectives. The description of a case is complex due to its expansive nature, which allows it to encompass multiple categories of cases (Yin, 2011; Hancock, Algozzine and Lim, 2021). This research strategy investigates a real world case, which may involve an individual, a group, a process, or an event. The investigation begins with an in depth investigation of a case, typically a current one, in order to obtain the most recent information (Creswell and Poth, 2018).

All five of the research strategies discussed above aim to advance knowledge. Though, they share many of the same components, such as starting with a research problem, collecting data, analysing the data, and arriving at meaning, these approaches differ significantly in their nature and application (Gray, 2020; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Therefore, because this research aims to investigate the construct of authentic leadership, the five qualitative research strategies discussed earlier were evaluated in relation to the research problem, which led to the selection of the phenomenological strategy. The study's chosen strategy was influenced by the research questions, philosophical links, and accessibility to potential respondents. Hence, the phenomenological research strategy proved to be the most effective in addressing the

research questions as it enabled the researcher to capture authentic leaders' and followers' distinct lived experiences and meaning. The subsequent subsection, 5.4.1, provides a detailed description of the study's phenomenological strategy.

5.4.1 Phenomenology

Phenomenology seeks to reveal individual experiences, and it exhibits adaptability, giving rise to a multitude of distinctive methodologies (Peoples, 2020). As a philosophy, it focuses on two complementary concerns: how individuals interpret their experience and make meaning of what they encounter in the world, and how philosophers access that world by suspending their understandings (Bryman, 2016; Dane, 2018).

The philosophy holds that knowledge of social reality must be based on how people perceive it (Gray, 2020). The phenomena must speak for itself (Bryman, 2016; Gray, 2020) and to explore the experiences of the participants, the researcher should make conscious efforts to reduce bias. The focus is obtaining meaning through small sample sizes to ensure an in depth exploration of the subject of enquiry (Gray, 2022). Therefore, at the core of phenomenology lies the goal of grasping phenomena on their own terms (Groenewald, 2004).

Predominantly, phenomenology is described as a philosophy and a research strategy employed in qualitative enquiry. However, for this study, it is employed as a strategy. Interestingly, more scientists interested in studying experiential phenomena are adopting a phenomenological approach (Giorgi, 2006). This research strategy uses interviews to probe for a phenomenon's concealed meaning, which becomes accessible through the respondents' narratives (Maggs-Rapport, 2000). With this strategy, personal biases and judgements were made explicit through journaling before data analysis, as recommended by Gibbons *et al.* (1994).

In line with their assertion that management scholars can benefit from adopting phenomenology, especially when seeking to expose the nature of management experiences and interactions within an organisation. Anosike, Ehrich and Ahmed

(2012) argue that phenomenological interview protocols can prove beneficial to a study where participants are prompted to provide specific instances they have encountered as probes. This approach facilitates a comprehensive exploration of the subject under investigation, leading to more detailed conclusions. This was evident in the research as the study employed the critical incident technique (Flanagan, 1954) in the enquiry process. This led to the unearthing of the complexities. As a meaningful reality was created by phenomenological enquiry on authentic leadership from the rich accounts of respondents (Peoples, 2020), allowing the researcher to gain a deep understanding of AL from the perspective of the participants. Furthermore, the research strategy revealed the complex experiences of the respondents through detailed descriptions. This is because it involved a methodical depiction of the nature of the phenomenon. As understanding social actors' lived experiences and discovering the essence of a phenomenon is a fundamental objective of phenomenological research (Dane, 2018; Gray, 2022).

5.5 Research Design

The primary framing component of research is its design. Simply put, a research design is described as a plan on how to conduct research. Extant literature describes it as an approach for carrying out research, and this is aptly captured by Yin (2009), where it is described as a rational plan from point A to point B. A research design can also be described as a framework that connects theoretical perspectives to enquiry strategies and methods of data collection (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Thus, Alvesson and Sandberg (2021) suggest that it is closely related to the method and lays out a process for carrying out the research in a cogent, logical, and systematic manner, justifying the design elements like sampling procedures, data collection techniques, and analysis strategies that will allow researchers address research inquiries.

The research design is a blueprint that outlines the approach to be taken in addressing the research questions. It includes data collection techniques, data sources, constraints

and ethical considerations, which all support the specific research plan adopted for the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). The structure for designing a qualitative study is not standardised. Though, scholars engaged in qualitative enquiry have offered various design suggestions, the techniques implemented influences a researcher's design choice (Creswell and Poth, 2018).

When mapping out a research design for a study, it is argued that researchers can only select between two broad ways of gathering primary data, namely observations and interaction with people, also known as the communication approach (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). As the name implies, observations consider circumstances, individuals, practises, etc., while the communication approach facilitates data collection by questioning respondents. Figure 18 below provides a visual representation of the research design of the study at critical stages.

Figure 18 Research design

5.5.1 Scoping Study

A scoping study was done to evaluate authentic leadership. The study clarified the nature of the field and helped determine whether a systematic literature review was necessary. This analysis identified the fundamental debates, key concepts and types of evidence that are prevalent in the domain of authentic leadership. It also exposed gaps within extant literature. Three questions served as the framework for the scoping study. The questions were:

- What is authentic leadership?
- What are the components of authentic leadership?
- What role do followers play in authentic leadership development?

The scoping review revealed that researchers predominantly utilised quantitative research methodologies in the literature. Furthermore, it identified research gaps that subsequently influenced the initial research questions of the study.

5.5.2 Systematic literature review

To broaden understanding of authentic leadership, it is important to explore the limits of existing knowledge by following the guidance of Xiao and Watson (2019) in mapping the existing literature and identifying areas that require further investigation. Hence, in line with the initial discoveries from the scoping review, it became evident that there was a need for a systematic review within the field. Systematic reviews are essential for uncovering what is currently understood about a phenomenon, elucidating the methodologies employed in acquiring this knowledge, and highlighting disparities in scholarly perspectives. These reviews are conducted using a clear, transparent, replicable, and rigorous protocol. To this end, 80 articles published between 1970 and 2021 were methodically identified and analysed. The results obtained from the systematic literature also contributed to the refinement of the research questions. Refer to chapter three for an expanded discussion of the review process and the findings.

5.5.3 Gaining access

Choosing a suitable study location and identifying people who can facilitate and maintain access to the respondents is crucial for collecting data (Billups, 2019). So, identifying and engaging with gatekeepers, networks, and contacts are essential in the research process because gaining physical access or entry may become problematic (Gummesson, 2000). This could be attributed to time and resource limitations within companies, especially when access requests fail to reach the gatekeepers or brokers. Furthermore, access may be restricted owing to the sensitive nature of the subject matter, perceived lack of value, concerns regarding confidentiality, or doubts about competency (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Therefore, gatekeepers are described as access points that link researchers to study participants, which Billups (2019) suggests may be achieved through snowballing or opportunistic strategies. Also according to Neuman (2000) a gatekeeper is defined as an individual who possesses the official or unofficial power to regulate entry to a specific location.

For this study, the gatekeepers were in two categories. Firstly, the regulatory agency “Department of Petroleum Resources Nigeria” (DPR) and, secondly, gatekeepers within the organisations that participated in the study. The regulatory agency DPR is mandated by the Nigerian legislation to oversee and regulate the Oil and Gas sector. This regulatory agency, amongst its other responsibilities, is tasked with managing the National Data Repository (NDR) and keeping records of the activities of the petroleum businesses, particularly those pertaining to petroleum reserves, production/exports, licences, and leases. Therefore, it was essential for the researcher to access additional resources, such as regulatory information, to identify and facilitate the selection of research participants from among the oil companies duly registered within the country. Hence, following Billups (2019) recommendation, clarity was provided on the importance of the data, protection of the data and participants in terms of privacy, confidentiality and anonymity. Overall, in facilitating access to authentic leaders and followers, the study made provision for the time in obtaining access, explored old and new contacts, highlighted benefits to the organisation, and

clarified the study's purpose and objective (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The subsequent chapter offers a discussion on the interactions with the gatekeepers and the study's findings.

5.5.4 Unit of Analysis

The research problem usually determines the unit of analysis. It determines the level at which data gathering will be undertaken and the objects of enquiry (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014). These units of analysis are also described as units of observation. They can be individuals, dyad, group, and organisational or social artefacts, with other possibilities identified by several scholars (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Bryman, 2016).

The study follows the recommendations of Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2014), in choosing the unit of analysis. These guidelines suggest that the researcher should first define the research problem and the specific phenomenon that the study aims to clarify. Secondly, the researcher should determine what aspects need to be investigated and measured to address the research questions. Finally, the researcher should evaluate the potential beneficiaries and users of the study's findings. Therefore, the unit of analysis of the study are authentic leaders and followers, as determined by the research questions and a careful reflection of the recommendations of scholars.

5.5.5 Sampling

Sampling is described as a process of choosing an appropriate group that represents a specific population of the real world (Bryman, 2016). It is also described as selecting who or what to observe in social research. Two main sampling approaches are probability (representative) and non-probability (judgemental) sampling techniques (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). If the objective of a study is to determine a unique characteristic of a broader population, then data collection that is random, unbiased, and large will be an appropriate sampling to be adopted, in essence,

probability sampling (Bernard, Wutich and Ryan, 2017). A probability sampling technique seeks to explore a broad selection range where diversity is equally represented and can be selected.

However, if the goal were to understand a process where explanations are provided, then the selection of respondents who can provide information rich data (Billups, 2019) would be more appropriate for the study; in essence, non-probability sampling (Bernard, Wutich and Ryan, 2017). Non-probability sampling is further described as a subjective sampling method (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023) and is rooted in individual decisions (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014). This sampling technique appears to be the most cost effective and may be most appropriate for studies with few sample frames as it enables researchers attain sampling objectives adequately (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014).

The selection of either probability or non-probability sampling methods is based on the research questions, study objectives, and the inferences that will be drawn from the study (Bryman, 2016; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). More critically, ensuring the sample size is adequate for the investigation is crucial for each study (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Therefore, non-probability sampling was the most suitable as it provided rich contributions, which uncovered theoretical insights and explored the research questions in depth. Furthermore, it is recommended that selected samples provide detailed descriptions and offer the best explanations for the phenomenon of the study (Janesick, 1994).

The types of non-probability sampling methods include convenience sampling, where researchers have the freedom to select any individual as a research participant without restrictions, and purposive sampling, which involves a specific criteria for participant selection (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014; Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). However, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) identified convenience, volunteer, quota and purposive as other non-probability sampling techniques. The first three were not selected based on the probability of more bias. Hence, the sampling

technique adopted was purposive sampling followed by snowballing which ensured that respondents that participated in the study were nested in the context (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). This facilitated an in depth exploration of their experiences.

5.5.5.1 Purposive Sampling

Purposive sampling seeks to engage with participants that can address the research questions or match the focus of enquiry (Clark and Bryman, 2019). It is also described by Welman and Kruger (1999) as the most important type of non-probability sampling used to identify primary participants. This sampling technique is underpinned by a set of criteria for the selection process of the unit of analysis (Bryman, 2016). In the adoption of this sampling technique, it draws on the recommendations of Bryman (2016) and Hafford-Letchfield (2015). These recommendations emphasise the importance of selecting sampling techniques that are suitable for the study's objectives and allow for timely access and recruitment of participants. For this reason, the research participants were chosen based on their own lived experiences and understanding of authentic leadership, as this sampling technique facilitated the gathering of detailed descriptions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023).

The selection of oil companies from two key locations was guided by the study's overarching research aim, which is “to examine the construct of authentic leadership within the context of a developing economy, identify its components, factors that inspire its development, investigate the challenges authentic leaders encounter, and illuminate the process of becoming authentic.” In the first stage, two energy hubs were selected to avoid chance associations (Yin, 2014). A conscious effort was also made to minimise bias. Therefore, oil companies that were considered for the study met the under listed criteria following the guidance of Edú Valsania, Moriano and Molero (2016):

- The oil company must be in Lagos or Abuja
- The oil company must be duly registered with DPR
- The oil company must have a minimum of five employees

- The oil company should have been operational for over four years

The second stage was the search for authentic leaders within these organisations. Seminal scholars were contacted to identify authentic leaders, and recommendations were provided that leaders undertake self assessment to determine if these leaders perceived themselves as authentic. Interestingly, identifying authentic leaders had proved cumbersome and challenging as the review of extant literature described authentic leaders based on their retroactive actions and achievements. Similarly, scholars have suggested utilising the authentic leadership questionnaire (ALQ) created by Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) and the authentic leadership inventory (ALI) developed by Neider and Schriesheim (2011).

In the process of collecting data, the researcher reached out to 40 Oil companies with the aim of identifying authentic leaders within them. Within these organisations, followers were approached and asked to share their experiences of authentic leadership. The goal was to identify the key components of authentic leadership based on these descriptions and align them with existing literature. Once followers described their experiences, the researcher sought to identify leaders who were perceived as authentic by at least two followers within each organisation. The researcher probed further to enquire about leaders they perceived as authentic and how they arrived at a decision. This involved the use of the snowballing sampling technique within this process, as the selection of the authentic leaders that participated in the study was based on a consensus from two subordinates or followers within the organisation. This strategy broadened the initial contacts.

Snowball sampling, as a sampling method, entails identifying an initial respondent who meets the predetermined criteria and then relying on this respondent to recommend others who also meet the same criteria (Clark and Bryman, 2019) and is valid for identifying samples that are difficult to reach. In defence of this strategy, Bryman (2016) argues that using other non-probability sampling strategies, such as the snowball, is frequently preceded by purposive sampling.

These leaders were then contacted to further assess their authenticity according to established criteria outlined in scholarly literature. The researcher initially asked these identified leaders to describe their leadership practices, evaluating whether their descriptions aligned with the components outlined in the Authentic Leadership Questionnaire (ALQ), a prominent self-referential tool for identifying authentic leaders.

Out of the 40 organisations contacted, authentic leaders from 16 participated in the study. The researchers specifically focused on identifying authentic leaders rather than seeking general descriptions of leadership to minimise potential biases. This approach ensured that followers were prompted to articulate their understanding of authentic leadership specifically. At the end of this process, 46 semi-structured interviews were conducted with followers and identified authentic leaders, respectively. In line with the ethical principles of confidentiality and anonymity at the University of the West of Scotland, all participants in the study were assigned pseudonyms. Specifically, individuals categorised as authentic leaders were assigned pseudonyms from A to P, while followers who identified a specific leader were assigned a subset of pseudonyms, namely A1 and B1, for the sake of clarity and reference. The distribution of leaders is captured in Table 13, respectively. However, Table 12 presents a summary of the demographic data of the 30 followers that participated in the study.

Table 12 Demography of the followers

Followers	Gender	Age	Educational Qualification	Length of Service
A1	Female	40	Masters	5 years
A2	Male	40 - 50	Bachelor's Degree	1 year
B1	Female	41	Bachelor's Degree	5 years
B2	Male	30	Bachelor's Degree	4 years
C1	Male	30 - 35	Masters	5 years
C2	Female	40 - 45	MBA	12 years
D1	Female	30 - 40	BSc	11 years
D2	Female	43	Masters	11 years
E1	Female	40	Postgraduate	Over 10 years

E2	Female	36	MBA	13 years
F1	Female	30 - 40	Bachelor's Degree	6 years
F2	Female	35	Masters	9 ½ years
G1	Male	Late 30s	Masters	6 years
G2	Female	25 – 30	Masters	3 – 5 years
H1	Male	58	Secondary School	19 years
H2	Male	29	BSc	7 years
I1	Male	43	Masters	3 years
I2	Female	50	BSc	4 years
J1	Male	32	MBA	7 – 8 years
J2	Female	30	Bachelor's Degree	7 years
K1	Male	38	HND	4 years
K2	Male	35	Did not disclose	5 years
L1	Female	55- 60	Masters	15 years
L2	Male	40 - 50	MBA	10 years
M1	Female	Early 40s	College	13 years
M2	Male	30 - 40	Bachelor's Degree	5 years
N1	Male	40 – 45	MSc	3 years
N2	Female	37	Bachelor's Degree	7 years
O1	Prefer not to say	30 - 35	Masters	6 years
O2	Female	30 - 40	Bachelor's Degree	5 years

In the study, the ratio of male to female followers was 43.3% of men to 53.3% of women, with 3.33% of followers deciding not to disclose their gender. Most of these respondents were middle age with 83.3% being between the ages of 30 to 49, 6.6% being in their late 20s, and the remaining 10% being above 50. These suggest that most followers fall into the middle aged demographic, implying that they likely have accumulated significant workplace experience and have interacted with various leaders throughout their careers.

All the followers are educated, with 50% of the followers possessing a post graduate degree, 40% possessing a graduate degree and the remaining 10% accounting for those who went to secondary school and the final participant who chose not to declare their educational qualification. This level of education may be predominant in the industry based on the specialist skills required to thrive in this competitive space. The demography of the identified authentic leaders is similar in profile to the followers except for the higher educational qualifications of these leaders. Table 13 presents a

summary of the demographic data of the 16 authentic leaders that participated in the study.

Table 13 Demography of the authentic leaders

Leaders	Gender	Age	Qualification	Length of Service	Location(s)
A	Female	35 - 40	Bachelor's degree	2	Lagos
B	Female	37	Masters	7	Lagos
C	Male	50 - 60	Masters	20	Lagos, Abuja
D	Female	44	Bachelor's degree	12	Lagos
E	Male	40 - 45	Postgraduate	8	Lagos
F	Female	45 - 50	MBA	11	Lagos
G	Female	40 - 45	Masters	10	Lagos
H	Female	54	Masters	20	Lagos
I	Female	38	Masters	5	Lagos
J	Female	39 - 41	Bachelor's degree	14	Lagos
K	Male	44	Bachelor's degree	12	Abuja
L	Male	60 - 70	Masters	7	Abuja
M	Female	40	BSc	4	Lagos
N	Male	39	MBA	2	Lagos
O	Male	50 - 60	LLB Law	22	Lagos
P	Female	42	BSc	14	Lagos

Across authentic leaders, there was a noticeable gender distribution, with 37.5% being male and 62.5% female. This suggests that even male followers recognised and identified authentic female leaders. Furthermore, many of these authentic leaders were in the middle aged category, with 75% aged between 30 to 49 and the remaining 25% aged above 50. A closer look at the middle aged authentic leaders between 30 to 49 revealed that 31.25% were between 30 and 39 years old, while 43.75% were between 40 and 49 years old. Like the followers' profile, all the authentic leaders had a good educational background, with 43.75% holding a graduate degree and 56.25% possessing a post graduate degree.

Throughout the enquiry, authentic leaders recounted their personal experiences, including discussing their position in their family and how this shaped their experiences. Interestingly 56.25 % of the authentic leaders had a first position in their family; they were either the firstborn in their family, or they were the first boy or girl.

25% were in the second position, either second born in the family or the second son or daughter. The outstanding 18.75% accounted for other positions. Overall, the study's samples were chosen based on the criteriology and the research objectives, specifically individuals who possess lived experiences pertaining to the phenomenon of study (Groenewald, 2004). This sampling technique was adopted for both the pilot and main study.

5.5.5.2 Sample size

In determining the appropriate and adequate sample size for the study, the suggestions of scholars were carefully considered. These involve time constraints, resource availability, the size of the population, the chosen research method, the concept of saturation, and the intended analysis technique to be applied. Furthermore, Bryman (2016) states that there needs to be more clarity on adequate sample size for research, especially concerning saturation within a study. This is critical as several qualitative researchers continue to emphasise the need for probing and capturing detailed descriptions of the respondents. This has led to scholars offering suggestions on minimum numbers of acceptability for qualitative studies. For instance, Bertaux (1981) proposed 15 as the ideal number for qualitative studies. Similarly, a range of 6-8 interviews is suggested for a homogenous sample, while a range of 12 – 20 is recommended to achieve maximum variation (Kuzel, 1992).

In the same vein, 12 is proposed if the objective is to assess the in depth perceptions of a homogenous group (Guest, Bunce and Johnson (2006) and 12 per group when exploring the divergences of two or more groups. According to Crouch and McKenzie (2006), their study on cancer survivors showed that sample sizes of under 20 allowed researchers to uncover and gather rich data. In addition, Mason (2010) conducted an analysis of doctoral dissertations in the United Kingdom and Ireland, employing interview based qualitative research methods. The researcher found that the 560 theses examined used samples that varied in size from 1 to 95.

Therefore, for the study, the researcher's stance on sample size considered the recommendations of scholars, such as Guest, Bunce and Johnson (2006) and Kuzel (1992) in the first instance, with further considerations on the qualitative study goal and purposive sampling technique adopted. The total number of 46, 30 followers and 16 identified authentic leaders were adequate for the study. Saturation in responses was initially reached during the interview with the 14th authentic leader. Nonetheless, the study proceeded to conduct two additional interviews, aligning with Francis *et al.* (2010) stopping criteria. These extra interviews were carried out to confirm the attainment of saturation. Overall, the samples were purposively selected, and the study relied on existing relationships with contacts and gatekeepers to negotiate and gain entry into the organisations (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

5.6 Pilot Study

The pilot study, also known as pre-testing, utilises a small sample to assess the adequacy and suitability of the data gathering instruments for the main study (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014). For the study, the pilot was used to assess the interview protocol's effectiveness, question validity, and whether the initial responses effectively addressed the research questions (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2018).

The main study was guided by the pilot study, which served as a testing ground for the research procedure. The results of the pilot study were beneficial and facilitated the refinement of the instrument for the main study. The study required the selection of authentic leaders who met the study's criteria. Initial efforts were made to reach out to two leaders described and acknowledged as authentic leaders in extant literature, Bill George and Faith Wambura Ngunjiri (George, 2003; Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017). Despite their recognised status, these leaders did not respond, leading to the recruitment of two different authentic leaders for the pilot study.

The difficulty of finding authentic leaders to participate in the study became immediately apparent. This led to the redesign of the sampling strategy, which was

purposive with the adoption of snowballing to widen access to authentic leaders. Secondly, the interview questions were modified because of this process, and the interview guide was reorganised to allow for a smooth flow of questioning. Additionally, it made it easier to spot questions with redundant responses from respondents and led to a reflection on various aspects of the study contributing to the methodological rigour of the study.

5.7 Data Collection

Data sources can be classified into two distinct categories: primary and secondary (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014). Primary data is the process of researchers actively gathering new information, while secondary data refers to pre-existing material that has been acquired or produced (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). To achieve the objectives of a study, appropriate data collection methods must be employed. The researcher has access to a variety of primary data collection methods, but the nature of the research problem is crucial in determining which approach (or procedures) to employ. Similarly, secondary data are frequently used to validate samples (Creswell and Creswell, 2017), however, the implementation of these secondary data should be thoroughly evaluated prior to adoption.

Data collection is at the core of all research, and the instrumentation that describes data collection methods varies in appearance (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). These data collection instruments differ in strengths and techniques (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Inevitably, the technique selected determines the results obtained. As, the findings of a study are influenced by the procedures used to collect data. Therefore, while deciding how structured the instrumentation should be, considerations such as the exploratory nature of the research and rich context description that grounds the investigation led to the selection of little prior instrumentation. This choice was made to ensure unanticipated findings would not be overlooked. The researcher also maintained an open mind about what needed to

be known by using interviews in the study, which facilitated the emergence of themes from the data (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022).

Qualitative interviews are guided conversations that are developed around questions about a particular topic. They differ from everyday conversations in that they are contextual, purpose-driven and provide the chance for mutual discovery, understanding, reflection, and the elucidation of the lived experiences of the subject of the inquiry (Charmaz, 2014; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). As a result, it gives the researcher access to context related information. In particular, scholars advise that one of the main goals of qualitative interviews should be to understand the respondents' perspectives and the factors that shape them (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Therefore, the interviews were carried out to provide respondents with opportunities to express their uninhibited worldviews, insights and interpretations. Data collection instruments that address the research question and facilitate the research objectives were considered with; semi-structured interviews being used within the study.

5.7.1 Semi-structured Interviews

Qualitative data proves to be the most beneficial and revealing when clarity is required on influences of behaviour or emotional state of individuals (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023). Hence, interviews have been aptly described as a prominent methodological instrument in the toolkit of qualitative researchers (Fontana and Frey, 1994) and the length of interviews varies from single short interactions to repeated cycles over a period. Interviews were selected as the main approach for collecting data due to its ability to provide in depth understanding of the complex relationships among the participants of the study (Peoples, 2020).

There are several forms of interviews, such as individual, group or telephone, which are categorised as structured, unstructured or semi-structured. Structured interviewing describes an interaction where the interviewer asks respondents predetermined questions with limited response types. This interviewing technique leave little or no room for flexibility, with the interviewer assuming a neutral role but

facilitating a balanced rapport (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2018). In contrast, the aim of unstructured interviewing is understanding, which supports open-ended responses from respondents. One limitation of unstructured interviews is the inconsistency in responses among different respondents, which can make the analysis process challenging (McTate and Leffler, 2017; Bihu, 2020). In what has been described, as the midpoint of this continuum of interview structure is the semi-structured interview adopted within this study. Semi-structured interviews were selected based on study questions that served as a roadmap throughout the interview process (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). During a typical semi-structured interview, the researcher would possess a predetermined set of topics, referred to as the interview guide, which the research participants can respond to in a manner they consider suitable. The inherent flexibility of this type of interview facilitates the emergence and development of fresh ideas or issues.

For the study, the semi-structured interview protocol enabled the researcher to create interview questions pertinent to the research inquiries, ensuring that essential aspects of the study were covered, while allowing participants to speak about additional information that might prove helpful.

The initial interviews permitted the participant's lived experience to flow naturally, followed by an in depth analysis of participant descriptions. Semi-structured interviews facilitated the methodical spontaneity of phenomenological research for the initial individual interviews (Giorgi, 1985). Follow up interviews were used to fill gaps in data capture, particularly for verifying the birth positions of authentic leaders who had not discussed its influence or role in their leadership. The inclusion of semi-structured interviews in the study aligns with the traditional approach to gathering data for phenomenological research, which involves conducting qualitative in depth interviews (Creswell *et al.*, 2007; Creswell and Poth, 2018).

The study considered a practical obstacle, which was the interview site. The study also explored other interviewing methods, including telephone interviews and various

online support technologies, due to the ongoing restrictions imposed by the COVID epidemic. Interestingly, Akemu and Abdelnour (2020) argue that digitally mediated interactions are valuable alternative forms of being present with research participants and are just as important as in person interactions, despite the belief of certain scholars that non face to face interviews may limit interactions with respondents.

Furthermore Bell, Bryman and Harley (2022) acknowledge that the COVID pandemic made it challenging to engage in direct, in person interactions with study participants. The suspension of face to face research fieldwork was implemented by the University to safeguard the wellbeing of both the researcher and the participants involved in the study. Hence, the semi-structured interviews were conducted using Microsoft Teams and the Zoom platform, but the choice of platform was solely at the discretion of the interviewee. The flexibility in scheduling accommodated the availability of authentic leaders, some of whom were senior executives. Additionally, these platforms offered a choice to reschedule when unexpected opportunities arose for these leaders to participate. This is consistent with the methodology employed by scholars, who have used virtual platforms to conduct research on authentic leadership (Stephenson, 2023).

In this study, the process of collecting data from research participants commenced with strict adherence to ethical guidelines. All participants provided informed consent and were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. As advised by Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2018) the interview sessions were recorded with the participants' consent to enhance the listening process. This enabled the precise transcription of the data and provided the researcher with the opportunity to engage with the data multiple times, thereby aiding in the data analysis process (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022).

During the interviews, notes were also taken, which facilitated the formulation of follow up questions and further exploration of the respondents' perspectives and experiences. The interview guide featured icebreakers to establish rapport and closing questions to make respondents feel valued. The initial part of the interview aimed to

gather demographic data from the respondent. The subsequent part introduced the research, provided reassurance to participants regarding the anonymity and confidentiality of the process, clarified the reasons for their selection, and ensured that participants were at ease with the research and all aspects of their consent.

The four subsequent sections focused on each research question. In particular, defining authentic leadership was challenging; hence respondents were asked to clarify their understanding of the construct following the recommendation of Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2018). After responding and describing the construct, on some occasions the researcher was also asked to offer a definition. In this instance, Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) definition as “A pattern of leader behaviour that draws upon and promotes both positive psychological capacities and a positive ethical climate to foster greater self awareness, an internalised moral perspective, balanced information processing, and relational transparency on the part of leaders working with followers, thereby fostering positive self development (p.94).” was offered with no further explanations provided. The researcher chose this approach to evaluate the respondents' grasp of authentic leadership.

During the synchronous sessions, open ended questions allowed respondents to report and reflect on their experiences, followed by appropriate probes and other questions. The critical incident technique (CIT) advanced by Flanagan (1954) was employed in conjunction with the in depth interviews to explore factors that inspired their authentic leadership development. Following the conclusion of the interview sessions, the recordings were saved and assigned codes. Furthermore, the researcher listened to the recordings and prepared more notes as soon as possible. The audio recordings were transcribed to accurately capture the content and manner of communication, ensuring a comprehensive record of the exchanges. In adhering to the recommendations of Bell, Bryman and Harley (2022), the recording and transcriptions were done to address the limitations of human memory and facilitate repeated examination of the data. The researcher transcribed the data verbatim,

adhering to transcription conventions, such as indicating areas where words are missing or unclear in preparation for data analysis, which is discussed in the next section.

5.8 Data Analysis

Qualitative research has been linked to large data sets because of the data collection techniques, and appropriate analytic pathways must be sought to capture its richness (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). The aim of the data analysis was to capture the individual lived experiences of the respondents and consolidate their experiences to determine their shared fundamental meanings (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). Prior to analysis, the researcher reviewed the transcripts many times to become familiar with the data. The researcher also adhered to methodological principles, such as iteration, to maintain an unbiased perspective when meanings developed into themes (Sundler *et al.*, 2019; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). This resonates with Stake (1995) argument that good research extends beyond the veracity of the method used to include good thinking that the researcher contributes to the process.

Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2018) also contend that the data analysis technique adopted in a study is closely linked to the philosophy that underpins it. This is because data analysis is a core stage in qualitative enquiry as it facilitates data transformation into research findings (Patton, 2015) and there is no specific formula for attaining this transition. But, scholars have offered guidelines and frameworks to accomplish this (Bryman, 2016; Gray, 2020; Gray, 2022). Thus, the researcher aimed to use a data analysis strategy for the study that would handle the data equally and lead to compelling conclusions.

Several approaches to qualitative data analysis have been advanced such as content analysis, which systematically examines textual, visual, or audio data to identify specific words or patterns. Narrative analysis, which examines the structure, content, and context of narratives to understand how experiences are constructed. Discourse

analysis, which explores how language and communication shape meaning and social reality, and thematic analysis, which entails recognising, and capturing patterns or themes. Thematic analysis, which discovers, analyses, and reports data patterns, was appropriate for this study as it is a technique used to uncover patterns within the dataset (Boyatzis, 1998).

While the search for themes is crucial in many data analysis methods, the history of thematic analysis lacks a well defined narrative (Bryman, 2016; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Several approaches have been advanced in conducting thematic analysis, such as Braun and Clarke (2006) six-stage thematic process which includes data familiarisation, generation of codes, search for themes, review of themes, definition and labelling of themes and finally, the reporting using evidence. In comparison, King and Horrocks (2010) offer a three-stage process that was shaped by Braun and Clarke (2006) and guided by Langdrige and Hagger-Johnson (2009) recommendations. The 3 stage process offered by King, Horrocks and Brooks (2019) was adopted with an acknowledgement that the process is not linear, which became evident in the study.

In preparation for the detailed analysis, preliminary decisions were made, and actions were taken following the suggestions of Patton (2015). During the semi-structured interviews, the notes taken were used to guide further probing, highlighting emerging ideas and potential themes. All interview recordings were labelled correctly, dated and saved on UWS OneDrive; a password protected drive provided by the University. A decision was also made to utilise the NVivo software, the university's qualitative data management software.

Familiarisation with the data was core, and this was the goal at the initial stages of engaging with the data as the researcher sought to be fully immersed to avoid leaps in the analysis process (Lyons and Coyle, 2016). At this stage, the focus was engaging with the data for data's sake without expecting likely themes.

During the familiarisation process with the data, it became evident that the followers and authentic leaders valued direction though, it was described differently. The followers described it as an expectation from the leaders, while the authentic leaders described it as a personal reference point for them, especially in times of ambiguity. As an example, leaders D and C emphasise the significance of grasping their purpose in the context of their leadership experiences and the value it brought to them as they described their leadership journeys. This is captured in table 14 below.

Table 14 Descriptions of direction

Leader D	<i>"I realised that I understand my purpose. I understand that I want to live a life of impact, not just on my job. You must be clear about what you are trying to achieve, how you will impact, how you will influence, and what you are going to.... What mark are you going to leave?"</i>
Leader C	<i>"First, you follow your vision because you need to know precisely where you are headed truly. You must lead with purpose. You must have a purpose; with purpose comes direction. So, that is the first thing I have done in terms of leadership. You need to have values that make a difference and that speak to how changes happen in society. Leaving the kind of legacy, you desire to see."</i>

This became salient across the respondents' descriptions during the immersion and familiarisation with the data. Another notable observation was how followers articulated the process of discerning whether a leader was authentic or inauthentic. For followers, the role of time became apparent as they repeatedly highlighted how long they interacted with the leaders to arrive at this decision and, in contrast, how quickly they could identify inauthentic leaders. These observations led to an in depth exploration and interrogation of the data, a crucial outcome of the familiarisation process (Lyons and Coyle, 2016).

The data analysis process began with a search for meaning using codes as distinct pots to capture the essence of authentic leadership. Saldaña (2021) states that codes assign a collective, salient attribute to chunks of data. This process is also described as the connection between raw empirical data and the interpreted meaning (Vogt *et al.*, 2014).

This technique involves categorising data to construct a framework of thematic ideas about the subject of enquiry (Gibbs, 2018).

Building on Miles, Huberman and Saldaña (2018) recommendation that coding requires deep reflection, a method of discovery that begins the data analysis process to arrive at an interpretation. The study adopted the In Vivo coding method to capture the respondents' voices and retain their verbatim descriptions (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018) enabling the lived experience of authentic leaders to be expressed adequately. The analysis process was systematic as it utilised King and Horrocks (2010) three-stage model, examining meaning at both the semantic and latent levels; how authentic leadership was experienced and the implicit arguments underpinning these descriptions. There are three tiers in this structure. The first, or descriptive stage, seeks to highlight interesting findings, searching out data to help address the research questions. Second, interpretive stage focuses on the interpretation that go beyond the accounts of the respondents, and third, the overarching themes that characterise the research's central ideas. These will be discussed in broader detail from subsections 5.8.1 to 5.8.3.

5.8.1 Descriptive Analysis

The transcripts were printed on paper and were first manually coded, and then it was transferred to the university's NVivo software. The paper version of the transcript was easy to engage with and offered flexibility at this stage. To ensure consistency, when the descriptive codes were applied across the transcripts, notes were recorded as they emerged from the data to reflect the reasoning process underpinning each code. Following the recommendations from King, Horrocks and Brooks (2019) and King and Horrocks (2010) that descriptive codes capture key elements of the interview that are important to the respondents, the researcher commenced the coding process by engaging with the transcripts again after the initial familiarisation process.

Then issues, contexts, and relevant underpinning information that enabled the researcher to understand the participants' perspectives, experiences and perceptions

were captured. Descriptive codes were assigned, which were long phrases initially, but these were pruned down to single words where possible and shorter phrases in most cases. After applying descriptive codes to a transcript, these were checked and reread to combine overlapping codes. Table 15, presented below, illustrates the descriptive coding process employed in the study to analyse how some authentic leaders depicted their leadership.

Table 15 Interview Extracts- A sample of the descriptive coding process

Respondent	Interview Extract	Comments	Descriptive codes
Leader A	Everyone is not the same and you have to adapt your style to suit each member of your team. You know some people learn when you give out strategies.	The leader highlights the differences in followers' competencies.	Adaptable
Leader A	I know everyone is working extra hours because of the pandemic, but we have to adapt, and we have to change, and you have to become more very accommodative. You know, because whoever you are giving this additional task to also has their burden. You do not know if they have a family member in the hospital. Many people have their kids in their houses. You know, this pandemic period has been very challenging.	The leader highlights differences in followers' unique personal circumstances.	Adaptable
Leader E	I am not sure I have one approach to, leadership per say.	The leader highlights flexibility in their leadership.	Adaptable
Leader D	Of course, over time my leadership skills or leadership style has evolved based on different environments that I have worked in or based on the situation of the of the business that I have worked in.	The leader highlights the change in their leadership approach across contexts.	Adaptable
Leader P	I am a leader in my church. I am a leader in my in my business. I am a leader amongst my friends, so it depends on in where I am. I mean I am a leader in different areas, so it depends on where I am where I am determines or who I am leading determines the way I lead, so I have to lead in the way that the follower or the person I'm leading is going to understand and follow me.	The authentic leader highlights the different leadership roles adopted.	Adaptable

5.8.2 Interpretive Analysis

For the interpretive analysis, the researcher was more analytical, which extended beyond capturing descriptions to the interpretation of the meanings based on evidence from the transcripts. The descriptive codes were condensed into smaller analytic categories at the interpretive level. Hence, descriptive codes were carefully reviewed iteratively to assess where shared meaning was evident and where it diverged. For the descriptive codes that had shared meanings, the researcher returned to the initial notes recorded that captured the nature and reasoning process behind each descriptive code to ensure this was preserved in the creation of the interpretive code. The descriptive codes became the basis of the interpretive code. There were several iterative cycles at this stage to ensure that codes were distinct and clearly defined (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2019; King and Horrocks, 2010) . Figure 19 below provides an example of the interpretive analysis process within the study.

Figure 19 A sample of the interpretive analysis process

5.8.3 Overarching Theme

The third and last stage was generating the overarching themes that characterise the analysis's key concepts. This stage utilised the interpretive codes as the building blocks for the overarching theme, as recommended by proponents of this framework, King, Horrocks and Brooks (2019). The themes emerged from a careful and rigorous data analysis. To determine the direction of the theme generation process and ensure that the themes represented meaningful interpretations of the data, references to the research questions were made during the theme development.

For instance, respondents repeatedly used terms such as consistency and transparency, which highlighted regularities and patterns within the context of the study. The interpretive codes were reconfigured as the themes emerged, subjecting the compelling themes to crosschecking. Finally, the overarching themes were reviewed in relation to the codes, data excerpts, and the complete dataset. Figure 20 below provides an example of the development of an overarching theme within the study.

Figure 20 A sample of the overarching theme process

5.9 Ethical Consideration

The appropriateness of the researchers' actions toward the subjects of their research or others who might be affected by it is called ethics in research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This concept is aptly summarised by Blumberg et al. (2005, p. 92) as “moral principles, norms or standards of behaviour that guide moral choices about our behaviour and our relationships with others.” The planning, execution, and reporting phases of the research process are all guided by ethical considerations (Gray, 2022). Which means that, ethical concerns pervade through the study's entire planning and design (Gray, 2022; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023).

In order to protect the research respondents, Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2014) suggest that researchers adhere to three principles. To begin, explain the objective and benefits of the research. Then, expound on the researcher's intentions to protect the respondents' rights and wellbeing; finally, obtain informed consent from the respondents to proceed. These principles are also captured in the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Advisory Board guidelines, which shaped the study (See Appendix 2 for the ethical approval obtained for the study). The research involved human participants, so meeting the guidelines of the Ethics Advisory Board was crucial. The main principles of, benefits and harm, privacy and confidentiality, autonomy and informed consent, justice and inclusiveness, guided the design and overall execution of the study (University Ethics Committee, 2023).

The principle of beneficence (benefits) and non-maleficence (harm) means ensuring that no harm is caused to the participants during and after the research. This consideration was also made in the use, analysis and reporting of findings. This was achieved by carefully designing the study to ensure participants were safeguarded from risks that could cause harm, such as psychological, physical, and emotional distress. This was done to extensively minimise the risk of a backlash for expressing honest opinions about leaders within the organisation, adhering to the principles of anonymity and confidentiality during the enquiry. Furthermore, interview sessions

were also arranged in consideration of the respondents' plans to avoid disrupting their schedules.

In terms of benefits, it entails striking a balance between the advantages of the research and the risks (University Ethics Committee, 2023). The notion of benefits was advanced by uncovering new aspects of authentic leadership. Both authentic leaders and followers benefited from this information as it allowed them to evaluate authentic leadership processes. This gave participating organisations a reference for authentic leadership development. Respondents were eager to commit more time than was required during the interview sessions.

According to the autonomy principle, participants must be informed of the study's goals, structure, and implications. This means that complete participant disclosure of the research design is necessary to achieve and demonstrate autonomy (King and Brooks, 2018; Gray, 2022). As such, participants were first given the participant information forms that provided an overview of the research, including the benefits of participation. Furthermore, a full briefing regarding the purpose, and implications of the study was given to the participants prior to obtaining consent from those who were willing to participate. This ensured that participants were adequately informed before consent was freely given. This is described by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) as "informed consent." Overall, consent was acquired from the authentic leaders and followers (see Appendix 3 for a copy of the consent form) based on information provided on the respondents' rights and use of data. In addition, participant information sheets served as reminders on the right to withdraw from the study and it included details on where to channel complaints if necessary (see Appendix 4 for a copy of the participant letter).

Regarding the principles of privacy and confidentiality, Sieber (1998) distinguishes between three concepts, privacy, confidentiality and anonymity, that are closely linked. In this study, the subtle differences were embraced and influenced the conduct of the research. In ensuring privacy, the respondents and researcher had control and

maintained boundaries. In adherence to confidentiality, respondents were informed on how the data will be handled, who will have access to it and how it will be used. The respondents were assured of anonymity to safeguard their identities and protect them when reporting the findings (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). So, the confidentiality and anonymity of participants were upheld to align with ethical standards.

Finally, the principle of justice demands the fair and equitable treatment of all research participants. This principle was adhered to by impartially treating all respondents, both authentic leaders and followers. In addition, ethical research is a scholarly undertaking that explores all available pieces of evidence in contrast to the selection of evidence that enhances the researcher's interests, agenda, and preferences of their worldview. Thus, integrity and honesty have shaped this study (Adams, Khan and Raeside, 2014) as ethics permeated all the phases of the research. For example, leading questions were not utilised during the inquiring process.

Similarly, appropriate planning of the research was completed with ethics guiding key stages such as gaining access to research participants (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019) and assessment conducted by the UWS Ethical Review Board. This facilitated the early identification of design based ethical challenges. The identified gaps were addressed by modifying the research design and protocol before the investigation commenced (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Figure 21 below provides an overview of the ethical principles that guided the study.

Figure 21 Principles of Ethics

5.10 Criteriology for establishing quality

Defining quality has been a subject of contention and debate among scholars (Cypress, 2017; Bazeley, 2021). These arguments are mainly aimed at assessing the worth of qualitative research based on the notion that there is a lack of set criteria to assess its value (Biesta, 2007; Hammersley, 2007). Traditionally, scholars belonging to the quantitative school argue that rigorous research must evidence validity and reliability by adhering to strict processes (Bazeley, 2021). However, Qualitative scholars, including seminal authors like Lincoln and Guba (1985) have dismissed these terminology and proposed other criteria for evaluating the quality of qualitative research. Their criteria emphasise trustworthiness which consists of four components: credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. Credibility seeks to evaluate the veracity of the conclusions, Transferability evaluates whether conclusions apply to other contexts, dependability evaluates the likelihood that conclusions will hold true in other situations, and confirmability evaluates the importance of the researcher's contributions to the research. These parameters, when

adopted within the framework, ensure methodological rigour. This aligns with the assertion that valid conclusions are linked to rigorous research methodology (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011), with scholars suggesting that these parameters are parallel to the quantitative school of thought (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Table 16 provides an overview of these comparisons.

Table 16 Criteria for quality

Quantitative Research	Qualitative Research
Internal validity	Credibility
External Validity	Transferability
Reliability	Dependability
Objectivity	Confirmability

Even though scholars disagree on the parameters for assessing quality in qualitative research, there is a consensus that procedures are required to demonstrate a sound basis for a researcher's inferences and conclusions (Bazeley, 2021). It is also recommended that strategies necessary to ensure rigour is incorporated into the research process, rather than only assessing it afterwards (Cypress, 2017). As a result, the study uses the criteria established by Lincoln and Guba (1985) for evaluating research.

5.10.1 Credibility

In ensuring credibility, rigorous methods and techniques were adopted to ensure the appropriate sampling of authentic leaders. This emerged through adopting a blend of purposive and snowball sampling techniques. It ensured that the research participants possessed the requisite expertise and experience to effectively address the research inquiries. Furthermore, the researcher had the requisite skills and training to undertake the research, having conducted a qualitative enquiry earlier in their

scholarship pursuit. As a result, high quality data emerged from the process, which was analysed systematically.

Triangulation of sources was used to capture the diverse ways that authentic leaders and followers experienced authentic leadership to minimise intrinsic bias that emerge from single perspectives. The triangulation of different sources was used to assess convergence and divergence on the descriptions provided by the respondents (Patton, 2015). Therefore, credibility lies both in the methodology and the presentation of findings as the process was documented transparently. The use of quotes serves as evidence to demonstrate that the content and expressed meanings are consistent.

5.10.2 Transferability

To assess the transferability of the findings, the study sought to uncover the relevance of the findings to similar contexts. Though, there are debates on the issues of generalisability and transferability relating to qualitative studies (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). The study aimed to capture in depth, rich descriptions from the participants, which informed the research participants' selection purposively. These thick descriptions provide a basis for evaluating other contexts (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022).

Therefore, in enhancing transferability, an expert, "A Professor", was used to assess the quality of the analysis and accuracy of the interpretations. This is also described as expert checking (Gray, 2020). This was also achieved through the systematic review of the domain, which facilitated the comparison of the findings with the extant debates in the literature. Furthermore, an audit trail of the data analysis process is provided, utilising the data set from which they originated to demonstrate that the analysis was underpinned by appropriate evidence.

5.10.3 Dependability

The study's dependability was enhanced by ensuring two researchers participated in the review of the findings. This began with discussions on the codes generated, the

relationships and links. The use of the NVivo tool also contributed positively to the process.

Furthermore, auditing underpins dependability, which ensures traceability and record keeping of all the stages involved in the enquiry process (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). It covers key activities such as the sampling phase, transcriptions and data analysis. Hence, the records of iterations, especially during the data analysis, have been documented. These were made available to peers to ensure adherence to proper procedures during the study. These were also assessed after key stages during the research process.

5.10.4 Confirmability

Regarding the confirmability of the study, the researcher acted in good faith during the enquiry process. Bias was minimised by adopting techniques to ensure that data spoke for itself. This is in direct response to arguments by researchers that qualitative research is subjective and is predominantly tainted by the researchers unsystematic approach to sense making, the meaning they have arrived at and also the relationships that researchers have or seek to have with research participants (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). Therefore, the researcher ensured transparency of the enquiry process with evidence of how conclusions were reached. A broad account was provided of how research participants were selected, as well as providing clarity on the data analysis process. In summary, the study generated results firmly rooted in empirical evidence.

5.11 Conclusion

This chapter outlined the methodological choices that have shaped the study. It provides a broad overview of the enquiry process, as research should have a strong philosophical grounding. Each section discussed a specific part of the enquiry process as the chapter guides the readership sequentially through all the steps involved in undertaking the research. The researcher also sought to establish the framework used

in data collection, analysis, and interpretation, along with the logic underpinning these decisions. By comparing methods, approaches, and philosophies, a rationale for the choices made in the study is provided, as discussed below.

The chapter introduced philosophical debates providing justifications for the selection of the interpretivism philosophy. This ensured a firm foundation for the methodological decisions made during the enquiry process. The following two sections offered arguments to support the research approach and method. The abductive approach to reasoning offered a complementary substitute that is a distinct and an essential alternative to inductive and deductive approaches. It draws from inductive and deductive reasoning logic but uses data to develop theory. The approach was appropriate for the study as it captures meanings and interpretations that deductive and inductive reasoning overlook. Thus, the study adopted abductive reasoning, as the research problem should adopt the approach that will best serve it.

The qualitative method was valuable as it uncovered otherwise hidden underlying processes in the study. Therefore, due to the exploratory nature of the study, five qualitative research strategies were assessed in relation to the research problem. This guided the final selection of the phenomenological research strategy. The subsequent subsections discussed the practicalities of designing and conducting the study, providing evidence of the study's rigorous enquiry process. Figure 22 provides an overview of the methodological choices that shaped the study.

Figure 22 Summary of methodological approach

CHAPTER 6. EMPIRICAL FINDINGS: AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP COMPONENTS AND DEVELOPMENTAL FACTORS

INTRODUCTION

The preceding chapter explained the methodological decisions that influenced the study and described how the empirical work was undertaken. It presented the researcher's philosophical views and the underpinning assumptions in addressing the four research questions. Given that the study aimed to explore authentic leadership within a developing economy context and fully illuminate the process of becoming authentic, a qualitative research method was adopted as it aligned with the researchers' interpretivist worldview. The thematic data analysis technique used in the study drew on King, Horrocks and Brooks (2019) recommendations. Thus, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 46 respondents, 16 authentic leaders, and 30 followers.

The key findings that emerged are presented across two chapters: chapters six and seven. Chapter six focuses on addressing the initial two research inquiries of the study: What are the components of authentic leadership, and what are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders? The responses of all 46 participants were examined to address the first research question about the components of authentic leadership. The goal was to uncover the lived experiences and bare their detailed descriptions of the components of authentic leadership. Hence, capturing accounts from the leader and follower perspectives was crucial as areas of divergence and convergence became evident, providing conceptual links in extant literature.

However, in addressing the second research question on the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders, only the responses of the 16 leaders are analysed, as these respondents possess specialist knowledge on the subject matter. The analysis of these leaders' responses facilitated the exploration of unique aspects of the authentic leadership construct that are lacking in earlier conceptualisations.

This chapter is organised thematically into three sections, which serve to highlight specific findings. Section 6.1 offers a summary of the specific areas in Nigeria where the participants are selected from to provide the context for the findings. Section 6.2 reveals the components of authentic leadership in depth, highlighting components that have been overlooked in extant literature. Section 6.3 outlines the four factors that inspire authentic leadership development. The chapter uses excerpts from participants to emphasise and provide evidence; these quotes are presented in italics. Finally, in adhering to the UWS ethical guidelines in research and scholarship on privacy and confidentiality (University Ethics Committee, 2023) all respondents were assigned pseudonyms to protect their identity and ensure anonymity.

6.1 Overview of cities of Lagos and Abuja

The selection of capital cities across Africa has been attributed mainly to colonialism, as most of these cities served as depots for transporting goods and services to Europe (Gale, 1979; Salau, 1977). Most of these capital cities were strategically chosen based on political and economic considerations (Abubakar and Doan, 2017; Santos and Mota, 2019). In this study, the respondents were drawn from oil companies operating in two strategic locations of the nation: Abuja Federal Capital Territory, the current capital of Nigeria and Lagos, the former capital of Nigeria (Etuk *et al.*, 2022).

Lagos, the former capital of Nigeria, is a coastal city, also identified as 'Eko' by most of its inhabitants (Bigon and Home, 2016; Olaniyi, 2021). It is Nigeria's economic hub, and financial nerve centre, characterised by a wide range of commercial operations across several industries (Adejuyigbe, 1970; Olowa and Olowa, 2015). The city is bursting with opportunities which has been accelerated by its rapid population growth. Lagos is described as the fifth largest economy in Africa, generating over 90% of the nation's trade (Osho and Adishi, 2019). Similarly, Abuja, Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory and current capital, was a vibrant trading route from Zaria to Lokoja pre colonisation (Thomas-Emeagwali, 1989). It was announced as the capital of

Nigeria in December 1991 and lies at the centre of the country (Nicholas and Patrick, 2015; Oluyori *et al.*, 2019). Its selection as the capital is primarily attributed to its centrality, low population density and accessibility. It is the current seat of power in Nigeria, hosting the seat of the government and several national agencies (Jacob, Jegede and Solomon, 2020). Figure 23 provides a visual representation of Nigeria with its 36 states.

Figure 23 Map of Nigeria with States

Source : Gayawan, Arogundade and Adebayo (2014) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

The prominence of these two cities is also evident in the oil Industry. Oil became a prominent economic support for the country after the Civil War (Odularu, 2008). Nigeria's oil sector is regulated, and companies require licences issued by the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) to operate commercially within the industry. This agency is plagued with the statutory responsibility of ensuring compliance with governing laws within the country.

Drawing from the records of DPR as of June 2021 on all the registered oil companies that were granted the Petroleum Products Haulage License. This is a licence that allows oil companies to trade legally in white products such as Automotive Gas Oil (AGO), Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) and Aviation Turbine Kerosene (ATK), also known as Diesel, Petrol /Gas and Jet fuel, respectively. The table below captures the agency's licensing activities in 2020 and based on this data only 30 applications were rejected, with 616 licences issued and 2 under processing. In 2021, there was a decline in submissions largely attributed to COVID. 380 applications were approved, 71 were returned, and seven were under processing. See below the breakdown of registered companies across states captured in Table 17 below.

Table 17 Breakdown of registered oil companies in 2020 and 2021

States	Registered Companies
Abia	3
Abuja	81
Adamawa	1
Akwa Ibom	9
Bauchi	1
Bayelsa	20
Cross River	4
Delta	76
Edo	7
Enugu	1
Gombe	1
Imo	5
Kaduna	13
Kano	8
Katsina	2
Lagos	559
Niger	2
Ogun	8
Ondo	3
Oyo	3
Plateau	5
Rivers	290

Based on the table above, the four notable states are Lagos, Rivers, Abuja, and Delta. However, this study draws samples predominantly from Lagos and Abuja. It is important to note that the respondents from Abuja worked for companies affiliated with a Lagos entity either as the head or as a branch office. It was unsurprising to note that most authentic leaders resided in Abuja, which may be linked to its role in Nigeria's economic and political landscape.

6.1.1 Profile of the respondents

The companies selected were all duly licensed oil companies trading white products. The samples were selected from a population of full time employees across diverse departments within these organisations. The study did not focus on gender; however, the 30 followers involved in the first stage of interviews were split across 16 females representing 53.3%, 13 males representing 43.3% and 1 follower representing 3.3% who expressly did not want to be associated with any gender. When questioned about authentic leadership, they expressed their perceptions and understanding of the construct. In addition to identifying two authentic leaders in their organisations, these followers were asked to define authentic leadership. Subsequently, a total of 16 authentic leaders were interviewed.

Regarding the authentic leaders that participated in this study, 10 out of the 16 leaders representing 62.5% were female leaders, and the remaining 6 authentic leaders representing 37.5% were male leaders. Like the followers, these authentic leaders were educated, all attaining a minimum of an undergraduate degree. 9 out of the 16 authentic leaders possessed master's degrees across diverse disciplines, and the remaining 7 authentic leaders possessed bachelor's degrees, which may be attributed to the technical nature of the industry. This mirrors the demographic descriptions in other studies in the oil industry, such as Aslam *et al.* (2021) study on the impact of blockchain technology in the oil industry, among the respondents, 6 individuals held degrees below the level of a bachelor's, 30 possessed bachelor's degrees, and 40 had master's degrees or other postgraduate qualifications.

The interviews began by asking the leaders to describe their leadership, which enabled them to offer in depth descriptions of their experiences. After these accounts, the leaders were asked to provide descriptions of authentic leadership. It was interesting to note that, despite their educational qualifications, some (J, B, E, F, G, I, L, N) required clarity on the construct of authentic leadership, for instance, asking for definitions of the construct. See below leader J's response when questioned about why she perceived herself as an authentic leader: "First of all, let me ask you a question again. What is your definition of an authentic leader?" Other examples are shown in Table 18 below when respondents were posed with the same question.

Table 18 Examples of questions asked by the authentic leaders

Leaders	Proof Quotes
Leader B	<i>"It depends on what you mean by an authentic leader because we hear all these trends, so maybe if you want to define what an authentic leader is"</i>
Leader E	<i>"It depends on how you define authentic right"</i>
Leader F	<i>"So, what is your definition of an authentic leader? Let me try to understand from that perspective"</i>
Leader G	<i>"For me to answer that, I think it's important we both at least have a baseline on what authentic leadership means"</i>

In response to all the questions from the respondents on either the definition or description of the construct Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) definition was provided. This definition was helpful and, in several instances, allowed respondents answer the questions. However, no further explanation was provided to avoid distorting their understanding and, inevitably, their accounts.

6.2 Components of authentic leadership

The section explores the shared understanding of all the respondents to answer the first question: What are the components of authentic leadership? In addressing the above, authentic leaders' and followers echoed a comparable understanding of authentic leadership. Their narratives provided the raw data for the extrapolation of the components evidenced below.

A thematic analysis was conducted on the responses of all 46 participants to identify the components of authentic leadership. Based on the detailed accounts given, six key components were identified. The respondents' descriptions consistently highlighted clarity of purpose, self awareness, internalised moral perspective, relational transparency, concern for people and follower development. Although self awareness, internalised moral perspective, and relational transparency have been discussed in extant literature (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008), the respondents further unpacked the fundamentals of these components providing conceptual links that will contribute to leadership interventions, development and repair. In addition, previously unacknowledged components were discovered and are presented. The following sections present discussions of these components.

6.2.1 Clarity of Purpose

All 46 respondents described clarity of purpose as a critical component of authentic leadership. These authentic leaders aspired to different things and made conscious decisions to pursue them relentlessly. There was a consensus on its value in authentic leadership. However, authentic leaders and followers described this theme from two distinct but complementary perspectives. Firstly, authentic leaders argued that clarity of purpose emerged from a clear understanding of self, and it is anchored on their authentic leadership journey. For instance, Leader D reiterates this clarity as captured in the quote *"I realised that I understand my purpose. I understand that I want to live a life of impact, not just on my job. You must be clear about what you are trying to achieve, how you will impact, how you will influence."* Compared to the leaders' descriptions, the followers suggested that the clarity of purpose emerged from the leader's knowledge that was essential for direction, guidance and success. Taken as a whole, all 16 authentic leaders described their purpose profoundly and explained its role in their leadership. This is aptly captured in Table 19 below, where all the authentic leaders highlight their awareness of their purpose and the consciousness to pursue it.

Table 19 Selected responses from the 16 authentic leaders

Authentic leaders	Quotes on Purpose
Leader A	<i>"I was on 30 different engagements. You see different seniors leading in different ways. You see the bad ones, and you are like, I do not want to be this kind of Leader. So, two years into my career, I decided... this is how I want to lead."</i>
Leader B	<i>"I am self-aware about my values as a person. I know the things that I exemplify, which is what I project with my team."</i>
Leader C	<i>"First, you follow your vision because you need to know precisely where you are headed truly. You must lead with purpose. You must have a purpose; with purpose comes direction. So that is the first thing I have done in terms of leadership. You need to have values that make a difference and that speak to how changes happen in society. Leaving the kind of legacy, you desire to see."</i>
Leader D	<i>"I realised that I understand my purpose. I understand that I want to live a life of impact, not just on my job. What mark are you going to leave?"</i>
Leader E	<i>"I just have a view that things can always be better, so because that is my natural way of looking at things whether what I am looking at operations or process or people I am dealing with.... I just want to make things improve. I am a dreamer, right? I always see what is possible."</i>
Leader F	<i>"It is a passion to leave no man behind. That is what drives me because I am thinking about the next person that will be able to replace me."</i>
Leader G	<i>"I hold personal integrity to the highest level. I like to lead by example and not make commitments that I am not willing and able to fulfil...I have taken that alongside, through my university days and even right here with my day-to-day career."</i>
Leader H	<i>"I know that being authentic gets things done. It moves you towards your goal. It makes you achieve the goals of your company. If you are not authentic, you cannot be realistic about your actions. I started this from the beginning because I know it has to do with my survival in my line of business."</i>
Leader I	<i>"I make sure that the company is placed on a pedestal that can sustain its business and even outgrow the people that were looking forward to being like in future."</i>
Leader J	<i>"You realise that as an individual, your moral values also come into play, and then whomever you work with also helps at a point. Moreover, that has shaped me and helped me be who I am."</i>
Leader K	<i>"The greatest thing about living is being able to improve others and see their potentials... So, for me, if anything that drives me in terms of leadership is how to improve someone to make them better in something that I do not think they were good at some point in time."</i>

Leader L	<i>"I believe that my character should be very predictable I have tried to remain the authentic leader I think I am. I would like to be remembered and known as a man of integrity. By my training all along, the most important thing or virtue a man should possess is integrity."</i>
Leader M	<i>"The more leaders you can build, the more authentic you are. It is not just about you anymore."</i>
Leader N	<i>"That desire to see other people succeed. The personal desire to succeed and ensure that everything that I do turns out well, helps me build the brand. I am also recognised for the integrity that my work provides."</i>
Leader O	<i>"I think it started from observing different leadership styles and leaders and realising that everyone works from a position of their background, environment and orientation. But do not forget that the goal of leadership or my style, is to get us to achieve certain things. And if people are not pushed beyond their normal capabilities, they will not achieve the excellence."</i>
Leader P	<i>"I lead based on conviction. I know that seedtime and harvest time shall not seize. You cannot do something and get away with it. So, that, for me is why I must be authentic. I am not telling you to do things that you have not done before. So, if I have principles, I practice it."</i>

From the above, 31.25% of the leaders expressly linked their clarity of purpose to their values. Though, intrinsic to these leaders, these values informed their outlook and became evident within the organisations. Authentic leaders demonstrated clarity of purpose by creating an enabling environment to attain success and being goal oriented. These sub-themes, enabling environment and goal orientation, were prominent in the descriptions provided by authentic leaders. This was unsurprising as followers also acknowledged the importance of the enabling environment and goal orientation. However, the followers identified a third salient subtheme of knowledge orientation which driven by the knowledge and experience of authentic leaders. This knowledge orientation demonstrated the authentic leader's clarity of purpose to the followers.

During the interviews, evidence was provided to emphasise this expectation, and participants expressed their frustration regarding its absence within their respective organisations. Clarity of purpose is clustered around three sub themes enabling environment, goal orientation and knowledge orientation.

Enabling Environment

Clarity of Purpose was evident within organisations as authentic leaders tried to create an ecosystem that facilitated the attainment of their goals. Authentic leaders created this enabling environment by pursuing three key objectives. Firstly, authentic leaders strive to create a positive organisational climate by addressing the organisational's emotional, sociological, economic, racial and political tensions. These actively solved organisational challenges, as confirmed by Leaders B, and K below:

"I lead with them, understanding that there is much diversity in the world. There is need for inclusion and objectivity, so I lead from that angle (Leader B)."

"You will have ups and downs, highs and lows and everything, but in the mix of everything is being able to resolve issues, resolve conflicts (Leader K)."

Secondly, authentic leaders described the effective management of all types of resources with particular emphasis on human resources. Leader G implied that leaders could not build a wall around themselves and expect to be seen as authentic,

as accessibility facilitates closer interactions between leaders and followers. Also, Leader M suggests that a positive environment is about people and should be made for people to thrive. Further emphasising the intentionality of the process as expressed below:

"I create an environment that is very conducive for them. They can run to me to talk about anything and everything, so they are comfortable and able to do what they are supposed to, and the overall objectives are attained (Leader M)."

Finally, respondents argued that understanding the vision was critical to creating an enabling environment. This envisioning could be personal or organisational but would chart the path for achievements. This is aptly captured by Leader C. *"First, you follow your vision because you need to know where you are truly headed. You must have a purpose because with purpose comes direction."* Furthermore, Leader I and P reiterate the importance of providing direction within organisations as expressed below:

"I do some thinking and brainstorming by myself, and then I come up with a list of guidelines that help the project or the transaction or whatever it is we need to do as a team (Leader I)."

"I said from the beginning as an authentic leader I also believe that I should let people see the numbers. See where we are going and see what we must put in (Leader P)."

Despite the complex and challenging business terrain, these leaders demonstrated an apparent doggedness in pursuing their vision. As Leader, B attests to this during the recount of the most challenging experience as an authentic leader. The story describes an incident during one of the company's deliveries to a high profile regulatory agency in Nigeria. The authentic leader gave details that the receiving officer at the delivery location approached her staff to request that only 28,000 out of 33,000 litres of Automotive Gasoil (AGO) be discharged into their storage tank. So that the outstanding 5,000 litres could be sold in the black market and proceeds shared equally by all parties. Her staff refused and was almost lynched. Leader B described the experience, which highlighted the determination to follow through on an investigation, thereby reiterating the importance of providing direction:

"So, I guided him through. I started to make calls. I intended to take this up immediately, and everybody involved would be brought to book, and that was what we did. I asked her; please escalate this to trusted

management staff. This is what is going on in your company. We do not do it, so I am reporting this to you. She did not respond to me, and I still went ahead to, you know, finish up the case with our Union representatives (Leader B)."

This quote mirrors the resolute nature of authentic leaders in shaping the atmosphere within organisations.

Goal Orientation

Clarity of Purpose was evident through the goal orientation of the authentic leaders within the organisations. The respondents broadly defined goal orientation as the creation and pursuit of goals. All the respondents described goal orientation as critical to authentic leadership as it contributes to attaining clarity of purpose. The prominence of goal orientation in the findings of the study is not startling as authentic leaders such as Bill George, Mother Theresa, Eleanor Roosevelt, Martin Luther King, Jr., Warren Buffet, Herb Kelleher, and John Gardner, the former Secretary of Health, Education and Welfare are recognised within extant literature as high achievers (George, 2003; Avolio *et al.*, 2004; du Plessis and Boshoff, 2018c).

The respondents also emphasised being hardworking and steering stakeholders towards attaining goals and objectives as necessary within organisations. These goals were either personal or organisational, but the respondents described attaining personal and organisational goals in parallel, as they did not separate their roles from their person. This was evident in both the leaders' and followers' accounts. In describing the attitude to work, Leader E talks about his dreaming nature and how it affects his work:

"I always dream and say, oh God, but this is possible. Even if it is hard, right? Sometimes I do not realise how much work that is. I dream of something, and I ask why not really. And that is, even if it is a small thing at home, I always believe even when I come to work. So maybe it is that desire always to want to push and do something else and carry everybody along (Leader E)."

Other examples of the goal orientation of leaders are captured in Table 20 below. This table also captures the admiration that followers have for authentic leaders who are goal oriented.

Table 20 Selected responses on goal orientation

Respondent	Quotes
Leader M	<i>"If you are a leader and do not achieve results, you are just there."</i>
Leader K	<i>"To be a leader means that you have people you are leading, or they are following you to achieve a goal or objective. Ensure that people reach their full potential as you achieve the objective."</i>
Follower D2	<i>"When, they have a goal and objective. The way they go at it even if they don't even have the resources or don't understand how to achieve it, they just give it all their best."</i>
Follower N1	<i>"He has a conviction so regardless of how people come, I'll give you an instance. I remember when we wanted to get a license, and somebody kept telling him that we cannot get our platform license. The guy just came and said we're going to get this thing and we got that in three weeks ..."</i>
Follower N1	<i>"So, he gets it done. I don't know how he does it."</i>
Follower L2	<i>"They have that confidence that no matter what, just keep pushing. That success is an unending thing and whatever you have now is just a measure of success."</i>

In several instances, the respondents expressed their tenacity in achieving their goals, describing this action as getting things done. In driving the performance within organisations, authentic leaders became involved in activities. This meant actively doing the work with the staff. Leader, I states, *"They see me do many things, which is why they always want to exceed what I do to ensure that we win."* Echoing the above, Leader M rolls up their sleeves and describes it as *"getting dirty"*. In the discussions on goal orientation, the respondents argued that goals must be set and attained. Leaders A, and K emphasise working together to attain objectives:

"You give out instructions, and they would run with it. While you must micromanage some, you must become more detailed and specific about the goal with others. You should have a general overview of how you want them to achieve the goal (Leader A)."

"Guide them from the beginning to the end of the process for which you are trying to achieve your goal. (Leader K)."

The followers also described goal orientation, and it was deemed a key success indicator for authentic leadership. Follower O1 acknowledged that the goal orientation of Leader O contributed to the success of the organisation. These followers also maintained that the goal orientation of authentic leaders was underpinned by vision. In their descriptions, followers emphasised that having a big picture of what

is to be attained was crucial for authentic leaders as the future perspective of authentic leaders contributed extensively to the goal orientation in the present. For instance, Followers C1 and D2 describe goal orientation as a present attitude to goals underpinned by a consideration of a future as captured below:

“But as usual, they have seen something in the near future that this thing will address, so I have had to do things I did not get the meaning. I did not understand why I should do it then, you know, after maybe a year or two, I did see the impact (Follower C1).”

“They ensure they achieve the objective of the now without compromising the business needs of tomorrow (Follower D2).”

The followers also highlighted results and proof of success as evidence of the goal orientation of authentic leaders. It was described as a high achievement disposition by most of the respondents. These findings seemed interesting as the followers emphasised its importance and, in some instances, affirmed that it was proof that the organisation was pulling in the right direction, hence reassuring that the authentic leader was on the right path. For instance, Follower O1 states: *“The result and evidence from how the organisation is growing shows that something must be different. He is doing something right for the organisation to have this kind of results.”* Goal orientation is evidence of clarity of purpose, a crucial component of authentic leadership.

Knowledge Orientation

Clarity of purpose was evident through the knowledge orientation of the authentic leaders within the organisations. Respondents described knowledge orientation as experiences, skills, and technical knowledge of authentic leaders that reinforce clarity of purpose. This sub-theme was crucial to outperforming set standards within and outside the organisations. The sub-theme of knowledge orientation was distinct because it was described from two unique perspectives. Authentic leaders emphasised their reliance on their prior experiences and how it influenced their leadership approach in their current role. These leaders highlighted the importance of transferring knowledge to their subordinates as these facilitated the attainment of the goals.

These leaders acknowledged their limitations. They actively sought help and support from their mentors, colleagues, peers, and followers who had more expertise in the areas concerned. Leaders G, I, O, and P aptly captured these in the descriptions below:

“I firmly believe in being able to transfer knowledge and not think of yourself as the paragon of knowledge, right? So, what I try to do is to ensure that my team is brought up to speed(Leader G).”

“When you are sincere, and you know your capacity. Either you get help or the support you need (Leader I).”

“When you try something, it does not work out. You acknowledge that it did not work out, so you return to the drawing board and try another method (Leader O).”

“I lead based on my past experiences, and leadership is in different strata and areas (Leader P).”

The evidence indicated that followers linked authentic leadership to a knowledge oriented approach exhibited by leaders through their progressive nature and deep understanding of the business landscape. The responses revealed that the followers had this knowledge demand as clear expectations of their authentic leaders. Furthermore, followers attributed the lack of knowledge orientation to a lack of clarity of purpose and even described such leaders as inauthentic. These excerpts are captured in Table 21 below.

Table 21 Selected responses on knowledge orientation

Respondent	Quotes
Follower B1	<i>“She knows her onions and what is going. In all the industry she knows so much, and it is a function of her determination to always read to always learn.”</i>
Follower B2	<i>“They should have industry knowledge of what they’re doing.”</i>
Follower C2	<i>“He is extremely hardworking, knowledgeable and a goal getter.”</i>
Follower G1	<i>“If you are a leader, you ought to have come from a particular place and probably had experience in that area to lead someone else better.”</i>
Follower J1	<i>“An authentic leader should be knowledgeable. You do not need to be all round, but at least you should have a small amount of everything. You should have a small quantity of everything.”</i>
Follower I1	<i>“I expect an authentic leader to be highly cerebral.”</i>
Follower L2	<i>“Anytime they sit, you see them bringing their wealth of experience into giving the company a good direction.”</i>
Follower N1	<i>“I would say he has a hip pocket skill, and it is the ability to be good at what you do. So, regardless of how complex that issue is or how unsurmountable we think it is when you take it to the authentic leader, he can make that issue look so simple.”</i>

The followers further reiterated the importance of knowledge orientation, evidenced by the forward-thinking approach of authentic leaders. This was facilitated by the degree of industry knowledge that these leaders had of their sector. Follower D2 expects that authentic leaders should possess strong business acumen and the ability to identify and exploit opportunities. These followers stressed that profit was not the primary goal but the overall good of the organisation.

Making judgment calls was also crucial in assessing the knowledge orientation of authentic leaders. Followers confirmed that they evaluated the judgment calls and decisions of authentic leaders keenly. Follower O1 states that an evaluation is done of both the situation and the decision to determine whether the resulting outcome was a bad or good decision. Follower O1 describes this iterative process below:

“When they have to make a judgment call, and they take a decision. I evaluate that situation and the decision. How I rank it a good or a bad decision would change my perception of them. So, if in my ranking, that is not a good decision that should be taken at that point, or maybe even if they did nothing when they should have done something, that also impacts my decision on my perception of them. I think judgment at every point in time is what I am always evaluating (Follower O1).”

These followers also assessed the knowledge orientation of the authentic leaders from their decision making as Follower G2 suggests that a knowledgeable authentic leader would demonstrate competency in their roles and the selection of human resources. This would then lead to followers trusting the authentic leaders' future judgments. This is aptly captured when describing the decision making of authentic leaders by followers G2 and N1.

“So, based on the facts and data, this is the right thing for us to pursue now. This is why we are doing this thing. So, we could trust your judgment (Follower G2).”

“You need to have the skill to break up large projects into smaller tasks with timelines and deadlines. Otherwise, those projects will come back to haunt you. Those decisions you have made that have created this scope creep will come back to haunt you as an incompetent leader (Follower N1).”

Finally, all the respondents, both leaders and followers, emphasised the importance of the authentic leader's value driven actions as they facilitate the attainment of personal and organisational goals. These value driven actions represent engagements

or activities that are the result of thorough evaluations of their short and long term consequences. This aspect is fundamental as it reveals the knowledge oriented approach of authentic leaders, thereby enhancing the clarity of their leadership purpose.

6.2.2 Follower Development

The "follower development" component was one of the most articulated themes within the study. The authentic leaders and followers discussed shared sub themes, such as role modelling and empathy but diverged on the other subcomponents. All the authentic leaders expressed a desire to facilitate the growth of their employees, while the respondents described their growth as an expectation of authentic leadership. The section will focus on the leaders' responses, while follower descriptions will be captured in the next chapter. See Figure 24 for an overview of the theme and sub-themes.

Figure 24 Follower Development

The authentic leaders described follower development as a key component of authentic leadership, with all 16 authentic leaders stating that it was at the centre of their leadership. The interviews facilitated leader reflections as they linked follower development to affirming their true self in the organisational context. These leaders freely acknowledged that they were conscious and intentional as they sought to influence those around them.

This, in alignment with other components within the study, sustained authentic leadership. Through the descriptions embedded in the data, authentic leaders identified a cluster of five sub themes of role modelling, psychological capital, competency development, provision of support and empathy that served as a confirmation and a reminder of their leadership goals. See Table 22 below, capturing excerpts from authentic leaders.

Table 22 Excerpts on follower development

Leaders	Quotes
Leader E	<i>"Do you see them grow, do you see people come in and three four years later have significantly grown in whatever roles or responsibilities they are in. My job is to make sure the people that work directly for me succeed in what they do."</i>
Leader H	<i>"You lead by watching over the life of others to be sure that they are good, and they are doing well."</i>
Leader K	<i>"Guide them from beginning to the end of the process and being able to work through their weaknesses. Also being able to harness all their, skills or potentials and everything." "The greatest thing about living is number one being able to improve others."</i>

The data in Table 22 illustrates that follower development is considered a self imposed obligation by authentic leaders, and there is a commitment to ensuring its achievement, as evidenced by its frequent mention in discussions on authentic leadership. While broader discussions on the subcomponents of role modelling, psychological capital, competency development, support and empathy from the leader's perspective are offered below, a discussion on the sub themes of role modelling and relationship management from the follower's perspective are captured in section 7.2.2 in the next chapter.

Role modelling

Role modelling was identified as a strategy that authentic leaders employ to foster the development of their followers. To attain effectiveness in both their organisations and personal lives, authentic leaders embraced this technique. Role modelling was described as an experiential learning process for followers, enabling authentic leaders to showcase alternative approaches within a specific context or organisation. Role

modelling was described in terms of leadership positioning and development approaches. Regarding leadership positioning, this varied as authentic leaders described leading by example, leading by following, leading from the front and finally from the back. Leadership positioning was an interesting concept as these diverse positions had distinct implications. There are several examples of role modelling where leaders explicitly described leading by example, as highlighted by 5 leaders below:

“For me, leading is by example. When they have that feeling, then they give you 100% on the task or the project (Leader A).”

“So, what has worked for me is leading by example. I do not lead as a boss (Leader F).”

“Trying to inspire, motivate and lead by example for the direct team that reports to me (Leader G).”

“Wow, I lead by example. I lead with respect. I lead with love. I lead by showing people what to do and doing it myself (Leader H).”

“I try to lead by example, which I think is key. If you are leading and your actions say otherwise, then that’s not the right direction to go (Leader K).”

All the authentic leaders acknowledged that leading by example facilitated positive outcomes within the organisation as role modelling resulted in effectiveness. Firstly, authentic leaders argued that leading by example motivated their employees to action, as role modelling provided a reference point for the followers. It also demonstrated to the followers that whatever the leader's expectation was, it could be attained as the leader charted the path and walked through it personally. In terms of leadership positioning, authentic leaders described diverse positions in their role modelling. For instance, Leader M stated that she leads from the front, which enables her to empower her team, unlocking the achievement mentality in them as captured below:

“I lead from the front. I lead by rolling my sleeves and showing my team how to do it. I show that I can do it to make them realise that anyone can do it (Leader M).”

Similarly, leading by following and leading from behind are highlighted by 2 authentic leaders where it is argued that this position provides affirmation to the followers. Leader E aptly describes this:

“They see that I am trying to support them to succeed, and they put in what is required. You know, the kind of drive to achieve the overall goal. I will say I lead from behind, rather than in front most of the time, right where I try and push the people (Leader E).”

Mentoring was also emphasised as a developmental approach by 6 authentic leaders. These respondents discussed its role, impact on their leadership journey and growth in their followers. This is highlighted in the excerpt below:

“I started mentoring her, and then she moved on. So, a promotion that she had lost for two years. She got it back. And all she wanted to do was to say thank you, and for me, that is a beautiful feeling when you know that you have impacted someone’s life (Leader F).”

These authentic leaders also valued mentoring, and the findings reveal that authentic leaders also require support. Especially during periods of uncertainty as these leaders seek to share their perspectives and approaches with others who can remind them of who they are and what they represent as they navigate through complex scenarios. These leaders stated that their mentors reminded them that they were not the first to walk that path and provided reassurance that their goals were achievable. This relationship with their mentors was mirrored in authentic leaders' relations with their followers, which facilitated follower development.

Psychological Capital

Psychological capital was described in various ways, such as giving people hope, being optimistic, building resilience, and developing efficacy. All the respondents discussed the psychological capital subcomponent of authentic leadership. Authentic leaders emphasised its importance to their followers and highlighted its role in their follower's mental wellbeing, mainly how it affects the organisational outcomes. Psychological capital was described as the intangible but evoked feelings and emotions that enabled followers to thrive, especially during challenging times. Followers acknowledged this as they admitted that psychological capital helped them to succeed. In the excerpt below, follower C1 affirms that hope is critical as it creates a glimpse of the preferred future in the mind of the followers, while reminding them that their contributions will make the aspirations or dreams a reality.

“Make people understand that there is hope and their service is not in vain. It is ensuring that people have hope that I am doing something, and it is worthwhile (Follower C1).”

Furthermore, the respondents also identified resilience as necessary as it provided staying power for authentic leaders in the face of resistance within or outside the organisation. This resilience, demonstrated by authentic leaders, became evident in their followers over time. The data revealed that resilience was critical to successful authentic leadership, and Leader N below adequately describes resilience, highlighting its importance across a range of activities below:

“You must have that staying power because when projects are launched, you know there will be pushback. Sometimes either by factors you can control or factors you cannot control. Then your ability as a leader to stay the course without being discouraged is crucial (Leader N).”

The insights obtained from the thick descriptions revealed that efficacy was critical for psychological capital. Authentic leaders had to possess self-efficacy to stay true to themselves and remain authentic despite internal and external exigencies. This facilitated follower development as followers began to trust in their capacities. Finally, optimism was highlighted, as a driving force for both authentic leaders and followers. Optimism breeds confidence to tackle challenges and exploit opportunities. Leader P described confidence as the "conqueror's backbone", which provides reassurance for followers. In the account, conquerors are authentic leaders. Follower N1 states that confidence allows authentic leaders push boundaries with no room for doubts from internal and external stakeholders. This, in turn, serves as inspiration for followers and stimulates their development.

Competency Development

Authentic leaders revealed that one of their key functions was facilitating the development of their followers' competencies. This development was well rounded as leaders went beyond skills development to other areas as required by the followers. The authentic leaders, though, focused on developing capacity for the jobs, confirmed that the needs of the followers determined the development focus. This subcomponent will be described broadly under skills development and other areas which capture

competency developments that are not work related. With skills development concentrating on the competencies necessary to deliver on the organisational objectives. This was a continuous task and perhaps never completed, as detailed by Leader K who maintained that ensuring individuals fulfil their full potential is an ongoing obligation of the leader.

The competency development of the followers was fostered by inspiring them to seek new opportunities. In certain cases, these leaders recommended followers for roles they had no experience on or possessed the expertise to fulfil. It was the potential that authentic leaders sought to harness, which was done in a safe and secure environment created by them. This approach enabled followers to embrace challenges and eventually succeed at new responsibilities as emphasised below:

“I believe in people, and I empower people to deliver. I help people fulfil their potential (Leader D).”

“It is all about what you can deliver and that you are aware that if you push, you know there is somebody at the back who will push you further (Leader E).”

“I would always delegate to subordinates to take on projects, and the reason I do that is just so that it is a learning process for subordinates, for them to acquire skills, the opportunity for them to make mistakes, for them to fail and to come to try again (Leader N).”

These leaders further explained that the development of followers in other areas of life was critical, and this growth seemed to fulfil their followers' inner and personal aspirations, while also seeking to attain external goals in parallel. Leader P described this as mental empowerment, which breeds growth in the followers' lives.

“I empower people mentally. You know, to move your point from point A to point B. If I can see that change, if I can see that growth, then I will say that I have succeeded. Letting you know that life is a seed and that we all should live a life of impact. (Leader P).”

The followers also acknowledged the efforts made by authentic leaders in facilitating competency development.

Support

The subtheme of "support" captures the authentic leaders' intentionality to ensure the attainment of organisation, personal and followers' goals simultaneously. These leaders described their commitment by ensuring that team members were never left

without support, regardless of the complexity of the situation. This support was described as an aspirational goal like attaining organisational objectives. Authentic leaders admitted that they never left or intended to leave anyone behind alone. The notion was consistent across all the accounts of authentic leaders. See below excerpts from leader D and N:

“And I believe in people, and I help people fulfil their potential (Leader D).”

“Like just getting things done without leaving anyone behind, and when I say anyone, I mean it takes into consideration the objectives of all the expectations of all the stakeholders (Leader N).”

This support also encompassed encouraging followers to reach and attain their full potential as Leader E states, “Supporting those that work for you to achieve their best.” This support highlights the actionable part of leadership. It involves the identification of inadequacies and managing the person's capacity wholly in an organisational context. Leader K states: *“Being able to work through their weaknesses, manage their weaknesses, and manage their strengths as we try to achieve the goal.”* Clearly, these leaders understand the differences in capacity and people but remained a pillar of support during the stable, unstable and complex times within the organisation.

These authentic leaders also emphasised the need to pursue the attainment of goals with their follower's side by side until progress is made or objective is achieved. Hence, followers always felt supported during the process, which was particularly beneficial during times of difficulty. Leader I stated that support is provided on the job and support is actively delivered to the follower that requires it promptly. Leaders F and I also reiterated their commitment to supporting followers. See excerpts below:

“I was in it with them when we were going down; we are going down together and going up... We are going up together. (Leader F).”

“I always follow up to see through that the work is done and, in any capacity, and I can help, I come in (Leader I).”

Furthermore, the support produced tangible results as Leader E disclosed that when the followers experienced support from him, they were more committed, which benefited all the stakeholders. This is captured in the excerpt below:

"And because many people see that, I am trying to support them to succeed people put in what is required for the overall goal (Leader E)."

Overall, Leader F concluded that support was critical, as it was passion driven from within to support followers. The final sub theme of empathy from the leader's perspective will be discussed in the next section.

Empathy

Both authentic leaders and their followers reiterated the sub theme of empathy. The respondents described empathy as a conscious awareness to the emotions of others. This also involved experiencing those feelings, whether it was a current or experience with the owner of the emotion. Authentic leaders described empathy as a key component of their leadership, with several leaders describing this as an underpinning pillar. Authentic leaders described this as necessary, mainly because these leaders recognised the value of humanity within organisations. This suggests an inherent hierarchy of stakeholders led by authentic leaders, with followers positioned high in this hierarchy. As these stakeholders drive all other aspects of the organisation. Authentic leaders B, F, D, G, M, and O discussed the importance of empathy in their descriptions, with leader M stating that empathy is a precursor to effectiveness: *"I will say empathy because you are dealing with human beings. You must understand the factors driving every human being on your team, trying to achieve the objectives with you. You must put them in a position where you can get the best out of them (Leader M)."*

Leader B states that empathy is consciously brought into perspective as decisions are made within the organisation. This leader asserts that she leads with compassion and empathy. Similarly, these authentic leaders highlighted empathy as an essential ability of an authentic leader, with Leader D stating that it is the most important skill. The respondents described empathy as a connection point between authentic leaders and followers, accelerating the development of follower commitment within organisations.

6.2.3 Relational Transparency

The theme of relational transparency was salient across descriptions by both authentic leaders and followers. This component was described as the most tangible aspect of authentic leadership. The component captured the intricate dynamics of the interactions between an authentic leader and a single follower, as well as multiple followers. Thus, respondents implied that authentic leaders could not experience relational transparency without followers. The respondents described relational transparency as the open communication of one's feelings and facts with others as captured below:

"I know the things that I exemplify and that is what I project as well with my team, try to be as transparent and as relational as possible (Leader B)".

"You know one to be very transparent right in what I do? OK, now transparent in the sense that you know whatever I am doing. Everybody sees what the purpose is for or what the objective is. You know, so transparent that's one, and I tried to communicate what I am doing (Leader E)".

This component places a focus on interpersonal relationships. In sum, relational transparency comes to life and becomes evident during leader-follower exchanges. The participants offered explanations on the sub themes of the component. The sub themes within this context are vulnerability, transparency and learning orientation.

Vulnerability

The respondents stated that authentic leadership is characterised by vulnerability. Both the authentic leaders' and followers' emphasised vulnerability in their description of relational transparency. Only authentic leaders were expected to be vulnerable during the leader and follower interactions. Also, when probed on instances where they felt most authentic in the leadership journey, respondents mainly highlighted vulnerable incidents, broadening the denotative meaning of vulnerability. This is because vulnerability was described as tangible evidence of the leaders' self awareness. Furthermore, it was portrayed as the capacity to be open and exposed with followers and not perceive it as a sign of weakness but strength as it demonstrates the leader's knowledge of themselves.

This vulnerability is not a helpless state of emotional exposure by the leader, but a confidence laced with genuine emotion. Leader G suggests that attaining a delicate balance between exposing one's inadequacy and leading concurrently is critical, as stated, *"Being able to speak up and get help when you need help and being able to be assertive at the same time. That is being vulnerable."* This vulnerability breeds trust for the leaders and affirms that leaders recognise their limitations, a term not often associated with leadership, as aptly captured by Leader G below:

"The ability to remain vulnerable and not see vulnerability as a weakness. Being able to be true to who you are because that is where you gain the highest level of respect. So not being afraid to be vulnerable, and when I say vulnerable, not in the loose sense of vulnerability that connotes weakness but being able to recognise that you are not the receptacle of knowledge and other people know certain things or do certain things better than you (Leader G)."

The respondents described the portrayal of vulnerability in four ways, firstly, by being open about experiences, whether personal or professional; secondly, by showing love, trust and respect to others; also, by self disclosure, especially during difficult times. For instance, Leader I states, *"When you are under pressure, things happen, and then you know some people try to cover everything. However, I always express myself."* The evidence within the data suggests that being open about experiences was crucial to being perceived as vulnerable. Openness about experiences also included acknowledging inadequacies that were core in Leader E's leadership. This openness extended to the organisation's performance, where followers were given access to the financial records to monitor its development and suggest initiatives and ideas that would benefit the organisation.

Like to all the interviews with the authentic leaders, Leader D was asked if she was an authentic leader. In response, Leader D confidently asserted her authenticity; however, additional questions were asked to clarify the primary criterion she used to reach this conclusion. Specifically, the focus was on illuminating the factors that influenced her introspective evaluation of her leadership. When confronted with this question, she offered the explanation below:

“As soon as you asked me, I just checked myself and realised that I was ok to be vulnerable, right? It was ok to share my story of how I became who I am today. My journey to where I am today ordinarily would have been something I would have struggled with before. Thus, for me, I was comfortable going back and explaining or telling you how...I was comfortable in my skin (Leader D).”

The respondents also described vulnerability as showing love, trust and respect, as these are emotional laden responses, especially within an organisational context. These leaders and followers described these as essential in building an organisational context where authentic leadership thrives. Leader L states that authentic leadership require love, trust and respect, and that is how the phenomenon has been conceptualised. The respondents also described self disclosure as a key part of demonstrating vulnerability. Leader I states that her authentic leadership journey has been a roller coaster, and rather than cover its aspects, she expresses her fears, concerns and excitement.

It allows followers engage with these leaders, disregarding the bureaucracy of hierarchy to offer assistance within organisations. Followers stated that vulnerability demonstrated the leader's acceptance that they are also limited in knowledge and capability. This increases a leader's capacity as they can seek the help required in any environment. Follower E1 further describes this vulnerability as an action laced emotion where authentic leaders actively develop from inadequacies, as captured by Follower E1 below:

“Vulnerability in sharing things like personality tests and getting everyone else to do a personality test that displays your strengths and your weaknesses. Telling us his strengths and weaknesses and how he has worked with his own team to identify where his blind spots are so that people understand him (Follower E1).”

Leader C also recommends that authentic leaders, irrespective of their achievements, be vulnerable as it keeps them connected to the reality of themselves, situations, followers, organisational context, and the wider environment. As this leader states, the authentic leaders remain fundamentally the person before the role, accomplishments, failures, and challenges.

Transparency

The sub theme of transparency had high saliency in the descriptions provided by the respondents. This transparency was open to scrutiny where the purpose or objectives of an action are perceivable, visible or observable to stakeholders. The leaders explained that they do not have one leadership approach but are flexible enough to account for contextual variables. Hence, transparency becomes critical as followers can assess each action's value independently. This is described by Leaders A, B and E below:

“So, you just want to be as transparent as possible when you are relating with your people and when you are relating with every other person. You balance the process where everybody is aware of what role they are playing. And what is expected of them (Leader A).”

“I know what I exemplify, which I also project with my team. I try to be as transparent and relational as possible (Leader B).”

“I am one to be very transparent in what I do. Transparent in the sense that you know whatever I am doing. Anyone who works for me has a sense of where we are going and clear transparency on performance. There is no hidden agenda, so feedback is instant (Leader E).”

Respondents suggest that transparency is primarily about the leaders and how they communicate with their followers. In describing transparency, several followers highlighted the lack of transparency as a key indicator of inauthentic leadership. These followers acknowledged that authentic leaders were also flawed and invariably not perfect. However, transparency was important for clarity as depicted in Table 23 below, capturing excerpts from respondents.

Table 23 Excerpts on transparency

Excerpts	Emphasis
<i>“There is a thin line between being transparent with me and being mindful of not saying anything disparaging about her own leader (Follower B1).”</i>	Clarity
<i>“She will not hide anything from you, and that makes it so simple. Everything is plain (Follower B2).”</i>	Clarity
<i>“So, when you are transparent, you let one know that yes, nobody no one is perfect. Let people see (Follower G1).”</i>	Clarity

Followers emphasised the importance of transparency, highlighting the implicit understanding that authentic leaders are not flawless beings. However, a more

comprehensive discussion of how followers interpret transparency is presented in chapter seven.

Learning Orientation

The respondents described learning orientation as a subcomponent of relational transparency. These respondents stated that learning orientation was a crucial outlook that authentic leaders and followers possess and demonstrate in their interactions. The learning orientation contributes to business continuity and progression, where individuals were groomed to handle organisational complexities as they arose. The respondents described this learning orientation as possessing a growth mindset, speaking up and being lifelong learners, respectively. The growth mindset is described as a leader's mental state concerning advancement. This was critical as the positive mindset allowed authentic leaders to thrive and develop. In particular, the growth mindset enabled authentic leaders to obtain value from criticisms and corrections as issues were viewed holistically. The respondents argued that the growth mindset required active listening, contributing to an optimistic outlook despite the complexities inherent in the leadership role. For instance, Leader D states below:

“The right mindset is the base for anything. You can build on a positive and a growth mindset because you think it is fertile ground. One that is positive and is willing to take criticisms and learnings. It is open to other perspectives and other ways of thinking. If you have that, you will be amazed at the growth you would experience (Leader D).”

With the growth mindset, authentic leaders possessed a heightened ability to address challenges within their environment. The growth mindset facilitates learning as the mindset pushes for self development. Furthermore, respondents suggested that the growth mindset allowed leaders identify and exploit learning opportunities. This contributes to the second subtheme of being a life longer learner.

Respondents indicated that being open to feedback proved that an authentic leader was a lifelong learner. For instance, Follower O1 stated, *“She would always ask line reports or subordinates to give honest feedback without fear.”* Leader C argued that the

positive approach to lifelong learning emerged from self reflection. This leader stated that reflection precedes continuous learning. Finally, in terms of speaking out, respondents defined relational transparency as a process in which leaders were open to acknowledging their weaknesses and seeking help when needed. These authentic leaders were unafraid of their emotions, feelings, and perceptions.

6.2.4 Self Awareness

All 46 respondents highlighted self awareness as a component of AL, with some further asserting this component as a precursor to other components in the study. Self awareness was described as a deliberate assessment of one's capabilities where knowledge does not bring pride or shame. However, such knowledge becomes a valuable tool in dealing with everyday complexities. The importance and role of this self awareness had high saliency in the explanations offered by the respondents, as captured in the excerpt of Leader C *"You are just one person, so it is important that when you stand before the mirror, even though you are self-aware. That self awareness is not one that makes you arrogant."*

The discussion on self awareness was intricately linked to the descriptions of the value system, which underpins their leadership. These respondents highlighted that self awareness emerged from understanding their beliefs and values, shaping their leadership. As Leader D, suggests: *"I am very aware of my strength. I am very aware of the things that I believe in. I have led people based on my personal beliefs and values"*. Self awareness captured the essence of who they are and how it cuts across different roles. They argued that a genuine understanding of these variables was beneficial and that remaining true to these variables facilitated authentic leadership. For instance, Leader D and N affirmed these below:

"First, the road to being authentic starts with being self-aware. I went to a business that required transformation. I went into an environment that was new to me. In doing that, I became more aware of who I was. I became more aware of my strengths and weaknesses, and once I understood them, I began to embrace who I was, and in embracing that, that made me more confident and comfortable with myself. I was then able to learn from the lessons (Leader D)."

“I say self awareness; you must be confident of your capacity and ability. If you are self-aware, you are knowledgeable. You know your strengths, and you try to amplify that without feeling any threat from anybody. That is a good thing (Leader N).”

Social awareness was also highlighted in the discussions with respondents suggesting that self awareness extends beyond the leader to include the external environment and the players within it as stated below:

“I think what is important to this is authentic leaders need to have an evident sense of self. There needs to be a level of self awareness and absolute clarity on their strengths and their weaknesses (Follower E1).”

“She knows about you. She is very aware of the goals and is able to cascade those to the team (Follower E2).”

“These people are emotionally intelligent. Which means that they are very self-aware (Follower I1).”

“Should be self-aware of things that are going on in our environment (Follower M1).”

Overall, respondents described self awareness as the capacity to introspect and evaluate one's own strengths and faults, while being open to receiving feedback and enhancing interpersonal relationships. Furthermore, respondents identified the component's sub components of self regulation and emotional intelligence discussed in the following sections.

Self-regulation

Self regulation is described as the use of self knowledge. This self regulation allows authentic leaders to respond appropriately to changing demands of the environment while remaining true to their beliefs and aspirations. For instance, Leader G established that self regulation facilitated a delineation from the self to feel the pulse and understand the conditions of the immediate environment as captured below:

“So self-regulating in the sense that I’m able to step out of myself and understand the pulse of my immediate environment understand the human aspect, understand why people are doing what they’re doing just so that I’m able to manage my expectation of the people (Leader G).”

The respondents described self reflection as a tool for achieving self regulation as captured in the excerpt of Leader G: *So, when it comes to self awareness you know that’s there then one aspect of my life is using my ability to self regulate and self reflect”. This required that authentic leaders step out of themselves, which enabled them to evaluate*

complex situations adequately, often leading to better judgement and decision making.

Emotional Intelligence

A subtheme of self awareness was emotional intelligence, where leaders consciously tried to build relationships of trust with their followers. Emotional intelligence became salient in their descriptions as authentic leaders were required to have a thorough understanding of the organisational intricacies at both a personal and professional level as stated in the excerpts below:

“An authentic leader would have to possess a number of qualities., one of which certainly has to be emotional intelligence (Follower I1).”

“Carry people along, the ability to direct to read feelings, to know what is going on with the team, (FollowerI2).”

“Number one is emotional intelligence (Follower O2).”

Followers revealed that emotional intelligence is a crucial quality of an authentic leader. For these respondents, self awareness extended beyond understanding who they were as authentic leaders to include an understanding of what was going on in the lives of their followers, especially the first, second, and third reporting lines. Emotional intelligence was also crucial for authentic leaders as self awareness extended beyond competencies, values and beliefs to include an awareness of their emotional state and how it could impact their leadership. Leader G described emotional intelligence as a skill, with Leader D suggesting that it was an essential capability an authentic leader must possess. This was also confirmed by Leader G and Follower C2, suggesting that a high degree was vital because emotional intelligence enable authentic leaders to own up to their mistakes. A key indicator of self awareness.

6.2.5 Internalised Moral Perspective

The respondents described internalised moral perspective as the outlook of authentic leaders shaped by internal exigencies rather than external influences, consequently emphasising the role of the moral compass within authentic leadership. These respondents discussed their childhood and highlighted the values ingrained in them

at a young age as their parents, church and environment instilled values in them even before they knew who they were as captured by the respondents below:

“So, values grow from inside out. It is something you have in you and your every behaviour of yours reflects what is contained inside of you. So, it started quite frankly, with my parents long before I was born. Inherent in the family has been the tradition of maintaining the right values and the right ethos, with morality being the benchmark of our behavior in the family (Leader C)”.

“You know family values obviously had a big role to play in my own personal values, so I had the opportunity of watching my parents. You know, live their lives watching my mom, you know the things she said the things she did. You know and that to a very large extent shaped me and I am not going to also discount the fact that I was brought up in a Christian home and I have had the opportunity of hearing and reading about certain women you know in the Bible and those for me were the kind of people I wanted to shape my life to be like (Leader G)”.

They possessed these values from childhood, and these values would often emerge when they encountered complex situations and were unsure of how to proceed. The respondents explained that their value system guided them as they navigated organisational difficulties. It is analogous to a latent seed ready to sprout in complexities. This internalised perspective had taken almost a lifetime to be integrated into the authentic leader's life but became evident when needed. The respondents used the two perspectives of being value driven and being unbiased to describe internalised moral perspectives in their accounts.

Value driven

Being value driven was a recurring theme that permeated all the descriptions provided by all the respondents. The responses revealed that authentic leaders upheld their commitments without fear of backlash or favour because their values influenced them. As justified by follower E1, the integrity comes with courage *“You need to be a person of integrity. You need to be courageous as well because integrity requires courage.”* The followers established that a lack of integrity destroyed hard work within organisations. Follower D1 also affirmed that integrity inspired confidence and belief in the leaders' guidance. Respondents took considerable time articulating the influences that shaped their values and spoke coherently about how these various

impacts combined to act as a compass for morality in their personal and professional lives.

Actively defending their values was also evident in the discussions on internalised moral perspective. Which encapsulates doing what is appropriate for oneself, one's followers, the organisation, and society. This may not imply total agreement with all stakeholders, but it does infer upholding their values regardless of how difficult it may be.

Unbiased

The followers emphasised that successful authentic leadership depends on the leader's objectivity. Fairness was highlighted by followers where evidence of it must be apparent in decision making, and treatment of employees. Follower B1 maintains that these leaders are very vocal. These leaders, like Follower B1's description believe in themselves, their vision, and their people and are willing to stand by these convictions regardless of the criticism they may face. They trust their abilities, their vision, and their followers. The respondents described being unbiased as essential to authentic leadership. Follower H1, described authentic leadership as a leadership approach that is not biased, especially regarding religion in a multi ethnic country like Nigeria. Where religion is a divisive tool that stirs sentiments amongst the populace.

6.2.6 Concern for People

The data revealed that concern for people is also a key component of AL, as described by all the respondents. Like follower development, the concern for people component was perceived by the authentic leaders as an obligation. At the same time, it was described as an expectation from authentic leaders by their followers. Authentic leaders and followers emphasised team focus and the 360 perspectives of followers as a critical subcomponent of the concern for people. Team focus was described as bringing people to work and winning together by the respondents. These two sub themes of team focus, and the 360 perspectives of followers are discussed below.

Team Focused

Authentic leaders described team focus as the joint effort and concentration of the followers towards a shared objective. It is further defined as the tendency of a group to cooperate, align their efforts, and strive towards a single goal. To attain team focus, authentic leaders actively brought followers together at each opportunity emphasising collaboration within an organisational context. Leaders A and J acknowledged that being team focused also required problem solving. This is because, contentions within organisations are identified and resolved by the leaders, which in turn facilitate leadership effectiveness. Leader I described team focus as an implicit understanding that the authentic leader fulfils an additional role.

Furthermore, authentic leaders affirmed that being team focused must be experienced and accepted by the followers as this foster seamless collaboration within the team.

Leader J describes this below:

“First, I can bring my team together. Where there are departmental issues, I can resolve them. I can make them work together and realise that we can only win as a team, not as individuals. When they are disagreements between individuals or characters are clashing. I am able to recognise that, speak to them and let them understand that we are here to work and not to bring each other down (Leader J).”

Leader D also highlighted that she assessed her ability to galvanise her team members in a new role to evaluate her authenticity in the role and reflect on her authentic leadership. In assessing her authentic leadership, Leader D examined her ability to inspire her team members in a new role. Interestingly, Leader G suggested that being team focused allow the team and followers to experience authentic leadership, as they were more likely to relate with you and collaborate more. These respondents described collaboration as evidence of being team focused.

360 Perspective of followers

The 360 perspective of followers was described as a subcomponent of concern for people by authentic leaders. The 360 perspectives encompassed concern for the follower's career, personal life, passion and wellbeing. Blurring the line between the follower's professional and personal life. Authentic leaders characterised followers as wholistic individuals, whose roles intersect, suggesting that these ensure that their

concern for followers extends to all facets of their lives, transcending mere professional roles within organisations to a 360 degree perspective. Leader A states that:

"A follower wants to know that you are concerned about them, and you do not see them as a tool or an asset just to get to get your objective; they want to know that you are invested in their lives and when they have that feeling they give you 100% on the task or project (Leader A)."

Followers argued that the 360 perspectives of followers' impact growth, implying that authentic leaders are not docile but actively seek to know their follower's professional and personal goals. This demonstrated that authentic leaders had concern for their followers, and as an outcome, followers experienced satisfaction in their personal and professional lives.

6.3 Factors that inspire authentic leadership development

In addressing the factors that inspire authentic leadership, the questions were directed at only the authentic leaders as the study sought to unpack the experiences that inspired this development. The critical incident technique enabled authentic leaders to reflect on their experiences in response to the interview questions. Interestingly, all the leaders stated that they had never questioned the driving force behind their leadership approach.

These authentic leaders were questioned about what motivated them to become authentic, when it began and if a key event initiated this choice. The authentic leaders responded to the second research question by identifying four factors that inspired their authentic leadership development namely, family structure, belief and conviction, leadership, and legacy. These factors are presented in the subsequent four sub sections with respondents indicating the timeframe of when these initially emerged.

6.3.1 Family Structure

The authentic leaders identified the family structure as a key factor that inspired authentic leadership development. These responses brought to the fore the impact of familial relationships and family like dynamics on authentic leadership development. In the description of this factor, two perspectives became evident in the descriptions offered by authentic leaders, firstly, the position occupied by these leaders in the family and the roles and responsibilities that plagued these positions. In describing the role of the birth position in the family, authentic leaders argued that their leadership approach and attitude towards their leadership responsibilities was influenced by their birth position. It was fascinating to uncover that most of the authentic leaders were either the first children in their families or the first of their gender, either male or female, in their families. Five of the authentic leaders were firstborn, and four were the first male or female children. For instance, Leader N and P affirmed that their positions as the firstborns exposed them to leadership very early in life, with their family background contributing to the process, as captured in the excerpts below from Leaders N and P:

“I am the firstborn, so some of the ways I lead will come from how I grew up from my parents (Leader N).”

“I am the first child of three girls... Of course, you know how it is for a girl from a girl family, so that is where I found myself (Leader P).”

The inherent hierarchy associated with the birth order meant that the expectations were different and higher, with a sense of high order purpose placed on the shoulders of the first child. This familial positioning contributed to the roles and responsibilities inadvertently assigned to these birth orders and positioning within the family. These respondents indicated that their first leadership role began in their homes and families. For instance, Leader P’s experience influenced her leadership as captured below.

“I was with my dad’s family, and my mom was not working. The man felt the woman should not be working, but over time, you find out the man is stating that nobody was contributing. Nobody is helping him, so I grew up hearing that (Leader P).”

The words and actions of Leader P's father were inconsistent, especially when it came to working and providing for the family. This lack of consistency from her father towards her mother's financial capability inspired Leader P's authentic leadership development.

The second evident perspective focused on the responsibilities plaguing their families' different birth orders. Regarding these roles and responsibilities, child orders are subject to different expectations and older ones are typically expected to watch over and care for their younger siblings. This elevated level of responsibility was initially viewed as a burden during their younger years but gradually became an integral part of their identity as they matured. This sense of duty over time is now seen as a part of who they are and their essence. Leader B claims that her upbringing significantly impacted her mentality as these initial responsibilities produced positive outcomes. These leaders went on to lead in different areas and times before their careers even began. Reiterating this claim, Leader P confirmed, she found her inspiration when she was growing up, as described below:

“So, I think responsibilities also pushed that on me because people left many things for me to handle. OK, I trust you to be the monitor, the class monitor. Next thing you need to be perfect. The community service prefect. From that, you, an internal club Vice president. From that, you are out of school and leading higher educator trainers; I think those are the things that inspired me the more (Leader P).”

Leader P stated that she is the first girl, and where she is from in Anambra state within Nigeria, the first girl is automatically like the first child. Consequently, the most responsible. This is further explicated in the excerpt below:

“It started when I was a child. My mom made me responsible for my younger ones when she came home. I am the first girl and have an older brother, but they burdened me. It was also a responsibility for me. So that burden made me grow fast and taught me the life of responsibility (Leader P).”

In conclusion, factors such as birth order, hierarchy, parental expectations, and responsibilities influenced the family structure that inspired authentic leadership development.

6.3.2 Beliefs and Conviction

Authentic leaders identified beliefs and convictions as critical factors in inspiring authentic leadership development. The factor was described as principles that guide a leader's decision making, shaping their priorities and actions. All 16 authentic leaders emphasised the importance of their beliefs in fostering authentic leadership development. Authentic leaders acknowledged that the beliefs, they were exposed to as children and those they have picked up along the road through followers, subordinates, organisations, and environments have influenced them. These authentic leaders were fiercely committed to their early ideals and demonstrated a clear understanding of these principles in the account by Leader F below:

“My values would be the most important thing to me. The value is to do the right thing, sometimes the right thing might not be what everybody thinks is correct (Leader F).”

These values are deeply ingrained and reflect the leaders' beliefs. When asked the most important factor they considered, when assessing if they were authentic leaders or not, these leaders also mentioned values. For instance, Leader G was clear about her values as the most critical parameter in this decision. Authentic leaders also noted that religious convictions played a significant role in authentic leadership development.

6.3.3 Leadership

Authentic leadership development was also said to be primarily influenced by exposure to leadership. It is interesting to note that authentic leadership development was sparked by both effective and ineffective leadership. For effective leadership, authentic leaders commenced by describing their early exposure to leadership, which encompassed their experiences with parents and positive encounters with their initial supervisors. Leaders B and P discussed their relationships with their parents and how these experiences inspired authentic leadership development. For other leaders within the study, it was the exposure to exceptional leaders, either personally or through reading about them in books. For instance, describing personal encounters, Leader I claimed that she was encouraged to become authentic by her bosses, while

Leader G acknowledged that certain female leaders inspired authentic leadership development. These leaders provided reassurance and encouragement that the leadership approach had value and was beneficial, as captured below:

“Well, I would not say it was an inspiration. It was just the way I was taught when I started work. I do not know how to explain it but from the beginning of my career. I was encouraged by my bosses at the time to be authentic (Leader I).”

Two authentic leaders M and P highlighted the role of reading books from leadership authors. These respondents established that other leaders have influenced their thought process and inspired authentic leadership development in them. With some leaders ensuring they met with these authors to assess their initial judgements of being authentic leaders. For instance, Leader P travelled to Dubai to meet John Maxwell as described below:

“I am a John Maxwell fan. I met him in Dubai. We went for training where he trained us, and I had a picture of John Maxwell with me. You can see he exudes leadership. It shows that you can get things done without it just being a natural leader, right? So, I was also inspired by John Maxwell’s life and the examples he gave us (Leader M).”

These participants expanded the discourse surrounding effective leadership by highlighting that while other authentic leaders served as positive sources of inspiration, they still remained self aware of their own identities and capabilities. So, the goal was not to mimic or copy the authentic leaders but to evaluate and embrace new strategies appropriate for their leadership.

In contrast to effective leadership, ineffective leadership also inspired authentic leadership development. Leader A gave a fascinating account of how, in her words, "bad leadership" inspired her authentic leadership development early in her career. She gave an example of a manager who turned into a bad role model, exemplifying what she would not be as a leader. Because of the leader's actions, she was able to recognise her ineffective leadership approach and worked to change them to become the kind of leader she aspired to be, as stated below:

“Sometimes you must see something bad, which helps you improve. Like I said in my consulting days, I was on 30 different engagements. You see different seniors leading in different ways. You see the bad ones, and you are like, I do not want to be this kind of leader (leader A).”

Furthermore, Leader F's authentic leadership development was inspired by her team's disgruntled response to her leadership. The followers' responses were described as a clear indication of failed leadership, and they motivated her to improve herself and her team. She acknowledged that, *“Failure and seeing very disgruntled people made me a better authentic leader. When I saw the group of people, it looked like there was no more hope. I think that encouraged and changed me.”*

Similarly, the respondents depicted how feedback on their leadership journey served as inspiration for their development as authentic leaders. Both organised and unstructured feedback was provided. In some cases, followers' opinions were sought, and in some instances, followers offered this feedback voluntarily. Leader M received personal feedback from a famous leadership coach, which inspired her development. In showcasing leadership feedback, Leaders D and O stated that adaptation was a part of the process when their adventure began. As a result, their development has been a journey from the beginning and is currently ongoing. This entailed experimenting with several leadership attitudes to determine which one best suited who they were and what they stood for rather than trying to replicate the leadership of others.

6.3.4 Legacy

The desire to leave a legacy also inspired authentic leadership development in most authentic leaders. These respondents described legacy as a deliberate attempt to create a lasting impact across time. These leaders had an inherent desire to leave something that would outlive them. In their descriptions, three key mechanisms inspired the desire to leave a legacy; crucibles, trigger events and personal fulfilment which in turn inspired their authentic leadership development. For these authentic leaders, crucibles were described as events that stirred a desire to change the existing order or how things were being done. Authentic leaders desired to improve situations and were driven by the benefits of change and the possibilities of a better alternative. In

fostering change, authentic leaders sought to live transparently and ensure appropriate approaches were adopted within organisations. These authentic leaders were prepared to adopt these alternative strategies and, in some instances, corrective steps on existing issues because they believed in the efficacy of corrective action. To facilitate these changes, Leaders B, E, K, and P established that there was an innate determination to drive these changes. Also, Leaders B and E described this as a personal responsibility to be that desired change.

“You know people can do better, and that just sums up my belief as wanting to be that change. I want to be that change that I want to see, which inspires me. Moreover, that inspires me even right now for my business, my family, and everything I do. I just do not want to talk. I want to do it (Leader B).”

“May because I am just a dreamer, I have that push. You know to improve things, create something you know, and bring something into reality (Leader E).”

The second sub theme highlighted was trigger events, which were made up of positive and negative experiences. These experiences ranged from failure at an early age to difficulties experienced at different stages in their lives. In describing these trigger events with reference to the negative experiences, these authentic leaders described a process of reassessing who they are and what was important after they left this world. Seemingly, an altruistic desire to do right by themselves.

These leaders emphasised the importance of these encounters and how they have inspired them to begin their authentic leadership journey. Leader F also stated that failure inspired her authentic leadership development. See excerpts Leaders C and K below:

“It is difficult for you to just wake up in the morning and say, hey, I am going to be an authentic leader in the strict sense of the word. For me, it is a range of experiences has shaped me into making me who I am today. Today, the challenges that I’ve had to face, the situation and the difficulties I’ve had to try to conquer. They have all led me to where I am today (Leader C).”

“The experiences I had in school, growing up and everything, experiences of failure. Experiences of having to start all over again. I was studying mechanical engineering; I had to start over again and start a new degree program for a different course. All those experiences. It kind of moulded me into who I am today (Leader K).”

Furthermore, these leaders also described their personal fulfilment as a key factor that inspired their authentic leadership development. This personal fulfilment spanned from empowering individuals to fostering both self and follower development. Leader L described it as a convenient way to live. For Leader D, driving followers to success gave her fulfilment as stated below:

“Being able to help people be the best version they can be was very fulfilling for me. I think that was my first motivation. I was inspired to see people who have worked with me go on to be better than me or succeed at a higher level. That really gave me satisfaction. So, I think that is where my inspiration started from (Leader D).”

The leaders were asked if a pivotal experience influenced their decision to become authentic and the critical incident technique was employed during the interviews. This technique was employed to evaluate whether there was congruence between their previous descriptions and the critical event or experience that was the most essential in shaping their decision to become authentic leaders. The findings from these questions were interesting as these 16 authentic leaders provided the responses categorised below, aligning with earlier descriptions. See Figure 25 for an overview of the theme and sub themes.

Figure 25 Pivotal Experiences

6.4 Conclusion

This chapter comprised of three key sections. The initial section of this chapter served as a foundation, providing an overview of two focal locations in Nigeria: Lagos and Abuja. By exploring the unique characteristics and dynamics of Lagos and Abuja, this section provides a contextual lens through which the subsequent findings can be interpreted. Following that, the chapter presents the results obtained from the initial two research inquiries of the study.

The first research question sought to uncover the components of authentic leadership. Through the analysis of the data set, six key components of authentic leadership were identified. These components include clarity of purpose, which offers organisational direction. Follower development, emphasising tangible follower growth. Relational transparency, highlighting open and honest communication. Self awareness, emphasising introspective understanding and reflection. Internalised moral perspective, highlighting an ethical compass and finally, concern for followers, extending beyond organisational exigencies. The second question uncovered factors that inspire the authentic leadership development. Four key factors were identified from the broad accounts of the authentic leaders. The numerous forms and manifestations of leadership stood out as a critical key factor in fostering authentic leadership development. In addition, the concept of legacy, powered by the desire to leave a lasting impact, emerged as a force driving the development of authentic leaders. The leaders also highlighted family structure, beliefs and convictions as key factors that inspired authentic leadership development.

Building upon the foundations laid in this chapter, the next chapter presents the findings of the last two research questions of the study.

CHAPTER 7. EMPIRICAL FINDINGS: CHALLENGES AND EMPLOYEE PERCEPTIONS OF AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP

INTRODUCTION

The preceding chapter provided an overview of some key findings and conclusions obtained from the data analysis. It presents the results obtained from investigating the initial two research questions: The components of authentic leadership and the factors responsible for fostering its development. In addressing the first research question, respondents identified 6 critical components of authentic leadership: clarity of purpose, follower development, relational transparency, self awareness, internalised moral perspective, and concern for people. In addressing the second research question, only the descriptions of authentic leaders were sought as this inquiry was linked to their personal experiences. These leaders highlighted four key factors family structure, belief and conviction, leadership and legacy, as the primary factors that inspired their authentic leadership development.

This final findings chapter summarises the conclusions from the last two research questions, the challenges authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy, and the actions that shape employee perceptions of authentic leaders. In addressing the first research question on the challenges that authentic leaders encounter within a developing economy, the responses of all 16 authentic leaders were analysed and synthesised meaningfully. However, in addressing the second research question on the actions that shape employee perceptions of authentic leaders, only the responses of the 30 followers are analysed, as these respondents possess specialist knowledge and have experienced the phenomenon. The analysis of these followers' responses facilitated the exploration of unique aspects of the authentic leadership construct that were lacking in earlier conceptualisations.

Structurally, the layout of this chapter is theme based across three sections that provide a clear account of the descriptions offered by the respondents. Section 7.1 outlines the challenges authentic leaders encounter within a developing economy. The section also provides evidence to support contextual and non contextual challenges of authentic leaders. Section 7.2 highlights the actions that shape employee perception of authentic leadership and Section 7.3 provides the conclusion of the chapter.

7.1 Challenges that authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy?

In exploring this research question, the enquiry was directed at authentic leaders as the study sought to uncover the complexities and challenges, they had experienced. These authentic leaders described external influences that shaped their authentic leadership initially before proceeding to discuss their personal paradoxes. In addressing the research question, the authentic leaders sought to explain their challenges primarily in association with the context of the study before proceeding to describe the complexities of dealing with these challenges. However, the authentic leaders identified four central challenges of authentic leadership evident within a developing economy context. These include financial challenges, poor governance and regulation, and economic challenges, which focus on contextual variables and finally the leadership challenges, which capture personal paradoxes they have encountered on their journey. These challenges are described in greater depth below.

7.1.1 Financial Challenges

The authentic leaders described financial challenges as problems in managing money, assets, and investments within the oil sector. Financial challenges are prevalent in most economies and are even more evident across developing economies. However, the financial challenges experienced in the oil sector are not based on the limited availability of resources but rather an evident misuse of funds. Authentic leaders identified two significant factors contributing to the financial challenges within this sector, specifically corruption and misappropriation of funds.

Corruption

All authentic leaders described corruption as a significant obstacle within the oil industry. They emphasised the detrimental impact it had on their organisation's processes, practices, and enactment of leadership. It was described as particularly challenging as corruption is widespread within the oil industry, as highlighted by the authentic leaders B, K and L below:

"They made us spend a lot of money because we wanted to do the right thing. They tagged my staff, and they threatened us. In fact, at some point, I felt that his life was in danger (Leader B)."

"Corruption on different levels (Leader K)."

"Corruption is a major challenge in the oil industry... Everybody wants to cut corners (Leader L)."

Regarding corruption, authentic leaders described it from two perspectives: the prevalence of fraudulent practices and the complexity of operating within the business terrain. In describing the fraudulent practices, these leaders began by explaining the extortion of companies within the industries by regulatory agencies across different levels. These organisational extortions were often conducted when companies sought to pay surcharges to government parastatals. These surcharges are supposedly payments due to the Government. Yet, at various stages, organisations were extorted initially before these companies were officially recognised and included in businesses that allowed them to trade. For instance, Leader M described the inherent bias against companies and company leaders that did not compromise with government officials. Regulators frequently imposed penalties on these leaders, resulting in limited economic opportunities for these organisations. This is explained in the excerpt provided by Leader M:

"The first challenge would be this bias in allocation because if everything was fair, nobody has to go and say, OK, give me some allocation. There will be no interference from the Government in your business number one. They can decide today that we are not giving your organisation and only these particular people. That is unfair. So, with just that decision, it could ruin us (Leader M)."

The opaque pricing structure evident in the industry was also highlighted in the descriptions of fraudulent practices by authentic leaders. The lack of transparency in pricing has resulted in volatility within the business, with prices experiencing rapid

and extreme fluctuations. This has left oil traders perplexed as they try to meet client expectations. These opaque pricing practices have also negatively impacted the purchasing power of oil companies as well as the consumers, as described by Leader H and I:

“Well, I will say prices. Prices are one of the main challenges. It is the dwindling of prices because many factors are attached to it (Leader H).”

“Because consumers cannot understand why things are so expensive now. They still want to buy at the older price, which is not feasible anymore because the cost of doing business has increased. (Leader I).”

The evident price volatility has made it difficult for authentic leaders to plan and invest for the long term. Similarly, the prevalence of unclear business practices, which also contributed to the financial challenges within the industry, was prevalent in the discussions of authentic leaders. Illegal products, also described as adulterated products, were sold at prices lower than prevailing market prices and, in some instances, at the same prices, which led to the breakdown of customers' equipment. The discussions on corruption were extensive and emotional for all the 16 authentic leaders.

Misappropriation of funds

The second perspective regarding the financial difficulties faced by these authentic leaders pertained to the misappropriation of funds. The authentic leaders stated that the Nigerian Government and its officials misappropriated funds majorly with the foreign exchange reserve. All the authentic leaders identified the scarcity of foreign exchange required for importing products as a major challenge within the industry. This was the most profound challenge, and it was attributed to the government processes as well as the questionable practices by Bureau of the Exchange (BDC) as described in excerpts by Leader A, I and M below:

“I know many of the things I have said cut across many countries, but the scarcity of the dollar in Nigeria and the devaluation of the naira are some of the extra issues that companies have been suffering (Leader A).”

“It has made the business environment very tough. People cannot import, so fewer people import products for sale. Because I cannot access dollars, I must source from the parallel market, which is very expensive. And then even scarce (Leader I).”

“Recently, there have been issues getting foreign exchange in Nigeria to settle your debt (Leader M).”

The rising national debt was also described as a source of financial challenges, leading to extensive borrowing. The authentic leaders emphasised that resources were limited, which made it challenging for leaders to implement their vision and facilitate meaningful changes within the industry.

7.1.2 Poor Governance and Regulation

Authentic leaders consistently identified inadequate governance and regulation as a significant obstacle they encounter in the context of a developing economy. This poor governance and regulations were evident in the policies and actions of the regulatory agencies, and it was manifested in two different areas: ineffective regulation and rising insecurity.

Ineffective regulation

Authentic leaders promptly voiced their opposition to ineffective regulation, which stemmed from inadequate policies. The existing laws and policies have failed to guide ethical practices within the industry; hence the Nigerian oil industry has been marred by scandals across the regulatory agencies. Furthermore, this has facilitated malpractices across these regulatory agencies. Also, authentic leaders acknowledged that ineffective regulation had led to bureaucratic processes. For instance, Leader F recognised that the current policies are inadequate to tackle the deficiencies in the oil sector.

“Working in some African countries, you will see that the regulations have helped them to have a seamless operation, but even with our regulations, there are still gaps. (Leader F).”

Authentic leaders also stated that government interference led to unstable policies and poor project planning. In the same vein, the lack of accountability contributed to ineffective regulation and, by extension, poor governance. This challenge was extensively discussed by authentic leaders and is believed to have contributed to the financial difficulties, as expressed by Leader B, who acknowledged that the lack of accountability had led to injustices within the industry.

Rising insecurity

Authentic leaders described rising insecurity within the country as a critical challenge and highlighted its negative impact, particularly within the oil industry. These respondents stressed that insecurity had escalated in the Nigerian, with several oil installations being destroyed and civilians being killed by insurgents. These insurgents, popularly known as militants, have destroyed millions of oil exploration equipment and infrastructure, adversely affecting the industry. Leaders B and G emphasised the implication of these militant activities on the sector, which impedes operations, exportation and negatively impacts the country's foreign exchange earnings. See excerpt by Leader G stating that it is the most significant challenge encountered within the industry *"So the biggest challenge to us today remains security, and that is why most companies are looking for alternatives."*

Similarly, herders have also contributed to the rising insecurity in the nation. The authentic leaders clarified that these herdsmen, described initially as nomadic cattle breeders in northern Nigeria, have become increasingly dangerous. These herdsmen armed with weapons, kill citizens and destroy farms because they want their cattle to graze without restrictions on people's fields. When these farm owners oppose the destruction, they are massacred across remote villages. As a result, there is a strong demand for state and regional governments to implement preventive measures to protect lives and property. Although, a few state governments have implemented measures to ensure safety, the Federal Government has been passive, leading citizens to criticise it for its indifference and perceived endorsement of a particular group of Nigerians associated with the presidency of the former President, Maj. Gen. (ret.) Muhammadu Buhari. These herdsmen are also accused of being promoters of the thriving kidnapping culture that has plagued the country. Kidnapping, which began during herdsmen raids across communities, has exacerbated and increased across different states in Nigeria. Unlike the raids of the herdsmen, whose activities occur predominantly in the North, the kidnappers are active both in the cities and the remote areas. Hence, security has become the personal burden of individuals within Nigeria.

This rising insecurity has led to oil theft affecting authentic leaders within Nigeria. Leaders B, G and K highlighted this in the excerpts below:

“Just the instability across, we also have insecurity (Leader B).”

“You have lost 60% off to theft and vandalism. That is a big issue (Leader G).”

“Yeah, we have oil theft and everything (Leader K).”

The worsening security situation has been aggravated by the presence of unmotivated security personnel who are forced to prioritise their safety because of inadequate wages and frequent lengthy delays in government payment. Likewise, if they die in the line of duty, their family members are typically abandoned and left to face the future alone. So these security officers only provide their services when they have determined that the risk level is extremely low or when there are personal incentives at stake, eliminating the need to put their lives in danger for nothing.

7.1.3 Economic Challenges

The authentic leaders described economic challenges as part of the difficulties encountered by authentic leaders in importing, distributing, and selling petroleum products within Nigeria. The authentic leaders recognised economic issues that include global economic concerns, the impact of COVID, and infrastructural deficit. These issues have had a significant impact on Nigeria's economic environment, with the oil industry playing a central role. The economic issues are examined in greater depth below.

Global economic concerns

In discussing the global economic concerns, the main issues highlighted by the authentic leaders were the rise of the taxes within the industry. Leader A stressed that the elevated tax rate facilitated corruption in oil companies, leading them to either decrease the amount paid or completely avoid taxes.

“The tax rate for oil and gas companies in Nigeria is 85% higher than the 30% company’s income tax charged to businesses, not in the oil and gas sector, so there is much burden for businesses in the oil and gas. There is much responsibility. You know there is a lot of focus from tax authorities, from communities (Leader A).”

“One of the things that had recently come up is paying taxes. They come back and say you cannot work with this insurance company. You cannot work with that insurance company. You have to pay cash as collateral for it and are given only 2 weeks period (Leader J).”

Leader J also offered her perspective on the taxes, and its implication on the business as captured above. Equally, the low access to financial instruments had caused economic challenges within the developing economy context. These challenges cut across the oil sector but were exacerbated by the impact of COVID, which is discussed subsequently.

COVID

The COVID pandemic hit the nation, and its impact was evident in the economic indices in the country. It had a significant impact on the entire industry in terms of employment, trade, exports, and revenues. The authentic leaders stated that COVID uncovered the layers of corruption; lack of investment and exposed the true nature of the deficit in the industry's infrastructure. Within the oil industry, the pandemic led to mass layoffs and redundancies across the sector. Leader A discussed the impact of COVID on employee performance and availability. This leader claimed that the pandemic had an impact on the human resources of oil firms, as illustrated below:

“We have had to lay off a lot. Lots of redundancies have happened in the last two years over the pandemic. We have seen businesses struggle with the financial position and revenue (Leader A).”

The pandemic also affected oil production and trading across the organisations. Authentic leaders acknowledged that the pandemic made them more empathetic, making their relational transparency outlook more evident during the period. In some instances, authentic leaders revealed that their most difficult leadership experience was during the pandemic, as they gave more of themselves emotionally to their staff.

7.1.4 Leadership Challenges

The descriptions offered by the respondents clearly highlighted leadership complexities. Authentic leaders define these leadership problems as the obstacles they encountered within their organisations, while attempting to lead, inspire, and steer others towards a common goal or objective. Inherently, these challenges were either personal or emerged during interactions with their followers. Authentic leaders were

quick to highlight the contentions that emerged when followers did not understand their beliefs and convictions, which hindered attaining personal and organisational goals. Although they clarified that their personal goals could not be inhibited, they experienced frustration in ensuring they did not compromise their convictions. These were often described as staff complexities, with key areas, such as being untrue, managing expectations, being emphasised during the discussions. The subsections highlight these personal challenges and then proceed to the leadership challenges that emerge from interactions with followers.

Personal leadership challenges

The authentic leaders described the personal leadership challenges involved in staying true to their convictions, beliefs and principles while leading within their diverse organisations. These personal challenges became evident due to changing nature of the work environment and broader society, where conflicting demands and competing priorities tested their will to stay true to their values and convictions. Furthermore, these challenges ranged from sticking to core values, balancing competing priorities, and entering new teams within their organisations.

Sticking to core values

Authentic leaders described instances where pressures from the external environment directly impacted their leadership within their business. These leaders described their reliance on inner strength to stay true to themselves and upholding their commitment to their principles and convictions. This struggle became evident particularly when external stakeholders did not uphold the right course of action in business, as captured by Leader B below.

“It would continue to remain a big challenge that is sticking to my core values. Just because we have a system riddled with malpractice and corruption, it has been very tough maintaining our core values, which are integrity, innovation and excellence. I have maintained, and will still maintain, standing up for what we believe. It is only sometimes accepted by customers or people we relate with. We lean towards people with whom we can comfortably do business and who will not compromise our core values. It has made us unpopular in some sections in some areas, but we are fine with that (Leader B).”

Leader B had to challenge the status quo of theft practices that were inconsistent with her values and acknowledged that navigating the conflict without compromising her principles in the process was challenging. In addition, authentic leaders highlighted instances where their values conflicted with the values of other stakeholders, and it was sometimes challenging to navigate these conflicts, while staying true to themselves. They, however, acknowledged that even though they were open enough to listen to other perspectives, they held on to their beliefs and values irrespective of the situation.

Balancing competing interests and priorities

Authentic leaders shared accounts of the challenging decisions they faced, balancing competing interests like prioritising the organization's interests while navigating the necessity to downsize their workforce due to the pandemic's impact on their company. Leader I was unhappy when she had to lay off some of her employees, even though they were high performers within the organisation. As Leader I explained, the decision was not performance based but a business based problem, as captured below:

"We had to do all the sentiment games through the Covid, and by December, we almost had a negative, so we had to rethink. I had to take that tough decision and say I am sorry it is not based on your performance. Business is not doing as great as it used to be, and we cannot continue to carry the cost as a company, and we had to let some people go. So, for me, that was one of the hardest things that I had to do because it was not like they were not doing their jobs. That was the biggest decision I had to take, which bothered me (Leader I)."

This leader provided insights into her internal struggles, where she was unable to justify whom to pick in this mass company layoff. She described the emotional labour that plagued her as she considered the impact of the news on their families and how they would have to justify why they were chosen over others to be let go. So, for the authentic leader, an admission was made on the intentionality and careful review of the process that eventually led to the termination of the affected staff.

New team dynamics

The authentic leaders discussed the difficulties they faced when they had to integrate into new teams and adjust to a different environment, particularly when it

considerably differed from what they are used too. This was described as challenging because team members were sometimes sceptical and resistant to change. These leaders stated that each team had a unique dynamic and they had to learn how to establish rapport to provide the support required. This is captured by Leader K below:

“I had to move from a new department to another and was not well versed in what was to be done in the other department. To learn, I had to humble myself. I needed to ask questions from people that I was supposed to be leading, and we needed to learn how things are done properly from other people. I wanted to give direction but was willing to learn well from those who were more technically versed than me (Leader K).”

These authentic leaders described the balance as challenging as they sought to ensure they could build the competencies required for their new roles and responsibilities within their teams. Finally, authentic leaders also described a significant challenge of balancing vulnerability and strength. These leaders confirmed that being vulnerable was a crucial part of their leadership with their followers. However, they recognised they also needed to project strength and confidence; hence finding the delicate balance between these became a challenge that confronted them within their organisations.

Interactional leadership challenges

Authentic leaders admitted that authentic leadership could be very effective within organisations, but challenges emerged during interactions with followers. These challenges differ from the personal leadership challenges, as discussed earlier because these are affiliated with others within the organisations. In expounding on interactional leadership challenges these authentic leaders identified balancing individual needs with the group's needs, managing expectations, being untrue and broadening followers' perspectives during the discussions.

Balancing individual needs with the needs of the group

Authentic leaders described their openness to multiple perspectives and self expression from their followers. These leaders stated that they valued the creativity and ingenuity of their followers but were faced with difficulty balancing the group's needs to ensure everyone was pulling in the same direction and working towards a shared goal. This challenge was apparent when followers were not self aware. Leader

D, acknowledging the gravity of the complexity, ensured that all her immediate subordinates had a personality assessment to get insight into their individual characteristics and potentially discover the factors that provoke them.

Several authentic leaders within the study either did the same for their immediate line reports or did one for themselves and shared the results with their followers to facilitate open and rewarding interactions. Leader D illustrates this in the excerpt below, where it seemed like she was behaving out of character as she did not openly give immediate feedback to the erring employee. She confirmed that in this specific case, she considered the individual team member's needs, which made her feel uneasy, as described below.

“One of the things I did was just do a personality test for everyone that reports to me. Moreover, the reason why I wanted to do that was so that I understood what the trigger for this person was. A particular team member of mine is a hard worker and result-driven struggles with criticism or even taking feedback. My approach to giving feedback is that I would come to team meetings and give feedback to you, but I did not do that for her. The challenge I faced was that it seemed like, I was being unfair to the others who ordinarily would have gotten feedback in the open if they had done the same thing (Leader D).”

These authentic leaders were, however, able to offer solutions to dealing with this frustration. They stated that they intentionally fostered a culture of self reflection and created opportunities for followers to reflect.

Managing expectations

Authentic leaders described the high expectations they have of themselves and others which covered a range of issues. Yet, they acknowledged that this became challenging for themselves and their followers when followers had different priorities or constraints within the organisation. Nonetheless, authentic leaders passionately talked about how they only resorted to giving up on these followers as a last option when the followers failed to align with their vision. Leader E acknowledged that giving up was the most significant challenge as an authentic leader, as described below:

“The biggest challenge is giving up. I do not like giving up on people, but sometimes you put in the best effort, you put in the best plans, you put in all the time, and you provide all support, but it simply does

not work right, and there will be many reasons. Sometimes you know the person you are trying to support and work with simply may not be at that phase of their life where you are pushing for that growth (Leader E)."

Overall, the authentic leaders acknowledged that they managed these expectations daily by clearly communicating goals and objectives.

Being Untrue

Authentic leaders stated that followers being untrue presented a significant challenge for them as it undermined the very foundations of their leadership. These leaders further asserted that being untrue created conflict between them and their followers which led to inconsistency and confusion within the organisation. Leader O described being untrue as a primary challenge for authentic leaders. This leader began this discussion by stating that organisations were untrue with their intentions which negatively impacted the leaders and followers. Hence, being untrue led to ethical dilemmas. For instance, if organisations were not truthful about their motives and actions, they were then faced with difficult decisions, when asked to account for their behaviour and actions, as captured by Leader O. For instance, when an International Oil Company (IOC) plans to drill for oil in a community, they typically initiate engagement with the residents. However, in many cases, the IOC's initial intentions may not align with their true objectives. They often make promises that they have no intention of fulfilling. Likewise, the community members and leaders also concentrate on advancing their own interests. Subsequently, disappointment emerges when individuals become aware that the stakeholders are solely preoccupied with their interests. Leader O revealed that in the scenario described above "*No one is thinking about contributing to development*", which is challenging as it may seem like the authentic leader is a lone wolf in that environment.

Broadening perspectives of followers

Finally, authentic leaders acknowledged that broadening followers' perspectives was very challenging as these individuals frequently possess deeply ingrained beliefs and convictions that may be resistant to change. These leaders claimed that certain followers exhibited emotional attachment to their beliefs and identities, hence posing a challenge to expanding their perspectives. In addition, authentic leaders stated that this process required followers re-evaluating some of their deeply held assumptions which seemed uncomfortable and even threatening in some instances. Hence, it required patience and sensitivity to these emotional attachments and constantly seeking ways to engage these followers in a constructive dialogue that encouraged openness. Authentic leaders emphasised that this broadening of the follower's perspective facilitated growth which was their key motivation for driving these changes within their followers. Table 24 presents some selected excerpts on the broadening the perspectives of followers.

Table 24 Excerpts on broadening perspectives of Followers

Leaders	Quotes
<i>Leader C</i>	<i>"Itis really growing a coalition or followership that believes in having the sense of purpose and direction that is required to translate the vision into reality."</i>
<i>Leader M</i>	<i>"The greatest challenge that I faced is having to ensure that they become great leaders. Bringing different tasks to ensure that they can overcome it."</i>

These financial challenges, inadequate governance and regulation, economic difficulties, and leadership challenges contributed extensively to the authentic leader's daily contention and paradoxes. In summary, authentic leaders described challenges as an inherent part of their leadership, which tested and strengthened their resolve.

7.2 Specific actions that shape the employee perceptions of authentic leaders?

In addressing this research question, the enquiry was directed at the followers as the question sought to explore the specific actions of authentic leaders that shaped employee perceptions. This question was critical to the study as it uncovered key actions that followers perceived as authentic, which, if embraced, offer a path to

leadership repair within organisations. Overall, the followers identified four main actions which are giving followers a voice, facilitating follower development, demonstrating consistency and being transparent when describing actions that shape their perceptions of authentic leadership. These are discussed below.

7.2.1 Followers Voice

The theme of giving followers a voice was characterised by the respondents' "followers" recounting instances where authentic leaders actively sought opinions and contributions. These interactions were embedded in environments described as safe and inclusive, where employees expressed their views without restraint. These followers affirmed that their voice empowered them within their various organisations. As a result, they embarked on new career trajectories and assumed personal responsibility for their work, gaining the self assurance necessary to make significant decisions within their organisations. Overall, the followers stated that authentic leaders gave their followers a platform to speak up. This supported the argument that these authentic leaders understood the importance of diversity and harnessed the power of collective intelligence within their organisations. Followers identified actions such as demonstrating balanced processing, being courageous and fostering collaboration, all of which played a role in empowering followers to having a voice.

Balanced Processing

The followers described the demonstration of balanced processing as a key action that positively shaped their perceptions of authentic leadership, emphasising that the lack of it was perceived as inauthentic leadership. These followers described balanced processing as consideration and evaluation diverse perspectives on an issue before a decision is taken by leaders. In describing balanced processing, the followers stated that this was demonstrable by being open to diverse perspectives. This is described by Followers C1 and G2 below:

“One of his actions is allowing you to have a voice. When I mean having a voice, your opinion matters as an individual whether you are an officer, manager, or senior manager. So, one of the things that I see that is good for authentic leadership is allowing people to voice and share their opinions right. And then when the time comes, you are allowed to share your opinion, so authentic leadership lets your team have a voice (Follower C1).”

“The leader’s attitude to ideas to people opinions. Even if you disagree, being able to communicate in a very respectful way. If your subordinates become timid because they feel you will shut them down. They cannot talk. They fear what to say. If you send them stuff to review and they are scared because they are like, if I review this thing, it may affect my appraisal (Follower G2).”

Followers argued that authentic leaders actively seek diversity in approaches. These leaders consider the viewpoints of other stakeholders within their organisation, as captured by Follower C1 above. Followers also described being open to diverse perspectives as being open to ideas, being open-minded and facilitating opinion sharing. These followers stated that authentic leaders must strive to create environments that facilitate sharing of honest opinions and concerns. Interestingly Follower H1 alluded that this made leaders humane.

Furthermore, followers argued that balanced processing was demonstrated by promoting equity within organisations. These authentic leaders prioritised equity throughout their organisations while considering the needs and requirements of all stakeholders. Follower N1 highlights the importance of fairness across board as captured in the excerpt, *“All people need to be treated fairly with no one getting a special advantage. Everyone gets a fair shot.”* These authentic leaders attempt to create equitable solutions for all parties while ensuring they are motivated by the greater good. For instance, follower G2 suggests that authentic leadership decisions should not be shaped by bias:

“It is not based on I do not like this person that I am not taking their decisions. Even if their ideas are the best in the room, it is based on the facts and data that this is the right thing for us to pursue at this time. This is why we are doing this thing (FollowerG2).”

Followers maintained that this involved using data and reliable information to underpin the decisions within the organisations, as these leaders did not allow their personal biases to cloud their judgement or influence their assessment of information.

Courage

Followers described the courage of authentic leaders as critical in giving followers a voice. This courage is demonstrated by authentic leaders when they stand up for their values, what is deemed right and what they believe in. These authentic leaders can speak up against injustice, prejudice, and unethical behaviour in their organisations and broader society. Follower E1 states, *"You must be courageous because integrity requires courage. It is not that people do not know what to do or do not want to do the right thing, but I have seen a lack of courage destroy a mountain of hard work."*

These followers also argued that courage was required when the challenges seemed to overwhelm organisations, and authentic leaders were required to face these difficult situations and make equally difficult decisions. In these complex situations, the authentic leaders faced it head on, seeking solutions even if the decisions were unpopular.

To achieve their personal and organisational goals, followers established that authentic leaders were prepared to take risks and make difficult decisions, as captured by follower E2: *"And I think they always stand up for what is right. They are very quick to state that if something is wrong, they will say we are not going to have a part of this, so I will call that very principled."* The courage demonstrated by these authentic leaders gave their followers strength, motivation, and a voice. Furthermore, the followers argued that the leader's passion fuelled this courage. Courage was a critical action that shaped followers' perceptions as it facilitated change and inspired followership within organisations. Empowering followers to voice their concerns about misconduct, unfairness, or express their perspectives on matters within the organisation.

Collaboration

Followers highlighted the importance of combining their abilities and making use of resources available to achieve collective results that exceeded what could be achieved individually. These followers described collaboration as the process of working together to achieve a shared vision or goal which fostered innovation within their organisations. The followers argued that these involved brainstorming about

challenges and developing solutions to meet specific goals. For instance, Follower E2 argues that this was attainable based on a leader's self awareness, captured in the excerpt "*They understand that do not know everything and open to you know that they are very collaborative.*"

Followers claimed that collaboration required mutual respect for followers to thrive, as this usually facilitated positive outcomes for the organisation. The respect transcended beyond competencies to recognising that each team member had weaknesses and strengths that did not define them as employees. Despite perceived shortcomings of leaders and followers, authentic leaders worked effectively to attain strategic alignment within the organisation. Follower J1 highlights the self awareness of the authentic leader's capacity as well as the awareness of the followers' capabilities, as captured in the excerpt: "*They also value the importance of teamwork and group efforts. Moreover, trusting certain team members to execute or do certain jobs (Follower J1).*"

These followers argued that collaboration was underpinned by active participation. A common sub theme amongst respondents was that collaboration was not one sided, but followers also expected authentic leaders to do the work and not just give direction. In some instances, this collaboration was described as engagement and in other instances, called offering a helping hand as stated by Followers J1, and O2 below:

"I mean, she is also one of the leaders willing to give you a helping hand. So even though you are given feedback, you know she is also asking where I can assist. Do you need my assistance? Do you need me to attend the next meeting (Follower J1)?"

"So, we see them doing the work. When they tell you to finish the task, it is not because they have gone out to play. They are also at the forefront getting other things done so that they are not just leaders, and they are not just dictating (Follower O2)."

All followers argued that having their voice heard within the organisation was essential for them.

7.2.2 Follower development

Follower development was covered in chapter six. However, that discussion focused on the perspective of authentic leaders. This is different from the descriptions offered by followers when identifying actions that shape their perceptions of authentic leadership. The respondents described follower development as a continuous identification of growth potential across employees and the nurturing these potentials. All followers agreed that authentic leaders facilitate follower growth because it strengthens their contributions and impacts the organisation's culture. These followers stated that authentic leaders who placed importance on developing their followers and actively dedicated their time to aiding this development showed an awareness that their growth contributed to the success of the organisation, as described below.:

“An authentic leader is somebody who is genuinely invested in the growth of the entire team.... the second example. It was also a manager of mine who told me at a time where I didn't see myself as a leader, but then pushed me and told me that I had those leadership qualities and because of that she wanted me to horn in on those skills, not shy away from taking on leadership roles, and she put me in prime positions (Follower A1)”.

“The individual is very conscious about the development of the subordinates. He is very interested in development and goes out of his way to ensure that people are carried along to understand where they are lagging areas for development and ensuring that those areas are closed as quickly as possible (Follower G2)”.

“Being a coach to me. He has shown me the, the way to manage some of the tasks I am handling now. He has given advice. Whatsoever ever I am doing which I report to him, he gives correction. He gives advice on the way to go (Follower K1)”.

While this was not the primary motivation for authentic leaders, the followers believed it was a value these leaders brought to their organisations. In unpacking follower development, followers like authentic leaders identified role modelling. However, these followers offered their distinct descriptions of this action. Furthermore, they also identified relationship management, contributing to follower development within their organisations.

Role modelling

Followers stated that role modelling was critical to facilitating follower development. In contrast to the descriptions of authentic leaders, where role modelling was described in terms of leadership positioning and development approaches. In terms of leadership positioning, authentic leaders emphasised leading by example, leading by following, leading from the front and finally, leading from the back as captured in the excerpts below:

"I try to lead by example right which I think is key. If you are leading and your actions say otherwise, then I don't think that's the right direction to go in terms of leading (Leader K)."

"I will say I lead from the front. I lead by rolling up my sleeves and showing my team how to do it and showing that I can do it so that makes them realise that you know anyone can do what we're doing? (Leader M)."

"They see that I'm trying to support them to succeed and people put in you know what is required, to kind of drive the overall goal, so if you put it that way, maybe I will say I lead from behind, rather than in front most of the time, right where I try and push the people (Leader E)."

"I will say I lead from the front. I lead by rolling up my sleeves (Leader M)."

The data revealed that the followers were not aware of the leadership positioning evident in the explanations of authentic leaders. Instead, followers described role modelling in parallel with leading by example. These followers described role modelling primarily as leading by example with leading by example being described as a process where authentic leaders set the standards of conduct and performance by exhibiting the same work ethic they anticipate from their followers, as described by Follower C2 *"They should be setting standards that are inspirational for others to follow and to emulate."*

These followers implied that authentic leaders demonstrated the values and principles that were important to them expressly. This served as a reference point for followers as role modelling made authentic leader expectations evident. Furthermore, followers required evidence of authentic leadership when describing role modelling and its impact on the leader's career and personal life, as detailed by Follower F1 *"I think setting good examples for everybody to emulate in all aspects (Follower F1)."* Leading by

example was also highlighted by Follower N1 and described as a lifestyle obvious in all facets of the authentic leader's life, as disclosed in Follower L1's description.

"They are guiding you to do what they lead you to do. You've seen where they started from, you've seen how far they have come, how they've climbed, how this started, where they were before, what they did to get them to where they are. So, once you can see the steps they have gone through before they become a leader. That will be an authentic leader for me (Follower L1)."

"Leading by example. You know a leader must be able to be seen as someone who leads by example. You need to take charge of responsibility (Follower N1)."

Given that authentic leaders set clear examples of success and excellence, followers who want to develop their abilities and adopt positive behaviours rated role modelling as helpful in their accounts.

Relationship Management

Followers argued that relationship management was critical in shaping their perceptions of authentic leadership. This relationship management enabled authentic leaders manage conflicting priorities and contentions within the organisations. According to these followers, these leaders fostered a sense of community within the organisation, reinforcing a positive work culture that supported followers. This allowed followers to learn from mistakes, enabling them to face their fears and develop from experiences. Follower K2 emphasised the importance of the authentic leaders' outlook on errors where it was an accepted belief that anyone could make mistakes within organisations *"Someone that lets you learn from your own mistakes without killing you for a mistake that anybody could have made (Follower K2)."*

Relationship management also extended beyond the internal stakeholders within the organisation to include partners, vendors etc. Follower B1 echoed this view and described the relationship management expertise of an authentic leader in her organisation. This leader was able to effectively manage relationships with internal and external stakeholders such that vendors chose to interact with her over the others, as stated: *"They prefer to deal with her and partner with us in helping us to sell off this cargo from the tank. So, that is relationship management (Follower B1)."*

Followers also identified the role of guidance in relationship management which enhanced employee satisfaction and facilitated follower development. The respondents characterised this guidance as a process in which authentic leaders empower their followers to establish goals and acquire the necessary skills and knowledge for achieving success. Several ways of providing guidance to followers were emphasised such as through feedback, breaking down the vision, validating the contribution of followers and training. This is described by Follower K1 in the excerpt below:

“Whatever I am doing, I report to him, so he gives corrections. He advises the way to go, so I see him as an authentic leader (Follower K1).”

By providing guidance, followers acknowledged that authentic leaders demonstrated their commitment to supporting follower development within organisations, creating a sense of loyalty. These respondents also asserted that guidance brought clarity to their roles within organisations, allowing them identify goals and develop plans to achieve them. Finally, the followers suggested that authentic leadership guidance was linked to follower engagement within their organisation but emphasised that the guidance is personal and tailored to everyone's needs. In highlighting inauthentic markers in leadership, Followers K1 and L1 emphasised the lack of guidance which facilitates follower growth as an indication of inauthentic leadership.

7.2.3 Consistency

Consistency was a salient sub theme across the responses of all the followers. This was evident from the beginning of the semi-structured interviews as the followers stressed it during their descriptions of authentic leaders. It was also a key parameter for deciding whom followers perceived as authentic within their organisations. Followers described consistency as the reliability, predictability and coherence demonstrated by authentic leaders over time. These followers stated the consistency was evidenced by alignment of the authentic leader's actions, principles and values across contexts. It was fascinating to note that consistency was not associated with any moral code, but followers confirmed that they disliked surprises from authentic leaders. For them, the

issue was not whether a particular action was right or wrong but rather the intended overall goal. This is because the motivations underpinning the actions of authentic leaders would have been unconsciously communicated during earlier interactions and are reiterated by ongoing actions, reactions, and judgements. All the followers expected consistency in authentic leadership, emphasising the consistency of approach and responses to organisational complexities. The followers also emphasised that words should always align with actions irrespective of the stakeholders. These respondents stipulated that authentic leadership should be consistent and dependable for all, as illustrated below:

“He is a picture of consistency because his work is very consistent with it, and we can see the impact in the business as well (Follower B1).”

“You have got to match what you say or what you do. The saying and the doing need to be harmonised (Follower E1).”

“You know what they stand for, their values, you know it does not change based on circumstance, you know, or it does not change based on who is there or even if they are with their bosses. Alternatively, they consistently want to see the organisational growth if you make a mistake. It is the consistency for me (Follower E2).”

“A leader is someone that lives what they preach or leaves what they teach. An authentic leader should also be consistent (Follower G1).”

“Consistent in the sense that you must practice what you preach (Follower J2).”

Followers also described consistency as the alignment of authentic leaders’ principles and values, which have been displayed over time. Consistency in the treatment of employees also meant authentic leaders were transparent and open in their decision making. Interestingly, transparency was also highlighted by all respondents as a core action that influences their perceptions, but this will be discussed in broader detail in section 7.2.4. Returning to the discussion on consistency, followers established that consistency produced a sense of predictability and reliability across all scenarios, which are captured in Table 25. Followers B1, E1, E2, G1, and J2 reiterated the importance of alignment between the words and actions of authentic leaders.

Table 25 Followers' excerpts on consistency

Excerpts	Perspective
<p><i>"You are doing your job. I am doing my job. He is a picture of consistency because in his work, he is very consistent with it, and we can see the impact in the business as well (Follower B1)."</i></p>	<p><i>Alignment of vision and performance</i></p>
<p><i>"What specific actions? I think you have got to match what you say or what you do. The saying and the doing need to be harmonised literally. But somebody who's tending perhaps to do one thing, and it is just doing something else (Follower E1)."</i></p>	<p><i>Alignment of words to actions</i></p>
<p><i>"Consistent as far as their personality is within the work environment and outside of that (Follower E2)."</i></p>	<p><i>Alignment across contexts</i></p>
<p><i>"A leader that is also consistent. Today you are the person who would say this, and tomorrow the person would be doing another thing (Follower G1)."</i></p>	<p><i>Alignment over time</i></p>
<p><i>"You should be consistent in the sense that you have to practice what you preach (Follower J2)."</i></p>	<p><i>Alignment of principles to actions</i></p>

These followers acknowledged that authentic leadership was imperfect and admitted that authentic leaders could be flawed in certain decisions. However, consistency helped to establish credibility within the organisation, which made followers more forgiving when these authentic leaders made mistakes. For instance, Follower E2 reiterated that the consistent actions of authentic leaders over time revealed their motives, values, and principles within organisations. See the excerpt by Follower E2 below:

"They get it wrong sometimes. However, I think the underlying bait is the motive. So even if the action they take comes off, you know the outcome is negative. The underlying reason they did it. When they did it, you could tell that it was with good intentions. So, have they consistently shown that they have good intentions? (Follower E2)."

Inconsistency was described as a critical marker for inauthentic leadership. Followers maintained that consistency was crucial in determining whether a leader was authentic. Follower O2 stated, *"It is just for him to choose one and stick to it; if he wants to be an authentic leader, he should be there 100%."* Finally, in describing consistency, followers argued that their presentation has no half measures. Authentic leaders had to be consistent across contexts as it helped maintain a clear sense of direction and purpose, which produced positive outcomes within organisations.

7.2.4 Transparency

Like consistency, all followers highlighted transparency as a crucial factor shaping their perceptions of authentic leadership. Although, closely linked to consistency, followers described transparency as the level of openness and honesty with which authentic leaders shared information across the organisation. Respondents were quick to assert that transparency is how much information executives provide to staff members about their choices, plans, and objectives, reiterating that authentic leaders are at the top of the spectrum in disclosing relevant information to followers. Authentic leaders are explicit and honest about their goals and motivations. While followers acknowledged that some information might be sensitive and confidential, they still expect that authentic leaders would be honest enough to admit the sensitivity of the information, communicating honestly with them. This is captured by Followers A1 and G1 below:

“I think it is a thin line between being transparent with us or with me to say. I want it done this way, but I cannot because there is a thin line between being transparent with me and telling me how she feels and being mindful of not disparaging her leader (Follower A1).”

“Yeah, I think that is the word. So, a leader is transparent and does not try to sugar-coat things (Follower G1).”

These respondents confirmed that transparency exhibited by authentic leaders fostered a feeling of inclusion and responsibility inside the company, motivating them to exceed expectations in performing their responsibilities. For instance, Followers B2, E1 and M1 provided quotes to support the importance of transparency in authentic leadership, with Follower E1 describing it as a requirement. A few are captured in the excerpts below.

“Yeah, like I said, one of the things that makes a leader seems authentic to me is transparency (Follower B2).”

“I think there is a level of transparency as well that is required with authentic leaders (Follower E1).”

“An authentic leader should be very transparent (Follower M1).”

Followers also highlighted that transparency demonstrated the human nature of authentic leaders, confirming the imperfection that plagues all human beings and

their decision making within the organisations. However, what makes transparency particularly useful from this perspective is that the context of the study is plagued by corruption, and followers are desperately seeking direction. Hence, transparency helped followers understand the motivation, fears, concerns, and expectations behind the decisions, as stated by Follower G1 *“Now, you also must be transparent. So, when you are transparent, you let people know no one is perfect.”*

Furthermore, followers argued that honesty in interactions and communications all contributed to perceptions of authentic leadership within organisations. Followers described honesty as the authentic leader's willingness to act and speak in a straightforward, sincere, and accurate manner. In several instances, honesty and truthfulness were used interchangeably by the respondents, with Follower M2 emphatically stating that authentic leaders should be who they are and be honest about it. Followers A2, K1, M2, and O1 all emphasised the importance of honesty in contributing to transparency, with some followers suggesting that transparency is one of the most important actions that shape their perceptions.

7.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, the results presented in this second and final chapter of the findings section of the study captures the challenges authentic leaders face and the actions that shape employee perceptions of AL. This chapter sought to answer two questions, focusing on two distinct respondent groups: authentic leaders and followers. By analysing the responses of these two categories of respondents, a broader understanding of authentic leadership was attained.

The first research question explored challenges that authentic leaders encounter within a developing economy context. The authentic leaders identified contextual issues as the main issues that they face in their leadership. Furthermore, leadership challenges, which captured the personal paradoxes authentic leaders encounter in their leadership, were also discussed. The findings stressed the intricate nature of AL,

emphasising the need for leaders to adeptly navigate these complexities. The second research question focused on the actions that shape employee perceptions of authentic leadership. By focusing solely on the responses of followers, four main actions were identified. These findings highlight the significance of leaders' actions in influencing employee perceptions, which in turn influence employee outlook and performance.

The findings presented in Chapters 6 and 7 of the study effectively addressed the research objectives and questions, demonstrating a clear link between the empirical data and the study aim. See an overview below:

Research Objective 1: To identify the key components of authentic leadership (RO1): The findings explore the components of authentic leadership as per research question 1 (RQ1). Six key components are identified: clarity of purpose, self awareness, internalised moral perspective, relational transparency, concern for people, and follower development of authentic leadership. This directly addresses RO1 by uncovering the key components of AL.

Research Objective 2: To examine the factors that inspire authentic leadership development (RO2): The study investigates factors inspiring authentic leadership development in response to Research Question 2 (RQ2). It identifies familial structure, belief systems, exposure to leadership, and the desire to leave a legacy as significant influences on authentic leadership development. These findings directly correspond to RO2, providing insights into the factors driving individuals toward authentic leadership.

Research Objective 3: To explore the challenges encountered by authentic leaders within a developing economy context (RO3): The challenges faced by authentic leaders within a developing economy context are examined in response to Research Question 3 (RQ3). Financial constraints, poor governance, economic difficulties, and leadership complexities are highlighted as significant challenges. By identifying and

exploring these challenges, the findings attain RO3 by shedding light on the contextual and leadership obstacles encountered by authentic leaders.

Research Objective 4: To examine actions that shape the followers' perceptions of authentic leadership (RO4): The study investigates actions shaping followers' perceptions of authentic leadership in line with Research Question 4 (RQ4). Key actions identified include giving followers a voice, facilitating their development, and demonstrating consistency and transparency. These actions directly relate to RO4, offering insights into the specific actions that influence followers' perceptions of authentic leadership.

Research Objective 5: To propose an empirical-based model that contributes to understanding authentic leadership (RO5): The findings from chapters 6 and 7 contribute to the attainment of the research objectives of the study and lay the groundwork for the empirical based model presented in chapter 8, contributing to the understanding of authentic leadership.

The next chapter connects the findings to the broader academic debates.

CHAPTER 8. DISCUSSION ON AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP

INTRODUCTION

This study is focused on the construct of authentic leadership because of its perceived value within organisations and the broader society. Though scholars have engaged in debates on the theorising of the construct (Alvesson and Sveningsson, 2013; Alvesson and Einola, 2019; Iszatt-White and Kempster, 2019; Einola and Alvesson, 2021), there are suggestions for more scholarly efforts in the refinement of the theory and alternative perspectives to examining it (Gardner *et al.*, 2021; Ladkin, 2021; Gardner and McCauley, 2022). It therefore becomes important for a study of this nature.

The preceding chapter presented the results of the final two research questions of the study: What are the challenges that authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy, and what are the actions that shape employee perceptions of authentic leaders? Together with the findings reported in chapter 6 uncovering new insights on authentic leadership. Multiple perspectives were explored during the inquiry process drawing on the recommendations of Gardner and McCauley (2022), who state that discussions on authentic leadership resonate with leaders and followers, with these followers, in general, offering descriptions of leaders they consider authentic. Critics of authentic leadership argue that scholars have not thoroughly examined the real world experiences of authentic leaders (Sinclair, 2013; Gardiner, 2016).

Therefore, this penultimate chapter assesses the research findings in relation to the research questions and extant literature. In contrast to positivist modes of inquiry that ignore lived experiences, this study explores the distinct experiences of authentic leadership in a developing economy. Building on the recommendations of Alvesson and Deetz (1999) advocating that scholars explore leadership's contextual nature, as nuances differ from country to country (Fotohabadi and Kelly, 2018) which has been overlooked within literature (Eagly, 2005; Gardiner, 2016).

This chapter is structured to align with the research questions of the study. Section 8.1 explores the discussions around the components of authentic leadership. While section 8.2 unpacks the arguments on the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders. In section 8.3, challenges that plague authentic leaders are discussed. Section 8.4 then proceeds to examine actions that shape follower perceptions of authentic leadership. By making inferences from the literature, the concluding section 8.5 presents an empirical model of authentic leadership in the context of a developing economy. Section 8.6 concludes the chapter with a summary of these discussions. Overall, the chapter compares the study's findings to extant literature, thereby offering fresh perspectives on authentic leadership.

8.1 Looking beyond the four components of authentic leadership

In exploring authentic leadership, the respondents provided varied but complementary descriptions of the construct. From the in depth explanations offered by all 46 respondents, components were teased out during the analysis and synthesis of the empirical data. Six components: clarity of purpose, follower development, relational transparency, self awareness, internalised moral perspective, and concern for people were identified. Even though, three of these components; self awareness, internalised moral perspective, and relational transparency are evident in extant literature (Walumbwa et al., 2008), the respondents identified the fundamentals of these components.

In describing the components of authentic leadership, scholars have used various alternative terms. For instance, “attributes” (Ahmed *et al.*, 2018), “behaviours” (Clarke, Kelliher and Schedlitzki, 2013), “characteristics” (Gardiner, 2016), “dimensions” (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Alilyyani, Wong and Cummings, 2018; Fotohabadi and Kelly, 2018), “behaviours” (Bandura, Kavussanu and Ong, 2019), “competencies” (Akuffo and Kivipold, 2019) have been used interchangeably within extant literature.

These components are further broken down into internal and external categories. The internal types include internalised moral perspective, self regulation, and self awareness, while the external category include relational transparency and balanced processing. It is claimed that a leader's ability determine their internal competencies, while their interactions and relationships with followers determine their outward competencies (Akuffo and Kivipold, 2019).

Within the study, respondents described the components of authentic leadership in terms of obligations and expectations, evidencing the distinctive perspectives of leaders and followers. Authentic leaders described the components as their obligations towards themselves, their followers, and organisation. This sense of responsibility is often driven by a commitment to principles and a desire to serve others. While the followers described the components as expectations, expanding the discussions to capture their beliefs and presumptions regarding what their leader should do or how they should act. The research findings uncovered a six component model of authentic leadership as evidenced in the study.

Regarding components of authentic leadership, several scholars, draw on Kernis (2003) description of authenticity, captured in the article on optimal self esteem. The author identified "awareness, unbiased processing, action, and relational orientation" respectively. These components were integrated into authentic leadership and refined further to reflect the main debates within the domain. Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang (2005) also identified four components of authentic leadership namely "self awareness, unbiased processing, authentic behaviour/actions and relational authenticity (p. 377)." In a similar vein Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) study identified components of self awareness, an internalised moral perspective, balanced processing, and relational transparency. Despite the existence of more than 40 meta analyses on authentic leadership (Hoch *et al.*, 2018; Wernsing, 2018), only a small number of researchers have explored the components of this construct beyond the four components described by Walumbwa *et al.* (2008). However, drawing on the

arguments of scholars who have differing opinions on the exact components that constitute authentic leadership, the following discussions evaluate the results of the study in relation to existing literature (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Peus *et al.*, 2012).

8.1.1 Clarity of Purpose

Every respondent emphasised that having a clear sense of purpose is a crucial component of AL. This is not surprising as several scholars have alluded to this as a core underpinning in its emergence. Particularly due to the instabilities within organisations which lead to a yearning for leaders who provided meaning and direction (Gardner *et al.*, 2005). Respondents identified enabling environment, goal and knowledge orientation as constituents of clarity of purpose.

Authentic leadership emerged as a key part of positive leadership studies from earlier conceptualisation maturing to being described as a “root construct” (Gardner *et al.*, 2005: p. 315). The construct was proposed by Luthans and Avolio (2003) and presented as a broader leadership framework. This conceptualisation of authentic leadership is considered influential (Clarke, Kelliher and Schedlitzki, 2013) and is described as a marriage of ideas of the key authors on transformational leadership and positive organisational behaviour. It is claimed that the integration of these approaches through authentic leadership is crucial for the success of businesses (Luthans and Avolio, 2003).

In the same vein, other scholars have offered alternate explanations for the emergence of authentic leadership. These propositions emerged from a diverse range of influences which have impacted society and particularly organisations. These influences have ranged from bombing, extremism, stock market crash, and corporate scandals (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008). These reasons are crucial, because historical figures like Gandhi and Churchill have consistently emerged as leaders that address challenges during times of crisis, highlighting the need of having a clear sense of purpose as a fundamental aspect of authentic leadership.

The leadership provided by these individuals have been described by Luthans and Avolio (2003) as positive leadership and it is claimed that the need for positive leadership extends beyond society as this uncertainty is mirrored in organisations with the proliferation of the internet, competitive pressures, and the newest threat by Covid 19.

Descriptions of enabling environment were salient in discussions on the need and subsequent emergence of authentic leadership. Interestingly, Caza and Jackson (2011) identified environmental dynamics as an antecedent of authentic leadership specifically highlighting positive organisational context amongst others as critical for authentic leadership (Avolio *et al.*, 2004). These scholars argue that authentic leaders establish environments that uphold the company's guiding principles and core values, enabling the team to accomplish its goals (Fotohabadi and Kelly, 2018). This was highlighted by the followers describing this positive organisational context as an enabling environment aiding organisational performance (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Gardner and McCauley, 2022). The authentic leaders purposefully created this environment to facilitate the attainment of personal and organisational goals.

In describing goal orientation, Gardner *et al.* (2021) suggest that clarity of actions and goals be explored within the organisational context as it is crucial in leadership and, by extension, authentic leadership. Likewise, in expanding on the sub theme of knowledge orientation, scholars have argued that authentic leaders enhance their credibility by demonstrating their knowledge and expertise, as well as consistently achieving tangible and quantifiable outcomes (Gardner *et al.*, 2005). This was very critical for the respondents especially the followers who maintained that knowledge orientation reinforced clarity of purpose and facilitated performance across the organisation.

8.1.2 Follower Development

Follower development, referred to as authentic followership in extant literature (Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang, 2005; Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Malloy and Kavussanu, 2021) is considered a key component of AL. However, the follower development salient in the descriptions of both leaders and followers differed from the follower development evident in extant literature often described as authentic followership. The implication for this finding becomes critical as Gardner *et al.* (2005) argue that “authentic followership development mirrors the developmental processes of authentic leadership (p. 5).” This suggests that followership development is a consequence of authentic leadership and should be evidenced across several organisations. Moreover, this brings to the fore an unresolved question regarding the stage at which authentic followers transition into authentic leaders, revealing a limitation of this framework (Gardner *et al.*, 2005).

There is a clear distinction between followers and authentic followership. The term followers describe individuals within a leader's formal organisation and may include individuals with no formal reporting relationship with the leader (Gardner *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, the study conducted by Crawford *et al.* (2018) specifically examines the authentic follower (actor), rather than authentic followership (the process). This study aligns with extant literature that followers develop in this context and is a core component of authentic leadership, but is distinct from the view that these followers are an extension of authentic leaders.

Existing research emphasises the need of authentic leaders setting a good example to effectively influence their followers. These scholars have established a connection between role modelling and the development of followers (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang, 2005). Hence, role modelling has been discussed extensively within the authentic leadership domain, with scholars such as Gardner *et al.* (2005) portraying it as the core means of follower development. These scholars incorporated a positive connotation by suggesting that it is called positive modelling. Which is described as an act of setting an example and exhibiting sincere, moral

principles that encourage and drive others to imitate them. While these positive connotations were acknowledged by the respondents within the study, however authentic leaders emphasised leadership positioning and its implication for follower development as a contributing factor to organisational effectiveness.

Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang (2005) also describe it as positive behavioural models. However, for the authentic leaders within the study, the intention was not to develop authentic followership, but rather inspire, and motivate their team members to excel and harness their potentials. In a similar vein, in describing psychological capital authentic leaders stressed its significance for their followers and how it positively impacted their mental health and the organisation's outcomes. They described psychological capital as intangible yet powerful emotions and feelings that help followers thrive, especially during challenging times.

Several scholars have confirmed the role psychological capital plays in facilitating positive outcomes for stakeholders within organisation (Luthans and Avolio, 2003; Avolio and Gardner, 2005). Authentic leaders within the study also identified psychological states such as giving people hope, being optimistic, building resilience and developing efficacy which align with the psychological states of authentic leaders advanced by Luthans *et al.* (2006) which also accelerate follower development.

Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang (2005) argue that authentic leadership plays a crucial role in promoting the growth of followers' competencies. This was also acknowledged by the followers as all respondents alluded to the fact that follower development offered evidence that an authentic leader was successful. Also, support facilitate followers development as established by the respondents which aligns, with Gardner and McCauley (2022) reiterating that genuine support facilitates follower growth and development.

8.1.3 Relational Transparency

All respondents emphasised transparency in relationships. This is because being transparent in relationships encourage open and honest interactions, enabling leaders and followers to build trust and respect other perspectives (Gardner *et al.*, 2021). This component was deemed the most complex part of authentic leadership, as respondents confirmed that it involved the intricate dynamics of the relationship between a leader and one or more followers (Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017). The respondents claimed that authentic leaders need followers to accomplish relational transparency. As noted by Avolio and Gardner (2005), relational transparency describes how authentic leaders, and their followers communicate openly with one another. Gardner *et al.* (2005) stress this as a heightened level of openness. Their argument posits that relational transparency, among other components, is pivotal (Bravo, 2018) and contributes to organisational stability, as the leader's behaviours remain consistent across different situations (Spitzmuller and Ilies, 2010).

Similarly, in describing relational transparency, Fotohabadi and Kelly (2018) highlighted that authentic leaders are assessed by their authenticity and how it is presented across contexts. This aligns with Gardner *et al.* (2021) recommendation that authentic leaders refrain from rash self disclosure to unrelated audiences.

The study's findings support ensuing arguments within extant literature that relational transparency is a key component of AL because it facilitates efficient conflict resolution and aids in expectation management. Crawford *et al.* (2020) note that although intrapersonal components are essential to relational transparency, the current authentic leadership model does not adequately address interpersonal relationships. These scholars contend that relational transparency resides not only within the individual, where it is self measured, but also in the context of broader organisational relationships. Respondents within the study inferred that organisational leaders are accountable to themselves and other stakeholders within and outside their sphere of influence. Therefore, relational transparency should be

explored across authentic leaders and the broader relational dynamics within an organisation.

Lending precision to this argument, Muntz, Dormann and Kronenwett (2019) emphasise the significance of interpersonal relationships. These authors argue that relational transparency extend beyond the interpersonal relationships between authentic leaders and followers, to making other components of authentic leadership more evident (Černe, Jaklič and Škerlavaj, 2013). This is because self awareness, balanced processing, and an internalised moral perspective, are predominantly concerned with introspection and self reflection. The findings of the study align with prior research conducted on relational transparency and has implications for the field of authentic leadership. This is because it reveals the structure of relational transparency by further breaking it down to its sub constituents. These sub constituents of vulnerability, transparency and learning orientation are discussed below.

Authentic leaders were expected to be vulnerable in their interactions, sharing the good and the bad, aligning with arguments advanced by Spitzmuller and Ilies (2010) that disclosing both positive and negative aspects of oneself was necessary for interactions. This was an expectation from only authentic leaders. It is, however, essential to note that respondents acknowledged the imperfect nature of authentic leaders and their thought processes, as noted by Alvesson and Einola (2019) who assert that the self to be disclosed is neither immutable nor a single entity, but rather a multifaceted, situational, and ever changing construct.

Kempster, Iszatt-White and Brown (2019) also argue that relational transparency in leadership practice is somewhat paradoxical because leaders may disregard their vulnerabilities to meet the expectations of their followers or may also be constrained by organisational processes, such as the need to maintain confidentiality, which could inhibit openness. These scholars imply that the tension between authenticity and practice may explain why authentic leadership theory and its implementation in real

world situations are sometimes at odds. Specifically, this research demonstrated that followers acknowledged this tension but still expect authentic leaders to be open about their challenges and focus on building relationships with them (Černe, Jaklič and Škerlavaj, 2013; Gardner *et al.*, 2021).

There are also suggestions within extant literature that showing vulnerability can help establish trust, which is beneficial for authentic leaders and their followers (Ladkin and Taylor, 2010; Gardner *et al.*, 2021). These respondents affirmed, that trust is built during this process, which contribute positively to organisational performance (Gardner *et al.*, 2005; Bandura and Kavussanu, 2018). Developing a trusting relationship between authentic leaders and followers created the foundation for developing transparency, the second constituent of relational transparency. This sub constituent of relational transparency fosters the development of connections within AL (Alexander and Lopez, 2018). These authors assert that two executives cited transparency as a crucial element of effective leadership. In addition, they argue that there is a significant correlation between transparency and trustworthiness.

This claim is supported by existing literature, which define transparency as presenting one's authentic self to others, by emphasising openness in relationships. Previous scholars such as Bravo (2018), Karacay, Ertenu and Kabasakal (2018); Ahmed *et al.* (2018) have all identified the relational transparency component as the hallmark of authentic leadership, which was also confirmed by the respondents within the study.

8.1.4 Self Awareness

The majority of the "Stanford Graduate School of Business's Advisory Council" as noted by George *et al.* (2007) established that self awareness is considered the most crucial skill for leaders to cultivate. Furthermore, Gardner *et al.* (2021) propose that self awareness "provides the foundation for authenticity (p. 17)." In other words, being aware of oneself is the cornerstone of being authentic.

In the same vein, Anwar, Abid and Waqas (2020) defined authentic leaders as individuals that demonstrate self awareness and consistently adhere to their

principles and values within their organisations. This approach leads to positive outcomes, as indicated by Puni and Hilton (2020). This claim was evident as all 46 respondents highlighted the importance of self awareness within authentic leadership. Therefore, for leaders to find their purpose and comprehend how their experiences shape their self perception through time, it is crucial for them to possess a strong sense of self.

Self awareness calls for regular introspection, probing into one's feelings and thoughts, and getting input from others (Wernsing, 2018). For the respondents within the study, this self awareness was linked to their value system and beliefs that emerged from a deeper grasp of their principles, feelings, weaknesses, and strengths. All 46 respondents emphasised the significance of self awareness within their organisation iteratively, aligning with Corriveau (2020) arguments that the foundations of morality and self awareness are both essential for effective leadership (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008).

Underpinning the concept of self awareness is the debate on what constitutes the self in self awareness. In earlier conceptualisations, scholars generally propose that self awareness has two forms, private and public (Fenigstein, Scheier and Buss, 1975), also referred to as objective and subjective self awareness (Duval and Wicklund, 1972). Private self awareness describes reflection on one's inner states, including thoughts, emotions, and impressions and making oneself the subject of awareness. While the public's self awareness focuses on external factors and how one's behaviour affects others (Wernsing, 2018) even though the individual still remains the focus of reflections. The respondents within the study described self awareness in tangible terms suggesting that internally and externally focused reflections are required in authentic leadership.

Self awareness is described as a deeper comprehension of the complex character of the self and how people derive meaning from their interactions with others (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008; Arda, Aslan and Alpkan, 2016). This depicts the significance in

interpersonal interactions, supporting the saliency of the component from all 46 respondents within the study. Authentic leaders found it easy to articulate their understanding of self awareness, and followers were able to recognise in their organisations. Reiterating Diddams and Chang (2012) arguments that, authentic leaders have more than just a deep knowledge of themselves but their self knowledge, uncertainties, contradictions, and limitations.

While Gardner *et al.* (2005) defined "values, emotions, and goals" as aspects of self awareness that aid in the development of authentic leadership. The respondents provided an explanation of how the self awareness of authentic leaders are recognised and evaluated. The respondents identified self regulation and emotional intelligence as sub components of self awareness and as methods for evaluating the self awareness of authentic leaders, which is a developing process (Avolio and Gardner, 2005).

The significance of self regulation in promoting consistency is evident in the authentic leadership literature. For instance, Luthans and Avolio (2003) assert that self regulation supports the alignment of one's actual self with one's behaviours. Accordingly, Sparrowe (2005) contends that self regulation seeks to ensure alignment and coherence. Therefore, verbal expressions mirror one's inner voice. Hence, self-regulation, according to this perspective, is a process that allows leaders to align their behaviour with their actual selves, both implicitly and explicitly (George, 2003; Luthans and Avolio, 2003). Notably, Avolio and Gardner (2005) and Gardner *et al.* (2005) have acknowledged that self regulation is an essential component of authentic leadership development. However, respondents, particularly the authentic leaders, characterised this as the act of aligning their values with their goals and behaviours. These findings indicate self regulation and self awareness is not a separate component of authentic leadership, but rather an outcome and subordinate part of self awareness. Self reflection was also described as a tool for attaining self regulation, which is in line with the suggestion of Gardner *et al.* (2005) that it enhances clarity.

Finally, in discussing emotional intelligence as a constituent of self awareness, respondents argued that self awareness extended beyond authentic leaders. It also involved having a thorough understanding of the complex dynamics within organisations considering both personal and professional factors. This finding supports the vast literature on emotional intelligence, suggesting it contributes to self awareness.

8.1.5 Internalised Moral Perspective

Gardner *et al.* (2021) describe internalised moral perspective as “the incorporation of basic values such as respect for other's justice that make it less likely that a leader striving for authenticity will seek to reconcile a values or goal conflict with followers by simply imposing his or her will (p. 3).” The mainstream conceptualisation of internalised moral perspective posits that it is an introspective endeavour in which authentic leaders are guided by internal references and principles (Alilyyani, Wong and Cummings, 2018).

Accordingly, Monzani *et al.* (2019) argue that authentic leaders are guided by their internal values, which enable them resist external pressures. This concept is further described by Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) as an “internalised and integrated form of self regulation steered by internal values (p. 95–96).” The main argument surrounding this component is the issue of morals. The term “moral” is open to various definitions and interpretations as evidenced within extant literature. Hence, while it generally entails positivity and societal benefits, Alvesson and Einola (2019) note that questions arise regarding the limits of these morals and who determines which moral are considered appropriate. Some scholars, including Hannah, Avolio and Walumbwa (2014) connote that followers may play a role in defining these morals.

Within the study, both authentic leaders and followers recognised the importance of morals which shaped the decision making, interpretation of events and interactions. These respondents described internalised moral perspectives as internal convictions that shape authentic leaders. It is argued that authentic leadership is deeply rooted in

morality, thus an attribution of idealistic goals to authentic leaders, depicting these leaders as moral giants (Alvesson and Sveningsson, 2013). These depictions have been linked to religious undertones and examples. Authentic leaders are described as liberators from organisational moral decadence. A criticism of the saint like ascription. During discussions, respondents affirmed the importance of a moral element and revealed that their childhood experiences significantly impacted the formation of their values at an early age.

Building on the debates on the appropriateness of morals as advanced by Alvesson and Einola (2019) , there are also debates of which stakeholders should benefit from these morals: organisations, personnel, or owners. Nonetheless, Penger and Černe (2014) suggest that authentic leaders ensure their values align with their environment's established values and moral standards. This is consistent with Lawler and Ashman (2012) argument that authentic leadership require the ability to respond appropriately to challenges in addition to a person's exceptional moral character. Respondents within the study confirmed that they upheld their values during adversity and were willing to stand by their convictions.

These respondents maintained that internalised moral perspective must be evident in the interactions of authentic leaders aligning with George *et al.* (2007) argument that leadership is ethical when a person's internal values are ethical and evident to others (Sparrowe, 2005). This explains why authentic leaders are described as leaders with high moral standards and integrity (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005). Accordingly, May *et al.* (2003) argue that leaders can align their roles with ethical obligations that take into account their diverse stakeholders, such as followers, community, and society. Respondents stated that authentic leaders provide proof of internalised moral perspective through their value laden interactions, upholding their convictions regardless of the consequences.

8.1.6 Concern for People

In critiquing authentic leadership, Gardner *et al.* (2021) note that leaders cannot pretend to be genuinely concerned for people, as followers are perceptive and can see through the deceit. Respondents within the study argued that a genuine and sincere interest in the wellbeing, growth, and success of others characterises concern for people in authentic leadership. These respondents also suggested that authentic leaders prioritise the nurturing of meaningful relationships with their followers and strive to understand their needs, viewpoints, and emotions. Additionally, authentic leaders cultivate an inclusive and supportive space where all individuals feel valued, respected, and included. They promote open communication, collaboration, and feedback. These leaders provide resources, offer guidance, and provide support to foster the personal and professional growth of their team members, enabling them to reach their full potential.

Moreover, authentic leaders set a positive tone and demonstrate behaviours that reflect their genuine concern for their team's success. They are approachable, available, and responsive to the demands of their followers. In addition, they advocate for fairness, equity, and diversity and seek to have a positive impact not only on their team but also on society. These components have been incorporated into the definition of AL by several different scholars (Gardner *et al.*, 2005; Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer, 2015a), among others. See table 26 below presenting definitions and the breakdown of the components.

Table 26 Definitions and components of authentic leadership

Author (s)	Definitions	Components
Luthans and Avolio (2003)	<i>"a process that draws from both positive psychological capacities and a highly developed organisational context which results in both greater self awareness and self-regulated positive behaviours on the part of leaders and associates fostering positive self-development (p. 243)."</i>	Self awareness
Begley (2001)	<i>"As a metaphor for professionally effective, ethically sound, and consciously reflective practices in educational administration. This is leadership that is knowledge based, values informed, and skilfully executed (p. 353)."</i>	Self awareness, Clarity of purpose

Begley (2004)	<i>"a function of self-knowledge, sensitivity to the orientations of others, and a technical sophistication that leads to a synergy of leadership action (p.5) ."</i>	Self awareness, Relational transparency
Walumbwa et al. (2008)	<i>"As a pattern of leader behaviour that draws upon and promotes both positive psychological capacities and a positive ethical climate, to foster greater self-awareness, an internalised moral perspective, balanced processing of Information, and relational transparency on the part of leaders working with followers, fostering positive self-development (p. 94)."</i>	Self awareness, Relational transparency, Internalised moral perspective, balanced processing
Fotohabadi and Kelly (2018)	<i>"a process in which the leader is genuinely aware of his or her thinking and behaviour and the context within which it lies (p. 72)."</i>	Self awareness

Adapted from Gardner et al. (2011)

The significance of identifying the key dimensions of authentic leadership that produce a theoretically grounded description of the construct was emphasised by Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005) over 16 years ago. With suggestions, scholars build on initial definitions offered within the domain and adopt a qualitative method deemed necessary in discovering these dimensions. This study responds to the call and defines authentic leadership as the "a purpose driven leadership anchored in the leader's self awareness. It thrives through transparent relationships with stakeholders, nurturing follower development in the attainment of organisational objectives."

8.2 Becoming an authentic leader: Critical factors

Leadership development is yet to receive adequate attention within the leadership scholarship domain (Avolio, 2010). Accordingly, there is a need for more research on leadership development including authentic leadership (Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer, 2015a). The development of authentic leaders has been a key part and an ongoing debate within authentic leadership theory (Caza and Jackson, 2011; Baron and Parent, 2015). It is a common theme within extant literature (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Sparrowe, 2005) with increasing attention placed on identifying practical and useful interventions (Gill and Caza, 2018). Several scholars have acknowledged the difficulty accompanying authentic leadership development

(Baron, 2016; Kuechler and Stedham, 2018; Byrne, Crossan and Seijts, 2018). These difficulties have been linked to complexities in the areas of personalities, attitudes and conduct (Baron, 2016) that are more aligned to traditional teaching techniques (Conger and Benjamin, 1999).

Within the study, authentic leaders identified four factors that inspire authentic leadership development: family structure, belief and conviction, leadership, and a desire to leave a legacy. In expanding the discussions on the role of family structure, the authentic leaders stated that their family positioning became the seed implanted in them during their childhood which blossomed into authentic leadership in their adult life. This was an interesting finding as extant literature highlights the role of the family and childhood experiences collectively described as personal histories as antecedents of AL. However, no explicit reference is made to family positioning (Sergeeva and Kortantamer, 2021).

These authentic leaders further emphasised the roles and responsibilities that plagued these family positioning serving as a subtle reinforcement. Within extant literature, scholars argue that authentic leadership capacities are innate which are then influenced by trigger events that will be discussed subsequently (Luthans and Avolio, 2003).

In expanding on the discussion on beliefs and convictions as one of the factors that inspire authentic leadership, this begins with a helpful definition of values offered by Schwartz (1999) "Which is the conception of the desirable that guide the way social actors select actions, evaluate people and events and explain their actions and evaluations (pp. 24-25)." Respondents established that their values informed their beliefs and convictions, which serve as a reference point during decision making, inspiring authentic leadership development.

Luthans and Avolio (2003) and May *et al.* (2003) have highlighted the role of a moral element within authentic leadership development, which help authentic leaders handle, moral quandaries and consistently come to morally sound choices. However, other scholars have concerns about describing authentic leadership as including this positive psychological trait (Sparrowe, 2005; Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005). Suggesting that the moral component may be antecedents or consequences of AL (Avolio and Gardner, 2005). This aligns with the responses of all the 16 authentic leaders that participated in the study, as their beliefs and convictions had been ingrained in them before their leadership journey began.

The 16 authentic leaders highlighted the significance of beliefs and convictions in cultivating authentic leadership. They viewed these as being fundamental principles that shape their priorities and actions. These authentic leaders emphasised the crucial role of values and beliefs in supporting authentic leadership development, highlighting their importance for fostering growth. Interestingly these beliefs and convictions were not described as moral or ethical components but as personal values. Interestingly, they recognised that their religious convictions also played a crucial role in their authentic leadership development.

In discussing the role of leadership in AL development, the respondents identified specific positive and negative leadership experiences that facilitated their authentic leadership development. This was a key finding of the study as extant literature have generally emphasised trigger events and leadership crucibles as factors that inspire authentic leadership development. Even though, these factors were highlighted by the respondents within the study and would be discussed subsequently, authentic leaders brought to the fore the implicit role of leadership in inspiring authentic leadership development.

Several leaders, including Chief executive officers of organisations, aspire to be authentic but must learn how to achieve authenticity in their leadership (George *et al.*, 2007). The study's findings established that no universal features, qualities, or tactics

enabled them to attain success. In contrast, their leadership developed from a myriad of personal experiences, which enabled leaders uncover who they were, affirming the reason and purpose of their leadership.

George *et al.* (2007) suggest that people can become authentic leaders by evaluating personal experiences to become more self aware. This will enable them act in accordance with their ideologies. This requires a delicate balance between actions shaped by inner values and external appropriateness, which may have associated rewards or penalties. In summary, to become authentic, you must first grasp your personal life story, which for authentic leaders extends broadly over the full array of positive and negative experiences. These experiences, whether positive or negative, are reframed by authentic leaders to discover the purpose of their leadership.

Respondents also highlighted the role of legacy in inspiring authentic leadership development and this desire to leave a legacy was motivated by: trigger events, crucibles, and personal fulfilment. Positive associations have been ascribed to trigger events that generally denote bad occurrences (Gardner *et al.* (2005), with suggestions that trigger events may capture positive life changing events. While these suggestions remain true, as evidenced by the respondents when re counting trigger events, particularly negative experiences, these authentic leaders described a process of introspection and reassessment of their values and priorities, contemplating their legacy and what truly mattered to them. This indicates a selfless and altruistic propensity to make decisions that reflect their values.

These trigger events may be prearranged or unplanned, and studies have supported trigger events stimulating authentic leadership development (Luthans and Avolio, 2003; Harvey, Martinko and Gardner, 2006). Trigger events shape a leader's outlook, principles and behaviours (Luthans and Avolio, 2003) and impact positive psychological capabilities, which is a state that can be developed. These positive psychological capabilities also contribute to the innate capabilities of authentic leaders. Therefore, there are suggestions that planned trigger events can be used

positively to develop authentic leadership, exploiting learned capabilities such as confidence, hope, optimism, and resiliency labelled as self development. Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005) suggest that adversities as well as recurring events (Luthans and Avolio, 2003), positive challenging experiences (Bennis and Thomas, 2002) and accumulation of smaller events (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005) contribute to AL development.

Similarly, Thomas (2008) suggests that trigger events and leadership crucibles are key to leadership development. This supports Avolio's (2005) assertion that leadership development is rooted in learning, propelling individuals to accomplish their leadership potential. Accordingly, Shannon *et al.* (2020) suggest that these learning measures comprise several formats. Their study explicitly examines trigger events and leadership crucibles and how these may contribute to developing authentic leaders' self awareness. Though, these two appear similar and have been used interchangeably by scholars, they are distinct concepts.

Equally, Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005) argue that significant life events may trigger personal growth necessary for authentic leadership development. These events impact and, in most circumstances, reshape the world views and leadership approach. In contrast, leadership crucibles are described by Thomas (2008) as difficulties or challenging situations which make individuals question their purpose and what they represent. Like trigger events, Bennis and Thomas (2002, p. 6) describe the ability to surpass challenges as a critical attribute of exceptional leaders, termed the "crucibles of leadership." This is like George *et al.* (2007) suggestion that the interpretations assigned to these events determine their implication for leadership development.

In discussing the legacy factor of authentic leadership development, personal fulfilment was also highlighted as a constituent of the legacy factor, and it was emphasised by the respondents. The individual choices of leaders drive the process of becoming authentic leaders. These choices define whom they become as leaders,

charting their path from a pool of endless possibilities (Lawler and Ashman, 2012). These arguments align with the findings of the study as respondents described distinct trigger events and crucibles that inspired their AL development.

In the earlier approach to leadership development, scholars examined the life stories of leaders, searching for events in their early life or career which may have contributed to the leader's development (Burns, 1978; Avolio and Gibbons, 1988). The authentic leaders within the study all shared a specific pivotal experience which occurred early in their childhood and launched their journey towards authentic leadership development.

These scholars have reiterated the importance of including context in leadership models (House and Aditya, 1997). Similarly, Day (2000) emphasises the importance of investigating the context of leadership development. In the same vein, Avolio (2003) suggests that leadership development transpires in diverse emerging contexts. Hence it becomes essential for the context to be prepared for leadership development.

8.3 Challenges of Authentic Leaders

In this subsection, the challenges of authentic leadership are explored, drawing upon extant literature to reveal the complexities experienced by authentic leaders. Even though, the leadership domain has retained an upward trend in exploration, there have been lulls in theory advancement (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005; Alvesson and Einola, 2019). Hence, by critically examining the challenges this thesis contributes to a deeper understanding of AL and its practical implications for leaders in organisational contexts.

The respondents described challenges that aptly captured the paradoxes they encounter in their leadership. Scholars have acknowledged these tensions, and arguments have been made in favour of the advantages that organisation stakeholders might obtain when authentic leaders attempt to resolve these tensions (Gardner *et al.*,

2021). It is widely accepted that authentic leaders may face challenges in living up to their stated ideals, particularly when making tough decisions (Gardner *et al.*, 2021; Gardner and McCauley, 2022). In these instances, it may be unrealistic for authentic leaders to always portray their true emotions in every situation without considering social cues. The respondents in the study acknowledged this struggle and recognised that the actions they needed to take in their organisations sometimes conflicted with their emotions. However, they were willing to prioritise their values over their feelings to uphold their authenticity. As authentic leadership demands the balancing of paradoxes and tensions with commitments and organisational needs (Ladkin and Taylor, 2010).

Within extant literature, positive organisational climates are critical in AL (Gardner *et al.*, 2005; Luthans and Avolio, 2003), as a supportive organisational climate creates more opportunities for authentic leadership to thrive. Such an enabling environment fosters the development of all organisational stakeholders (Gardner *et al.*, 2005). Hence, the lack of such a climate becomes problematic for authentic leadership.

Einola and Alvesson (2021) in their critique of AL suggest that organisational complexities impact the authenticity of authentic leaders, as these contexts offer limited opportunities for authentic leadership to thrive (Einola and Alvesson, 2021; Gardner *et al.*, 2021). In contrast, Gardner *et al.* (2021) argue that there are organisational climates that facilitate AL development.

Within the study, respondents recognised the role of organisational and, in a broader sense, the national context of the study, Nigeria, which is marred corruption and instability issues. These authentic leaders stated that the context of study is problematic and sometimes frustrating when navigating the challenges. However, these authentic leaders affirmed their resolve to uphold their values and convictions in challenging contexts. At the same time, the followers in the study emphasised the importance of a positive organisational context the authentic leaders could create, foster and nurture despite broader challenges within and outside the organisational

context. The findings from the study confirm that organisational complexities and broader societal influences impact authentic leadership and are identified as challenges authentic leaders encounter within a developing economy context.

8.4 Specific actions that shape the employee perceptions of authentic leaders

It is crucial to understand how followers perceive leadership (Bradley-Cole, 2018). These leadership perceptions by followers emerge from key mental groups or leader prototypes (Braun, Peus and Frey, 2018) rooted in the experiences of the followers. Hence, drawing present conclusions from past interactions to determine if the individual is a leader or not. Scholars have examined how followers affirm if their leaders are authentic or not. This ongoing debate revolves around the assessment of a leader's authenticity. Some contend that it resides exclusively within the leader's domain, while others argue that it is a matter of attribution, subject to the perceptions of others (Černe, Jaklič and Škerlavaj, 2013).

Authentic leadership emerges from internal processes driven by the authentic leader, accessed through introspection and external perceptions by others, both of which are central to leadership effectiveness (Černe, Jaklič and Škerlavaj, 2013). Furthermore, Goffee and Jones (2005) argue that the followers' perception of authentic leadership carries more significance than the leader's personal perception. Inclusion, transparency, integrity, collaboration, courage, empowerment and vision, have been identified as key behaviours of authentic leaders, especially when they are just starting out in their career (Bradley-Cole, 2018). Similarly, authentic leadership behaviours within extant literature include integrity and honesty (Avolio et al., 2004). It is crucial to uncover this perspective as followers respond favourably to leaders who are perceived as authentic (Caza and Jackson, 2011).

The process of human perception is believed to involve various elements, including acquaintance, overlap, shared meaning, consistency, extraneous information and communication (Fields, 2007). The term acquaintance describes the extent of

information flowing from the principal to the perceiver. Overlap describes the degree to which two or more perceivers see identical behaviours from the principal. Furthermore, shared meaning describes the level to which perceivers assign similar meanings to the principal's behaviours. Consistency describes the stability of the principal's behaviours across diverse contexts. While extraneous information describes the extent to which a principal is evaluated based on information instead of only personal traits and behaviours. Communication outlines how frequently individuals express their opinions about the principal. These components capture the elements that inform followers' inferences about authenticity; however, the leader's role within a specific context and previous conduct also contribute to a follower's perception (Fields, 2013).

Furthermore, employees' impression of their manager's or leaders' authenticity have favourable consequences for the authentic leader (Goffee and Jones, 2005; Banks *et al.*, 2016). Specifically, research suggests that the extent to which leaders' and followers' perception of authentic leadership align results in favourable outcomes (Černe, Jaklič and Škerlavaj, 2013), positive emotions (Jensen and Luthans, 2006a) and performance (Walumbwa *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, it is essential to identify these actions and assess whether they produce authentic leadership perceptions.

It may be challenging for followers to evaluate a leader's authenticity and the degree to which their actions reflect their inner values, unless they can observe the actions of these leaders (Mehmood, Hamstra and Schreurs, 2019). Likewise, there is an argument that the prevailing perception of authenticity in leaders is self referential, making it a concealed and challenging aspect to evaluate for both leaders and their followers. (Alvesson and Einola, 2019).

The actions of authentic leaders are critical within authentic leadership as they serve as a tangible representation of authentic leaders' values and beliefs. These actions are avenues through which authentic leaders communicate with followers (May *et al.*, 2003). Furthermore, Gardner *et al.* (2005) contend that the actions of leaders shape

followers' perceptions of authentic leadership, which is critical as Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005) argue that perceptions vary across authentic leaders and followers. Therefore, authentic leaders should ensure that their actions are consistent with their values to shape the way their followers perceive them.

The study supports current thinking in emerging followership research by highlighting the role of followers in the leadership process, as emphasised in the literature (Carsten *et al.*, 2010; Gardner *et al.*, 2021). The actions of authentic leaders are critical as they serve as a tangible representation of authentic leaders' values and beliefs. Ladkin and Taylor (2010) suggest that AL is an experience and authentic leaders' "an embodiment of self (p. 65)" to be seen as authentic by followers. Drawing on Stanislavski (1961) arguments, actions are not just physical portrayals but are laden with purpose and meaning. Hence, Ladkin and Taylor (2010) suggest scholars explore ways that inform the follower's perception of authentic leadership, which have implications for authentic leadership development.

Within the study, followers identified four key actions that shape their perceptions of authentic leadership: followers' voice, follower development, consistency, and transparency. These followers implied that the alignment of words and actions inspired, empowered, and motivated them, contributing to organisational performance. These followers were quick to establish that authentic leaders communicate their plans, goals, concerns, and messages through their actions, demonstrating what they stand for. In addition, followers evaluated a leader's authenticity by observing the leader's actions (Černej, Jaklič and Škerlavaj, 2013).

Interestingly, studies suggest that these follower perceptions are shaped over time, confirming that authentic leaders' actions become discernible over time (Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim, 2005). The assertion has been validated by respondents in the study as followers clarified that their perceptions of or not attributing authentic leadership to organisational leaders occurred over a long period, impacting outcomes and performance within the organisation. In giving followers a voice, the respondents

explained that this became evident from collaborative processes, balanced processing and courage initiated and demonstrated by the authentic leaders. Within literature, collaboration is described as an outcome of authentic leadership (Regan, Laschinger and Wong, 2016; Shirey, White-Williams and Hites, 2019).

In describing follower voice within extant literature, scholars have argued in favour of granting voice to the values of authentic leaders and reiterating the benefits of their opinions, perspectives and thoughts (Gardner *et al.*, 2021). This was a departure from the followers' voice highlighted within the study.

The term unbiased processing emerged from Kernis (2003) work on optimal self esteem, where four constituents of authenticity were identified. Unbiased processing describes the presentation of information without denials or distortions. Avolio and Gardner (2005) introduced the term balanced processing acknowledging research in cognitive psychology that suggest that humans have inherent biases (Tice and Wallace, 2003) . Thus, recognising the capacity of authentic leaders to explore several perspectives. Despite being acknowledged as a component of authentic leadership by various scholars (Gardner *et al.*, 2005), the respondents within this study described it as a constituent of the follower's voice. Fotohabadi and Kelly (2018) argue that a crucial sign of authentic leadership is outlining one's position on issues within the organisation, which contributes to balanced processing. Courageous leaders also serve as prime examples of authentic leadership, a notion supported by the findings of Gardner *et al.* (2021), which was corroborated by the respondents of the study with specificity to followers.

In describing follower development, Gardner *et al.* (2005) suggest that through “increased self awareness, self regulation and positive modelling authentic leaders foster the development of authenticity in followers (p. 317).” Furthermore, positive role modelling is described by Avolio and Gardner (2005) and Luthans and Avolio (2003) as an approach to facilitating follower development.

An authentic relationship, by as defined by Gardner *et al.* (2005) is a process characterised by a sequence of encounters between leaders and followers. In this process, both sides actively develop self awareness and mutually influence each other. Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang (2005) qualify these relationships as heightened, leading to reciprocity that positively impacts followers. Within the study, followers highlighted the importance of relationship management in shaping their perception of authentic leadership within their organisations instead of authentic relationships. In contrast, they viewed relationship management as authentic leaders' proactive approach to establish and maintain strong relationships with stake holders. This enabled authentic leaders handle conflicting organisational priorities and disputes constructively. According to these followers, relationship management included interactions with individual followers and the organisation. The statement above suggests that not all followers led by authentic leaders achieved authentic followership as a result.

Consistency was also salient in the discussions on actions that shape employee perceptions of authentic leadership. Interestingly, scholars such as Sparrowe (2005) have described consistency emerging as a “ result of self awareness and self regulation working in concert (p. 423)”. With followers actively searching for this consistency in authentic leaders. It is argued that authentic leaders must act with integrity consistently to be perceived as authentic (Endrissat, Müller and Kaudela-Baum, 2007). This aligned with the findings of the study where authentic leaders were expected to demonstrate consistency in their actions and their espoused beliefs, aligning with existing arguments that consistency should be demonstrated in beliefs, values , morals and interactions with others (Hirst *et al.*, 2016; Onyalla, 2018; McAuliffe, Bostain and Witchel, 2019).Furthermore, Gill *et al.* (2018) describe consistency as one of the three distinct features that reflect authentic leadership . This is unsurprising as all followers highlighted the importance of consistency. In describing consistency followers argued that authentic leaders demonstrate their convictions over time across

diverse contexts thus bringing to the fore their essence in their daily interactions across organisational settings.

Finally, considering transparency, Bradley-Cole (2018) contends authentic relationships are established mainly by the conduct of the authentic leader, which includes qualities such as transparency and openness. Transparency and consistency were discussed side by side by most respondents and when asked the most influential actions that shaped their perceptions these two actions are reiterated by the followers. In some instances, laced with emotions as these respondents' described leaders, they had encountered who had not demonstrated these in their leadership.

Most of the discussions on transparency within extant literature have been linked to the component of relational transparency (Hassan and Ahmed, 2011; Petan and Bocarnea, 2016; Puni and Hilton, 2020; Al-Jaradat *et al.*, 2020). These studies emphasise openness in emotions, opinions, and views without misleading their followers on their true intentions. This perspective was evident during discussions with followers as they confirmed that this openness allowed them to give their leaders second chances where errors were perceived to have been made. They were also more forgiving of their leaders whenever in doubt in their various organisations. Transparency in communication has also been explored extensively within extant literature with scholars suggesting transparent communication of authentic leaders facilitate leadership effectiveness (Men and Stacks, 2014; Jiang and Luo, 2018). Followers upheld this view as transparent organisational communication was discussed as a critical action that shaped their perceptions of their leaders whether authentic or not. However, for authentic leaders it was critical as followers described it as a lubricant that glued their perceptions despite the complexities that emerged within organisations while awaiting clarity on decisions made within the organisation (Tijani and Okunbanjo, 2020; Jiang and Shen, 2023). In essence, these actions highlighted above impacted the perceptions of followers and should be explored further in

developing interventions for authentic leadership development. The next section presents the empirical model of the study.

8.5 Empirical model of authentic leadership

The study's conceptual framework is represented in Figure 16, and the research findings have subsequently informed the creation of the empirical model presented in below. This section presents a six component model of AL, their comparative consequence, and the interrelationships across the variables. Considering that most of the scholarly works that have emerged have been largely conceptual with other studies being predominantly quantitative in nature. This empirical model offers a reference point that will be valuable in organisations, leadership programmes and the broader society. Using the data obtained from the synthesis in the earlier sections of the chapter, it is expected that this study will steer further debates on authentic leadership across diverse contexts. As scholars have emphasised the need for several perspectives in unpacking this construct.

Central to this were four research questions that guided the study as captured in section 1.5. The study systematically addressed each research question, attempting to reveal nuanced insights into the phenomenon of authentic leadership. It began with an exploration of the components of authentic leadership, uncovering its underlying structure and essence. The study then explored the factors that inspire its development. By synthesising the empirical evidence, it identified key factors that contribute to its development, thereby enriching existing debates on leadership development. A significant aspect of the thesis was the investigation of the contextual challenges encountered by authentic leaders operating within a developing economy. It sought to reveal the unique socio economic dynamics that shape the practice of authentic leadership in such environments.

The study examined the complexities of leader-follower interactions, analysing how leaders' actions influence the perceptions of authenticity among followers. Through

the data provided by the respondents, it uncovered the specific actions that contribute to the perceptions of authentic leadership. All the findings of the four research questions contributed to the development of the empirical model that offers a nuanced understanding of AL, attaining objective 5 of this study, which was “To propose an empirical based model that contributes to understanding authentic leadership.” This model represents a significant contribution to the academic discourse and complexities inherent in authentic leadership.

An empirically developed model offers benefits for the field. This is because it can act as a valuable catalyst for broadening the current understanding on authentic leadership. Furthermore, qualitative studies can offer reliable methods for building distinct models and finding practise areas that are challenging (Husbands *et al.*, 2017). While quantitative studies have been closely associated with model development, qualitative studies have also been recognised as providing robust approaches to model development. An empirical model that will serve as the basis for more research has been developed through this in depth exploration of AL. This model pulls together components and viewpoints to provide a foundation for directing more research and discovery. See figure 26 presenting the six component model of authentic leadership.

Figure 26 Six Component Model of Authentic Leadership

This model is built upon the assumption that organisations, particularly in the context of developing economies, are experiencing growing challenges. Thus, requiring leaders that can address the complexities and organisational problems. The six component model of authentic leadership outlines six crucial components. While self awareness, relational transparency, and internalised moral perspective have been extensively discussed in the literature, the remaining three components follower development (Hinojosa *et al.*, 2014; Yasir *et al.*, 2016), clarity of purpose (Beddoes-Jones, 2011; Gardiner, 2015), and concern for people (Ogunyemi and Ogunyemi, 2020) have not received sufficient attention. Follower development is recognised as a critical aspect of authentic leadership, however clarity of purpose, although vaguely associated with performance and concern for people lacks detailed explorations as components of authentic leadership.

Several conceptual models of authentic leadership emphasise leaders occupying important roles within organisations and the broader society. These models concentrate on top leaders in their descriptions and debates. However, the six component model suggests that authentic leadership can be inspired by four main factors which can occur at any level of the organisation as evidenced from the findings of the study. However, what is critical to note is the link between challenges of authentic leadership and the factors that inspire its development in the first instance. There is a mutually reinforcing relationship between these two components of the model. This directly influences the psychological and emotional states of authentic leaders, thereby opening avenues for additional research into the nature of the relationship between the challenges of AL and the factors that stimulate its growth. Figure 27 below provides an expanded overview of this mutually reinforcing relationship.

Figure 27 Reinforcing relationship between factors and challenges

A positive feedback loop between challenges of AL and factors that inspire its development was evident from the data. Therefore, when authentic leaders confronted challenges on their leadership journey, the outcomes of these experiences further strengthened their initial aspiration to be authentic, intensifying their initial desire and subsequently expediting the entire process. The loop at the bottom of the diagram suggests that positive feedback loop initiates a mutually reinforcing cycle which facilitates the authentic leadership development process. However, it is critical to state that if not properly aligned and balanced, this loop may also lead to unfavourable outcomes.

The challenges posed by authentic leadership also had an influence on the actions of authentic leaders within the organisations, subsequently shaping the perceptions of the followers. This finding holds significant importance as these perceptions have a substantial impact on organisational performance, either positively or negatively, depending on how followers perceive them. These four actions of authentic leaders when demonstrated positively shaped the perceptions of followers. Also, these

positive perceptions have contributed to organisational outcomes. In a similar vein, these actions shaped the experiences of the followers influencing their sense making and descriptions of AL.

Finally, the model captures the six components of AL uncovered within the study. This is crucial for the authentic leadership domain as it provides conceptual links for the components of authentic leadership. The new components: clarity of purpose, concern for people and follower development uncovered within the study bring to light the importance of the expectation of followers within the domain. Furthermore, it unveils the critical constituents of these components, which will facilitate leadership development within the domain. It is also crucial to state that components of authentic leadership serve as pillars of support for the perceptions connected to this leadership approach. When all these components are in place and working together, a strong foundation is established for leaders to demonstrate authentic leadership. Therefore, these components underpin authentic leadership actions. This influences how followers perceive the situation, motivating them to engage more actively and positively within the organisational context, as supported by the empirical evidence revealed in the study.

In conclusion, organisations may develop leaders who embody authenticity by exploring the variables of the model which support and underpin perceptions of authentic leadership. With this knowledge, aspiring authentic leaders or failed leaders may use their authentic selves to establish connections, develop meaningful interactions with followers, and uphold moral principles. The model serves as a valuable tool as it can be implemented by directly applying the principles outlined in the model to guide leadership development initiatives. Furthermore, it can serve as a valuable guide and reference for fostering effectiveness, offering insights that would inform the design and execution of leadership development initiatives.

8.6 Conclusion

This chapter provides an interpretation of the study's findings, incorporating a synthesis of the data to address research questions. It involves a review and comparison of the study's findings with the existing literature on authentic leadership. In uncovering the components of authentic leadership, the study extends current knowledge revealing three additional components of authentic leadership: clarity of purpose, follower development and concern for people. The study unpacks constituents of the prominent components of relational transparency and self awareness, internalised moral perspective offering new implications for research and practice of authentic leadership.

In addressing the second research question on factors that inspire authentic leadership development, four factors; family structure, belief and conviction, leadership, and legacy, were salient across descriptions offered by the respondents. These factors provide complementary interventions for AL development, particularly within the study context. In addressing the third research question, four key challenges were identified respectively: financial challenges, inadequate governance and regulation, and economical challenges, which focus on context and finally the leadership challenges, which capture personal paradoxes of these leaders. In addressing the final research question of the study, the followers identified giving followers a voice, facilitating follower development, and demonstrating consistency and being transparent when describing actions that shape their perceptions of AL.

Finally, in the penultimate section of this chapter an empirical model is presented capturing the findings, and the interrelationships across the variables within the model. The next and concluding chapter provides an overview of the thesis, highlighting the contributions and constraints of the study. It summarises findings of the study at both theoretical and practical levels, emphasising the contributions to knowledge and real world applications.

CHAPTER 9. CONCLUSION

INTRODUCTION

This concluding chapter offers a snapshot of the investigative process in unpacking the construct of AL within a developing economy context. In the introductory sections of the study, an exploration of authentic leadership was conducted, assessing how scholars have examined the construct. The review of extant literature offered several themes to be explored, as evidenced in chapters 2, 3 and 4 of the study.

For this study, a qualitative enquiry was done partly, because the domain is replete with quantitative studies focused on the leadership approach's outcomes. Which has led to several studies supporting the value of authentic leadership on organisational outcomes without adequate appraisal of the construct and inherent relationships that facilitate its development. Inspiration was also drawn from Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005) recommendations that the construct be rigorously researched before interventions are proposed in order to avoid the pitfalls that previous leadership approaches have encountered. Even though, this article was written over 18 years ago, recent studies continue to reiterate the need for further theorising of authentic leadership (Gardner *et al.*, 2021; Iszatt-White and Kempster, 2019; Einola and Alvesson, 2021) in order to expand on aspects of the theory that appear puzzling. Scholars such as Avolio and Gardner (2005); Luthans and Avolio (2003), van Droffelaar and Jacobs (2017) and practitioners George (2003) have been advocating for the development of authentic leaders, which has become amplified in the face of instability exasperated by the COVID pandemic (Omeihe, Omeihe and Harrison, 2021; Tourish, 2020).

Therefore, the study explores the underpinning building blocks of authentic leadership by investigating its key components, further unpacking its subcomponents, and identifying factors that inspire its development in the face of

challenges encountered by these leaders. These are juxtaposed with an understanding of actions that shape follower perceptions to offer an empirical model for authentic leadership.

With the evident paucity of research examining authentic leadership outside the predominant western narratives, especially the limited research on developing economy context, the study addresses this gap in the literature by addressing four research questions within the study:

What are the components of authentic leadership?

What are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders?

What are the challenges that authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy?

What are the actions that shape employee perceptions of authentic leaders?

In the inquiry process, a theoretical approach which involved the scrutiny of authentic leadership literature was undertaken, and the conclusions drawn from this led to the development of the conceptual framework in chapter 4. The conceptual framework acknowledged authentic leadership as a valuable approach, especially in times of instability, with several benefits for the authentic leader, followers, organisation, and the broader society. However, the underpinning components of the construct and subcomponents have yet to be adequately explored hence the evident stagnation and, in recent times, gaslighting of the domain (Gardner and McCauley, 2022; Alvesson and Einola, 2022). Please refer to Figure 16 for the conceptual framework.

This chapter begins with a summary of key arguments within each chapter, where discussions on authentic leadership and its exploration are evaluated. Then, the methodological choices that shaped the study are highlighted, summarising key research findings. The chapter goes ahead to provide an overview of the research's strengths, limitations, and emphasises its unique contributions to both theory and practice. The evidence from the study corroborates the recommendations of Tourish (2019) and Gardner *et al.* (2021) regarding the significance of establishing a connection between theory and practice.

The chapter then highlights the research implications of the study and concludes with plausible research directions for future efforts. The subsequent section presents an overview of each chapter in the study.

9.1 Summary of chapters

Chapter 1 offers an entry point to the exploration of authentic leadership. It introduces the research topic, the research problem's background, and the study's rationale. This chapter justifies the need to study authentic leadership by explicating its role, value, and significance within the organisational context. In expanding on the rationale for the study, the chapter presents the gaps identified within extant literature, emphasising the need for the study, within a developing economy context.

The rationale for the adoption of a qualitative study is provided justifying why an abductive reasoning approach was adopted in the exploration of the construct. The phenomenological research strategy was employed to uncover new insights into the phenomenon of authentic leadership, and it involved collecting data through semi-structured interviews, which were analysed using King, Horrocks and Brooks (2019) three-stage thematic process. When examining the originality of this study, it becomes apparent that it brings fresh perspectives, and novel insights that go beyond the current understanding of the construct in three crucial areas drawing on the recommendations of Phillips and Pugh (1994); Guetzkow, Lamont and Mallard (2004).

The contribution section describes the relevance of the research and the gaps the study has addressed. Specifically, the study made empirical, theoretical, and methodological contributions. In terms of empirical contributions, the study collected primary data to generate empirical findings from authentic leaders and their followers in addressing the four research questions of the study. Firstly, the identification strategy adopted for authentic leaders advanced the field as extant literature is replete with famous leaders identified as authentic with little or no guidance on identifying these leaders in

context. So, the study identified followers who, in turn, identified the authentic leaders that offered profound insights into the authentic leadership construct.

The empirical contributions had implications for the theoretical aspect of the study as the findings challenged some established models like the “self based model of authentic leaders and follower development” advanced by Gardner et al. (2005). This model is useful for developing authentic leadership and followership, who would also become authentic leaders. However, followers within the study did not seek to become authentic leaders in the future.

Regarding the theoretical contribution of the study, a model for unpacking authentic leadership and its development within a developing economy is offered, expanding the current theoretical understanding of the leadership domain.

Regarding the methodological contribution, a systematic literature review was conducted within the domain to understand the boundaries of knowledge within authentic leadership. Accordingly, this study utilised two non-probability sampling techniques: purposive and snowballing, in identifying authentic leaders within the study. This was to ensure authentic leaders were identified objectively by the followers and not by the intuitions or personal evaluations of the researcher. The chapter concludes with a discussion on the organisation of the study. It describes how the subsequent chapters are structured to convey the research process and findings. The layout of this chapter serves as a roadmap for navigating the thesis.

Chapters 2, 3 and 4 are review chapters. These three chapters examine aspects of leadership, leadership development, authenticity, authentic leadership, and context, providing a critical analysis of the existing research in the field. In Chapter 2, leadership, leadership development and authenticity are explored. The chapter commenced by assessing the evolution of leadership theories, tracing their development from the Great Man, Trait, Behavioural, and Contingency theories to the emergence of newer theories within the field. Also, theories which are argued to share

similarities with authentic leadership were examined. The section sought to examine the peculiarities of these leadership theories to ascertain, whether these theories were essentially different names for the same fundamental leadership construct. The section concludes with a brief exploration of authentic leadership.

The chapter then appraises leadership development and explores approaches evidenced in extant literature. The existing research on leadership development was examined as a lens to investigate the process of becoming authentic. Though, the research did not aim to explore authentic leadership development, it was essential to gain an understanding of the arguments within domain. Through the literature review, the section identified key emerging themes in leadership development. Finally, the concluding section of chapter 2 explores authenticity. It investigates the concept and its implications across a variety of domains providing a foundation for further investigation on authentic leadership in Chapter 3.

In chapter 3 a systematic literature review of AL was conducted. This was undertaken to uncover the boundaries of knowledge in the authentic leadership domain, revealing what is known about the construct, how this is known and how it differed across scholars. Consequently, the introductory section of the chapter provided an overview of the systematic process adopted in the review process before it offered descriptive analysis and discussed the review's findings. The results of the systematic literature analysis indicate that researchers moved on from examining theory to assessing their impact on organisational outcomes.

To address these concerns, a reconceptualisation of the concept is proposed with calls for scholars to investigate and uncover additional components of authentic leadership, particularly in diverse environments. The SLR also established that scholarly efforts have primarily examined authentic leadership from the Western perspectives, focusing on identifying outcomes within these contexts, which support the need for further research.

Chapter 4 examined the context of study, Nigeria, with specificity to the oil sector. The first of the three sections of the chapter offered discussions on the taxonomy of economies which served as a foundation for discussing the characteristics and dynamics of developing economies. The second section presented an extended discussion on Nigeria, while the third section explored the oil industry. The chapter concluded with a discussion on the conceptual framework, which synthesised findings from the literature review chapters within the study. Overall, the three review chapters established the context for the study. Chapter 2 and most of 3 situate the research within the existing literature in the domain. It identifies the gaps, controversies, debates and outlines the need for the study. The conceptual framework of authentic leadership is provided in chapter 4, which comprises of the theoretical perspectives and concepts used to frame the research problem.

Chapter 5 provided an extended discussion on the methodological choices that shaped the study. The chapter describes the investigative process, offering a detailed account of how previously unexplored facets of authentic leadership were illuminated. It accomplishes this by making clear the assumptions, philosophy, approach, research method, strategy, data collection techniques, and analytical methods employed to reveal these previously unknown aspects of authentic leadership.

This study's research design and methodology provide a rigorous and systematic evaluation of AL within a developing economy context. Therefore, an interpretivist philosophy was the most appropriate for exploring the phenomenon. This is because it allowed the researcher to examine the subjective feelings, meanings, and interpretations that lay at the root of this phenomenon. In the approach to reasoning, abductive reasoning was adopted as this reasoning is a type of inference that proves valuable in developing new theories, when there is a lack of information that is either comprehensive or certain. Abductive reasoning was an appropriate approach to

probing authentic leadership because it facilitated the generation of new insights into the complex and multifaceted nature of this construct.

Aligning with the qualitative method adopted for the study, a phenomenological strategy was chosen as this strategy focuses on the study of human experience. Its purpose is to investigate the processes by which individuals take in information from their surroundings and construct meaning from that information. The phenomenological strategy facilitated an in depth investigation of the individual experiences of authentic leaders and their followers.

Semi-structured interviews were utilised as the data collection technique for the study as they are adaptable and allowed the dialogue to flow naturally while still preserving some level of the structure. This data gathering technique allowed the researchers to probe for clarification and elaboration, resulting in a broader understanding of the construct. In analysing the empirical data, King and Horrocks (2010) thematic analysis technique was adopted as this has been described as an effective strategy for analysing data acquired from semi-structured interviews and other qualitative methodologies. It was useful for locating and making sense of the many recurring themes and patterns within the data. The chapter also provided a discussion on the ethical principles that guided the study and the criteria for evaluating the quality of the research process. Overall, the methodology chapter discussed the investigative process and outlined the assumptions that ensured the research was conducted systematically and rigorously.

Chapters 6 and 7 are the findings chapters within the study. These two chapters presented the key findings of the study in a detailed and well organised manner. These chapters are at the core of the study as they offer an in depth evaluation of the data, and the potential implications. Therefore, these chapters are organised in line with the four questions of the study. They present an analysis of the empirical data, focusing on the patterns and trends uncovered in addressing the study's research questions. Chapter 6 outlines the findings of the two research questions on components of AL and factors that inspire its development. The responses of all the

46 respondents were examined which led to the identification of six key components: clarity of purpose, self-awareness, internalised moral perspective, relational transparency, concern for people, and follower development of authentic leadership. The respondents described these components of authentic leadership in terms of obligations and expectations revealing the divergent perspectives of leaders and followers.

One of the aspects of the study that was well articulated was the "follower development" component of authentic leadership. The respondents described their growth as an expectation of authentic leadership. While discussing common sub themes like empathy and role modelling, authentic leaders and followers diverged on the other sub themes.

In answering the second research question on the factors that inspire AL development, the authentic leaders identified four factors: family structure, belief and conviction, leadership, and legacy as inspiring authentic leadership development. The respondents highlighted the influence of familial ties and familial dynamics on the development of authentic leadership. The significance of values and beliefs in promoting the development of AL was also emphasised by all the 16 authentic leaders. Likewise, authentic leaders affirmed that exposure to leadership had the biggest impact on their authentic leadership development. Interestingly, both effective and ineffective leadership inspired the development of AL. Finally, the desire to leave a legacy also inspired authentic leadership development in most authentic leaders. The findings from adopting the critical incident technique advanced by Flanagan (1954) and extended by Chell (1998) were presented in the figure 24. Authentic leaders were asked to reflect on critical experiences with specificity to a key event that shaped their choice. This technique proved valuable in triangulating the descriptions offered in response to the factors that inspired them to become authentic.

Chapter 7 extended the discussion by presenting the findings of the last two questions captured in the introductory section of the chapter. It is worth noting that when responding to the research question, the authentic leaders initially sought to elucidate their challenges primarily within the context of the study's environment before subsequently addressing the obstacles they encountered in overcoming these difficulties. These authentic leaders highlighted four types of challenges: financial challenges, poor governance and regulation, and economic difficulties, all of which are contextual and leadership challenges that encapsulate personal paradoxes the authentic leaders confront on their journey.

The chapter concludes with the findings on actions that shape follower perceptions of authentic leadership. The respondents identified: giving followers a voice, facilitating follower development, and demonstrating consistency and transparency. It is interesting that chapter six also addressed follower development. However, that focused on follower development from the perspective of authentic leaders, which was significantly different from the descriptions provided by followers in describing the actions that influence their perceptions of AL.

According to the respondents, follower development is continuously identifying employees' growth potential. Even though, role modelling was identified when followers and authentic leaders unpacked follower development. These followers, however, provided their own unique accounts of this action. A recurring sub theme in all the followers' responses was consistency. The followers emphasised this while describing authentic leaders. It was a crucial factor in determining who they assessed as authentic in their organisations. Finally, all followers emphasised transparency as a significant action influencing their perceptions of authentic leadership, much like consistency.

9.1.1 Overview of Findings

The thesis is both novel and timely as it reveals four critical findings that have both theoretical and practical significance for the field of authentic leadership. Firstly, it

confirms that there are aspects of AL that have not been recognised in existing research. The study broadens the understanding of this construct beyond its initial conceptualisation to offer a path for further development and application across diverse contexts. Secondly, the study identifies significant factors that inspire its development supporting existing arguments that authenticity is on a continuum as authentic leadership development begins early in the life of authentic leaders and is nurtured over time before manifestation in their leadership.

Thirdly, the study uncovered challenges of authentic leadership peculiar to a distinct context ,which may be applicable to similar developing economies. Fourthly, the study revealed the salient role of authentic leader actions to the perceptions of followers, bringing to fore the bidirectional focus of scholars in the exploration AL. The findings from the study also reveal the active role of the perceptions of followers and how this impacts the outcome of authentic leadership within organisations. Finally, an empirical based definition of authentic leadership is offered in chapter 8 section 8.1 accordingly.

In conclusion, the findings of the thesis provide evidence that the aim of the study was attained as it illuminated numerous important aspects of authentic leadership thorough a methodical examination of the construct. A summary of all the key findings is captured in Table 27 below.

Table 27 Summary of Findings

QUESTIONS	FINDINGS	CONSTITUENTS
Components of AL	Clarity of Purpose	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enabling environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Positive organisational climate ○ Management of resources ○ Vision 2. Goal orientation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Creation of goals ○ Pursuit of goals 3. Knowledge orientation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Prior experiences ○ Skills ○ Technical knowledge
	Follower Development	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Role Modeling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Leadership positioning (by example, following, front and back) ○ Development approaches: Mentoring 2. Psychological capital <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hope ○ optimism ○ Building resilience ○ Efficacy 3. Competency development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Skills development ○ Other areas that are not work related 4. Support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Follow up on actions ○ Follow through side by side with followers

		5. Empathy
	Relational Transparency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vulnerability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open about experiences ○ Showing love, trust and respect ○ Self-disclosure ○ Being approachable 2. Transparency 3. Learning orientation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Growth mindset ○ Speaking up ○ Lifelong learning
	Self awareness	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Self-regulation 2. Emotional Intelligence
	Internalised moral perspective	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Value driven 2. Unbiased
	Concern for people	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Team focus 2. 360 Perspective
Factors that inspire AL development	Family Structure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Birth Positioning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ First born ○ First girl ○ First boy 2. Roles and Responsibilities
	Beliefs and Conviction	
	Leadership	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ineffective leadership 2. Effective leadership
	Legacy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trigger events 2. Crucibles 3. Personal fulfilment

Challenges of AL	Financial Challenges	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Corruption 2. Misappropriation of funds
	Poor Governance and Regulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ineffective regulation 2. Rising insecurity
	Economic Challenges	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Global economic concerns 2. COVID
	Leadership Challenges	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Personal challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Sticking to core values o Balancing competing priorities o New team dynamics 2. Interactional challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Balancing individual with group needs o Managing expectation o Being untrue o Broadening follower perspectives
Actions that shape follower perceptions	Followers voice	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Balanced processing 2. Being courageous 3. Collaboration
	Follower development	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Role Modeling 2. Relationship management
	Consistency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Alignment
	Transparency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Honesty in interactions 2. Communication

Chapter 8 provided discussions, drew conclusions, and explored the larger implications of the study. The discussion chapter explored the implications of the findings presented in the two preceding chapters, as well as the ongoing debates and arguments found in existing literature. Thus, highlighting the research's contributions to authentic leadership by placing the results in the context of prior literature. At the end of this chapter, an authentic leadership model is presented in Figure 26.

9.2 Implications of the study

In general, qualitative research have broad implications that can influence theory, practice, and policy in addition to the conclusions within the study. Therefore, the implications of this study are discussed in the following three subsections, highlighting how the conclusions may influence future research directions and contribute to real world applications.

9.2.1 Theoretical Implications

Across extant literature scholars have upheld the role of qualitative research in theory development as these studies offer alternative perspectives, expand current understanding, add, or contradict existing debates within the domain. This study offered fresh theoretical perspectives on authentic leadership by exploring experiences, perceptions and meaning ascribed by authentic leaders and their followers. The study extends existing literature on authentic leadership by adding to the current components of authentic leadership. This proposed six component model captured in Figure 26 extends the current literature by revealing that authentic leadership can be inspired by four main factors which can occur at any level of the organisation. Also, the model lays bare the link between challenges of AL and the factors that inspire its development, which is not evident within extant literature. The model also outlines the six components of authentic leadership, while providing conceptual links to its core constituents. These components offer support for the

behaviours and perceptions connected to this leadership approach. Therefore, offering a new departure point for the examination of authentic leadership.

Authentic leadership, while well established in theory, lacks effective mechanisms for achieving leadership development and potential repair if and when needed. This emphasises the need of unpacking the distinct viewpoints of leaders and followers and how these differences impact the process of making sense within organisations. The research asserts that though leaders and followers agree on key components of authentic leadership, these respondents differ on some subcomponents, which has practical implication for leadership development. Therefore, a clearer grasp of authentic leadership and inherent differences in sense making would shape future research priorities.

Authentic leadership challenges are yet to be explored adequately as most studies have focused primarily on the difficulties these leaders address within organisations (Mhatre and Conger, 2011; Crawford *et al.*, 2020) with a few highlighting the difficulties encountered by authentic leaders in demographic minorities and multi-cultural contexts (Ladkin and Spiller, 2013; Fine, 2017; Ngunjiri and Hernandez, 2017). This study enhances the existing knowledge by revealing the specific categories of leadership difficulties encountered by authentic leaders. Furthermore, it explicates the relationship between the difficulties encountered by authentic leaders and the factors that first encouraged its development. This demonstrates that these two model constituents are mutually reinforcing. It has an important effect on the mental and emotional states of authentic leaders, providing avenues for further study on the connection between the difficulties faced by authentic leadership and the factors that facilitate its growth.

A systematic literature review of the domain was conducted which illuminated the boundaries of the domain from 1970 to 2021. The arguments in the review provided an evaluation of past and current leadership research. This was essential because the array of perspectives provided a strong and wide ranging understanding of the

construct. The review investigated the form and practice of AL and outlines a research agenda which is a significant theoretical contribution of the study.

In terms of the methodological implication, the study proposed and implemented the use of an integrated approach to sampling seemingly inaccessible participants. Within the study, identifying authentic leaders was problematic hence an integrated purposive and snowballing termed “Purposive Rolling” sampling strategy was adopted. Furthermore, adopting an evidenced based methodology utilising the systematic literature review, to offer unbiased data explicating knowledge gaps in literature and new areas of enquiry was effective in the enquiry process. Given that the SLR facilitates an unbiased evaluation and review of data, this rigorous technique is particularly appropriate for organisational sciences (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009).

The study's empirical contribution is apparent within the context. This study offers empirical data on authentic leadership within the Nigerian oil business, highlighting the contextual nature of this construct (Algera and Lips-Wiersma, 2012; Fortin, Baron and Renucci, 2018) and revealing the challenges of AL within the context of study.

9.2.2 Practice Implications

This study has applicability in real world settings and can facilitate effective decision making across organisations and the broader society. The findings of the study provide context specific insights that quantitative methodologies may overlook. The significance of context, Nigeria is evident as the context impacts the practice and experience of authentic leadership. Hence, practitioners can adjust interventions to groups or locations with the aid of this contextual data and the empirical model presented in chapter 8.

Evidenced from the data, authentic leaders are in the minority within organisations. Therefore, the study offers a voice to the contextual challenges of these leaders. Furthermore, the voices of the followers are also magnified while acknowledging the power dynamics within organisations. By drawing on the research findings the study

offers a theoretical lens for professional development of authentic leadership with organisations.

The significance of resilience is also salient within the study as authentic leaders encounter challenges within and outside their organisations. These leaders are expected to be goal oriented nurturing an enabling environment that drive performance. Therefore, resilience training should be prioritised by practitioners so that leaders are equipped to handle organisational complexities and ensure leadership effectiveness.

Further along these lines, leadership development programmes should be emphasised by practitioners to harness the potential of leaders across all levels. The importance of mentoring and coaching were highlighted by the respondents within the study offering a path to lifelong learning for aspiring authentic leaders. These mentoring and coaching programmes would be beneficial and should be prioritised by practitioners.

Expanding the discussion on lifelong learning mentioned above, practitioners should nurture environments that support lifelong learning. As evidenced from the findings, leadership is a lifelong process of growth and learning for both authentic leaders and followers. As, respondents acknowledged the value of an environment, which allowed followers to, learn, thrive and eventually perform, contributing positively to organisational performance. Practitioners ought to create an enabling environment which stimulate the pursuit for knowledge through different avenues such as job rotation, further training through workshops, seminars, and peer learning.

Also, to drive lifelong learning across organisations, practitioners should emphasise the development of three key areas, self awareness, emotional intelligence and effective communication for authentic leaders. To nurture self awareness of leaders, practitioners should incorporate reflective activities into their organisations. This is important as leaders will be able to identify and acknowledge strengths and

weaknesses. This will be beneficial as targeted interventions will positively impact leadership effectiveness.

Regarding emotional intelligence, effective leadership is largely influenced by the quotient of emotional intelligence leaders possess. This study made explicit the role of emotional intelligence, confirming its significance as a component of self awareness. This aspect is particularly relevant as leaders can effectively manage not only their own emotions but also those of other stakeholders within and outside the organisation. This will contribute to leadership effectiveness, positive organisational outcomes and foster rewarding relationships across organisations.

Finally, communication is critical across any organisation, particularly within authentic leadership as it is also used to assess the authenticity of leaders. Hence, effective communication should be a key priority for practitioners, because it enables leaders share their vision, offer feedback, and engage with stakeholders. Effective communication fosters an enabling culture within organisations, helping to build credibility and trust with diverse stakeholders.

9.2.3 Policy Implications

This study integrates theories, empirical data from real world applications to offer an empirical model that can guide the development and repair of leadership. This tool will be beneficial to policy makers as it will stir discussions and critical decisions on incorporating leadership development within the curriculum at an early stage. This is because leaders are largely shaped by their education. Additionally, this will streamline the process of identifying and training prospective leaders.

Policies should actively promote the establishment of robust succession planning initiatives within organisations. Hence, driving the arguments for an inclusion of leadership education in curricula for higher education and in classroom settings. These discussions are crucial as more research will contribute to the establishment of policies based on evidence. Policy makers should seek to promote policies that safeguard organisations against leadership malfeasance before they occur on a grand

scale by ensuring polices consider the role followers can play in inhibiting these occurrences. Policies should also acknowledge the distinctive influence of followers and offer resources that drive accountability across organisations. Policies should also endorse initiatives aimed at nurturing the mental wellbeing of both leaders and followers, equipping these key stakeholders with the necessary resources to navigate the intricacies within organisational settings.

9.3 Limitations of the study

In light of the ongoing debates surrounding the rigor and quality of qualitative research that have persisted over the years. Scholars argue its value in the investigation of phenomena, which require in depth understanding. The qualitative method was best suited for the investigation conducted within the study. However, like the more prominent quantitative method, the qualitative research method has limitations and a demonstration of an awareness of these limitations are crucial when the method is adopted.

First, there are arguments on the sample size and generalisability of the findings, with suggestions that sample sizes are usually smaller and may limit the application of the findings of a study. The study sought to explore authentic leadership in depth within a specific context, thus the sample size of 46 was adequate. The study aimed to capture rich descriptions from the participants, which informed the research participants' selection purposively. These thick descriptions provide a basis for evaluating other contexts (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2022). In qualitative research, it is acknowledged that researchers bring subjectivity and bias into their work. To mitigate this risk, ongoing self reflection was conducted, and the research process and findings were reported as impartially as possible..

9.4 Future research agenda

Building upon the findings of this exploratory study and the insights discussed in section 9.2 this subsection offers potential directions for future research.

Proposed future question 1: What are the unique components or dimensions of authentic leadership that emerge in diverse cultural, organisational, and contextual settings?

This study revealed further components of authentic leadership that go beyond the four recognised components of self awareness, internalised moral perspective, relational transparency, and balanced processing (Gardner *et al.*, 2021; Gardner and McCauley, 2022). However, further research on the components across diverse contexts may uncover additional components of AL. Quantitative studies would prove valuable in validating the findings of this study, which will advance further research into new measures for the construct. This is because the existing measures: the Authentic leadership questionnaire (ALQ) proposed by Walumbwa *et al.* (2008) and Authentic leadership inventory (ALI) advanced by Neider and Schriesheim (2011) are primarily underpinned by the existing four components of authentic leadership highlighted above.

Proposed future question 2: What are the underlying processes and mechanisms through which the individual components of authentic leadership contribute to leadership effectiveness and follower outcomes?

Closely linked to the first research question is the second research question. By exploring the underlying processes and mechanisms through which the individual components of authentic leadership contribute to leadership effectiveness and follower outcomes, such research efforts would support the development of bespoke developmental strategies for individuals across organisations.

Proposed future question 3: How do followers' perceptions influence the development and manifestation of authentic leadership, and what are the implications for leader-follower dynamics?

This question may serve as a departure point for a future PhD thesis as several exploratory, explanatory, descriptive studies may emerge from the overarching

question above. This will bring to the fore the iterative role followers' perceptions play in developing authentic leadership. An investigation into the role of these perceptions and how it shapes authentic leadership development will advance the domain.

Finally, proposed future question 4: What are the strategies for repairing authentic leadership?

While studies have been conducted on the factors that inspire AL development such as crucibles, life stories and trigger events with this study expanding these factors to include leadership, family structure, beliefs and conviction. Extant literature is yet to explore authentic leadership repair which is mirrored across other leadership domain. The quest to develop empirically testable repair models of leadership lies at the core of research efforts into leadership repair. As this research path will allow for comparisons across multiple leadership theories. Furthermore, it will facilitate the discovery of the intricate array of variables associated with leadership effectiveness.

9.5 Closing remarks

In conclusion, it is evident that the objectives of the study have been achieved with the key findings summarised as follows:

- There were six components of authentic leadership uncovered within a developing economy context namely, clarity of purpose, self awareness, internalised moral perspective, relational transparency, concern for people and follower development.
- The study offered a new definition of authentic leadership underpinned by the findings of the study. Authentic leadership is defined as the “a purpose driven leadership anchored in the leader's self awareness. It thrives through transparent relationships with stakeholders, nurturing follower development while attaining organisational objectives.”

- The study uncovered factors that inspire authentic leadership development. These factors of family structure, belief and conviction, leadership, and legacy provide complementary interventions for authentic leadership development.
- The challenges that authentic leaders encounter within a developing economy, were also identified with an evident distinction between personal and interactional challenges, which focus on contextual and personal paradoxes of these leaders.
- Finally, the followers identified giving followers a voice, facilitating follower development, and demonstrating consistency and transparency when describing actions that shape their perceptions of authentic leadership.

Ultimately, it is anticipated that the study's contributions to the field will strengthen the effectiveness of leadership in practice.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Summary of SLR articles

Name of author	Focus
Agote, Aramburu and Lines (2016)	The article investigates how perceptions of authentic leadership affected the trust and emotions of 102 Spanish human resource managers during a period of transition. According to the results of the study, perceptions of authentic leadership are associated with the positive emotions of followers, which increases followers' trust in leaders.
Algera and Lips-Wiersma (2012)	The limitations of the conceptualisation of authentic leadership are examined in this article. It indicates that current conceptualisations of the construct may need to be re-aligned with their intended purposes. First, the paper contends that complete authenticity is unattainable. Second, personal interpretations are involved. It is not intrinsically moral, and it does not suggest aligning beliefs and objectives. The study is profoundly rooted in the existential perspective and provides a fundamental shift in emphasis from leaders to the conditions that shape authentic leadership behaviours within organisations.
Alilyyani, Wong and Cummings (2018)	The article focuses on the relational nature of authentic leadership and its effects on organisational outcomes. It contends that followers (nurses) have faith in their leaders and feel more empowered when they perceive their leaders to be authentic
Alvesson and Einola (2019)	The article problematises the construct of authentic leadership. It cautions scholars on the positivistic outlook of the construct, and the authors critically examine prominent arguments within the field, exposing weaknesses in the current conceptualisations.
Avolio and Gardner (2005)	The article outlines the 2005 special issue of <i>Leadership Quarterly</i> focused on authentic leadership development. The article presents an overview of the emergent nature of the field, describing the factors that have contributed to the emergence of the construct. The authors describe the conceptual foundations, definitions, components and features of authentic leadership in detail.
Avolio <i>et al.</i> (2004)	The article presents a broad theoretical foundation for the exploration of the impact of authentic leadership on followers' outcomes. A very influential study which describes the processes of influence. With specificity to how authentic leaders use this impact. The study provides one of the prominent definitions of the construct and advances a model which has served as the tool for several empirical studies.
Avolio, Walumbwa and Weber (2009)	The article reviews the development of leadership literature. It examines the current state of the domain and charts the path for future research.

Bakari, Hunjra and Niazi (2017)	The empirical study examines the impact of authentic leadership perceptions during change within a Pakistani context. The survey findings reveal that authentic leaders are required to shape the employee's perception in readiness for transition to attain success. The study advanced a model drawing from Lewin's (1947) three-step change model.
Balogun, Mahembe and Allen-Ile (2020)	The empirical study tests the reliability and constructs validity of the Authentic Leadership Inventory within the banking sector in a Nigerian context.
Banks <i>et al.</i> (2016)	The authors conduct a comparison between authentic and transformational leadership. Within the review, meta-analytic techniques are used for the comparative analysis of 100 samples and 25,452 people. The study's findings reveal that authentic and transformational leadership are closely related, indicating construct redundancy. Secondly, there needs to be apparent incremental validity between the two constructs. Thirdly, transformational leadership yields higher outcomes in relation to authentic leadership. Finally, authentic leadership shows dominance in predicting organisational performance.
Baron and Parent (2015)	The article examines the development of authentic leadership within a formalised training context with findings drawn from 24 managers in Canada. The results show that authentic leadership development occurs in two key phases: exploration and integration.
Beddoes-Jones and Swailes (2015)	The article advances a three-component measure of authentic leadership. This model measures the authentic leader's self awareness, ethics and self-regulation. The study attempts to merge the previous conceptualisations of authentic leadership.
Bishop (2013)	The author investigates the concept of authentic leadership. The article contends that value is the foundation of authentic leadership and is characterised as the "real thing" that transcends a beyond a style of leadership.
Cooper, Scandura and Schriesheim (2005)	The article suggests a comprehensive examination of authentic leadership to avoid the pitfalls of other leadership approaches. The article suggests that scholars investigate the construct's validity and collaborate to avoid duplication and advance the field. Additionally, the article advocates for further research before attempting to develop leadership interventions.
Černe <i>et al.</i> (2014)	The empirical study examines how leaders' self-perception and followers' perceptions of authentic leadership contribute to employee job satisfaction. The findings from the Slovenian study suggest that aligning a leader's self and followers' perception of authentic leadership increases positive outcomes.
Corriveau (2020)	The article describes a leadership course examining the impact of experiential education. Findings from the study support the use of this method in the development of authentic leadership within a business school context.

Copeland (2014)	The conceptual study investigated the prominent value-based leadership theories, namely the authentic, ethical, and transformational models. The article suggests that when subordinates perceive leaders to exhibit any of the leadership styles, they are more effective. The article concludes with research suggestions for the future.
Crawford <i>et al.</i> (2020)	The article emphasises the fragmented character of the authentic leadership domain. The authors investigate in depth the fundamental limitations of the domain and propose a revised conceptualisation of the construct. The research offers recommendations on how to differentiate between authentic leaders, individuals, and followers.
De Bruyckere and Kirschner (2016)	This study investigates the perceptions of authenticity in a Belgian educational context. Students' perceptions of a teacher's authenticity are influenced by four factors: expertise, passion, uniqueness, and distance.
Duignan and Bhindi (1997)	This article investigates the emergence of authentic leadership, existing literature and the author's personal reflections. The article proposes a new model for authentic leadership.
Duignan (2014)	The article emphasises on the emergence of authentic educational leadership. The study's findings indicate that existing literature is fragmented. Nonetheless, key themes permeate the literature, such as the prominent argument on the self and the existence or absence of moral foundations. In conclusion, the article argues that authentically professional executives are essential for achieving objectives.
Emuwa and Fields (2017)	This study investigates the relationship between authentic leadership dimensions, organisational commitment, and leader effectiveness in Nigeria. The findings derived from 212 employees indicate that authentic leadership dimensions are positively associated with organisational commitments and leader effectiveness. This is the first study to evaluate how authentic leadership components influence organisational commitment and leader effectiveness in Nigeria.
Fields (2007)	The author argues that a leader's authenticity and emotions must be apparent to the team members. The perceptibility primarily impacts the leader's influence within the group. Furthermore, the article examines how the actions, attributes, context of interaction influences the followers' perception of leaders' authenticity.
Ford and Harding (2011)	The article argues that there are inherent dangers within authentic leadership. This is evident from the authentic leaders' inability to be true to themselves. Furthermore, it is affirmed that the current conceptualisations of authentic leadership need to recognise the inadequacies of the leaders.
Fusco, O'Riordan and Palmer (2015a)	The empirical study investigates the effect of group mentoring on authentic leadership development in the United Kingdom. A model

	was developed that outlined four essential concepts of authentic leadership, with subcategories describing the necessary leadership skills.
Gaddy <i>et al.</i> (2017)	The focus of the study is the relationship between perceptions of authentic leadership and resilience in the United States Army. The findings of the study indicate a correlation between perceptions of a supervisor's authentic leadership and the resilience of subordinates.
Gardner <i>et al.</i> (2005)	The article proposes a paradigm for the development of authentic leaders and followers. This model is investigated in terms of follower performance.
Gardner <i>et al.</i> (2011)	The review examines the evolution of the authentic leadership construct. It was the first review conducted within the domain, presenting the state of knowledge. The review charts the path for future research.
Gill and Caza (2018)	The empirical study examines the multidimensional nature of authentic leadership and its effect on followers. The article contends that personalised and generalised AI have distinct effects on followers. Personalised AL influenced four crucial responses, while generalised AL influenced two more. The study was conducted in a large multinational organisation that included both leaders and subordinates in its sample frame.
Giordano-Mulligan and Eckardt (2019)	This article presents a conceptual framework for authentic leadership in the health sector. The purpose of the study was to determine how nurses' perceptions influence their work environment and engagement. The study demonstrates that perceptions of authentic leadership contribute to employee engagement and healthful work environments
Glowacki-Dudka and Griswold (2016)	This study investigates the reflections on authentic leadership written at the Highlander research centre in 2013 and 2014. These reflections evolved into a case study that was investigated further to determine the impact of the workshop on the participants. The case study findings validate the Highlander experience.
Hanold (2017)	The article argues that authentic leadership encompasses collective power dynamics within a particular context, in addition to the authentic leader. In the study, findings from the sport context in the United States suggest a learning process in which both self and followers actively contribute, resulting in the co-creation of authentic leadership. The term for this is witness thinking. Thus, the article provides a method for capturing the influence of others that is embodied and authentic. In the research, shared comprehension between leaders and followers is portrayed as an ongoing interaction.
Hendricks and Toth-Cohen (2018)	In a South African context, this study assesses the authentic leadership development of twelve black occupational therapy students. The pilot study reveals that perceptions of authentic

	leadership development can be categorised into four groups: perception of self, perception of others, main aim of leadership development and impacts of leadership. Based on the findings of the research, a model for students was developed.
Hughes, Gong and Sims (2017)	This article examines the leadership of small business proprietors who are women. The article argues that small business owners are more likely to be authentic because they establish their enterprises in accordance with their true selves. Nonetheless, role mismatch plays a role in the demonstration of leader authenticity.
Ilies, Morgeson and Nahrgang (2005)	The study examines the relationship between authentic leadership and eudaemonic well-being. It investigates the processes that contribute to the development of eudaemonic well-being. Additionally, it investigates the antecedents and outcomes of authentic leadership.
Iszatt-White and Kempster (2019)	The review paper investigates the evolution of authentic leadership and proposes a reconceptualisation of the concept to resolve the domain's theoretical ambiguity.
Johnsen (2018)	Using Deleuze's argument on Platonism, the article attempts to elucidate the differences between authentic and inauthentic leaders.
Joo and Jo (2017)	The empirical study investigates the relationship between the followers' fundamental self-evaluation and their perception of the leader's authenticity within one of the largest large Korean organisations. The study's findings indicate that perceived authentic leadership, fundamental self-evaluation, and psychological empowerment influence employees' organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB).
Joo and Nimon (2014)	The empirical study investigates the connection between authentic leadership and transformational leadership. The findings of the study indicate a relationship between authentic leadership and transformational leadership. This was derived from the perceptions of employees at a Korean non-profit organisation. Followers suggest that authentic leaders are transformational leaders and vice versa, highlighting the strong relationship between the dimensions of both constructs. Nonetheless, the authors assert that these two leadership styles are not interchangeable.
Kempster, Iszatt-White and Brown (2019)	Examining how leaders conceal their true emotions, the study raises concerns about transparency. In pursuance of authenticity, the leader displays emotions deemed appropriate and desired by followers within the context.
Kernis (2003)	This article presents a theoretical perspective on "optimal" self-esteem. The article provides an influential conceptualisation of authenticity and identifies four essential components of authenticity, namely: "awareness, unbiased processing, action, and relational orientation".
Khilji <i>et al.</i> (2015)	The article investigates authentic leadership across nations. Leaders from India, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka were interviewed, and

	the study provides empirical evidence that authentic leadership, through relevance, varies across cultures. Furthermore, the multidimensional nature of the construct was evident, and the study advanced a cross-cultural model of the construct.
Kiersch and Byrne (2015)	The article verifies a multilevel mediation model. The study investigates how leaders influence followers' perceptions of fairness and how these perceptions influence well-being, commitment, and intention to leave. The study's findings confirm that authentic leaders influence followers.
Kurian and Nafukho (2021)	The article investigates the relationship between authentic leadership and perceptions of organisational justice in the hospitality industry in the United States. The study's findings indicate that authentic leadership is positively associated with followers' perceptions of organisational justice.
Ladkin and Taylor (2010)	The article contends that perceptions of authentic leadership result from the manifestation of one's true self.
Lawler and Ashman (2012)	The article contends that perceptions of authentic leadership result from the manifestation of one's genuine self.
Lemoine, Hartnell and Leroy (2019)	The article attempts to clarify the points of divergence and convergence between authentic, ethical, and servant leadership. The three leadership approaches all emphasise moral consistency and conduct.
Levesque-Côté <i>et al.</i> (2018)	The empirical study examines the multidimensional nature of authentic leadership using two significant scales; the authentic leadership questionnaire and the authentic leadership inventory developed within the domain. The findings drawn from French Canadians' responses affirm the construct's multidimensional nature and demonstrate the content overlap between the two instruments. This has led to the development of a new measure of authentic Leadership Integrated Questionnaire (AL-IQ).
Liu, Cutcher and Grant (2017)	The study examines the portrayal of four CEOs in Australia's banking sector during the financial crises. The media's description of the leader's words and actions were analysed. The study's findings coherence, consistency and conformity are crucial for authentic leadership perception. More importantly, it was shaped by the context.
McFarlane (2011)	The article examines the role of authentic leadership perceptions and how it interacts with leadership effectiveness, focusing on the author's interactions with authentic leaders and recommending that leaders be authentic in their actions and practises to inspire authentic leadership development in their followers.
Mehmood, Schreurs and Hamstra (2019)	The empirical study investigates whether a manager's political skill contributes to employees' perception of authentic leadership. The findings suggest that a manager's sincerity positively contributes to employees' perception of authentic leadership within organisations in Pakistan. Furthermore, networking capacity contributes to

	employees' perceptions of authentic leadership among male managers.
Monzani <i>et al.</i> (2015)	The empirical study examines the biological differences between genders and how team prototypicality diminishes the role of congruency. The study's findings reveal essential differences between male and female authentic leadership.
Neider and Schriesheim (2011)	The study evaluates the authentic leadership questionnaire proposed by Walumbwa <i>et al.</i> (2008). Limitations were identified with the validation process of this measure, which included using a small sample, thus raising doubts on the validity of this measure. Consequently, Neider and Schriesheim (2011) proposed a new measure of authentic leadership inventory to address the inadequacies and shortcomings of authentic leadership questionnaires.
Ngunjiri and Hernandez (2017)	The study contends that authentic leadership is highly contextual. The empirical study examines the experiences of two black immigrant women in a predominantly white college and higher education institution. It documents the paradoxes encountered by these women in the execution of authentic leadership.
Novicevic <i>et al.</i> (2006)	The article evaluates authentic leadership through the lens of Barnard's work and reconstructs the concept of authenticity. It also analyses the philosophical and psychological perspectives of authenticity, laying the groundwork for future research.
Nyberg and Sveningsson (2014)	The study investigates the socially constructed nature of authentic leadership. The study's findings reveal that authentic leaders face a paradox in their quest to be authentic and mask their feelings to be perceived as good authentic leaders. It highlights the tensions inherent in relational transparency.
Olckers, du Plessis and Casaleggio (2020)	The empirical study evaluates the effect of followers' perceptions of authentic leadership on citizenship behaviour and plans to resign in a South African context. The study's findings indicate that perceptions of authentic leadership contribute positively to organisational citizenship behaviour and reduce employees' plans or intentions to resign.
Petan and Bocarnea (2016)	The empirical study investigates the relationship between perceptions of authentic leadership and culture in Romania and the United States. The study's findings indicate no discernible difference between Romanian and American followers' perceptions of authentic leadership.
Peus <i>et al.</i> (2012)	The study identifies self-knowledge and consistency as antecedents of authentic leadership within the business context. Self-consistency and knowledge increased perceptions of authentic leadership in the first study. The second study was conducted within two government organisations and provided empirical evidence of authentic leadership.

Puente, Crous and Venter (2007)	The study evaluates the actions of Rudolph Giuliani in the United States, who exhibited authentic leadership qualities after the September 11 terrorist attacks and demonstrates that both positive and negative events can trigger the development of authentic leadership.
Raso, Fitzpatrick and Masick (2020)	The empirical study investigates the relationship between the nurses' perceptions of their managers' authentic leadership and the workgroup. The results indicate that perceptions of authentic leadership are positively associated with a healthy and fulfilling work environment.
Shamir and Eilam (2005)	It distinguishes and describes "authentic leaders, authentic leadership, and authentic leadership development" and promotes the life story method for authentic leadership development, which is deeply rooted in the sense-making and meanings leaders attribute to their personal experiences.
Shannon <i>et al.</i> (2020)	The article investigates the role of trigger events and life crucibles within organisations in the United States. The study's findings provide empirical evidence that triggers, events, and crucibles are essential to authentic leadership development.
Shrivastava (2018)	The author investigates the developmental aspect of authentic leadership. The paper examines how personal histories and trigger events influence leadership development. The study's findings indicate that authentic leadership development is tied to the answer to the question "Who am I?" The answer involves connecting the self to identity and beliefs.
Sidani and Rowe (2018)	A follower's perception of a leader's authenticity shapes the article's definition of authentic leadership as a legitimate process involving dialogue and negotiation.
Sims, Gong and Hughes (2017)	The empirical study examines the role of gender and leadership identities in determining how authentic a leader is perceived within 63 small businesses in the United States. The study's findings indicate that identity interference is a precursor to authentic leadership, particularly for women in non-traditional industries.
Sparrowe (2005)	The article examines leadership authenticity and is profoundly rooted in the hermeneutic philosophy and the author contends that authenticity emerges from a narrative process.
Steffens <i>et al.</i> (2016)	The empirical study investigates the effect of collective interests on authentic leadership. The study's findings indicate that leaders are perceived as more authentic when they put the group's interests ahead of their own. This enhanced perception inspires followership, especially among the group members being led by the authentic leader.
Stewart <i>et al.</i> (2017)	The study reveals that these authentic leaders were influenced by their native and dual cultures but made conscious efforts to remain true to their values and preferences.

Stiers <i>et al.</i> (2019)	The empirical study investigates how followers assess the authenticity of political leaders. The study's findings indicate that perceptions of authenticity are strongly associated with successful political careers.
Suhonen, Malila and Lunkka (2018)	This is a scoping review of authentic leadership within the health sector. The study aimed to identify gaps and chart the path for future research efforts. The findings revealed that four research themes were prevalent across the 29 articles included in the study. These themes are "wellbeing at work, work environment, authentic leadership promotion and patient care quality". The prevalent use of quantitative research method, authentic leadership questionnaire (ALQ) and cross sectional research design was evident.
Tate (2008)	The empirical study of 15 undergraduates demonstrates that followers' perceptions of authentic leadership are closely linked to their changing mental representations of the traits of desired leaders. The study also developed the first measure of authentic leadership based on the five dimensions of authentic leadership. George (2003) advanced these dimensions and the behaviours that facilitate them.
van Droffelaar and Jacobs (2017)	The article evaluates the effect of wilderness experiences on the development of authentic leadership. The intentions of participants in a leadership training programme were evaluated. The study's findings indicate that leaders' peak experiences related to increased self awareness, values, connectedness, and presence trigger the intention to develop authentic leadership.
Weischer, Weibler and Petersen (2013)	The empirical study investigates the effects of enactment on followers' perceptions of leaders' authenticity. The findings of the study indicate that trust and emotions are outcomes of perceived authenticity.
Wright (2015)	The article investigates the authentic leadership development of an executive, which was prompted by personal experiences and frightening global events. The study's findings indicate that vulnerability, which involves acknowledging difficult emotions, is essential for authentic leadership development and is positively associated with creativity, innovation, and change.
Walumbwa et al. (2008)	Using samples from three countries, the study developed the Authentic Leadership Questionnaire (ALQ). The ALQ was designed to address the limitations of self-reporting, thus requiring inputs from followers to avoid impression management and biases in self-reports. It is described as a higher-order construct exemplified by four dimensions that dominate existing literature.
Wulffers, Bussin and Hewitt (2016)	The article investigates the effectiveness of authentic leadership programmes within a 10-member leadership group. the study's findings indicate that authentic leadership development was facilitated by the programmes.

Yammarino <i>et al.</i> (2008)	The article examined authentic leadership and positive organisational behaviour from a multilevel perspective. Authentic leadership was examined as a multilevel construct that produced multilevel criteria, outcomes, and performance for Positive organisational behaviour (POB).
Al Zaabi, Ahmad and Hossan (2016)	The article examines authentic leadership in the UAE petroleum industry. The study examines authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour, and work engagement within the context. The study's findings indicate that authentic leadership has a positive effect on work engagement and organisational citizenship behaviour.
Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2012)	From a sociological and philosophical standpoint, the study develops a theory of authentic leadership. Eight small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) were examined, and the study's findings disclose contextual differences in the interpretation of authentic leadership. Furthermore, authentic leaders in China are both authentic to self and context.

Appendix 2. Ethical Approval

31/03/2021

Dear Ibiyemi Omeihe,

Your application [REDACTED] Authentic Leadership in a Developing Economy Context A Study of Nigerian Oil SMEs, submission [REDACTED] has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner

Individual Consent Form

Authentic Leadership in a Developing Economy Context

A Study of Nigerian Oil SMEs

Principal Investigator: *Ibiyemi Omeihe*
Name of Supervisor: *Dr. Christian Harrison*

Personal details withheld.

Title of Dissertation	Authentic Leadership in a Developing Economy Context <i>A Study of Nigerian Oil SMEs</i>
Name of Researcher	Ibiyemi Omeihe
Name of Supervisor	Dr. Christian Harrison
Telephone	██████████
Email address	██████████
Description of the broad nature of research	To collect data towards examining authentic leadership within a developing economy context, to identify its components, investigate the challenges authentic leaders encounter, and fully illuminate the process of becoming authentic.
Description of participant involvement, nature of commitment and nature of questions.	<p>The duration of the interview per participant is expected to last approximately 60 minutes.</p> <p>The inquiry would adopt a semi-structured interview process that aims to combine a pre-determined set of open questions to enable the investigator to explore particular themes and in-depth responses from the lens of the respondents.</p> <p>Unlike the structured interview inquiry, the semi-structured interview allows respondents to discuss details previously not considered. The interview discussions would be recorded using a digital voice recorder and subsequently transcribed verbatim, while the names of the respondents would be anonymised on the interview transcripts.</p> <p>Respondents would have access to the information on the interview transcripts to ensure consistency and accuracy. They would also be free to make amendments where necessary.</p> <p>All data would be treated with full confidentiality and stored securely. Electronic data would be coded on an external drive while hard copies are secured in private drawers.</p> <p>Furthermore, the Director of Studies may have access to the interview transcripts to ensure research validity.</p>
Research Time frame	Data collection period: May 2021

Appendix 4. Participant information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

**Authentic Leadership in a Developing Economy
Context**

A Study of Nigerian Oil SMEs

Principal Investigator: *Ibiyemi Omeihe*
Name of Supervisor: *Dr Christian Harrison*

Personal details withheld.

Title of Dissertation	Authentic Leadership in a Developing Economy Context <i>A Study of Nigerian Oil SMEs</i>
Name of Researcher	Ibiyemi Omeihe
Director of Studies	Dr. Christian Harrison
Telephone	Mobile: [REDACTED]
Email address	[REDACTED]
Purpose of the research	<p>The purpose of the research is to examine authentic leadership within a developing economy context, to identify its components, investigate the challenges authentic leaders encounter, and fully illuminate the process of becoming authentic.</p> <p>If this is examined, new and aspiring authentic leaders would be able to develop effectively and be perceived as authentic by their followers.</p> <p>The findings of the study will have both policy and practical implications for the field of authentic leadership as they will inform leadership interventions within organisations. Also, it will provide leaders with knowledge and access to resources to help them overcome challenges of associated with SMEs.</p>
Who are we?	UWS is an officially recognised University in the top 5% of universities worldwide. The interviewer is who is the principal investigator is undertaking a doctoral research with the university. The study is fully self-funded and forms an important aspect of the doctoral research.
Why have I been asked to take part?	<p>The study focuses on authentic leaders and followers operating within the oil SMEs in the Nigerian environment.</p> <p>We are asking some leaders how they have developed into authentic leaders. In particular, the discussion will cover the negotiation process with followers and how they overcome challenges within the context of the study.</p> <p>Also, followers will be asked about their perceptions of authentic leadership which will be used to triangulate findings from the authentic leaders.</p> <p>The study is completely confidential, and your name will not be recorded anywhere.</p>

<p>What will I have to do if I take part?</p>	<p>What will I have to do if I take part?</p> <p>All you would have to do:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Fill out a consent form. 2 The interviewer will then proceed to ask you questions which takes about 60 mins to complete in a private area of exchange. 3 Questions – these include general questions about your firm, background information leadership perceptions, and experience, etc.
<p>Notes</p>	<p>Your name is not being recorded in this study. This means that neither you nor anyone else can find out your answers</p>
<p>Do I have to take part?</p>	<p>Do I have to take part?</p> <p>No. Participation in this study is voluntary, we would be grateful for your help, but the choice is yours.</p> <p>Even If you choose to participate in the study, you can withdraw at any time you wish, and your form will be destroyed.</p>
<p>Confidentiality</p>	<p>The forms are entirely confidential, although subject to normal legal requirements.</p> <p>Your name will not be written on the form.</p> <p>Your answers will not be given nor exchanged with anyone else.</p> <p>The University of the West of Scotland is registered under the data protection Act and has an Information Security Policy to safeguard the collection, processing, and storage of confidential information.</p>
<p>What if I want to find out more or have a complaint about research?</p>	<p>If you want to find out more about the Thesis or have a complaint about this research, please contact:</p> <p>Dr Christian Harrison Director of Studies</p>

PARTICIPANT INTERVIEW GUIDE

Authentic Leadership in a Developing Economy Context

A Study of Nigerian Oil Companies

Principal Investigator: *Ibiyemi Omeihe*
Name of Supervisor: *Dr Christian Harrison*

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

Part 1

Details of the Company and Participants Information

Details	Description
Name of Enterprise	
Name of owner(s)	
Date of establishment	
Location of business	
Type and nature of business	
Number of employees	

Details	Description
Name of Participant(s)	
Gender	
Age bracket	
Ethnicity	
Level of Education	
How long have you worked here?	
How many managers have you reported to within this period?	
Do you work in a team or on your own?	
Do you have line reports, if yes how many?	

Part 2

Introduction to Research

2a. Introduction to the researcher and the research to be undertaken	
2b. Assurance of anonymity and confidentiality of the process to the research participants	
2c. Ensure that research participants are comfortable with the research and all aspects of consent	
2d. Explain why they have been selected as authentic leaders?	

Part 3

Authentic leadership Questions?

3a. How do you lead?	
3b. Do you think you are an authentic leader? If yes, why? If no, why not?	
3c. When do you think the process started?	
3d. What does authentic leadership mean to you and what does it mean to be an authentic leader within Nigeria's context?	
3e. What is the most important factor that you consider in determining if you are authentic or not?	
3f. Can you define authentic leadership in your own words?	

3g. Briefly describe the skills you believe make a good authentic leader must possess.	
3h Are your beliefs and values internally or externally shaped?	

Part 4

What are the challenges that authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy?

4a. What are the main challenges in the Oil sector in Nigeria?	
4b. What are the challenges facing your business?	
4c. Who are the principal actors/ people propagating these problems?	
4d. What is the biggest challenge that you've faced as an authentic leader and how did you handle it?	
4e. Do you think it has made them authentic? Based on response which challenge and why?	
4f. Describe a scenario in your leadership role that you felt you were most authentic and why?	

Part 5

What are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development in leaders?

5a. What inspired you to become authentic?	
5b. When did you take that decision to be authentic and why?	
5c. What event or experience will you say was the most pivotal to that decision to become authentic?	
5d. Have other events made you question that choice? If yes what?	
5e. What factors do you think contribute to authentic leadership development?	<i>Rep</i>
5f. Which of the factors is the most important and why?	
5g. When do these factors contribute to AL development?	
5h. How do these factors contribute to AL development?	

Part 6

What is the role of the followers' perceptions in shaping authentic leadership development?

6a. Do your follower's perception influence or shape your leadership? If yes, how? And then when?	
6b. Is it a particular follower's perception or the perceptions of a group followers that have shaped your authentic leadership development? If yes, how? And then when?	
6c. What role do followers' perceptions play in shaping your authentic leadership development?	
6d. If you were to pick one over the other based on your personal experiences, which will it be? And why?	

Appendix 6. Interview protocol for followers

PARTICIPANT INTERVIEW GUIDE

**Authentic Leadership in a Developing Economy
Context**

A Study of Nigerian Oil Companies

Principal Investigator: *Ibiyemi Omeihe*

Name of Supervisor: *Dr Christian Harrison*

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

Part 1

Details of the SMEs and Participants Information

Details	Description
Name of SME	
Date of establishment	
Location of business	
Type and nature of business	
Number of employees	

Details	Description
Name of Participant(s)	
Gender	
Age bracket	
Ethnicity	
Level of Education	
How long have you worked here?	
How many managers have you reported to within this period?	
Do you work in a team or on your own?	
Do you have line reports, if yes how many?	

Part 2

Introduction to Research

2a. Introduction to the researcher and the research to be undertaken	
2b. Assurance of anonymity and confidentiality of the process to the research participants	
2c. Ensure that research participants are comfortable with the research and all aspects of consent	
2d. Define authentic leadership	

Part 3

Authentic leadership Questions?

3a. Describe a person you regard as an authentic/ genuine leader	
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3b. Can you give two examples of authentic leaders within your organisation, if any	
3c. What are the positions of these leaders within the organisation?	
3d. Why do you think these leaders are authentic?	
3e. When and how did you decide that the leader was authentic?	
3f. What is the most important factor that you consider in determining if a leader is authentic or not?	
3g. Is there a leader that was authentic before but now you think the leader is not authentic anymore?	
3h. If yes, on what basis did you take that decision?	
3i. Do you think you can give that leader a second chance and why?	
3j. What are the attributes or skills of these authentic/ genuine leader?	

Part 4

What are the specific actions that shape the employee perceptions of authentic leaders?

4a. What are the specific actions of leaders that shape your perceptions of authentic leaders?	
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Appendix 7. Coding frame

1. Components of authentic leadership

Overarching themes	Interpretive codes	Descriptive
Clarity of Purpose	Knowledge orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forward thinking • Values-based decision-making • Making judgement calls
	Enabling environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive organisational climate • Resource Management • Envisioning
	Goal orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal creation • Result oriented • High achiever
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal Pursuit • Steering stakeholders towards set goals
Relational Transparency	Vulnerability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open about experiences • Love, trust & respect • Self-disclosure • Approachable
	Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open to scrutiny
	Learning Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth mind-set • Speaking up • Lifelong learner

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachable
Follower Development	Role Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership positioning (Leading by example, leading by following, leading from the front, Leading from the back) • Development approaches (Mentoring/ Coaching)
	Psychological capital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hope, resilience, efficacy and optimism
	Competency Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skill development (knowledge and capacity) • Develop well rounded followers
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivates to action (Drive followers to succeed) • Empowerment • Inspiration
	Providing support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitment (Leaving no one behind, supporting people to achieve their best) • Pursuit to a conclusion (Following through / Following up)
Concern for people	Team focused	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Galvanizing followers • Collaboration

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synergistic (Bringing people together, winning together, Working together)
	360 perspectives of followers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concern for followers' career • Concern for followers' personal life • Concern for followers' passion
Self awareness	Self regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-reflection • Objective (Step out of myself, set aside personal views)
	Emotional Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed • Self-management (On top of what is going on) • Social awareness •
	True to self	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of weakness, • Awareness of strength • Awareness of capabilities • Genuine
Internalised moral perspective	Unbiased	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courageous • Fairness
	Morally upright	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Honest • Accountable • Defence of self-worth (Standup for their selves & others) • Self Confidence

	Value driven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrity (Guided by value & ethics, keeps their word, principled)
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1a Description of authentic leadership by followers (components by followers)

Concern for people	Leading with purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledgeable • Produces tangible results
	Team focused	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration • Getting involved (Getting their hands dirty) • Empathetic
	Consistent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equitable • Dependable

2. What are the factors that inspire authentic leadership development?

Overarching themes	Interpretive codes	Descriptive
Family Structure	Position in the family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Birth Order (First born, First child, First girl, First boy) • Hierarchy • Social Issues (Relationship between father and mother, Women not working, Family influence)
	Roles and Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upbringing • Parental expectation (Responsible for younger ones) • Task and Duties

Belief and conviction	Morals and Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Values (from home, organisation, followers, direct reports)
	Religious beliefs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foundational training (Faith in God, Fear of God, Word of God)
Leadership	Good Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early leadership experience (First experience, good leadership with first manager, Exposure to leadership early) • Reassurance (Encouragement from bosses, guidance from bosses) • Exemplary leaders (Living transparently) • Reading books (about other leaders like Richard Branson and Jack Welch)
	Bad Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failed leaders • Disgruntled followers
	Feedback on leadership journey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership experimentation • Leadership Training (Meeting with John Maxwell, workshops) • Feedback (Structured and unstructured)
Legacy	Crucibles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To bring change (Driven by the benefits of change, Driven by possibilities) • Effective corrective action
	Trigger Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bad/Good Experiences • Failure (at an early age, Starting all over again)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early challenges and difficulties
	Personal fulfilment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-actualisation

2b Pivotal Experience

Overarching themes	Interpretive codes	Descriptive
External Influences	Leadership Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentor / Role models • Bad leaders (One sided leaders) • Workshops/ Trainings/ Books
	Organisational Influences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational structure (Time in role / evolution, slow career restructuring: merger with new company) • Organisational challenges and success
	Early Childhood experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facing fears • Failures

3. What are the challenges that authentic leaders encounter in a developing economy?

Overarching themes	Interpretive codes	Descriptive
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Financial Challenges	Corruption	<p>Fraudulent practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extortion of organisations • Subsidies and surcharges • Opaque pricing structure <p>Unclear Business Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illegal products (Unhealthy competition) • Illegitimate businesses
	Misappropriation of funds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scarcity of Forex (Hoarding of Forex by BDCs) • Rising debt (Extensive borrowing)
Poor governance and regulation	Ineffective regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malpractices • Bureaucratic processes
	Government interferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unstable government policies (Practices from the central bank) • Poor project planning
	Lack of accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mismanagement of oil proceeds • Depletion of foreign reserves
	Rising Insecurity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insurgents • Militants • Herdsmen • Kidnappers (Unmotivated security personnel)
Economic challenges	Global Economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unsustainable taxes

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Devaluation of the currency • Low access to capital and financial instruments
	High inflation rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uneven supply curve • Low purchasing power
	COVID	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Redundancies / lay off • Reduction in production (Less demand for product) • Reduced revenue • Reduction in exports
	Infrastructure deficit	<p>Destruction of existing infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pipelines and other fittings, • Bombings of installation facilities) <p>Lack of upgrade of existing infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate power supply • Dilapidated roads • Lack of appropriate technology • White elephant refineries
Social Challenges	Ethnic and Religious Bias	<p>Favouritism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of consistency and predictability • Lack of transparency
	Human Resource complexities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal sentiments • Instant wealth appeal • Lack of Integrity

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of competence
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4. What are the specific actions that shape employee perceptions of authentic leaders?

Overarching themes	Interpretive codes	Descriptive
Giving followers a voice	Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Alignment • Active participation (Engagement, Get hands dirty) • Know the strengths and weaknesses of the team (Works effectively in teams)
	Passionate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confident • Self-assured
	Inclusivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotes equity • Accessibility • Learning and development
	Balanced Processing	Open to diverse perspectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open to ideas • Opinion sharing • Open minded
Follower development	Role modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leading by example • Mentorship/ Coaching
	Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humanistic behaviours (Showing the human side) • Empathetic concern (Understanding how followers feel)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compassion
	Relationship management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leveraging diversity • Good interpersonal skills • Provides validation (Provides validation through their actions) • Positive environment (Allow followers to learn from mistakes) • Prioritise followers' interests (Ensure followers life are going well, interested in all aspects of followers' life and consistently shows interest)
	Guidance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback (Provides feedback on performance) • Clear communicator (effective, respectful) • Provides resources (Materials and information that is required)
Consistent	Rational thinker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuity • Process driven (Right approach for every issue) • Predictability
	Dependable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trustworthiness (Demonstrate what they say / preach) • Credibility (Matching what you say or what you do)
Transparent	Accountable to stake holders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accountable to followers • Accountable to peers • Accountable to leaders • Accountable to bosses and followers (on the vision) • Allows an inner circle
	Honesty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Takes action (Take responsibility for actions, own up to responsibilities)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• No blaming (Takes ownership of mistakes and errors)• Honest to self and others• Defend beliefs (Stands up for what is right, Genuine in intentions and actions)
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Appendix 8. Research and Scholarship

Publications

- [1] "How Does Entrepreneurial Leadership Pay off for Small Businesses? Exploring Context to understand the value of entrepreneurial leadership." (with Kingsley Obi Omeihe). *International Review of Entrepreneurship*. February 2024, Special Issue Volume.
- [2] "Trade Associations and Trust in Weak Institutional Contexts: Exploring SME relationships in Nigeria" (with Kingsley Obi Omeihe, Amon Simba and Veronika Gustafsson). *International Review of Entrepreneurship*, April 2021, Volume 18 (4)
- [3] "Leading the way: the entrepreneur of the leader" (with Christian Harrison, Amon Simba and Kingsley Obi Omeihe,). *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, November 2020, Volume 11 (3)
- [4] "Getting Personal: the issues on trust and distrust in small and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria" (with Kingsley Obi Omeihe, Isaac Oduro-Amoako, Veronika Gustafsson, and Mohammad Saud Khan). *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*. November 2020.
- [5] "The role of the entrepreneurial leader: A study of Nigerian SMEs" (with, Christian Harrison, Simba Amon and Kingsley Obi Omeihe). *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*. May 2020.
- [6] "Transformative Reflexivity: Teaching and quality enterprise pedagogy" (with Kingsley Obi Omeihe). *Journal of Higher Education Service Science and Management*. September 2019, Volume 2 (1)
- [7] "Leading in an entrepreneurial context: Present and future perspectives" (with Kingsley Omeihe, Christian Harrison) *International Review of Entrepreneurship*, November 2022. Special Issue

Selected presentations at peer reviewed scientific meetings

- [8] "The many barriers to ethnic minority entrepreneurship: Interpreting the hidden narratives of ethnic minority entrepreneurs in Edinburgh", (with Bekee Bariture and Kingsley Omeihe), ISBE Conference, York, 2022.
- [9] "The strength of trust, social norms and entrepreneurship for trade networks: Evidence from Nigerian trader-owned enterprises" (with Kingsley Omeihe), 82nd Annual meeting Academy of Management, 2022.

- [10] “Authentic leadership repair within a developing economy context”, (with Kingsley Omeihe and Christian Harrison), 36th Annual meeting British Academy of Management, 2022.
- [11] “The strength of norms shaping entrepreneurial relationships: evidence from Nigerian SMEs, (with Kingsley Omeihe), 36th Annual meeting British Academy of Management, 2022.
- [12] “Authentic entrepreneurial leadership within the Igbo trade apprenticeship system” (with Kingsley Omeihe, Christian Harrison and Olamide Olusegun), 36th Annual meeting British Academy of Management, 2022.
- [13] “The rise or fall of authentic leadership. Submission no: 13926” (with Kingsley Omeihe), 81st Annual meeting Academy of Management, 2022.
- [14] “Authentic leadership skills within a developing economy context” (with Christian Harrison and Kingsley Omeihe), 35th Annual meeting British Academy of Management, 2021.
- [15] “Authentic Leadership: A systematic literature review” (with Christian Harrison and Kingsley Omeihe), 35th Annual meeting British Academy of Management, 2021.

Chaired symposiums at peer reviewed scientific meetings

- [16] Conference Session Chair: African Studies Track. British Academy of Management Conference, Bridgton, England, September 2023.
- [17] Conference Session Chair: 7th CAREED Conference, Paisley, Scotland, June 2023.
- [18] Conference Session Chair: African Studies Track. British Academy of Management Conference, Manchester, England, September 2022.
- [19] Conference Session Chair: 6th CAREED Conference, Paisley, Scotland, 2022.
- [20] Conference Organiser, 6th Annual Centre for African Research on Enterprise and Economic Development Conference, Paisley, Scotland, 2022.

Selected lectures and facilitations

- [21] “Reinforcing Entrepreneurial Universities by Design: An evaluation of pedagogies, practices and perspectives”. Entrepreneurship Discussion. February 2023.
- [22] “Empowering women in business: the near, next and future. Entrepreneurship Discussion. March 2023.
- [23] “Demystifying the entrepreneurial skills and knowledge of the Silicon Valley/Internet Economy start-up playbook”. Entrepreneurship Discussion. November 2022.

Honors, Fellowships, and Awards

- 2023 Gold Ambassador: Researcher Life
- 2023 Researcher: UWS Researcher Development Award
- 2022 Gold Ambassador: Researcher Life
- 2022 Researcher: UWS Researcher Development Award
- 2022 Star Ambassador: Researcher Life
- 2022 Lecturer of the Year: University of the West of Scotland
- 2021 Certificate of Achievement: University of the West of Scotland
- 2021 African Studies: Best Developmental Award: British Academy of Management
- 2021 Nomination for Lecturer of the Year Award, Students Union Big Awards, 2021 (SAUWS)
- 2019 Court Medallist, University of the West of Scotland

Public service positions

- 2024 British Academy of Management Treasurer
- 2023 Scottish Women in Business Committee Member
- 2021 Academy for African Studies (AFAS) SIG Chair
- 2021 Women's Budget Group Member
- 2020 Cross-Party Group on Oil and Gas Member